

Palindromic-Type Pandigital Patterns in Pythagorean Triples

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Abstract

*This paper brings examples of Palindromic-Type Pandigital Patterns in Pythagorean Triples. These are constructed in a padronized way. This means that in all the patterns we have **pandigital palindromic-type expressions**. The only change appears is in the middle terms and the last numbers of the first and third values. The results are obtained in such a way that we have total values as: 9, 99, 999, 9999, 99999, etc. The construction is based on a procedure well known in the literature. There is very much uniformity among the results. In this work we have two different types of **palindromic-type expressions**, such as blocks of **121, 12321, 1234321, ...**, and blocks of **10201, 102030201, 1020304030201, ...**. This work is a combinations of author's previous two works [7, 8].*

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1 Procedure

Let's consider the following three functions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(m, n) &:= m^2 - n^2 \\
 G(m, n) &:= 2mn \\
 H(m, n) &:= m^2 + n^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.1}$$

Then we can easily check that

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(m, n)^2 + G(m, n)^2 &= (m^2 - n^2)^2 + (2mn)^2 \\
 &= m^4 - 2m^2n^2 + n^4 + 4m^2n^2 \\
 &= m^4 + 2m^2n^2 + n^4 \\
 &= (m^2 + n^2)^2 = H(m, n)^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

This proves that the triple (F, G, H) is a **Pythagorean triple**. The Procedure (1.1) is very famous in the literature [1]. Some patterned examples based on the Procedure (1.1) are studied by author [6]. Some particular cases are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (F(3, 2), G(3, 2), H(3, 2)) &\Rightarrow (5, 12, 13) \\
 (F(4, 2), G(4, 2), H(4, 2)) &\Rightarrow (12, 16, 20) \\
 (F(5, 2), G(5, 2), H(5, 2)) &\Rightarrow (21, 20, 29) \\
 (F(6, 2), G(6, 2), H(6, 2)) &\Rightarrow (32, 24, 40) \\
 (F(9, 3), G(9, 3), H(9, 3)) &\Rightarrow (72, 54, 90) \\
 (F(9, 7), G(9, 7), H(9, 7)) &\Rightarrow (32, 126, 130) \\
 (F(10, 9), G(10, 9), H(10, 9)) &\Rightarrow (19, 180, 181)
 \end{aligned}$$

The aim of this work is to write **Palindromic-Type Pandigital Patterns in Pythagorean Triples**. This we have done in three different ways. First way give 9 patterns, second way give 99 patterns, and the third way give 999 patterns. All the patterns are very much similar in terms of **palindromic-type pandigital patterns**. This similarity we call as "**uniformity of results**". This uniformity is explained in the following section.

2 Uniformity of Results

In order to get **Palindromic-Type Pandigital Patterns in Pythagorean Triples**, the following pattern appears automatically in the beginning of each part:

$$\begin{aligned}
 99^2 + 20^2 &= 101^2 && := 10201 \\
 9999^2 + 200^2 &= 10001^2 && := 100020001 \\
 999999^2 + 2000^2 &= 1000001^2 && := 1000002000001 \\
 99999999^2 + 20000^2 &= 100000001^2 && := 10000000200000001 \\
 999999999^2 + 200000^2 &= 10000000001^2 && := 100000000020000000001 \\
 9999999999^2 + 2000000^2 &= 1000000000001^2 && := 1000000000002000000000001
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

The above pattern is obtained by considering $n = 1; m = 9, 99, 999, 9999, 99999, \dots$ in the following Procedure:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_1(m, n) &:= m(2n + m) \\
 G_1(m, n) &:= 2n(n + m) \\
 H_1(m, n) &:= m^2 + 2mn + 2n^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

More details on the Procedures given in (1.1) and (2.2) can be seen in Taneja [6].

We shall show below as an idea how each row is connected with our results. Let's rewrite the pattern given (2.1) representing each line separately. It gives us total number of results in each case. See below

$99^2 + 20^2 = 101^2$	→	Line 1 ⇒ Total patterns: 9
$9999^2 + 200^2 = 10001^2$	→	Line 2 ⇒ Total patterns: 99
$999999^2 + 2000^2 = 1000001^2$	→	Line 3 ⇒ Total patterns: 999
$99999999^2 + 20000^2 = 100000001^2$	→	Line 4 ⇒ Total patterns: 9999
$999999999^2 + 200000^2 = 10000000001^2$	→	Line 5 ⇒ Total patterns: 99999
...	...	...

(2.3)

Based on each line of (2.3), we shall construct blocks of **pandigital palindromic-type Pythagorean triples**. This construction is in two different type. Each type has same number of examples.

3 First Block

Below are 9 examples of **pattern in Pythagorean triples** with 9 digits from 1 to 9 written as **palindromic-type**, where the **first line** of first pattern is the same as **first line** of example (2.1) or (2.3)

3.1 First Type

• For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 7, 8, 9$:

Let's consider

$$m = 10, 110, 1110, 11110, 111110, 1111110, 11111110, 111111110$$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 7, 8, 9$; there are 9 palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 099^2 + 20^2 &= 101^2 \\
 12099^2 + 220^2 &= 12101^2 \\
 1232099^2 + 2220^2 &= 1232101^2 \\
 123432099^2 + 22220^2 &= 123432101^2 \\
 12345432099^2 + 222220^2 &= 12345432101^2 \\
 1234565432099^2 + 2222220^2 &= 1234565432101^2 \\
 123456765432099^2 + 22222220^2 &= 123456765432101^2 \\
 12345678765432099^2 + 222222220^2 &= 12345678765432101^2 \\
 1234567898765432099^2 + 2222222220^2 &= 1234567898765432101^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 096^2 + 40^2 &= 104^2 \\
 12096^2 + 440^2 &= 12104^2 \\
 1232096^2 + 4440^2 &= 1232104^2 \\
 123432096^2 + 44440^2 &= 123432104^2 \\
 12345432096^2 + 444440^2 &= 12345432104^2 \\
 1234565432096^2 + 4444440^2 &= 1234565432104^2 \\
 123456765432096^2 + 44444440^2 &= 123456765432104^2 \\
 12345678765432096^2 + 444444440^2 &= 12345678765432104^2 \\
 1234567898765432096^2 + 4444444440^2 &= 1234567898765432104^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
091^2 + 60^2 &= 109^2 \\
12091^2 + 660^2 &= 12109^2 \\
1232091^2 + 6660^2 &= 1232109^2 \\
123432091^2 + 66660^2 &= 123432109^2 \\
12345432091^2 + 666660^2 &= 12345432109^2 \\
1234565432091^2 + 6666660^2 &= 1234565432109^2 \\
123456765432091^2 + 66666660^2 &= 123456765432109^2 \\
12345678765432091^2 + 666666660^2 &= 12345678765432109^2 \\
1234567898765432091^2 + 6666666660^2 &= 1234567898765432109^2
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
084^2 + 80^2 &= 116^2 \\
12084^2 + 880^2 &= 12116^2 \\
1232084^2 + 8880^2 &= 1232116^2 \\
123432084^2 + 88880^2 &= 123432116^2 \\
12345432084^2 + 888880^2 &= 12345432116^2 \\
1234565432084^2 + 8888880^2 &= 1234565432116^2 \\
123456765432084^2 + 88888880^2 &= 123456765432116^2 \\
12345678765432084^2 + 888888880^2 &= 12345678765432116^2 \\
1234567898765432084^2 + 8888888880^2 &= 1234567898765432116^2
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
075^2 + 100^2 &= 125^2 \\
12075^2 + 1100^2 &= 12125^2 \\
1232075^2 + 11100^2 &= 1232125^2 \\
123432075^2 + 111100^2 &= 123432125^2 \\
12345432075^2 + 1111100^2 &= 12345432125^2 \\
1234565432075^2 + 11111100^2 &= 1234565432125^2 \\
123456765432075^2 + 111111100^2 &= 123456765432125^2 \\
12345678765432075^2 + 1111111100^2 &= 12345678765432125^2 \\
1234567898765432075^2 + 11111111100^2 &= 1234567898765432125^2
\end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
064^2 + 120^2 &= 136^2 \\
12064^2 + 1320^2 &= 12136^2 \\
1232064^2 + 13320^2 &= 1232136^2 \\
123432064^2 + 133320^2 &= 123432136^2 \\
12345432064^2 + 1333320^2 &= 12345432136^2 \\
1234565432064^2 + 13333320^2 &= 1234565432136^2 \\
123456765432064^2 + 133333320^2 &= 123456765432136^2 \\
12345678765432064^2 + 1333333320^2 &= 12345678765432136^2 \\
1234567898765432064^2 + 13333333320^2 &= 1234567898765432136^2 \quad (3.6)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
051^2 + 140^2 &= 149^2 \\
12051^2 + 1540^2 &= 12149^2 \\
1232051^2 + 15540^2 &= 1232149^2 \\
123432051^2 + 155540^2 &= 123432149^2 \\
12345432051^2 + 1555540^2 &= 12345432149^2 \\
1234565432051^2 + 15555540^2 &= 1234565432149^2 \\
123456765432051^2 + 155555540^2 &= 123456765432149^2 \\
12345678765432051^2 + 1555555540^2 &= 12345678765432149^2 \\
1234567898765432051^2 + 15555555540^2 &= 1234567898765432149^2 \quad (3.7)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
036^2 + 160^2 &= 164^2 \\
12036^2 + 1760^2 &= 12164^2 \\
1232036^2 + 17760^2 &= 1232164^2 \\
123432036^2 + 177760^2 &= 123432164^2 \\
12345432036^2 + 1777760^2 &= 12345432164^2 \\
1234565432036^2 + 17777760^2 &= 1234565432164^2 \\
123456765432036^2 + 177777760^2 &= 123456765432164^2 \\
12345678765432036^2 + 1777777760^2 &= 12345678765432164^2 \\
1234567898765432036^2 + 17777777760^2 &= 1234567898765432164^2 \quad (3.8)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 019^2 + 180^2 &= 181^2 \\
 12019^2 + 1980^2 &= 12181^2 \\
 1232019^2 + 19980^2 &= 1232181^2 \\
 123432019^2 + 199980^2 &= 123432181^2 \\
 12345432019^2 + 1999980^2 &= 12345432181^2 \\
 1234565432019^2 + 19999980^2 &= 1234565432181^2 \\
 123456765432019^2 + 199999980^2 &= 123456765432181^2 \\
 12345678765432019^2 + 1999999980^2 &= 12345678765432181^2 \\
 1234567898765432019^2 + 19999999980^2 &= 1234567898765432181^2 \tag{3.9}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Second Type

• For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 7, 8, 9$:

Let's consider

$m = 10, 1010, 101010, 10101010, 1010101010, 101010101010, 10101010101010, 1010101010101010, 101010101010101010$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 7, 8, 9$; there are 9 palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 099^2 + 20^2 &= 101^2 \\
 1020099^2 + 2020^2 &= 1020101^2 \\
 10203020099^2 + 202020^2 &= 10203020101^2 \\
 102030403020099^2 + 20202020^2 &= 102030403020101^2 \\
 1020304050403020099^2 + 2020202020^2 &= 1020304050403020101^2 \\
 10203040506050403020099^2 + 202020202020^2 &= 10203040506050403020101^2 \\
 102030405060706050403020099^2 + 20202020202020^2 &= 102030405060706050403020101^2 \\
 1020304050607080706050403020099^2 + 2020202020202020^2 &= 1020304050607080706050403020101^2 \\
 10203040506070809080706050403020099^2 + 202020202020202020^2 &= 10203040506070809080706050403020101^2 \tag{3.10}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 096^2 + 40^2 &= 104^2 \\
 1020096^2 + 4040^2 &= 1020104^2 \\
 10203020096^2 + 404040^2 &= 10203020104^2 \\
 102030403020096^2 + 40404040^2 &= 102030403020104^2 \\
 1020304050403020096^2 + 4040404040^2 &= 1020304050403020104^2 \\
 10203040506050403020096^2 + 404040404040^2 &= 10203040506050403020104^2 \\
 102030405060706050403020096^2 + 40404040404040^2 &= 102030405060706050403020104^2 \\
 1020304050607080706050403020096^2 + 4040404040404040^2 &= 1020304050607080706050403020104^2 \\
 10203040506070809080706050403020096^2 + 404040404040404040^2 &= 10203040506070809080706050403020104^2 \tag{3.11}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&091^2 + 60^2 &&= 1\ 09^2 \\
&1020\ 091^2 + 6060^2 &&= 10201\ 09^2 \\
&10203020\ 091^2 + 606060^2 &&= 102030201\ 09^2 \\
&102030403020\ 091^2 + 60606060^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 09^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 091^2 + 6060606060^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 09^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 091^2 + 606060606060^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 09^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 091^2 + 60606060606060^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 09^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 091^2 + 6060606060606060^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 09^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 091^2 + 606060606060606060^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 09^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.12}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&084^2 + 80^2 &&= 1\ 16^2 \\
&1020\ 084^2 + 8080^2 &&= 10201\ 16^2 \\
&10203020\ 084^2 + 808080^2 &&= 102030201\ 16^2 \\
&102030403020\ 084^2 + 80808080^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 16^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 084^2 + 8080808080^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 16^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 084^2 + 808080808080^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 16^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 084^2 + 80808080808080^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 16^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 084^2 + 8080808080808080^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 16^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 084^2 + 808080808080808080^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 16^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.13}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&075^2 + 100^2 &&= 1\ 25^2 \\
&1020\ 075^2 + 10100^2 &&= 10201\ 25^2 \\
&10203020\ 075^2 + 1010100^2 &&= 102030201\ 25^2 \\
&102030403020\ 075^2 + 101010100^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 25^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 075^2 + 10101010100^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 25^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 075^2 + 1010101010100^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 25^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 075^2 + 101010101010100^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 25^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 075^2 + 10101010101010100^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 25^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 075^2 + 1010101010101010100^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 25^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.14}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&064^2 + 120^2 &&= 136^2 \\
&1020064^2 + 12120^2 &&= 1020136^2 \\
&10203020064^2 + 1212120^2 &&= 10203020136^2 \\
&102030403020064^2 + 121212120^2 &&= 102030403020136^2 \\
&1020304050403020064^2 + 12121212120^2 &&= 1020304050403020136^2 \\
&10203040506050403020064^2 + 1212121212120^2 &&= 10203040506050403020136^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020064^2 + 121212121212120^2 &&= 102030405060706050403020136^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020064^2 + 12121212121212120^2 &&= 1020304050607080706050403020136^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020064^2 + 1212121212121212120^2 &&= 10203040506070809080706050403020136^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&051^2 + 140^2 &&= 149^2 \\
&1020051^2 + 14140^2 &&= 1020149^2 \\
&10203020051^2 + 1414140^2 &&= 10203020149^2 \\
&102030403020051^2 + 141414140^2 &&= 102030403020149^2 \\
&1020304050403020051^2 + 14141414140^2 &&= 1020304050403020149^2 \\
&10203040506050403020051^2 + 1414141414140^2 &&= 10203040506050403020149^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020051^2 + 141414141414140^2 &&= 102030405060706050403020149^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020051^2 + 14141414141414140^2 &&= 1020304050607080706050403020149^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020051^2 + 1414141414141414140^2 &&= 10203040506070809080706050403020149^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&036^2 + 160^2 &&= 164^2 \\
&1020036^2 + 16160^2 &&= 1020164^2 \\
&10203020036^2 + 1616160^2 &&= 10203020164^2 \\
&102030403020036^2 + 161616160^2 &&= 102030403020164^2 \\
&1020304050403020036^2 + 16161616160^2 &&= 1020304050403020164^2 \\
&10203040506050403020036^2 + 1616161616160^2 &&= 10203040506050403020164^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020036^2 + 161616161616160^2 &&= 102030405060706050403020164^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020036^2 + 16161616161616160^2 &&= 1020304050607080706050403020164^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020036^2 + 1616161616161616160^2 &&= 10203040506070809080706050403020164^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.17}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&019^2 + 180^2 &&= 181^2 \\
&1020019^2 + 18180^2 &&= 1020181^2 \\
&10203020019^2 + 1818180^2 &&= 10203020181^2 \\
&102030403020019^2 + 181818180^2 &&= 102030403020181^2 \\
&1020304050403020019^2 + 18181818180^2 &&= 1020304050403020181^2 \\
&10203040506050403020019^2 + 1818181818180^2 &&= 10203040506050403020181^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020019^2 + 181818181818180^2 &&= 102030405060706050403020181^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020019^2 + 18181818181818180^2 &&= 1020304050607080706050403020181^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020019^2 + 1818181818181818180^2 &&= 10203040506070809080706050403020181^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.18}$$

Based on above 9 results given in subsections 3.1 and 3.2, below are some remarks:

3.3 Remarks

(i) The **first line** of first pattern (3.1) and (3.10) is the **first line** as given in Example (2.1) or (2.3), i.e.,

$$99^2 + 20^2 = 101^2.$$

(ii) There is a symmetry in squared value for last two digits of each Example:

$$\text{Examples (3.1) and (3.10)} \Rightarrow 01 = 1^2$$

$$\text{Examples (3.2) and (3.11)} \Rightarrow 04 = 2^2$$

$$\text{Examples (3.3) and (3.12)} \Rightarrow 09 = 3^2$$

$$\text{Examples (3.1) and (3.13)} \Rightarrow 16 = 4^2$$

$$\text{Examples (3.2) and (3.14)} \Rightarrow 25 = 5^2$$

$$\text{Examples (3.3) and (3.15)} \Rightarrow 36 = 6^2$$

$$\text{Examples (3.7) and (3.16)} \Rightarrow 49 = 7^2$$

$$\text{Examples (3.8) and (3.17)} \Rightarrow 64 = 8^2$$

$$\text{Examples (3.9) and (3.18)} \Rightarrow 81 = 9^2.$$

(iii) The sum of the **last two digits** of the first and the third members of each line is equal, i.e.,

$$\text{Examples (3.1) and (3.10)} \Rightarrow 99 + 01 = 100$$

$$\text{Examples (3.2) and (3.11)} \Rightarrow 96 + 04 = 100$$

$$\text{Examples (3.3) and (3.12)} \Rightarrow 91 + 09 = 100$$

$$\text{Examples (3.4) and (3.13)} \Rightarrow 84 + 16 = 100$$

$$\text{Examples (3.5) and (3.14)} \Rightarrow 75 + 25 = 100$$

$$\text{Examples (3.6) and (3.15)} \Rightarrow 64 + 36 = 100$$

$$\text{Examples (3.7) and (3.16)} \Rightarrow 51 + 49 = 100$$

$$\text{Examples (3.8) and (3.17)} \Rightarrow 36 + 64 = 100$$

$$\text{Examples (3.9) and (3.18)} \Rightarrow 19 + 81 = 100$$

4 Second Block

Below are 99 examples of **pattern in Pythagorean triples** with 9 digits from 1 to 9 written as **palindromic-type**, where the **first line** of the first pattern is the same as **second line** of example (2.1) or (2.3).

4.1 First Type

• For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 97, 98, 99$:

This subsection is divided in two parts. The first part give first 19 results as complete patterns. The other 80 are written only with first five lines. The other four lines follows on similar way.

4.1.1 First Part

For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 19$:

Let's consider

$$m = 100, 1100, 11100, 111100, 1111100, 11111100, 111111100, 1111111100, 11111111100$$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 19$; there are 19 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns** given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09999^2 + 200^2 &&= 1\ 0001^2 \\
 &12\ 09999^2 + 2200^2 &&= 121\ 0001^2 \\
 &1232\ 09999^2 + 22200^2 &&= 12321\ 0001^2 \\
 &123432\ 09999^2 + 222200^2 &&= 1234321\ 0001^2 \\
 &12345432\ 09999^2 + 2222200^2 &&= 123454321\ 0001^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 09999^2 + 22222200^2 &&= 12345654321\ 0001^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 09999^2 + 222222200^2 &&= 1234567654321\ 0001^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 09999^2 + 2222222200^2 &&= 123456787654321\ 0001^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 09999^2 + 22222222200^2 &&= 12345678987654321\ 0001^2 \quad (4.1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09996^2 + 400^2 &&= 1\ 0004^2 \\
 &12\ 09996^2 + 4400^2 &&= 121\ 0004^2 \\
 &1232\ 09996^2 + 44400^2 &&= 12321\ 0004^2 \\
 &123432\ 09996^2 + 444400^2 &&= 1234321\ 0004^2 \\
 &12345432\ 09996^2 + 4444400^2 &&= 123454321\ 0004^2 \\
 &1234565432\ 09996^2 + 44444400^2 &&= 12345654321\ 0004^2 \\
 &123456765432\ 09996^2 + 444444400^2 &&= 1234567654321\ 0004^2 \\
 &12345678765432\ 09996^2 + 4444444400^2 &&= 123456787654321\ 0004^2 \\
 &1234567898765432\ 09996^2 + 44444444400^2 &&= 12345678987654321\ 0004^2 \quad (4.2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09991^2 + 600^2 &= 1\ 0009^2 \\
12\ 09991^2 + 6600^2 &= 121\ 0009^2 \\
1232\ 09991^2 + 66600^2 &= 12321\ 0009^2 \\
123432\ 09991^2 + 666600^2 &= 1234321\ 0009^2 \\
12345432\ 09991^2 + 6666600^2 &= 123454321\ 0009^2 \\
1234565432\ 09991^2 + 66666600^2 &= 12345654321\ 0009^2 \\
123456765432\ 09991^2 + 666666600^2 &= 1234567654321\ 0009^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09991^2 + 6666666600^2 &= 123456787654321\ 0009^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09991^2 + 66666666600^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 0009^2 \quad (4.3)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09984^2 + 800^2 &= 1\ 0016^2 \\
12\ 09984^2 + 8800^2 &= 121\ 0016^2 \\
1232\ 09984^2 + 88800^2 &= 12321\ 0016^2 \\
123432\ 09984^2 + 888800^2 &= 1234321\ 0016^2 \\
12345432\ 09984^2 + 8888800^2 &= 123454321\ 0016^2 \\
1234565432\ 09984^2 + 88888800^2 &= 12345654321\ 0016^2 \\
123456765432\ 09984^2 + 888888800^2 &= 1234567654321\ 0016^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09984^2 + 8888888800^2 &= 123456787654321\ 0016^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09984^2 + 88888888800^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 0016^2 \quad (4.4)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09975^2 + 1000^2 &= 1\ 0025^2 \\
12\ 09975^2 + 11000^2 &= 121\ 0025^2 \\
1232\ 09975^2 + 111000^2 &= 12321\ 0025^2 \\
123432\ 09975^2 + 1111000^2 &= 1234321\ 0025^2 \\
12345432\ 09975^2 + 11111000^2 &= 123454321\ 0025^2 \\
1234565432\ 09975^2 + 111111000^2 &= 12345654321\ 0025^2 \\
123456765432\ 09975^2 + 1111111000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 0025^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09975^2 + 11111111000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 0025^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09975^2 + 111111111000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 0025^2 \quad (4.5)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09964^2 + 1200^2 &= 1\ 0036^2 \\
12\ 09964^2 + 13200^2 &= 121\ 0036^2 \\
1232\ 09964^2 + 133200^2 &= 12321\ 0036^2 \\
123432\ 09964^2 + 1333200^2 &= 1234321\ 0036^2 \\
12345432\ 09964^2 + 13333200^2 &= 123454321\ 0036^2 \\
1234565432\ 09964^2 + 133333200^2 &= 12345654321\ 0036^2 \\
123456765432\ 09964^2 + 1333333200^2 &= 1234567654321\ 0036^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09964^2 + 13333333200^2 &= 123456787654321\ 0036^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09964^2 + 133333333200^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 0036^2 \quad (4.6)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09951^2 + 1400^2 &= 1\ 49^2 \\
12\ 09951^2 + 15400^2 &= 121\ 0049^2 \\
1232\ 09951^2 + 155400^2 &= 12321\ 0049^2 \\
123432\ 09951^2 + 1555400^2 &= 1234321\ 0049^2 \\
12345432\ 09951^2 + 15555400^2 &= 123454321\ 0049^2 \\
1234565432\ 09951^2 + 155555400^2 &= 12345654321\ 0049^2 \\
123456765432\ 09951^2 + 1555555400^2 &= 1234567654321\ 0049^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09951^2 + 15555555400^2 &= 123456787654321\ 0049^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09951^2 + 155555555400^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 0049^2 \quad (4.7)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09936^2 + 1600^2 &= 1\ 0064^2 \\
12\ 09936^2 + 17600^2 &= 121\ 0064^2 \\
1232\ 09936^2 + 177600^2 &= 12321\ 0064^2 \\
123432\ 09936^2 + 1777600^2 &= 1234321\ 0064^2 \\
12345432\ 09936^2 + 17777600^2 &= 123454321\ 0064^2 \\
1234565432\ 09936^2 + 177777600^2 &= 12345654321\ 0064^2 \\
123456765432\ 09936^2 + 1777777600^2 &= 1234567654321\ 0064^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09936^2 + 17777777600^2 &= 123456787654321\ 0064^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09936^2 + 177777777600^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 0064^2 \quad (4.8)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09919^2 + 1800^2 &= 181^2 \\
1209919^2 + 19800^2 &= 1210081^2 \\
123209919^2 + 199800^2 &= 123210081^2 \\
12343209919^2 + 1999800^2 &= 12343210081^2 \\
1234543209919^2 + 19999800^2 &= 1234543210081^2 \\
123456543209919^2 + 199999800^2 &= 123456543210081^2 \\
12345676543209919^2 + 1999999800^2 &= 12345676543210081^2 \\
1234567876543209919^2 + 19999999800^2 &= 1234567876543210081^2 \\
123456789876543209919^2 + 199999999800^2 &= 123456789876543210081^2 \quad (4.9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09900^2 + 2000^2 &= 10100^2 \\
1209900^2 + 22000^2 &= 1210100^2 \\
123209900^2 + 222000^2 &= 123210100^2 \\
12343209900^2 + 2222000^2 &= 12343210100^2 \\
1234543209900^2 + 22222000^2 &= 1234543210100^2 \\
123456543209900^2 + 222222000^2 &= 123456543210100^2 \\
12345676543209900^2 + 2222222000^2 &= 12345676543210100^2 \\
1234567876543209900^2 + 22222222000^2 &= 1234567876543210100^2 \\
123456789876543209900^2 + 222222222000^2 &= 123456789876543210100^2 \quad (4.10)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09879^2 + 2200^2 &= 10121^2 \\
1209879^2 + 24200^2 &= 1210121^2 \\
123209879^2 + 244200^2 &= 123210121^2 \\
12343209879^2 + 2444200^2 &= 12343210121^2 \\
1234543209879^2 + 24444200^2 &= 1234543210121^2 \\
123456543209879^2 + 244444200^2 &= 123456543210121^2 \\
12345676543209879^2 + 2444444200^2 &= 12345676543210121^2 \\
1234567876543209879^2 + 24444444200^2 &= 1234567876543210121^2 \\
123456789876543209879^2 + 244444444200^2 &= 123456789876543210121^2 \quad (4.11)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09856^2 + 2400^2 &= 1\ 0144^2 \\
12\ 09856^2 + 26400^2 &= 121\ 0144^2 \\
1232\ 09856^2 + 266400^2 &= 12321\ 0144^2 \\
123432\ 09856^2 + 2666400^2 &= 1234321\ 0144^2 \\
12345432\ 09856^2 + 26666400^2 &= 123454321\ 0144^2 \\
1234565432\ 09856^2 + 266666400^2 &= 12345654321\ 0144^2 \\
123456765432\ 09856^2 + 2666666400^2 &= 1234567654321\ 0144^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09856^2 + 26666666400^2 &= 123456787654321\ 0144^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09856^2 + 266666666400^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 0144^2 \quad (4.12)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09831^2 + 2600^2 &= 1\ 0169^2 \\
12\ 09831^2 + 28600^2 &= 121\ 0169^2 \\
1232\ 09831^2 + 288600^2 &= 12321\ 0169^2 \\
123432\ 09831^2 + 2888600^2 &= 1234321\ 0169^2 \\
12345432\ 09831^2 + 28888600^2 &= 123454321\ 0169^2 \\
1234315432\ 09831^2 + 288888600^2 &= 12343154321\ 0169^2 \\
123431765432\ 09831^2 + 2888888600^2 &= 1234317654321\ 0169^2 \\
12343178765432\ 09831^2 + 28888888600^2 &= 123431787654321\ 0169^2 \\
1234317898765432\ 09831^2 + 288888888600^2 &= 12343178987654321\ 0169^2 \quad (4.13)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09804^2 + 2800^2 &= 1\ 0196^2 \\
12\ 09804^2 + 30800^2 &= 121\ 0196^2 \\
1232\ 09804^2 + 310800^2 &= 12321\ 0196^2 \\
123432\ 09804^2 + 3110800^2 &= 1234321\ 0196^2 \\
12345432\ 09804^2 + 31110800^2 &= 123454321\ 0196^2 \\
1234565432\ 09804^2 + 311110800^2 &= 12340454321\ 0196^2 \\
123456765432\ 09804^2 + 3111110800^2 &= 1234047654321\ 0196^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09804^2 + 31111110800^2 &= 123404787654321\ 0196^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09804^2 + 311111110800^2 &= 12340478987654321\ 0196^2 \quad (4.14)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09775^2 + 3300^2 &= 1\ 0225^2 \\
12\ 09775^2 + 33000^2 &= 121\ 0225^2 \\
1232\ 09775^2 + 333000^2 &= 12321\ 0225^2 \\
123432\ 09775^2 + 3333000^2 &= 1234321\ 0225^2 \\
12345432\ 09775^2 + 33333000^2 &= 123454321\ 0225^2 \\
1234045432\ 09775^2 + 333333000^2 &= 12340454321\ 0225^2 \\
123404765432\ 09775^2 + 3333333000^2 &= 1234047654321\ 0225^2 \\
12340478765432\ 09775^2 + 33333333000^2 &= 123404787654321\ 0225^2 \\
1234047898765432\ 09775^2 + 333333333000^2 &= 12340478987654321\ 0225^2 \quad (4.15)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09744^2 + 3200^2 &= 1\ 0256^2 \\
12\ 09744^2 + 35200^2 &= 121\ 0256^2 \\
1232\ 09744^2 + 355200^2 &= 12321\ 0256^2 \\
123432\ 09744^2 + 3555200^2 &= 1234321\ 0256^2 \\
12345432\ 09744^2 + 35555200^2 &= 123454321\ 0256^2 \\
1234045432\ 09744^2 + 355555200^2 &= 12340454321\ 0256^2 \\
123404765432\ 09744^2 + 3555555200^2 &= 1234047654321\ 0256^2 \\
12340478765432\ 09744^2 + 35555555200^2 &= 123404787654321\ 0256^2 \\
1234047898765432\ 09744^2 + 355555555200^2 &= 12340478987654321\ 0256^2 \quad (4.16)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09711^2 + 3400^2 &= 1\ 0289^2 \\
12\ 09711^2 + 37400^2 &= 121\ 0289^2 \\
1232\ 09711^2 + 377400^2 &= 12321\ 0289^2 \\
123432\ 09711^2 + 3777400^2 &= 1234321\ 0289^2 \\
12345432\ 09711^2 + 37777400^2 &= 123454321\ 0289^2 \\
1234045432\ 09711^2 + 377777400^2 &= 12340454321\ 0289^2 \\
123404765432\ 09711^2 + 3777777400^2 &= 1234047654321\ 0289^2 \\
12340478765432\ 09711^2 + 37777777400^2 &= 123404787654321\ 0289^2 \\
1234047898765432\ 09711^2 + 377777777400^2 &= 12340478987654321\ 0289^2 \quad (4.17)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09676^2 + 3600^2 &= 1\ 0324^2 \\
12\ 09676^2 + 39600^2 &= 121\ 0324^2 \\
1232\ 09676^2 + 399600^2 &= 12321\ 0324^2 \\
123432\ 09676^2 + 3999600^2 &= 1234321\ 0324^2 \\
12345432\ 09676^2 + 39999600^2 &= 123454321\ 0324^2 \\
1234565432\ 09676^2 + 399999600^2 &= 12340454321\ 0324^2 \\
123456765432\ 09676^2 + 3999999600^2 &= 1234047654321\ 0324^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09676^2 + 39999999600^2 &= 123404787654321\ 0324^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09676^2 + 399999999600^2 &= 12340478987654321\ 0324^2 \quad (4.18)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09639^2 + 3800^2 &= 1\ 0361^2 \\
12\ 09639^2 + 41800^2 &= 121\ 0361^2 \\
1232\ 09639^2 + 421800^2 &= 12321\ 0361^2 \\
123432\ 09639^2 + 4221800^2 &= 1234321\ 0361^2 \\
12345432\ 09639^2 + 42221800^2 &= 123454321\ 0361^2 \\
12345645432\ 09639^2 + 422221800^2 &= 12340454321\ 0361^2 \\
123456765432\ 09639^2 + 4222221800^2 &= 1234047654321\ 0361^2 \\
12345678765432\ 09639^2 + 42222221800^2 &= 123404787654321\ 0361^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 09639^2 + 422222221800^2 &= 12340478987654321\ 0361^2 \quad (4.19)
\end{aligned}$$

4.1.2 Second Part

- For $n = 20, 21, 23, \dots, 97, 98, 99$:

Let's consider

$$m = 100, 1100, 11100, 111100, 1111100, 11111100, 111111100, 1111111100, 11111111100$$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 20, 21, 23, \dots, 97, 98, 99$; there are 80 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns** given below. In each case, only first four values are written. The other 5 values can be written on similar lines.

$$\begin{aligned}
09600^2 + 4000^2 &= 1\ 0400^2 & 09559^2 + 4200^2 &= 1\ 0441^2 \\
12\ 09600^2 + 44000^2 &= 121\ 0400^2 & 12\ 09559^2 + 46200^2 &= 121\ 0441^2 \\
1232\ 09600^2 + 444000^2 &= 12321\ 0400^2 & 1232\ 09559^2 + 466200^2 &= 12321\ 0441^2 \\
123432\ 09600^2 + 4444000^2 &= 1234321\ 0400^2 \quad (4.20) & 123432\ 09559^2 + 4666200^2 &= 1234321\ 0441^2 \quad (4.21)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09516^2 + 4400^2 &= 1\ 0484^2 \\
12\ 09516^2 + 48400^2 &= 121\ 0484^2 \\
1232\ 09516^2 + 488400^2 &= 12321\ 0484^2 \\
123432\ 09516^2 + 4888400^2 &= 1234321\ 0484^2 \quad (4.22)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09471^2 + 4600^2 &= 1\ 0529^2 \\
12\ 09471^2 + 50600^2 &= 121\ 0529^2 \\
1232\ 09471^2 + 510600^2 &= 12321\ 0529^2 \\
123432\ 09471^2 + 5110600^2 &= 1234321\ 0529^2 \quad (4.23)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09424^2 + 4800^2 &= 1\ 0576^2 \\
12\ 09424^2 + 52800^2 &= 121\ 0576^2 \\
1232\ 09424^2 + 532800^2 &= 12321\ 0576^2 \\
123432\ 09424^2 + 5332800^2 &= 1234321\ 0576^2 \quad (4.24)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09375^2 + 5000^2 &= 1\ 0625^2 \\
12\ 09375^2 + 55000^2 &= 121\ 0625^2 \\
1232\ 09375^2 + 555000^2 &= 12321\ 0625^2 \\
123432\ 09375^2 + 5555000^2 &= 1234321\ 0625^2 \quad (4.25)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09324^2 + 5200^2 &= 1\ 0676^2 \\
12\ 09324^2 + 57200^2 &= 121\ 0676^2 \\
1232\ 09324^2 + 577200^2 &= 12321\ 0676^2 \\
123432\ 09324^2 + 5777200^2 &= 1234321\ 0676^2 \quad (4.26)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09271^2 + 5400^2 &= 1\ 0729^2 \\
12\ 09271^2 + 59400^2 &= 121\ 0729^2 \\
1232\ 09271^2 + 599400^2 &= 12321\ 0729^2 \\
123432\ 09271^2 + 5999400^2 &= 1234321\ 0729^2 \quad (4.27)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09216^2 + 5600^2 &= 1\ 0784^2 \\
12\ 09216^2 + 61600^2 &= 121\ 0784^2 \\
1232\ 09216^2 + 621600^2 &= 12321\ 0784^2 \\
123432\ 09216^2 + 6221600^2 &= 1234321\ 0784^2 \quad (4.28)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09159^2 + 5800^2 &= 1\ 0841^2 \\
12\ 09159^2 + 63800^2 &= 121\ 0841^2 \\
1232\ 09159^2 + 643800^2 &= 12321\ 0841^2 \\
123432\ 09159^2 + 6443800^2 &= 1234321\ 0841^2 \quad (4.29)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09100^2 + 6000^2 &= 1\ 0900^2 \\
12\ 09100^2 + 66000^2 &= 121\ 0900^2 \\
1232\ 09100^2 + 666000^2 &= 12321\ 0900^2 \\
123432\ 09100^2 + 6666000^2 &= 1234321\ 0900^2 \quad (4.30)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
09039^2 + 6200^2 &= 1\ 0961^2 \\
12\ 09039^2 + 68200^2 &= 121\ 0961^2 \\
1232\ 09039^2 + 688200^2 &= 12321\ 0961^2 \\
123432\ 09039^2 + 6888200^2 &= 1234321\ 0961^2 \quad (4.31)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08976^2 + 6400^2 &= 1\ 1024^2 \\
12\ 08976^2 + 70400^2 &= 121\ 1024^2 \\
1232\ 08976^2 + 710400^2 &= 12321\ 1024^2 \\
123432\ 08976^2 + 7110400^2 &= 1234321\ 1024^2 \quad (4.32)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08911^2 + 6600^2 &= 1\ 1089^2 \\
12\ 08911^2 + 72600^2 &= 121\ 1089^2 \\
1232\ 08911^2 + 732600^2 &= 12321\ 1089^2 \\
123432\ 08911^2 + 7332600^2 &= 1234321\ 1089^2 \quad (4.33)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08844^2 + 6800^2 &= 1\ 1156^2 \\
12\ 08844^2 + 74800^2 &= 121\ 1156^2 \\
1232\ 08844^2 + 754800^2 &= 12321\ 1156^2 \\
123432\ 08844^2 + 7554800^2 &= 1234321\ 1156^2 \quad (4.34)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08775^2 + 7000^2 &= 1\ 1225^2 \\
12\ 08775^2 + 77000^2 &= 121\ 1225^2 \\
1232\ 08775^2 + 777000^2 &= 12321\ 1225^2 \\
123432\ 08775^2 + 7777000^2 &= 1234321\ 1225^2 \quad (4.35)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08704^2 + 7200^2 &= 1\ 1296^2 \\
12\ 08704^2 + 79200^2 &= 121\ 1296^2 \\
1232\ 08704^2 + 799200^2 &= 12321\ 1296^2 \\
123432\ 08704^2 + 7999200^2 &= 1234321\ 1296^2 \quad (4.36)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08631^2 + 7400^2 &= 1\ 1369^2 \\
12\ 08631^2 + 81400^2 &= 121\ 1369^2 \\
1232\ 08631^2 + 821400^2 &= 12321\ 1369^2 \\
123432\ 08631^2 + 8221400^2 &= 1234321\ 1369^2 \quad (4.37)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08556^2 + 7600^2 &= 11444^2 \\
1208556^2 + 83600^2 &= 1211444^2 \\
123208556^2 + 843600^2 &= 123211444^2 \\
12343208556^2 + 8443600^2 &= 12343211444^2 \quad (4.38)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08479^2 + 7800^2 &= 11521^2 \\
1208479^2 + 85800^2 &= 1211521^2 \\
123208479^2 + 865800^2 &= 123211521^2 \\
12343208479^2 + 8665800^2 &= 12343211521^2 \quad (4.39)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08400^2 + 8000^2 &= 11600^2 \\
1208400^2 + 88000^2 &= 1211600^2 \\
123208400^2 + 888000^2 &= 123211600^2 \\
12343208400^2 + 8888000^2 &= 12343211600^2 \quad (4.40)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08319^2 + 8200^2 &= 11681^2 \\
1208319^2 + 90200^2 &= 1211681^2 \\
123208319^2 + 910200^2 &= 123211681^2 \\
12343208319^2 + 9110200^2 &= 12343211681^2 \quad (4.41)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08236^2 + 8400^2 &= 11764^2 \\
1208236^2 + 92400^2 &= 1211764^2 \\
123208236^2 + 932400^2 &= 123211764^2 \\
12343208236^2 + 9332400^2 &= 12343211764^2 \quad (4.42)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08151^2 + 8600^2 &= 11849^2 \\
1208151^2 + 94600^2 &= 1211849^2 \\
123208151^2 + 954600^2 &= 123211849^2 \\
12343208151^2 + 9554600^2 &= 12343211849^2 \quad (4.43)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
08064^2 + 8800^2 &= 11936^2 \\
1208064^2 + 96800^2 &= 1211936^2 \\
123208064^2 + 976800^2 &= 123211936^2 \\
12343208064^2 + 9776800^2 &= 12343211936^2 \quad (4.44)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07975^2 + 9000^2 &= 12025^2 \\
1207975^2 + 99000^2 &= 1212025^2 \\
123207975^2 + 999000^2 &= 123212025^2 \\
12343207975^2 + 9999000^2 &= 12343212025^2 \quad (4.45)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07884^2 + 9200^2 &= 12116^2 \\
1207884^2 + 101200^2 &= 1212116^2 \\
123207884^2 + 1021200^2 &= 123212116^2 \\
12343207884^2 + 10221200^2 &= 12343212116^2 \quad (4.46)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07791^2 + 9400^2 &= 12209^2 \\
1207791^2 + 103400^2 &= 1212209^2 \\
123207791^2 + 1043400^2 &= 123212209^2 \\
12343207791^2 + 10443400^2 &= 12343212209^2 \quad (4.47)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07696^2 + 9600^2 &= 12304^2 \\
1207696^2 + 105600^2 &= 1212304^2 \\
123207696^2 + 1065600^2 &= 123212304^2 \\
12343207696^2 + 10665600^2 &= 12343212304^2 \quad (4.48)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07599^2 + 9800^2 &= 12401^2 \\
1207599^2 + 107800^2 &= 1212401^2 \\
123207599^2 + 1087800^2 &= 123212401^2 \\
12343207599^2 + 10887800^2 &= 12343212401^2 \quad (4.49)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07500^2 + 10000^2 &= 12500^2 \\
1207500^2 + 110000^2 &= 1212500^2 \\
123207500^2 + 1110000^2 &= 123212500^2 \\
12343207500^2 + 11110000^2 &= 12343212500^2 \quad (4.50)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07399^2 + 10200^2 &= 12601^2 \\
1207399^2 + 112200^2 &= 1212601^2 \\
123207399^2 + 1132200^2 &= 123212601^2 \\
12343207399^2 + 11332200^2 &= 12343212601^2 \quad (4.51)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07296^2 + 10400^2 &= 12704^2 \\
1207296^2 + 114400^2 &= 1212704^2 \\
123207296^2 + 1154400^2 &= 123212704^2 \\
12343207296^2 + 11554400^2 &= 12343212704^2 \quad (4.52)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07191^2 + 10600^2 &= 1\ 2809^2 \\
12\ 07191^2 + 116600^2 &= 121\ 2809^2 \\
1232\ 07191^2 + 1176600^2 &= 12321\ 2809^2 \\
123432\ 07191^2 + 11776600^2 &= 1234321\ 2809^2 \quad (4.53)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07084^2 + 10800^2 &= 1\ 2916^2 \\
12\ 07084^2 + 118800^2 &= 121\ 2916^2 \\
1232\ 07084^2 + 1198800^2 &= 12321\ 2916^2 \\
123432\ 07084^2 + 11998800^2 &= 1234321\ 2916^2 \quad (4.54)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06975^2 + 11000^2 &= 1\ 3025^2 \\
12\ 06975^2 + 121000^2 &= 121\ 3025^2 \\
1232\ 06975^2 + 1221000^2 &= 12321\ 3025^2 \\
123432\ 06975^2 + 12221000^2 &= 1234321\ 3025^2 \quad (4.55)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06864^2 + 11200^2 &= 1\ 3136^2 \\
12\ 06864^2 + 123200^2 &= 121\ 3136^2 \\
1232\ 06864^2 + 1243200^2 &= 12321\ 3136^2 \\
123432\ 06864^2 + 12443200^2 &= 1234321\ 3136^2 \quad (4.56)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06751^2 + 11400^2 &= 1\ 3249^2 \\
12\ 06751^2 + 125400^2 &= 121\ 3249^2 \\
1232\ 06751^2 + 1265400^2 &= 12321\ 3249^2 \\
123432\ 06751^2 + 12665400^2 &= 1234321\ 3249^2 \quad (4.57)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06636^2 + 11600^2 &= 1\ 3364^2 \\
12\ 06636^2 + 127600^2 &= 121\ 3364^2 \\
1232\ 06636^2 + 1287600^2 &= 12321\ 3364^2 \\
123432\ 06636^2 + 12887600^2 &= 1234321\ 3364^2 \quad (4.58)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06519^2 + 11800^2 &= 1\ 3481^2 \\
12\ 06519^2 + 129800^2 &= 121\ 3481^2 \\
1232\ 06519^2 + 1309800^2 &= 12321\ 3481^2 \\
123432\ 06519^2 + 13109800^2 &= 1234321\ 3481^2 \quad (4.59)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06400^2 + 12000^2 &= 1\ 3600^2 \\
12\ 06400^2 + 132000^2 &= 121\ 3600^2 \\
1232\ 06400^2 + 1332000^2 &= 12321\ 3600^2 \\
123432\ 06400^2 + 13332000^2 &= 1234321\ 3600^2 \quad (4.60)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06279^2 + 12200^2 &= 1\ 3721^2 \\
12\ 06279^2 + 134200^2 &= 121\ 3721^2 \\
1232\ 06279^2 + 1354200^2 &= 12321\ 3721^2 \\
123432\ 06279^2 + 13554200^2 &= 1234321\ 3721^2 \quad (4.61)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06156^2 + 12400^2 &= 1\ 3844^2 \\
12\ 06156^2 + 136400^2 &= 121\ 3844^2 \\
1232\ 06156^2 + 1376400^2 &= 12321\ 3844^2 \\
123432\ 06156^2 + 13776400^2 &= 1234321\ 3844^2 \quad (4.62)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06031^2 + 12600^2 &= 1\ 3969^2 \\
12\ 06031^2 + 138600^2 &= 121\ 3969^2 \\
1232\ 06031^2 + 1398600^2 &= 12321\ 3969^2 \\
123432\ 06031^2 + 13998600^2 &= 1234321\ 3969^2 \quad (4.63)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05904^2 + 12800^2 &= 1\ 4096^2 \\
12\ 05904^2 + 140800^2 &= 121\ 4096^2 \\
1232\ 05904^2 + 1420800^2 &= 12321\ 4096^2 \\
123432\ 05904^2 + 14220800^2 &= 1234321\ 4096^2 \quad (4.64)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05775^2 + 13000^2 &= 1\ 4225^2 \\
12\ 05775^2 + 143000^2 &= 121\ 4225^2 \\
1232\ 05775^2 + 1443000^2 &= 12321\ 4225^2 \\
123432\ 05775^2 + 14443000^2 &= 1234321\ 4225^2 \quad (4.65)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05644^2 + 13200^2 &= 1\ 4356^2 \\
12\ 05644^2 + 145200^2 &= 121\ 4356^2 \\
1232\ 05644^2 + 1465200^2 &= 12321\ 4356^2 \\
123432\ 05644^2 + 14665200^2 &= 1234321\ 4356^2 \quad (4.66)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05511^2 + 13400^2 &= 1\ 4489^2 \\
12\ 05511^2 + 147400^2 &= 121\ 4489^2 \\
1232\ 05511^2 + 1487400^2 &= 12321\ 4489^2 \\
123432\ 05511^2 + 14887400^2 &= 1234321\ 4489^2 \quad (4.67)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05376^2 + 13600^2 &= 1\ 4624^2 \\
12\ 05376^2 + 149600^2 &= 121\ 4624^2 \\
1232\ 05376^2 + 1509600^2 &= 12321\ 4624^2 \\
123432\ 05376^2 + 15109600^2 &= 1234321\ 4624^2 \quad (4.68)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05239^2 + 13800^2 &= 14761^2 \\
1205239^2 + 151800^2 &= 1214761^2 \\
123205239^2 + 1531800^2 &= 123214761^2 \\
12343205239^2 + 15331800^2 &= 12343214761^2 \quad (4.69)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05100^2 + 14000^2 &= 14900^2 \\
1205100^2 + 154000^2 &= 1214900^2 \\
123205100^2 + 1554000^2 &= 123214900^2 \\
12343205100^2 + 15554000^2 &= 12343214900^2 \quad (4.70)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04959^2 + 14200^2 &= 15041^2 \\
1204959^2 + 156200^2 &= 1215041^2 \\
123204959^2 + 1576200^2 &= 123215041^2 \\
12343204959^2 + 15776200^2 &= 12343215041^2 \quad (4.71)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04816^2 + 14400^2 &= 15184^2 \\
1204816^2 + 158400^2 &= 1215184^2 \\
123204816^2 + 1598400^2 &= 123215184^2 \\
12343204816^2 + 15998400^2 &= 12343215184^2 \quad (4.72)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04671^2 + 14600^2 &= 15329^2 \\
1204671^2 + 160600^2 &= 1215329^2 \\
123204671^2 + 1620600^2 &= 123215329^2 \\
12343204671^2 + 16220600^2 &= 12343215329^2 \quad (4.73)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04524^2 + 14800^2 &= 15476^2 \\
1204524^2 + 162800^2 &= 1215476^2 \\
123204524^2 + 1642800^2 &= 123215476^2 \\
12343204524^2 + 16442800^2 &= 12343215476^2 \quad (4.74)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04375^2 + 15000^2 &= 15625^2 \\
1204375^2 + 165000^2 &= 1215625^2 \\
123204375^2 + 1665000^2 &= 123215625^2 \\
12343204375^2 + 16665000^2 &= 12343215625^2 \quad (4.75)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04224^2 + 15200^2 &= 15776^2 \\
1204224^2 + 167200^2 &= 1215776^2 \\
123204224^2 + 1687200^2 &= 123215776^2 \\
12343204224^2 + 16887200^2 &= 12343215776^2 \quad (4.76)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04071^2 + 15400^2 &= 15929^2 \\
1204071^2 + 169400^2 &= 1215929^2 \\
123204071^2 + 1709400^2 &= 123215929^2 \\
12343204071^2 + 17109400^2 &= 12343215929^2 \quad (4.77)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03916^2 + 15600^2 &= 16084^2 \\
1203916^2 + 171600^2 &= 1216084^2 \\
123203916^2 + 1731600^2 &= 123216084^2 \\
12343203916^2 + 17331600^2 &= 12343216084^2 \quad (4.78)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03759^2 + 15800^2 &= 16241^2 \\
1203759^2 + 173800^2 &= 1216241^2 \\
123203759^2 + 1753800^2 &= 123216241^2 \\
12343203759^2 + 17553800^2 &= 12343216241^2 \quad (4.79)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03600^2 + 16000^2 &= 16400^2 \\
1203600^2 + 176000^2 &= 1216400^2 \\
123203600^2 + 1776000^2 &= 123216400^2 \\
12343203600^2 + 17776000^2 &= 12343216400^2 \quad (4.80)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03439^2 + 16200^2 &= 16561^2 \\
1203439^2 + 178200^2 &= 1216561^2 \\
123203439^2 + 1798200^2 &= 123216561^2 \\
12343203439^2 + 17998200^2 &= 12343216561^2 \quad (4.81)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03276^2 + 16400^2 &= 16724^2 \\
1203276^2 + 180400^2 &= 1216724^2 \\
123203276^2 + 1820400^2 &= 123216724^2 \\
12343203276^2 + 18220400^2 &= 12343216724^2 \quad (4.82)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03111^2 + 16600^2 &= 16889^2 \\
1203111^2 + 182600^2 &= 1216889^2 \\
123203111^2 + 1842600^2 &= 123216889^2 \\
12343203111^2 + 18442600^2 &= 12343216889^2 \quad (4.83)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
02944^2 + 16800^2 &= 17056^2 & 01536^2 + 18400^2 &= 18464^2 \\
1202944^2 + 184800^2 &= 1217056^2 & 1201536^2 + 202400^2 &= 1218464^2 \\
123202944^2 + 1864800^2 &= 123217056^2 & 123201536^2 + 2042400^2 &= 123218464^2 \\
12343202944^2 + 18664800^2 &= 12343217056^2 & 12343201536^2 + 20442400^2 &= 12343218464^2
\end{aligned} \tag{4.84} \tag{4.92}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
02775^2 + 17000^2 &= 17225^2 & 01351^2 + 18600^2 &= 18649^2 \\
1202775^2 + 187000^2 &= 1217225^2 & 1201351^2 + 204600^2 &= 1218649^2 \\
123202775^2 + 1887000^2 &= 123217225^2 & 123201351^2 + 2064600^2 &= 123218649^2 \\
12343202775^2 + 18887000^2 &= 12343217225^2 & 12343201351^2 + 20664600^2 &= 12343218649^2
\end{aligned} \tag{4.85} \tag{4.93}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
02604^2 + 17200^2 &= 17396^2 & 01164^2 + 18800^2 &= 18836^2 \\
1202604^2 + 189200^2 &= 1217396^2 & 1201164^2 + 206800^2 &= 1218836^2 \\
123202604^2 + 1909200^2 &= 123217396^2 & 123201164^2 + 2086800^2 &= 123218836^2 \\
12343202604^2 + 19109200^2 &= 12343217396^2 & 12343201164^2 + 20886800^2 &= 12343218836^2
\end{aligned} \tag{4.86} \tag{4.94}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
02431^2 + 17400^2 &= 17569^2 & 00975^2 + 19000^2 &= 19025^2 \\
1202431^2 + 191400^2 &= 1217569^2 & 1200975^2 + 209000^2 &= 1219025^2 \\
123202431^2 + 1931400^2 &= 123217569^2 & 123200975^2 + 2109000^2 &= 123219025^2 \\
12343202431^2 + 19331400^2 &= 12343217569^2 & 12343200975^2 + 21109000^2 &= 12343219025^2
\end{aligned} \tag{4.87} \tag{4.95}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
02256^2 + 17600^2 &= 17744^2 & 00784^2 + 19200^2 &= 19216^2 \\
1202256^2 + 193600^2 &= 1217744^2 & 1200784^2 + 211200^2 &= 1219216^2 \\
123202256^2 + 1953600^2 &= 123217744^2 & 123200784^2 + 2131200^2 &= 123219216^2 \\
12343202256^2 + 19553600^2 &= 12343217744^2 & 12343200784^2 + 21331200^2 &= 12343219216^2
\end{aligned} \tag{4.88} \tag{4.96}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
02079^2 + 17800^2 &= 17921^2 & 00591^2 + 19400^2 &= 19409^2 \\
1202079^2 + 195800^2 &= 1217921^2 & 1200591^2 + 213400^2 &= 1219409^2 \\
123202079^2 + 1975800^2 &= 123217921^2 & 123200591^2 + 2153400^2 &= 123219409^2 \\
12343202079^2 + 19775800^2 &= 12343217921^2 & 12343200591^2 + 21553400^2 &= 12343219409^2
\end{aligned} \tag{4.89} \tag{4.97}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
01900^2 + 18000^2 &= 18100^2 & 00396^2 + 19600^2 &= 19604^2 \\
1201900^2 + 198000^2 &= 1218100^2 & 1200396^2 + 215600^2 &= 1219604^2 \\
123201900^2 + 1998000^2 &= 123218100^2 & 123200396^2 + 2175600^2 &= 123219604^2 \\
12343201900^2 + 19998000^2 &= 12343218100^2 & 12343200396^2 + 21775600^2 &= 12343219604^2
\end{aligned} \tag{4.90} \tag{4.98}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
01719^2 + 18200^2 &= 18281^2 & 00199^2 + 19800^2 &= 19801^2 \\
1201719^2 + 200200^2 &= 1218281^2 & 1200199^2 + 217800^2 &= 1219801^2 \\
123201719^2 + 2020200^2 &= 123218281^2 & 123200199^2 + 2197800^2 &= 123219801^2 \\
12343201719^2 + 20220200^2 &= 12343218281^2 & 12343200199^2 + 21997800^2 &= 12343219801^2
\end{aligned} \tag{4.91} \tag{4.99}$$

4.2 Second Type

• For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 97, 98, 99$:

This subsection is divided in two parts. The first part give first 19 results as complete patterns. The other 80 are written only with four lines. The other four lines follows on similar lines.

4.2.1 First Part

• For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 19$:

Let's consider

$$m = 100, 10100, 1010100, 101010100, 10101010100, 1010101010100, 101010101010100, 10101010101010100, 1010101010101010100$$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 19$; there are 19 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns** given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09999^2 + 200^2 &&= 1\ 0001^2 \\
 &1020\ 09999^2 + 20200^2 &&= 10201\ 0001^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09999^2 + 2020200^2 &&= 102030201\ 0001^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09999^2 + 202020200^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0001^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09999^2 + 20202020200^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0001^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09999^2 + 2020202020200^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0001^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09999^2 + 202020202020200^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0001^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09999^2 + 20202020202020200^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0001^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09999^2 + 20202020202020200^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0001^2 \tag{4.100}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09996^2 + 400^2 &&= 1\ 0004^2 \\
 &1020\ 09996^2 + 40400^2 &&= 10201\ 0004^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09996^2 + 4040400^2 &&= 102030201\ 0004^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09996^2 + 404040400^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0004^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09996^2 + 40404040400^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0004^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09996^2 + 4040404040400^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0004^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09996^2 + 404040404040400^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0004^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09996^2 + 40404040404040400^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0004^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09996^2 + 40404040404040400^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0004^2 \tag{4.101}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09991^2 + 600^2 &&= 1\ 0009^2 \\
 &1020\ 09991^2 + 60600^2 &&= 10201\ 0009^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09991^2 + 6060600^2 &&= 102030201\ 0009^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09991^2 + 606060600^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0009^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09991^2 + 60606060600^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0009^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09991^2 + 6060606060600^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0009^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09991^2 + 606060606060600^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0009^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09991^2 + 60606060606060600^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0009^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09991^2 + 60606060606060600^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0009^2 \tag{4.102}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&09984^2 + 800^2 &&= 1\ 0016^2 \\
&1020\ 09984^2 + 80800^2 &&= 10201\ 0016^2 \\
&10203020\ 09984^2 + 8080800^2 &&= 102030201\ 0016^2 \\
&102030403020\ 09984^2 + 808080800^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0016^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 09984^2 + 80808080800^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0016^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 09984^2 + 8080808080800^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0016^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 09984^2 + 808080808080800^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0016^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 09984^2 + 80808080808080800^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0016^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09984^2 + 8080808080808080800^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0016^2 \quad (4.103)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&09975^2 + 1000^2 &&= 1\ 0025^2 \\
&1020\ 09975^2 + 101000^2 &&= 10201\ 0025^2 \\
&10203020\ 09975^2 + 10101000^2 &&= 102030201\ 0025^2 \\
&102030403020\ 09975^2 + 1010101000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0025^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 09975^2 + 101010101000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0025^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 09975^2 + 10101010101000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0025^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 09975^2 + 1010101010101000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0025^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 09975^2 + 101010101010101000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0025^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09975^2 + 10101010101010101000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0025^2 \quad (4.104)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&09964^2 + 1200^2 &&= 1\ 0036^2 \\
&1020\ 09964^2 + 121200^2 &&= 10201\ 0036^2 \\
&10203020\ 09964^2 + 12121200^2 &&= 102030201\ 0036^2 \\
&102030403020\ 09964^2 + 1212121200^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0036^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 09964^2 + 121212121200^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0036^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 09964^2 + 12121212121200^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0036^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 09964^2 + 1212121212121200^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0036^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 09964^2 + 121212121212121200^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0036^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09964^2 + 12121212121212121200^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0036^2 \quad (4.105)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&09951^2 + 1400^2 &&= 1\ 0049^2 \\
&1020\ 09951^2 + 141400^2 &&= 10201\ 0049^2 \\
&10203020\ 09951^2 + 14141400^2 &&= 102030201\ 0049^2 \\
&102030403020\ 09951^2 + 1414141400^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0049^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 09951^2 + 141414141400^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0049^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 09951^2 + 14141414141400^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0049^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 09951^2 + 1414141414141400^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0049^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 09951^2 + 141414141414141400^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0049^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09951^2 + 14141414141414141400^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0049^2 \quad (4.106)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09936^2 + 1600^2 &&= 1\ 0064^2 \\
 &1020\ 09936^2 + 161600^2 &&= 10201\ 0064^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09936^2 + 16161600^2 &&= 102030201\ 0064^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09936^2 + 1616161600^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0064^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09936^2 + 161616161600^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0064^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09936^2 + 16161616161600^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0064^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09936^2 + 1616161616161600^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0064^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09936^2 + 161616161616161600^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0064^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09936^2 + 16161616161616161600^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0064^2 \tag{4.107}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09919^2 + 1800^2 &&= 1\ 0081^2 \\
 &1020\ 09919^2 + 181800^2 &&= 10201\ 0081^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09919^2 + 18181800^2 &&= 102030201\ 0081^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09919^2 + 1818181800^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0081^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09919^2 + 181818181800^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0081^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09919^2 + 18181818181800^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0081^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09919^2 + 1818181818181800^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0081^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09919^2 + 181818181818181800^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0081^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09919^2 + 18181818181818181800^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0081^2 \tag{4.108}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09900^2 + 2000^2 &&= 1\ 0100^2 \\
 &1020\ 09900^2 + 202000^2 &&= 10201\ 0100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09900^2 + 20202000^2 &&= 102030201\ 0100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09900^2 + 2020202000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09900^2 + 202020202000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09900^2 + 20202020202000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09900^2 + 2020202020202000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09900^2 + 202020202020202000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09900^2 + 20202020202020202000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0100^2 \tag{4.109}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09879^2 + 2200^2 &&= 1\ 0121^2 \\
 &1020\ 09879^2 + 222200^2 &&= 10201\ 0121^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09879^2 + 22222200^2 &&= 102030201\ 0121^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09879^2 + 2222222200^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0121^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09879^2 + 222222222200^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0121^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09879^2 + 22222222222200^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0121^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09879^2 + 2222222222222200^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0121^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09879^2 + 222222222222222200^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0121^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09879^2 + 22222222222222222200^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0121^2 \tag{4.110}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&09856^2 + 2400^2 &&= 1\ 0144^2 \\
&1020\ 09856^2 + 242400^2 &&= 10201\ 0144^2 \\
&10203020\ 09856^2 + 24242400^2 &&= 102030201\ 0144^2 \\
&102030403020\ 09856^2 + 2424242400^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0144^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 09856^2 + 242424242400^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0144^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 09856^2 + 24242424242400^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0144^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 09856^2 + 2424242424242400^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0144^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 09856^2 + 242424242424242400^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0144^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09856^2 + 24242424242424242400^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0144^2 \quad (4.111)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&09831^2 + 2600^2 &&= 1\ 0169^2 \\
&1020\ 09831^2 + 262600^2 &&= 10201\ 0169^2 \\
&10203020\ 09831^2 + 26262600^2 &&= 102030201\ 0169^2 \\
&102030403020\ 09831^2 + 2626262600^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0169^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 09831^2 + 262626262600^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0169^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 09831^2 + 26262626262600^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0169^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 09831^2 + 2626262626262600^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0169^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 09831^2 + 262626262626262600^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0169^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09831^2 + 26262626262626262600^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0169^2 \quad (4.112)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&09804^2 + 2800^2 &&= 1\ 0196^2 \\
&1020\ 09804^2 + 282800^2 &&= 10201\ 0196^2 \\
&10203020\ 09804^2 + 28282800^2 &&= 102030201\ 0196^2 \\
&102030403020\ 09804^2 + 2828282800^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0196^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 09804^2 + 282828282800^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0196^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 09804^2 + 28282828282800^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0196^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 09804^2 + 2828282828282800^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0196^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 09804^2 + 282828282828282800^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0196^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09804^2 + 28282828282828282800^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0196^2 \quad (4.113)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&09775^2 + 3000^2 &&= 10225^2 \\
&1020\ 09775^2 + 303000^2 &&= 10201\ 0225^2 \\
&10203020\ 09775^2 + 30303000^2 &&= 102030201\ 0225^2 \\
&102030403020\ 09775^2 + 3030303000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0225^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 09775^2 + 303030303000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0225^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 09775^2 + 30303030303000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0225^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 09775^2 + 3030303030303000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0225^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 09775^2 + 303030303030303000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0225^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09775^2 + 30303030303030303000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0225^2 \quad (4.114)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09744^2 + 3200^2 &&= 10256^2 \\
 &1020\ 09744^2 + 323200^2 &&= 10201\ 0256^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09744^2 + 32323200^2 &&= 102030201\ 0256^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09744^2 + 3232323200^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0256^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09744^2 + 323232323200^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0256^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09744^2 + 32323232323200^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0256^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09744^2 + 3232323232323200^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0256^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09744^2 + 323232323232323200^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0256^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09744^2 + 32323232323232323200^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0256^2 \tag{4.115}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09711^2 + 3400^2 &&= 10289^2 \\
 &1020\ 09711^2 + 343400^2 &&= 10201\ 0289^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09711^2 + 34343400^2 &&= 102030201\ 0289^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09711^2 + 3434343400^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0289^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09711^2 + 343434343400^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0289^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09711^2 + 34343434343400^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0289^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09711^2 + 3434343434343400^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0289^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09711^2 + 343434343434343400^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0289^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09711^2 + 34343434343434343400^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0289^2 \tag{4.116}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09676^2 + 3600^2 &&= 10324^2 \\
 &1020\ 09676^2 + 363600^2 &&= 10201\ 0324^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09676^2 + 36363600^2 &&= 102030201\ 0324^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09676^2 + 3636363600^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0324^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09676^2 + 363636363600^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0324^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09676^2 + 36363636363600^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0324^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09676^2 + 3636363636363600^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0324^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09676^2 + 363636363636363600^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0324^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09676^2 + 36363636363636363600^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0324^2 \tag{4.117}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &09639^2 + 3800^2 &&= 10361^2 \\
 &1020\ 09639^2 + 383800^2 &&= 10201\ 0361^2 \\
 &10203020\ 09639^2 + 38383800^2 &&= 102030201\ 0361^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 09639^2 + 3838383800^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 0361^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 09639^2 + 383838383800^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 0361^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 09639^2 + 38383838383800^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 0361^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 09639^2 + 3838383838383800^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 0361^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 09639^2 + 383838383838383800^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 0361^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 09639^2 + 38383838383838383800^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 0361^2 \tag{4.118}
 \end{aligned}$$

4.2.2 Second Part

• For $n = 20, 21, 23, \dots, 97, 98, 99$:

Let's consider

$$m = 100, 10100, 1010100, 101010100, 10101010100, 1010101010100, 101010101010100, 10101010101010100, 1010101010101010100$$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 20, 21, 23, \dots, 97, 98, 99$; there are **80 palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns** given below. In each case, only first four values are written. The other 5 values can be written on similar lines.

$$\begin{aligned} 09600^2 + 4000^2 &= 1\ 0400^2 \\ 1020\ 09600^2 + 404000^2 &= 10201\ 0400^2 \\ 10203020\ 09600^2 + 40404000^2 &= 102030201\ 0400^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09600^2 + 4040404000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0400^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.119)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09559^2 + 4200^2 &= 1\ 0441^2 \\ 1020\ 09559^2 + 424200^2 &= 10201\ 0441^2 \\ 10203020\ 09559^2 + 42424200^2 &= 102030201\ 0441^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09559^2 + 4242424200^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0441^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.120)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09516^2 + 4400^2 &= 1\ 0484^2 \\ 1020\ 09516^2 + 444400^2 &= 10201\ 0484^2 \\ 10203020\ 09516^2 + 44444400^2 &= 102030201\ 0484^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09516^2 + 4444444400^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0484^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.121)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09471^2 + 4600^2 &= 1\ 0529^2 \\ 1020\ 09471^2 + 464600^2 &= 10201\ 0529^2 \\ 10203020\ 09471^2 + 46464600^2 &= 102030201\ 0529^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09471^2 + 4646464600^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0529^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.122)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09424^2 + 4800^2 &= 1\ 0576^2 \\ 1020\ 09424^2 + 484800^2 &= 10201\ 0576^2 \\ 10203020\ 09424^2 + 48484800^2 &= 102030201\ 0576^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09424^2 + 4848484800^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0576^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.123)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09375^2 + 5000^2 &= 1\ 0625^2 \\ 1020\ 09375^2 + 505000^2 &= 10201\ 0625^2 \\ 10203020\ 09375^2 + 50505000^2 &= 102030201\ 0625^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09375^2 + 5050505000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0625^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.124)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09324^2 + 5200^2 &= 1\ 0676^2 \\ 1020\ 09324^2 + 525200^2 &= 10201\ 0676^2 \\ 10203020\ 09324^2 + 52525200^2 &= 102030201\ 0676^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09324^2 + 5252525200^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0676^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.125)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09271^2 + 5400^2 &= 1\ 0729^2 \\ 1020\ 09271^2 + 545400^2 &= 10201\ 0729^2 \\ 10203020\ 09271^2 + 54545400^2 &= 102030201\ 0729^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09271^2 + 5454545400^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0729^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.126)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09216^2 + 5600^2 &= 1\ 0784^2 \\ 1020\ 09216^2 + 565600^2 &= 10201\ 0784^2 \\ 10203020\ 09216^2 + 56565600^2 &= 102030201\ 0784^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09216^2 + 5656565600^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0784^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.127)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09159^2 + 5800^2 &= 1\ 0841^2 \\ 1020\ 09159^2 + 585800^2 &= 10201\ 0841^2 \\ 10203020\ 09159^2 + 58585800^2 &= 102030201\ 0841^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09159^2 + 5858585800^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0841^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.128)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09100^2 + 6000^2 &= 1\ 0900^2 \\ 1020\ 09100^2 + 606000^2 &= 10201\ 0900^2 \\ 10203020\ 09100^2 + 60606000^2 &= 102030201\ 0900^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09100^2 + 6060606000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0900^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.129)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09039^2 + 6200^2 &= 1\ 0961^2 \\ 1020\ 09039^2 + 626200^2 &= 10201\ 0961^2 \\ 10203020\ 09039^2 + 62626200^2 &= 102030201\ 0961^2 \\ 102030403020\ 09039^2 + 6262626200^2 &= 1020304030201\ 0961^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.130)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 08976^2 + 6400^2 &= 1\ 1024^2 \\ 1020\ 08976^2 + 646400^2 &= 10201\ 1024^2 \\ 10203020\ 08976^2 + 64646400^2 &= 102030201\ 1024^2 \\ 102030403020\ 08976^2 + 6464646400^2 &= 1020304030201\ 1024^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.131)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 08911^2 + 6600^2 &= 1\ 1089^2 \\ 1020\ 08911^2 + 666600^2 &= 10201\ 1089^2 \\ 10203020\ 08911^2 + 66666600^2 &= 102030201\ 1089^2 \\ 102030403020\ 08911^2 + 6666666600^2 &= 1020304030201\ 1089^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.132)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 08844^2 + 6800^2 &= 1\ 1156^2 \\ 1020\ 08844^2 + 686800^2 &= 10201\ 1156^2 \\ 10203020\ 08844^2 + 68686800^2 &= 102030201\ 1156^2 \\ 102030403020\ 08844^2 + 6868686800^2 &= 1020304030201\ 1156^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.133)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 08775^2 + 7000^2 &= 1\ 1225^2 \\ 1020\ 08775^2 + 707000^2 &= 10201\ 1225^2 \\ 10203020\ 08775^2 + 70707000^2 &= 102030201\ 1225^2 \\ 102030403020\ 08775^2 + 7070707000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 1225^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.134)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 08704^2 + 7200^2 = 1\ 1296^2 \\
& 1020\ 08704^2 + 727200^2 = 10201\ 1296^2 \\
& 10203020\ 08704^2 + 72727200^2 = 102030201\ 1296^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 08704^2 + 7272727200^2 = 1020304030201\ 1296^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.135)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 08631^2 + 7400^2 = 1\ 1369^2 \\
& 1020\ 08631^2 + 747400^2 = 10201\ 1369^2 \\
& 10203020\ 08631^2 + 74747400^2 = 102030201\ 1369^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 08631^2 + 7474747400^2 = 1020304030201\ 1369^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.136)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 08556^2 + 7600^2 = 1\ 1444^2 \\
& 1020\ 08556^2 + 767600^2 = 10201\ 1444^2 \\
& 10203020\ 08556^2 + 76767600^2 = 102030201\ 1444^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 08556^2 + 7676767600^2 = 1020304030201\ 1444^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.137)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 08479^2 + 7800^2 = 1\ 1521^2 \\
& 1020\ 08479^2 + 787800^2 = 10201\ 1521^2 \\
& 10203020\ 08479^2 + 78787800^2 = 102030201\ 1521^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 08479^2 + 7878787800^2 = 1020304030201\ 1521^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.138)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 08400^2 + 8000^2 = 1\ 1600^2 \\
& 1020\ 08400^2 + 808000^2 = 10201\ 1600^2 \\
& 10203020\ 08400^2 + 80808000^2 = 102030201\ 1600^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 08400^2 + 8080808000^2 = 1020304030201\ 1600^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.139)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 08319^2 + 8200^2 = 1\ 1681^2 \\
& 1020\ 08319^2 + 828200^2 = 10201\ 1681^2 \\
& 10203020\ 08319^2 + 82828200^2 = 102030201\ 1681^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 08319^2 + 8282828200^2 = 1020304030201\ 1681^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.140)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 08236^2 + 8400^2 = 1\ 1764^2 \\
& 1020\ 08236^2 + 848400^2 = 10201\ 1764^2 \\
& 10203020\ 08236^2 + 84848400^2 = 102030201\ 1764^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 08236^2 + 8484848400^2 = 1020304030201\ 1764^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.141)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 08151^2 + 8600^2 = 1\ 1849^2 \\
& 1020\ 08151^2 + 868600^2 = 10201\ 1849^2 \\
& 10203020\ 08151^2 + 86868600^2 = 102030201\ 1849^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 08151^2 + 8686868600^2 = 1020304030201\ 1849^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.142)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 08064^2 + 8800^2 = 1\ 1936^2 \\
& 1020\ 08064^2 + 888800^2 = 10201\ 1936^2 \\
& 10203020\ 08064^2 + 88888800^2 = 102030201\ 1936^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 08064^2 + 8888888800^2 = 1020304030201\ 1936^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.143)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 07975^2 + 9000^2 = 1\ 2025^2 \\
& 1020\ 07975^2 + 909000^2 = 10201\ 2025^2 \\
& 10203020\ 07975^2 + 90909000^2 = 102030201\ 2025^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 07975^2 + 9090909000^2 = 1020304030201\ 2025^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.144)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 07884^2 + 9200^2 = 1\ 2116^2 \\
& 1020\ 07884^2 + 929200^2 = 10201\ 2116^2 \\
& 10203020\ 07884^2 + 92929200^2 = 102030201\ 2116^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 07884^2 + 9292929200^2 = 1020304030201\ 2116^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.145)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 07791^2 + 9400^2 = 1\ 2209^2 \\
& 1020\ 07791^2 + 949400^2 = 10201\ 2209^2 \\
& 10203020\ 07791^2 + 94949400^2 = 102030201\ 2209^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 07791^2 + 9494949400^2 = 1020304030201\ 2209^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.146)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 07696^2 + 9600^2 = 1\ 2304^2 \\
& 1020\ 07696^2 + 969600^2 = 10201\ 2304^2 \\
& 10203020\ 07696^2 + 96969600^2 = 102030201\ 2304^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 07696^2 + 9696969600^2 = 1020304030201\ 2304^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.147)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 07599^2 + 9800^2 = 1\ 2401^2 \\
& 1020\ 07599^2 + 989800^2 = 10201\ 2401^2 \\
& 10203020\ 07599^2 + 98989800^2 = 102030201\ 2401^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 07599^2 + 9898989800^2 = 1020304030201\ 2401^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.148)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 07500^2 + 10000^2 = 1\ 2500^2 \\
& 1020\ 07500^2 + 1010000^2 = 10201\ 2500^2 \\
& 10203020\ 07500^2 + 101010000^2 = 102030201\ 2500^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 07500^2 + 10101010000^2 = 1020304030201\ 2500^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.149)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 07399^2 + 10200^2 = 1\ 2601^2 \\
& 1020\ 07399^2 + 1030200^2 = 10201\ 2601^2 \\
& 10203020\ 07399^2 + 103030200^2 = 102030201\ 2601^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 07399^2 + 10303030200^2 = 1020304030201\ 2601^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.150)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 07296^2 + 10400^2 = 1\ 2704^2 \\
& 1020\ 07296^2 + 1050400^2 = 10201\ 2704^2 \\
& 10203020\ 07296^2 + 105050400^2 = 102030201\ 2704^2 \\
& 102030403020\ 07296^2 + 10505050400^2 = 1020304030201\ 2704^2 \\
& \hspace{10em} (4.151)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07191^2 + 10600^2 &= 1\ 2809^2 \\
1020\ 07191^2 + 1070600^2 &= 10201\ 2809^2 \\
10203020\ 07191^2 + 107070600^2 &= 102030201\ 2809^2 \\
102030403020\ 07191^2 + 10707070600^2 &= 1020304030201\ 2809^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.152}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
07084^2 + 10800^2 &= 1\ 2916^2 \\
1020\ 07084^2 + 1090800^2 &= 10201\ 2916^2 \\
10203020\ 07084^2 + 109090800^2 &= 102030201\ 2916^2 \\
102030403020\ 07084^2 + 10909090800^2 &= 1020304030201\ 2916^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.153}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06975^2 + 11000^2 &= 1\ 3025^2 \\
1020\ 06975^2 + 1111000^2 &= 10201\ 3025^2 \\
10203020\ 06975^2 + 111111000^2 &= 102030201\ 3025^2 \\
102030403020\ 06975^2 + 11111111000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 3025^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.154}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06864^2 + 11200^2 &= 1\ 3136^2 \\
1020\ 06864^2 + 1131200^2 &= 10201\ 3136^2 \\
10203020\ 06864^2 + 113131200^2 &= 102030201\ 3136^2 \\
102030403020\ 06864^2 + 11313131200^2 &= 1020304030201\ 3136^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.155}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06751^2 + 11400^2 &= 1\ 3249^2 \\
1020\ 06751^2 + 1151400^2 &= 10201\ 3249^2 \\
10203020\ 06751^2 + 115151400^2 &= 102030201\ 3249^2 \\
102030403020\ 06751^2 + 11515151400^2 &= 1020304030201\ 3249^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.156}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06636^2 + 11600^2 &= 1\ 3364^2 \\
1020\ 06636^2 + 1171600^2 &= 10201\ 3364^2 \\
10203020\ 06636^2 + 117171600^2 &= 102030201\ 3364^2 \\
102030403020\ 06636^2 + 11717171600^2 &= 1020304030201\ 3364^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.157}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06519^2 + 11800^2 &= 1\ 3481^2 \\
1020\ 06519^2 + 1191800^2 &= 10201\ 3481^2 \\
10203020\ 06519^2 + 119191800^2 &= 102030201\ 3481^2 \\
102030403020\ 06519^2 + 11919191800^2 &= 1020304030201\ 3481^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.158}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06400^2 + 12000^2 &= 1\ 3600^2 \\
1020\ 06400^2 + 1212000^2 &= 10201\ 3600^2 \\
10203020\ 06400^2 + 121212000^2 &= 102030201\ 3600^2 \\
102030403020\ 06400^2 + 12121212000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 3600^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.159}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06279^2 + 12200^2 &= 1\ 3721^2 \\
1020\ 06279^2 + 1232200^2 &= 10201\ 3721^2 \\
10203020\ 06279^2 + 123232200^2 &= 102030201\ 3721^2 \\
102030403020\ 06279^2 + 12323232200^2 &= 1020304030201\ 3721^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.160}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06156^2 + 12400^2 &= 1\ 3844^2 \\
1020\ 06156^2 + 1252400^2 &= 10201\ 3844^2 \\
10203020\ 06156^2 + 125252400^2 &= 102030201\ 3844^2 \\
102030403020\ 06156^2 + 12525252400^2 &= 1020304030201\ 3844^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.161}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
06031^2 + 12600^2 &= 1\ 3969^2 \\
1020\ 06031^2 + 1272600^2 &= 10201\ 3969^2 \\
10203020\ 06031^2 + 127272600^2 &= 102030201\ 3969^2 \\
102030403020\ 06031^2 + 12727272600^2 &= 1020304030201\ 3969^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.162}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05904^2 + 12800^2 &= 1\ 4096^2 \\
1020\ 05904^2 + 1292800^2 &= 10201\ 4096^2 \\
10203020\ 05904^2 + 129292800^2 &= 102030201\ 4096^2 \\
102030403020\ 05904^2 + 12929292800^2 &= 1020304030201\ 4096^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.163}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05775^2 + 13000^2 &= 1\ 4225^2 \\
1020\ 05775^2 + 1313000^2 &= 10201\ 4225^2 \\
10203020\ 05775^2 + 131313000^2 &= 102030201\ 4225^2 \\
102030403020\ 05775^2 + 13131313000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 4225^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.164}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05644^2 + 13200^2 &= 1\ 4356^2 \\
1020\ 05644^2 + 1333200^2 &= 10201\ 4356^2 \\
10203020\ 05644^2 + 133333200^2 &= 102030201\ 4356^2 \\
102030403020\ 05644^2 + 13333333200^2 &= 1020304030201\ 4356^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.165}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05511^2 + 13400^2 &= 1\ 4489^2 \\
1020\ 05511^2 + 1353400^2 &= 10201\ 4489^2 \\
10203020\ 05511^2 + 135353400^2 &= 102030201\ 4489^2 \\
102030403020\ 05511^2 + 13535353400^2 &= 1020304030201\ 4489^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.166}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05376^2 + 13600^2 &= 1\ 4624^2 \\
1020\ 05376^2 + 1373600^2 &= 10201\ 4624^2 \\
10203020\ 05376^2 + 137373600^2 &= 102030201\ 4624^2 \\
102030403020\ 05376^2 + 13737373600^2 &= 1020304030201\ 4624^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.167}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05239^2 + 13800^2 &= 1\ 4761^2 \\
1020\ 05239^2 + 1393800^2 &= 10201\ 4761^2 \\
10203020\ 05239^2 + 139393800^2 &= 102030201\ 4761^2 \\
102030403020\ 05239^2 + 13939393800^2 &= 1020304030201\ 4761^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.168}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
05100^2 + 14000^2 &= 14900^2 \\
102005100^2 + 1414000^2 &= 102014900^2 \\
1020302005100^2 + 141414000^2 &= 1020302014900^2 \\
10203040302005100^2 + 14141414000^2 &= 10203040302014900^2 \quad (4.169)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04959^2 + 14200^2 &= 15041^2 \\
102004959^2 + 1434200^2 &= 102015041^2 \\
1020302004959^2 + 143434200^2 &= 1020302015041^2 \\
10203040302004959^2 + 14343434200^2 &= 10203040302015041^2 \quad (4.170)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04816^2 + 14400^2 &= 15184^2 \\
102004816^2 + 1454400^2 &= 102015184^2 \\
1020302004816^2 + 145454400^2 &= 1020302015184^2 \\
10203040302004816^2 + 14545454400^2 &= 10203040302015184^2 \quad (4.171)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04671^2 + 14600^2 &= 15329^2 \\
102004671^2 + 1474600^2 &= 102015329^2 \\
1020302004671^2 + 147474600^2 &= 1020302015329^2 \\
10203040302004671^2 + 14747474600^2 &= 10203040302015329^2 \quad (4.172)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04524^2 + 14800^2 &= 15476^2 \\
102004524^2 + 1494800^2 &= 102015476^2 \\
1020302004524^2 + 149494800^2 &= 1020302015476^2 \\
10203040302004524^2 + 14949494800^2 &= 10203040302015476^2 \quad (4.173)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04375^2 + 15000^2 &= 15625^2 \\
102004375^2 + 1515000^2 &= 102015625^2 \\
1020302004375^2 + 151515000^2 &= 1020302015625^2 \\
10203040302004375^2 + 15151515000^2 &= 10203040302015625^2 \quad (4.174)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04224^2 + 15200^2 &= 15776^2 \\
102004224^2 + 1535200^2 &= 102015776^2 \\
1020302004224^2 + 153535200^2 &= 1020302015776^2 \\
10203040302004224^2 + 15353535200^2 &= 10203040302015776^2 \quad (4.175)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
04071^2 + 15400^2 &= 15929^2 \\
102004071^2 + 1555400^2 &= 102015929^2 \\
1020302004071^2 + 155555400^2 &= 1020302015929^2 \\
10203040302004071^2 + 15555555400^2 &= 10203040302015929^2 \quad (4.176)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03916^2 + 15600^2 &= 16084^2 \\
102003916^2 + 1575600^2 &= 102016084^2 \\
1020302003916^2 + 157575600^2 &= 1020302016084^2 \\
10203040302003916^2 + 15757575600^2 &= 10203040302016084^2 \quad (4.177)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03759^2 + 15800^2 &= 16241^2 \\
102003759^2 + 1595800^2 &= 102016241^2 \\
1020302003759^2 + 159595800^2 &= 1020302016241^2 \\
10203040302003759^2 + 15959595800^2 &= 10203040302016241^2 \quad (4.178)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03600^2 + 16000^2 &= 16400^2 \\
102003600^2 + 1616000^2 &= 102016400^2 \\
1020302003600^2 + 161616000^2 &= 1020302016400^2 \\
10203040302003600^2 + 16161616000^2 &= 10203040302016400^2 \quad (4.179)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03439^2 + 16200^2 &= 16561^2 \\
102003439^2 + 1636200^2 &= 102016561^2 \\
1020302003439^2 + 163636200^2 &= 1020302016561^2 \\
10203040302003439^2 + 16363636200^2 &= 10203040302016561^2 \quad (4.180)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03276^2 + 16400^2 &= 16724^2 \\
102003276^2 + 1656400^2 &= 102016724^2 \\
1020302003276^2 + 165656400^2 &= 1020302016724^2 \\
10203040302003276^2 + 16565656400^2 &= 10203040302016724^2 \quad (4.181)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
03111^2 + 16600^2 &= 16889^2 \\
102003111^2 + 1676600^2 &= 102016889^2 \\
1020302003111^2 + 167676600^2 &= 1020302016889^2 \\
10203040302003111^2 + 16767676600^2 &= 10203040302016889^2 \quad (4.182)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
02944^2 + 16800^2 &= 17056^2 \\
102002944^2 + 1696800^2 &= 102017056^2 \\
1020302002944^2 + 169696800^2 &= 1020302017056^2 \\
10203040302002944^2 + 16969696800^2 &= 10203040302017056^2 \quad (4.183)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
02775^2 + 17000^2 &= 17225^2 \\
102002775^2 + 1717000^2 &= 102017225^2 \\
1020302002775^2 + 171717000^2 &= 1020302017225^2 \\
10203040302002775^2 + 17171717000^2 &= 10203040302017225^2 \quad (4.184)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
02604^2 + 17200^2 &= 17396^2 \\
102002604^2 + 1737200^2 &= 102017396^2 \\
1020302002604^2 + 173737200^2 &= 1020302017396^2 \\
10203040302002604^2 + 17373737200^2 &= 10203040302017396^2 \quad (4.185)
\end{aligned}$$

$02431^2 + 17400^2 = 17569^2$	$01164^2 + 18800^2 = 18836^2$
$102002431^2 + 1757400^2 = 102017569^2$	$102001164^2 + 1898800^2 = 102018836^2$
$1020302002431^2 + 175757400^2 = 1020302017569^2$	$1020302001164^2 + 189898800^2 = 1020302018836^2$
$10203040302002431^2 + 17575757400^2 = 10203040302017569^2$ (4.186)	$10203040302001164^2 + 18989898800^2 = 10203040302018836^2$ (4.193)
$02256^2 + 17600^2 = 17744^2$	$00975^2 + 19000^2 = 19025^2$
$102002256^2 + 1777600^2 = 102017744^2$	$102000975^2 + 1919000^2 = 102019025^2$
$1020302002256^2 + 177777600^2 = 1020302017744^2$	$1020302000975^2 + 191919000^2 = 1020302019025^2$
$10203040302002256^2 + 17777777600^2 = 10203040302017744^2$ (4.187)	$10203040302000975^2 + 19191919000^2 = 10203040302019025^2$ (4.194)
$02079^2 + 17800^2 = 17921^2$	$00784^2 + 19200^2 = 19216^2$
$102002079^2 + 1797800^2 = 102017921^2$	$102000784^2 + 1939200^2 = 102019216^2$
$1020302002079^2 + 179797800^2 = 1020302017921^2$	$1020302000784^2 + 193939200^2 = 1020302019216^2$
$10203040302002079^2 + 17979797800^2 = 10203040302017921^2$ (4.188)	$10203040302000784^2 + 19393939200^2 = 10203040302019216^2$ (4.195)
$01900^2 + 18000^2 = 18100^2$	$00591^2 + 19400^2 = 19409^2$
$102001900^2 + 1818000^2 = 102018100^2$	$102000591^2 + 1959400^2 = 102019409^2$
$1020302001900^2 + 181818000^2 = 1020302018100^2$	$1020302000591^2 + 195959400^2 = 1020302019409^2$
$10203040302001900^2 + 18181818000^2 = 10203040302018100^2$ (4.189)	$10203040302000591^2 + 19595959400^2 = 10203040302019409^2$ (4.196)
$01719^2 + 18200^2 = 18281^2$	$00396^2 + 19600^2 = 19604^2$
$102001719^2 + 1838200^2 = 102018281^2$	$102000396^2 + 1979600^2 = 102019604^2$
$1020302001719^2 + 183838200^2 = 1020302018281^2$	$1020302000396^2 + 197979600^2 = 1020302019604^2$
$10203040302001719^2 + 18383838200^2 = 10203040302018281^2$ (4.190)	$10203040302000396^2 + 19797979600^2 = 10203040302019604^2$ (4.197)
$01536^2 + 18400^2 = 18464^2$	$00199^2 + 19800^2 = 19801^2$
$102001536^2 + 1858400^2 = 102018464^2$	$102000199^2 + 1999800^2 = 102019801^2$
$1020302001536^2 + 185858400^2 = 1020302018464^2$	$1020302000199^2 + 19999800^2 = 1020302019801^2$
$10203040302001536^2 + 18585858400^2 = 10203040302018464^2$ (4.191)	$10203040302000199^2 + 199999800^2 = 10203040302019801^2$ (4.198)
$01351^2 + 18600^2 = 18649^2$	
$102001351^2 + 1878600^2 = 102018649^2$	
$1020302001351^2 + 187878600^2 = 1020302018649^2$	
$10203040302001351^2 + 18787878600^2 = 10203040302018649^2$ (4.192)	

Based on above 99 results given in subsections 4.1 and 4.2.2, below are some remarks:

4.3 Remarks

- (i) The **first line** of first pattern (4.1) and (4.100) is the **second line** as given in pattern (2.1) or (2.3), i.e.,

$$9999^2 + 200^2 = 10001^2.$$

(ii) There is a symmetry in squared values for last two digits of each Example:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Examples (4.2) and (4.101)} &\Rightarrow 0004 = 2^2 \\
 \text{Examples (4.3) and (4.102)} &\Rightarrow 0009 = 3^2 \\
 \text{Examples (4.4) and (4.103)} &\Rightarrow 0016 = 4^2 \\
 \dots &\dots \\
 \dots &\dots \\
 \text{Examples (4.97) and (4.196)} &\Rightarrow 9409 = 97^2 \\
 \text{Examples (4.98) and (4.197)} &\Rightarrow 9604 = 98^2 \\
 \text{Examples (4.99) and (4.198)} &\Rightarrow 9801 = 99^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

(iii) The sum of the **last four digits** of first and third members of each line is equal, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Examples (4.1) and (4.100)} &\Rightarrow 9999 + 0001 = 10000 \\
 \text{Examples (4.2) and (4.101)} &\Rightarrow 9996 + 0004 = 10000 \\
 \text{Examples (4.3) and (4.102)} &\Rightarrow 9991 + 0009 = 10000 \\
 \text{Examples (4.4) and (4.103)} &\Rightarrow 9984 + 0016 = 10000 \\
 \dots &\dots \\
 \dots &\dots \\
 \text{Examples (4.97) and (4.196)} &\Rightarrow 0591 + 9409 = 10000 \\
 \text{Examples (4.98) and (4.197)} &\Rightarrow 0396 + 9604 = 10000 \\
 \text{Examples (4.99) and (4.198)} &\Rightarrow 0199 + 9801 = 10000
 \end{aligned}$$

(iv) In many cases, the second term in the first line is out of pattern, but the continuations is well patterned. From $n = 20$ to 99, we have written only first four lines. The rest 5 lines follows on similar way as of $n=1$ to 19 given in subsections 4.1 and 4.2.2.

5 Third Block

Below are 999 examples of **pattern in Pythagorean triples** with 9 digits from 1 to 9 written as **palindromic-type**, where the **first line** of first pattern is the same as **third line** of example (2.1) or (2.3). First 19 examples are complete. Then from 20 to 999, the results are written in reduced form. These can be completed on similar lines.

5.1 First Type

- For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 997, 998, 999$:

This subsection is divided in two parts. The first part give first 19 results give complete patterns. The other 80 are with first four lines.

5.1.1 First Part

- For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 19$:

Let's consider

$$m = 1000, 11000, 111000, 1111000, 11111000, 111111000, 1111111000, 11111111000, 111111111000$$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 19$; there are 19 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns** given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 0999999^2 + 2000^2 &= 1\ 000001^2 \\
 12\ 0999999^2 + 22000^2 &= 121\ 000001^2 \\
 1232\ 0999999^2 + 222000^2 &= 12321\ 000001^2 \\
 123432\ 0999999^2 + 2222000^2 &= 1234321\ 000001^2 \\
 12345432\ 0999999^2 + 22222000^2 &= 123454321\ 000001^2 \\
 1234565432\ 0999999^2 + 222222000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000001^2 \\
 123456765432\ 0999999^2 + 2222222000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000001^2 \\
 12345678765432\ 0999999^2 + 22222222000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000001^2 \\
 1234567898765432\ 0999999^2 + 222222222000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000001^2 \quad (5.1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 0999996^2 + 4000^2 &= 1\ 000004^2 \\
 12\ 0999996^2 + 44000^2 &= 121\ 000004^2 \\
 1232\ 0999996^2 + 444000^2 &= 12321\ 000004^2 \\
 123432\ 0999996^2 + 4444000^2 &= 1234321\ 000004^2 \\
 12345432\ 0999996^2 + 44444000^2 &= 123454321\ 000004^2 \\
 1234565432\ 0999996^2 + 444444000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000004^2 \\
 123456765432\ 0999996^2 + 4444444000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000004^2 \\
 12345678765432\ 0999996^2 + 44444444000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000004^2 \\
 1234567898765432\ 0999996^2 + 444444444000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000004^2 \quad (5.2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999991^2 + 6000^2 &= 1\ 000009^2 \\
12\ 0999991^2 + 66000^2 &= 121\ 000009^2 \\
1232\ 0999991^2 + 666000^2 &= 12321\ 000009^2 \\
123432\ 0999991^2 + 6666000^2 &= 1234321\ 000009^2 \\
12345432\ 0999991^2 + 66666000^2 &= 123454321\ 000009^2 \\
1234565432\ 0999991^2 + 666666000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000009^2 \\
123456765432\ 0999991^2 + 6666666000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000009^2 \\
12345678765432\ 0999991^2 + 66666666000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000009^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 0999991^2 + 666666666000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000009^2 \quad (5.3)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999984^2 + 8000^2 &= 1\ 000016^2 \\
12\ 0999984^2 + 88000^2 &= 121\ 000016^2 \\
1232\ 0999984^2 + 888000^2 &= 12321\ 000016^2 \\
123432\ 0999984^2 + 8888000^2 &= 1234321\ 000016^2 \\
12345432\ 0999984^2 + 88888000^2 &= 123454321\ 000016^2 \\
1234565432\ 0999984^2 + 888888000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000016^2 \\
123456765432\ 0999984^2 + 8888888000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000016^2 \\
12345678765432\ 0999984^2 + 88888888000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000016^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 0999984^2 + 888888888000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000016^2 \quad (5.4)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999975^2 + 10000^2 &= 1\ 000025^2 \\
12\ 0999975^2 + 110000^2 &= 121\ 000025^2 \\
1232\ 0999975^2 + 1110000^2 &= 12321\ 000025^2 \\
123432\ 0999975^2 + 11110000^2 &= 1234321\ 000025^2 \\
12345432\ 0999975^2 + 111110000^2 &= 123454321\ 000025^2 \\
1234565432\ 0999975^2 + 1111110000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000025^2 \\
123456765432\ 0999975^2 + 11111110000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000025^2 \\
12345678765432\ 0999975^2 + 111111110000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000025^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 0999975^2 + 1111111110000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000025^2 \quad (5.5)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999964^2 + 12000^2 &= 1\ 000036^2 \\
12\ 0999964^2 + 132000^2 &= 121\ 000036^2 \\
1232\ 0999964^2 + 1332000^2 &= 12321\ 000036^2 \\
123432\ 0999964^2 + 13332000^2 &= 1234321\ 000036^2 \\
12345432\ 0999964^2 + 133332000^2 &= 123454321\ 000036^2 \\
1234565432\ 0999964^2 + 1333332000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000036^2 \\
123456765432\ 0999964^2 + 13333332000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000036^2 \\
12345678765432\ 0999964^2 + 133333332000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000036^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 0999964^2 + 1333333332000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000036^2 \quad (5.6)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999951^2 + 14000^2 &= 1\ 000049^2 \\
12\ 0999951^2 + 154000^2 &= 121\ 000049^2 \\
1232\ 0999951^2 + 1554000^2 &= 12321\ 000049^2 \\
123432\ 0999951^2 + 15554000^2 &= 1234321\ 000049^2 \\
12345432\ 0999951^2 + 155554000^2 &= 123454321\ 000049^2 \\
1234565432\ 0999951^2 + 1555554000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000049^2 \\
123456765432\ 0999951^2 + 15555554000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000049^2 \\
12345678765432\ 0999951^2 + 155555554000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000049^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 0999951^2 + 1555555554000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000049^2 \quad (5.7)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999936^2 + 16000^2 &= 1\ 000064^2 \\
12\ 0999936^2 + 176000^2 &= 121\ 000064^2 \\
1232\ 0999936^2 + 1776000^2 &= 12321\ 000064^2 \\
123432\ 0999936^2 + 17776000^2 &= 1234321\ 000064^2 \\
12345432\ 0999936^2 + 177776000^2 &= 123454321\ 000064^2 \\
1234565432\ 0999936^2 + 1777776000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000064^2 \\
123456765432\ 0999936^2 + 17777776000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000064^2 \\
12345678765432\ 0999936^2 + 177777776000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000064^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 0999936^2 + 1777777776000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000064^2 \quad (5.8)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999919^2 + 18000^2 &= 1\ 000081^2 \\
12\ 0999919^2 + 198000^2 &= 121\ 000081^2 \\
1232\ 0999919^2 + 1998000^2 &= 12321\ 000081^2 \\
123432\ 0999919^2 + 19998000^2 &= 1234321\ 000081^2 \\
12345432\ 0999919^2 + 199998000^2 &= 123454321\ 000081^2 \\
1234565432\ 0999919^2 + 1999998000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000081^2 \\
123456765432\ 0999919^2 + 19999998000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000081^2 \\
12345678765432\ 0999919^2 + 199999998000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000081^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 0999919^2 + 1999999998000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000081^2 \quad (5.9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999900^2 + 20000^2 &= 1\ 000100^2 \\
12\ 0999900^2 + 220000^2 &= 121\ 000100^2 \\
1232\ 0999900^2 + 2220000^2 &= 12321\ 000100^2 \\
123432\ 0999900^2 + 22220000^2 &= 1234321\ 000100^2 \\
12345432\ 0999900^2 + 222220000^2 &= 123454321\ 000100^2 \\
1234565432\ 0999900^2 + 2222220000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000100^2 \\
123456765432\ 0999900^2 + 22222220000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000100^2 \\
12345678765432\ 0999900^2 + 222222220000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000100^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 0999900^2 + 2222222220000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000100^2 \quad (5.10)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999879^2 + 22000^2 &= 1\ 000121^2 \\
12\ 0999879^2 + 242000^2 &= 121\ 000121^2 \\
1232\ 0999879^2 + 2442000^2 &= 12321\ 000121^2 \\
123432\ 0999879^2 + 24442000^2 &= 1234321\ 000121^2 \\
12345432\ 0999879^2 + 244442000^2 &= 123454321\ 000121^2 \\
1234565432\ 0999879^2 + 2444442000^2 &= 12345654321\ 000121^2 \\
123456765432\ 0999879^2 + 24444442000^2 &= 1234567654321\ 000121^2 \\
12345678765432\ 0999879^2 + 244444442000^2 &= 123456787654321\ 000121^2 \\
1234567898765432\ 0999879^2 + 2444444442000^2 &= 12345678987654321\ 000121^2 \quad (5.11)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999856^2 + 24000^2 &= 1\,000144^2 \\
12\,0999856^2 + 264000^2 &= 121\,000144^2 \\
1232\,0999856^2 + 2664000^2 &= 12321\,000144^2 \\
123432\,0999856^2 + 26664000^2 &= 1234321\,000144^2 \\
12345432\,0999856^2 + 266664000^2 &= 123454321\,000144^2 \\
1234565432\,0999856^2 + 2666664000^2 &= 12345654321\,000144^2 \\
123456765432\,0999856^2 + 26666664000^2 &= 1234567654321\,000144^2 \\
12345678765432\,0999856^2 + 266666664000^2 &= 123456787654321\,000144^2 \\
1234567898765432\,0999856^2 + 2666666664000^2 &= 12345678987654321\,000144^2 \quad (5.12)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999831^2 + 26000^2 &= 1\,000169^2 \\
12\,0999831^2 + 286000^2 &= 121\,000169^2 \\
1232\,0999831^2 + 2886000^2 &= 12321\,000169^2 \\
123432\,0999831^2 + 28886000^2 &= 1234321\,000169^2 \\
12345432\,0999831^2 + 288886000^2 &= 123454321\,000169^2 \\
1234565432\,0999831^2 + 2888886000^2 &= 12345654321\,000169^2 \\
123456765432\,0999831^2 + 28888886000^2 &= 1234567654321\,000169^2 \\
12345678765432\,0999831^2 + 288888886000^2 &= 123456787654321\,000169^2 \\
1234567898765432\,0999831^2 + 2888888886000^2 &= 12345678987654321\,000169^2 \quad (5.13)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999804^2 + 28000^2 &= 1\,000196^2 \\
12\,0999804^2 + 308000^2 &= 121\,000196^2 \\
1232\,0999804^2 + 3108000^2 &= 12321\,000196^2 \\
123432\,0999804^2 + 31108000^2 &= 1234321\,000196^2 \\
12345432\,0999804^2 + 311108000^2 &= 123454321\,000196^2 \\
1234565432\,0999804^2 + 3111108000^2 &= 12345654321\,000196^2 \\
123456765432\,0999804^2 + 31111108000^2 &= 1234567654321\,000196^2 \\
12345678765432\,0999804^2 + 311111108000^2 &= 123456787654321\,000196^2 \\
1234567898765432\,0999804^2 + 3111111108000^2 &= 12345678987654321\,000196^2 \quad (5.14)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999775^2 + 30000^2 &= 1\,000225^2 \\
12\,0999775^2 + 330000^2 &= 121\,000225^2 \\
1232\,0999775^2 + 3330000^2 &= 12321\,000225^2 \\
123432\,0999775^2 + 33330000^2 &= 1234321\,000225^2 \\
12345432\,0999775^2 + 333330000^2 &= 123454321\,000225^2 \\
1234565432\,0999775^2 + 3333330000^2 &= 12345654321\,000225^2 \\
123456765432\,0999775^2 + 33333330000^2 &= 1234567654321\,000225^2 \\
12345678765432\,0999775^2 + 333333330000^2 &= 123456787654321\,000225^2 \\
1234567898765432\,0999775^2 + 3333333330000^2 &= 12345678987654321\,000225^2 \quad (5.15)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999744^2 + 32000^2 &= 1\,000256^2 \\
12\,0999744^2 + 352000^2 &= 121\,000256^2 \\
1232\,0999744^2 + 3552000^2 &= 12321\,000256^2 \\
123432\,0999744^2 + 35552000^2 &= 1234321\,000256^2 \\
12345432\,0999744^2 + 355552000^2 &= 123454321\,000256^2 \\
1234565432\,0999744^2 + 3555552000^2 &= 12345654321\,000256^2 \\
123456765432\,0999744^2 + 35555552000^2 &= 1234567654321\,000256^2 \\
12345678765432\,0999744^2 + 355555552000^2 &= 123456787654321\,000256^2 \\
1234567898765432\,0999744^2 + 3555555552000^2 &= 12345678987654321\,000256^2 \quad (5.16)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999711^2 + 34000^2 &= 1\,000289^2 \\
12\,0999711^2 + 374000^2 &= 121\,000289^2 \\
1232\,0999711^2 + 3774000^2 &= 12321\,000289^2 \\
123432\,0999711^2 + 37774000^2 &= 1234321\,000289^2 \\
12345432\,0999711^2 + 377774000^2 &= 123454321\,000289^2 \\
1234565432\,0999711^2 + 3777774000^2 &= 12345654321\,000289^2 \\
123456765432\,0999711^2 + 37777774000^2 &= 1234567654321\,000289^2 \\
12345678765432\,0999711^2 + 377777774000^2 &= 123456787654321\,000289^2 \\
1234567898765432\,0999711^2 + 3777777774000^2 &= 12345678987654321\,000289^2 \quad (5.17)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999676^2 + 36000^2 &= 1\,000324^2 \\
12\,0999676^2 + 396000^2 &= 121\,000324^2 \\
1232\,0999676^2 + 3996000^2 &= 12321\,000324^2 \\
123432\,0999676^2 + 39996000^2 &= 1234321\,000324^2 \\
12345432\,0999676^2 + 399996000^2 &= 123454321\,000324^2 \\
1234565432\,0999676^2 + 3999996000^2 &= 12345654321\,000324^2 \\
123456765432\,0999676^2 + 39999996000^2 &= 1234567654321\,000324^2 \\
12345678765432\,0999676^2 + 399999996000^2 &= 123456787654321\,000324^2 \\
1234567898765432\,0999676^2 + 3999999996000^2 &= 12345678987654321\,000324^2 \quad (5.18)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999639^2 + 38000^2 &= 1\,000361^2 \\
12\,0999639^2 + 418000^2 &= 121\,000361^2 \\
1232\,0999639^2 + 4218000^2 &= 12321\,000361^2 \\
123432\,0999639^2 + 42218000^2 &= 1234321\,000361^2 \\
12345432\,0999639^2 + 422218000^2 &= 123454321\,000361^2 \\
1234565432\,0999639^2 + 4222218000^2 &= 12345654321\,000361^2 \\
123456765432\,0999639^2 + 42222218000^2 &= 1234567654321\,000361^2 \\
12345678765432\,0999639^2 + 422222218000^2 &= 123456787654321\,000361^2 \\
1234567898765432\,0999639^2 + 4222222218000^2 &= 12345678987654321\,000361^2 \quad (5.19)
\end{aligned}$$

5.1.2 Second Part

For $n = 20, 21, 22, \dots, 97, 98, 99 \dots, 997, 998, 999$:

Let's consider

$$m = 1000, 11000, 111000, 1111000, 11111000, 111111000, 1111111000, 11111111000, 111111111000$$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 20, 21, 22, \dots, 97, 98, 99 \dots, 997, 998, 999$; there are 980 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns** given below. In each case, only first four values are written. The other 5 values can be written in a similar way.

$$\begin{aligned}
0999600^2 + 40000^2 &= 1\,000400^2 & 0999559^2 + 42000^2 &= 1\,000441^2 \\
12\,0999600^2 + 440000^2 &= 121\,000400^2 & 12\,0999559^2 + 462000^2 &= 121\,000441^2 \\
1232\,0999600^2 + 4440000^2 &= 12321\,000400^2 & 1232\,0999559^2 + 4662000^2 &= 12321\,000441^2 \\
123432\,0999600^2 + 44440000^2 &= 1234321\,000400^2 \quad (5.20) & 123432\,0999559^2 + 46662000^2 &= 1234321\,000441^2 \quad (5.21)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999516^2 + 44000^2 &= 1\ 000484^2 \\
12\ 0999516^2 + 484000^2 &= 121\ 000484^2 \\
1232\ 0999516^2 + 4884000^2 &= 12321\ 000484^2 \\
123432\ 0999516^2 + 48884000^2 &= 1234321\ 000484^2 \quad (5.22)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999039^2 + 62000^2 &= 1\ 000961^2 \\
12\ 0999039^2 + 682000^2 &= 121\ 000961^2 \\
1232\ 0999039^2 + 6882000^2 &= 12321\ 000961^2 \\
123432\ 0999039^2 + 68882000^2 &= 1234321\ 000961^2 \quad (5.31)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999471^2 + 46000^2 &= 1\ 000529^2 \\
12\ 0999471^2 + 506000^2 &= 121\ 000529^2 \\
1232\ 0999471^2 + 5106000^2 &= 12321\ 000529^2 \\
123432\ 0999471^2 + 51106000^2 &= 1234321\ 000529^2 \quad (5.23)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998976^2 + 64000^2 &= 1\ 001024^2 \\
12\ 0998976^2 + 704000^2 &= 121\ 001024^2 \\
1232\ 0998976^2 + 7104000^2 &= 12321\ 001024^2 \\
123432\ 0998976^2 + 71104000^2 &= 1234321\ 001024^2 \quad (5.32)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999424^2 + 48000^2 &= 1\ 000576^2 \\
12\ 0999424^2 + 528000^2 &= 121\ 000576^2 \\
1232\ 0999424^2 + 5328000^2 &= 12321\ 000576^2 \\
123432\ 0999424^2 + 53328000^2 &= 1234321\ 000576^2 \quad (5.24)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998911^2 + 66000^2 &= 1\ 001089^2 \\
12\ 0998911^2 + 726000^2 &= 121\ 001089^2 \\
1232\ 0998911^2 + 7326000^2 &= 12321\ 001089^2 \\
123432\ 0998911^2 + 73326000^2 &= 1234321\ 001089^2 \quad (5.33)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999375^2 + 50000^2 &= 1\ 000625^2 \\
12\ 0999375^2 + 550000^2 &= 121\ 000625^2 \\
1232\ 0999375^2 + 5550000^2 &= 12321\ 000625^2 \\
123432\ 0999375^2 + 55550000^2 &= 1234321\ 000625^2 \quad (5.25)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998844^2 + 68000^2 &= 1\ 001156^2 \\
12\ 0998844^2 + 748000^2 &= 121\ 001156^2 \\
1232\ 0998844^2 + 7548000^2 &= 12321\ 001156^2 \\
123432\ 0998844^2 + 75548000^2 &= 1234321\ 001156^2 \quad (5.34)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999324^2 + 52000^2 &= 1\ 000676^2 \\
12\ 0999324^2 + 572000^2 &= 121\ 000676^2 \\
1232\ 0999324^2 + 5772000^2 &= 12321\ 000676^2 \\
123432\ 0999324^2 + 57772000^2 &= 1234321\ 000676^2 \quad (5.26)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998775^2 + 70000^2 &= 1\ 001225^2 \\
12\ 0998775^2 + 770000^2 &= 121\ 001225^2 \\
1232\ 0998775^2 + 7770000^2 &= 12321\ 001225^2 \\
123432\ 0998775^2 + 77770000^2 &= 1234321\ 001225^2 \quad (5.35)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999271^2 + 54000^2 &= 1\ 000729^2 \\
12\ 0999271^2 + 594000^2 &= 121\ 000729^2 \\
1232\ 0999271^2 + 5994000^2 &= 12321\ 000729^2 \\
123432\ 0999271^2 + 59994000^2 &= 1234321\ 000729^2 \quad (5.27)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998704^2 + 72000^2 &= 1\ 001296^2 \\
12\ 0998704^2 + 792000^2 &= 121\ 001296^2 \\
1232\ 0998704^2 + 7992000^2 &= 12321\ 001296^2 \\
123432\ 0998704^2 + 79992000^2 &= 1234321\ 001296^2 \quad (5.36)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999216^2 + 56000^2 &= 1\ 000784^2 \\
12\ 0999216^2 + 616000^2 &= 121\ 000784^2 \\
1232\ 0999216^2 + 6216000^2 &= 12321\ 000784^2 \\
123432\ 0999216^2 + 62216000^2 &= 1234321\ 000784^2 \quad (5.28)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998631^2 + 74000^2 &= 1\ 001369^2 \\
12\ 0998631^2 + 814000^2 &= 121\ 001369^2 \\
1232\ 0998631^2 + 8214000^2 &= 12321\ 001369^2 \\
123432\ 0998631^2 + 82214000^2 &= 1234321\ 001369^2 \quad (5.37)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999159^2 + 58000^2 &= 1\ 000841^2 \\
12\ 0999159^2 + 638000^2 &= 121\ 000841^2 \\
1232\ 0999159^2 + 6438000^2 &= 12321\ 000841^2 \\
123432\ 0999159^2 + 64438000^2 &= 1234321\ 000841^2 \quad (5.29)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998556^2 + 76000^2 &= 1\ 001444^2 \\
12\ 0998556^2 + 836000^2 &= 121\ 001444^2 \\
1232\ 0998556^2 + 8436000^2 &= 12321\ 001444^2 \\
123432\ 0998556^2 + 84436000^2 &= 1234321\ 001444^2 \quad (5.38)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0999100^2 + 60000^2 &= 1\ 000900^2 \\
12\ 0999100^2 + 660000^2 &= 121\ 000900^2 \\
1232\ 0999100^2 + 6660000^2 &= 12321\ 000900^2 \\
123432\ 0999100^2 + 66660000^2 &= 1234321\ 000900^2 \quad (5.30)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998479^2 + 78000^2 &= 1\ 001521^2 \\
12\ 0998479^2 + 858000^2 &= 121\ 001521^2 \\
1232\ 0998479^2 + 8658000^2 &= 12321\ 001521^2 \\
123432\ 0998479^2 + 86658000^2 &= 1234321\ 001521^2 \quad (5.39)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998400^2 + 80000^2 &= 1\ 001600^2 \\
12\ 0998400^2 + 880000^2 &= 121\ 001600^2 \\
1232\ 0998400^2 + 8880000^2 &= 12321\ 001600^2 \\
123432\ 0998400^2 + 88880000^2 &= 1234321\ 001600^2 \quad (5.40)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997599^2 + 98000^2 &= 1\ 002401^2 \\
12\ 0997599^2 + 1078000^2 &= 121\ 002401^2 \\
1232\ 0997599^2 + 10878000^2 &= 12321\ 002401^2 \\
123432\ 0997599^2 + 108878000^2 &= 1234321\ 002401^2 \quad (5.49)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998319^2 + 82000^2 &= 1\ 001681^2 \\
12\ 0998319^2 + 902000^2 &= 121\ 001681^2 \\
1232\ 0998319^2 + 9102000^2 &= 12321\ 001681^2 \\
123432\ 0998319^2 + 91102000^2 &= 1234321\ 001681^2 \quad (5.41)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997500^2 + 100000^2 &= 1\ 002500^2 \\
12\ 0997500^2 + 1100000^2 &= 121\ 002500^2 \\
1232\ 0997500^2 + 11100000^2 &= 12321\ 002500^2 \\
123432\ 0997500^2 + 111100000^2 &= 1234321\ 002500^2 \quad (5.50)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998236^2 + 84000^2 &= 1\ 001764^2 \\
12\ 0998236^2 + 924000^2 &= 121\ 001764^2 \\
1232\ 0998236^2 + 9324000^2 &= 12321\ 001764^2 \\
123432\ 0998236^2 + 93324000^2 &= 1234321\ 001764^2 \quad (5.42)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997399^2 + 102000^2 &= 1\ 002601^2 \\
12\ 0997399^2 + 1122000^2 &= 121\ 002601^2 \\
1232\ 0997399^2 + 11322000^2 &= 12321\ 002601^2 \\
123432\ 0997399^2 + 113322000^2 &= 1234321\ 002601^2 \quad (5.51)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998151^2 + 86000^2 &= 1\ 001849^2 \\
12\ 0998151^2 + 946000^2 &= 121\ 001849^2 \\
1232\ 0998151^2 + 9546000^2 &= 12321\ 001849^2 \\
123432\ 0998151^2 + 95546000^2 &= 1234321\ 001849^2 \quad (5.43)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997296^2 + 104000^2 &= 1\ 002704^2 \\
12\ 0997296^2 + 1144000^2 &= 121\ 002704^2 \\
1232\ 0997296^2 + 11544000^2 &= 12321\ 002704^2 \\
123432\ 0997296^2 + 115544000^2 &= 1234321\ 002704^2 \quad (5.52)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0998064^2 + 88000^2 &= 1\ 001936^2 \\
12\ 0998064^2 + 968000^2 &= 121\ 001936^2 \\
1232\ 0998064^2 + 9768000^2 &= 12321\ 001936^2 \\
123432\ 0998064^2 + 97768000^2 &= 1234321\ 001936^2 \quad (5.44)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997191^2 + 106000^2 &= 1\ 002809^2 \\
12\ 0997191^2 + 1166000^2 &= 121\ 002809^2 \\
1232\ 0997191^2 + 11766000^2 &= 12321\ 002809^2 \\
123432\ 0997191^2 + 117766000^2 &= 1234321\ 002809^2 \quad (5.53)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997975^2 + 90000^2 &= 1\ 002025^2 \\
12\ 0997975^2 + 990000^2 &= 121\ 002025^2 \\
1232\ 0997975^2 + 9990000^2 &= 12321\ 002025^2 \\
123432\ 0997975^2 + 99990000^2 &= 1234321\ 002025^2 \quad (5.45)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997084^2 + 108000^2 &= 1\ 002916^2 \\
12\ 0997084^2 + 1188000^2 &= 121\ 002916^2 \\
1232\ 0997084^2 + 11988000^2 &= 12321\ 002916^2 \\
123432\ 0997084^2 + 119988000^2 &= 1234321\ 002916^2 \quad (5.54)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997884^2 + 92000^2 &= 1\ 002116^2 \\
12\ 0997884^2 + 1012000^2 &= 121\ 002116^2 \\
1232\ 0997884^2 + 10212000^2 &= 12321\ 002116^2 \\
123432\ 0997884^2 + 102212000^2 &= 1234321\ 002116^2 \quad (5.46)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0996975^2 + 110000^2 &= 1\ 003025^2 \\
12\ 0996975^2 + 1210000^2 &= 121\ 003025^2 \\
1232\ 0996975^2 + 12210000^2 &= 12321\ 003025^2 \\
123432\ 0996975^2 + 122210000^2 &= 1234321\ 003025^2 \quad (5.55)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997791^2 + 94000^2 &= 1\ 002209^2 \\
12\ 0997791^2 + 1034000^2 &= 121\ 002209^2 \\
1232\ 0997791^2 + 10434000^2 &= 12321\ 002209^2 \\
123432\ 0997791^2 + 104434000^2 &= 1234321\ 002209^2 \quad (5.47)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0996864^2 + 112000^2 &= 1\ 003136^2 \\
12\ 0996864^2 + 1232000^2 &= 121\ 003136^2 \\
1232\ 0996864^2 + 12432000^2 &= 12321\ 003136^2 \\
123432\ 0996864^2 + 124432000^2 &= 1234321\ 003136^2 \quad (5.56)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0997696^2 + 96000^2 &= 1\ 002304^2 \\
12\ 0997696^2 + 1056000^2 &= 121\ 002304^2 \\
1232\ 0997696^2 + 10656000^2 &= 12321\ 002304^2 \\
123432\ 0997696^2 + 106656000^2 &= 1234321\ 002304^2 \quad (5.48)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0996751^2 + 114000^2 &= 1\ 003249^2 \\
12\ 0996751^2 + 1254000^2 &= 121\ 003249^2 \\
1232\ 0996751^2 + 12654000^2 &= 12321\ 003249^2 \\
123432\ 0996751^2 + 126654000^2 &= 1234321\ 003249^2 \quad (5.57)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0996636^2 + 116000^2 &= 1\ 003364^2 \\
12\ 0996636^2 + 1276000^2 &= 121\ 003364^2 \\
1232\ 0996636^2 + 12876000^2 &= 12321\ 003364^2 \\
123432\ 0996636^2 + 128876000^2 &= 1234321\ 003364^2 \quad (5.58)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0995511^2 + 134000^2 &= 1\ 004489^2 \\
12\ 0995511^2 + 1474000^2 &= 121\ 004489^2 \\
1232\ 0995511^2 + 14874000^2 &= 12321\ 004489^2 \\
123432\ 0995511^2 + 148874000^2 &= 1234321\ 004489^2 \quad (5.67)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0996519^2 + 118000^2 &= 1\ 003481^2 \\
12\ 0996519^2 + 1298000^2 &= 121\ 003481^2 \\
1232\ 0996519^2 + 13098000^2 &= 12321\ 003481^2 \\
123432\ 0996519^2 + 131098000^2 &= 1234321\ 003481^2 \quad (5.59)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0995376^2 + 136000^2 &= 1\ 004624^2 \\
12\ 0995376^2 + 1496000^2 &= 121\ 004624^2 \\
1232\ 0995376^2 + 15096000^2 &= 12321\ 004624^2 \\
123432\ 0995376^2 + 151096000^2 &= 1234321\ 004624^2 \quad (5.68)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0996400^2 + 120000^2 &= 1\ 003600^2 \\
12\ 0996400^2 + 1320000^2 &= 121\ 003600^2 \\
1232\ 0996400^2 + 13320000^2 &= 12321\ 003600^2 \\
123432\ 0996400^2 + 133320000^2 &= 1234321\ 003600^2 \quad (5.60)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0995239^2 + 138000^2 &= 1\ 004761^2 \\
12\ 0995239^2 + 1518000^2 &= 121\ 004761^2 \\
1232\ 0995239^2 + 15318000^2 &= 12321\ 004761^2 \\
123432\ 0995239^2 + 153318000^2 &= 1234321\ 004761^2 \quad (5.69)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0996279^2 + 122000^2 &= 1\ 003721^2 \\
12\ 0996279^2 + 1342000^2 &= 121\ 003721^2 \\
1232\ 0996279^2 + 13542000^2 &= 12321\ 003721^2 \\
123432\ 0996279^2 + 135542000^2 &= 1234321\ 003721^2 \quad (5.61)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0995100^2 + 140000^2 &= 1\ 004900^2 \\
12\ 0995100^2 + 1540000^2 &= 121\ 004900^2 \\
1232\ 0995100^2 + 15540000^2 &= 12321\ 004900^2 \\
123432\ 0995100^2 + 155540000^2 &= 1234321\ 004900^2 \quad (5.70)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0996156^2 + 124000^2 &= 1\ 003844^2 \\
12\ 0996156^2 + 1364000^2 &= 121\ 003844^2 \\
1232\ 0996156^2 + 13764000^2 &= 12321\ 003844^2 \\
123432\ 0996156^2 + 137764000^2 &= 1234321\ 003844^2 \quad (5.62)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0994959^2 + 142000^2 &= 1\ 005041^2 \\
12\ 0994959^2 + 1562000^2 &= 121\ 005041^2 \\
1232\ 0994959^2 + 15762000^2 &= 12321\ 005041^2 \\
123432\ 0994959^2 + 157762000^2 &= 1234321\ 005041^2 \quad (5.71)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0996031^2 + 126000^2 &= 1\ 003969^2 \\
12\ 0996031^2 + 1386000^2 &= 121\ 003969^2 \\
1232\ 0996031^2 + 13986000^2 &= 12321\ 003969^2 \\
123432\ 0996031^2 + 139986000^2 &= 1234321\ 003969^2 \quad (5.63)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0994816^2 + 144000^2 &= 1\ 005184^2 \\
12\ 0994816^2 + 1584000^2 &= 121\ 005184^2 \\
1232\ 0994816^2 + 15984000^2 &= 12321\ 005184^2 \\
123432\ 0994816^2 + 159984000^2 &= 1234321\ 005184^2 \quad (5.72)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0995904^2 + 128000^2 &= 1\ 004096^2 \\
12\ 0995904^2 + 1408000^2 &= 121\ 004096^2 \\
1232\ 0995904^2 + 14208000^2 &= 12321\ 004096^2 \\
123432\ 0995904^2 + 142208000^2 &= 1234321\ 004096^2 \quad (5.64)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0994671^2 + 146000^2 &= 1\ 005329^2 \\
12\ 0994671^2 + 1606000^2 &= 121\ 005329^2 \\
1232\ 0994671^2 + 16206000^2 &= 12321\ 005329^2 \\
123432\ 0994671^2 + 162206000^2 &= 1234321\ 005329^2 \quad (5.73)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0995775^2 + 130000^2 &= 1\ 004225^2 \\
12\ 0995775^2 + 1430000^2 &= 121\ 004225^2 \\
1232\ 0995775^2 + 14430000^2 &= 12321\ 004225^2 \\
123432\ 0995775^2 + 144430000^2 &= 1234321\ 004225^2 \quad (5.65)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0994524^2 + 148000^2 &= 1\ 005476^2 \\
12\ 0994524^2 + 1628000^2 &= 121\ 005476^2 \\
1232\ 0994524^2 + 16428000^2 &= 12321\ 005476^2 \\
123432\ 0994524^2 + 164428000^2 &= 1234321\ 005476^2 \quad (5.74)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0995644^2 + 132000^2 &= 1\ 004356^2 \\
12\ 0995644^2 + 1452000^2 &= 121\ 004356^2 \\
1232\ 0995644^2 + 14652000^2 &= 12321\ 004356^2 \\
123432\ 0995644^2 + 146652000^2 &= 1234321\ 004356^2 \quad (5.66)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0994375^2 + 150000^2 &= 1\ 005625^2 \\
12\ 0994375^2 + 1650000^2 &= 121\ 005625^2 \\
1232\ 0994375^2 + 16650000^2 &= 12321\ 005625^2 \\
123432\ 0994375^2 + 166650000^2 &= 1234321\ 005625^2 \quad (5.75)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0994224^2 + 152000^2 &= 1\ 005776^2 & 0992775^2 + 170000^2 &= 1\ 007225^2 \\
12\ 0994224^2 + 1672000^2 &= 121\ 005776^2 & 12\ 0992775^2 + 1870000^2 &= 121\ 007225^2 \\
1232\ 0994224^2 + 16872000^2 &= 12321\ 005776^2 & 1232\ 0992775^2 + 18870000^2 &= 12321\ 007225^2 \\
123432\ 0994224^2 + 168872000^2 &= 1234321\ 005776^2 & 123432\ 0992775^2 + 188870000^2 &= 1234321\ 007225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.76} \tag{5.85}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0994071^2 + 154000^2 &= 1\ 005929^2 & 0992604^2 + 172000^2 &= 1\ 007396^2 \\
12\ 0994071^2 + 1694000^2 &= 121\ 005929^2 & 12\ 0992604^2 + 1892000^2 &= 121\ 007396^2 \\
1232\ 0994071^2 + 17094000^2 &= 12321\ 005929^2 & 1232\ 0992604^2 + 19092000^2 &= 12321\ 007396^2 \\
123432\ 0994071^2 + 171094000^2 &= 1234321\ 005929^2 & 123432\ 0992604^2 + 191092000^2 &= 1234321\ 007396^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.77} \tag{5.86}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0993916^2 + 156000^2 &= 1\ 006084^2 & 0992431^2 + 174000^2 &= 1\ 007569^2 \\
12\ 0993916^2 + 1716000^2 &= 121\ 006084^2 & 12\ 0992431^2 + 1914000^2 &= 121\ 007569^2 \\
1232\ 0993916^2 + 17316000^2 &= 12321\ 006084^2 & 1232\ 0992431^2 + 19314000^2 &= 12321\ 007569^2 \\
123432\ 0993916^2 + 173316000^2 &= 1234321\ 006084^2 & 123432\ 0992431^2 + 193314000^2 &= 1234321\ 007569^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.78} \tag{5.87}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0993759^2 + 158000^2 &= 1\ 006241^2 & 0992256^2 + 176000^2 &= 1\ 007744^2 \\
12\ 0993759^2 + 1738000^2 &= 121\ 006241^2 & 12\ 0992256^2 + 1936000^2 &= 121\ 007744^2 \\
1232\ 0993759^2 + 17538000^2 &= 12321\ 006241^2 & 1232\ 0992256^2 + 19536000^2 &= 12321\ 007744^2 \\
123432\ 0993759^2 + 175538000^2 &= 1234321\ 006241^2 & 123432\ 0992256^2 + 195536000^2 &= 1234321\ 007744^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.79} \tag{5.88}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0993600^2 + 160000^2 &= 1\ 006400^2 & 0992079^2 + 178000^2 &= 1\ 007921^2 \\
12\ 0993600^2 + 1760000^2 &= 121\ 006400^2 & 12\ 0992079^2 + 1958000^2 &= 121\ 007921^2 \\
1232\ 0993600^2 + 17760000^2 &= 12321\ 006400^2 & 1232\ 0992079^2 + 19758000^2 &= 12321\ 007921^2 \\
123432\ 0993600^2 + 177760000^2 &= 1234321\ 006400^2 & 123432\ 0992079^2 + 197758000^2 &= 1234321\ 007921^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.80} \tag{5.89}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0993439^2 + 162000^2 &= 1\ 006561^2 & 0991900^2 + 180000^2 &= 1\ 008100^2 \\
12\ 0993439^2 + 1782000^2 &= 121\ 006561^2 & 12\ 0991900^2 + 1980000^2 &= 121\ 008100^2 \\
1232\ 0993439^2 + 17982000^2 &= 12321\ 006561^2 & 1232\ 0991900^2 + 19980000^2 &= 12321\ 008100^2 \\
123432\ 0993439^2 + 179982000^2 &= 1234321\ 006561^2 & 123432\ 0991900^2 + 199980000^2 &= 1234321\ 008100^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.81} \tag{5.90}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0993276^2 + 164000^2 &= 1\ 006724^2 & 0991719^2 + 182000^2 &= 1\ 008281^2 \\
12\ 0993276^2 + 1804000^2 &= 121\ 006724^2 & 12\ 0991719^2 + 2002000^2 &= 121\ 008281^2 \\
1232\ 0993276^2 + 18204000^2 &= 12321\ 006724^2 & 1232\ 0991719^2 + 20202000^2 &= 12321\ 008281^2 \\
123432\ 0993276^2 + 182204000^2 &= 1234321\ 006724^2 & 123432\ 0991719^2 + 202202000^2 &= 1234321\ 008281^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.82} \tag{5.91}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0993111^2 + 166000^2 &= 1\ 006889^2 & 0991536^2 + 184000^2 &= 1\ 008464^2 \\
12\ 0993111^2 + 1826000^2 &= 121\ 006889^2 & 12\ 0991536^2 + 2024000^2 &= 121\ 008464^2 \\
1232\ 0993111^2 + 18426000^2 &= 12321\ 006889^2 & 1232\ 0991536^2 + 20424000^2 &= 12321\ 008464^2 \\
123432\ 0993111^2 + 184426000^2 &= 1234321\ 006889^2 & 123432\ 0991536^2 + 204424000^2 &= 1234321\ 008464^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.83} \tag{5.92}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0992944^2 + 168000^2 &= 1\ 007056^2 & 0991351^2 + 186000^2 &= 1\ 008649^2 \\
12\ 0992944^2 + 1848000^2 &= 121\ 007056^2 & 12\ 0991351^2 + 2046000^2 &= 121\ 008649^2 \\
1232\ 0992944^2 + 18648000^2 &= 12321\ 007056^2 & 1232\ 0991351^2 + 20646000^2 &= 12321\ 008649^2 \\
123432\ 0992944^2 + 186648000^2 &= 1234321\ 007056^2 & 123432\ 0991351^2 + 206646000^2 &= 1234321\ 008649^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.84} \tag{5.93}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0991164^2 + 188000^2 &= 1\ 008836^2 \\
12\ 0991164^2 + 2068000^2 &= 121\ 008836^2 \\
1232\ 0991164^2 + 20868000^2 &= 12321\ 008836^2 \\
123432\ 0991164^2 + 208868000^2 &= 1234321\ 008836^2 \quad (5.94)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0990591^2 + 194000^2 &= 1\ 009409^2 \\
12\ 0990591^2 + 2134000^2 &= 121\ 009409^2 \\
1232\ 0990591^2 + 21534000^2 &= 12321\ 009409^2 \\
123432\ 0990591^2 + 215534000^2 &= 1234321\ 009409^2 \quad (5.97)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0990975^2 + 190000^2 &= 1\ 009025^2 \\
12\ 0990975^2 + 2090000^2 &= 121\ 009025^2 \\
1232\ 0990975^2 + 21090000^2 &= 12321\ 009025^2 \\
123432\ 0990975^2 + 211090000^2 &= 1234321\ 009025^2 \quad (5.95)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0990396^2 + 196000^2 &= 1\ 009604^2 \\
12\ 0990396^2 + 2156000^2 &= 121\ 009604^2 \\
1232\ 0990396^2 + 21756000^2 &= 12321\ 009604^2 \\
123432\ 0990396^2 + 217756000^2 &= 1234321\ 009604^2 \quad (5.98)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0990784^2 + 192000^2 &= 1\ 009216^2 \\
12\ 0990784^2 + 2112000^2 &= 121\ 009216^2 \\
1232\ 0990784^2 + 21312000^2 &= 12321\ 009216^2 \\
123432\ 0990784^2 + 213312000^2 &= 1234321\ 009216^2 \quad (5.96)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0990199^2 + 198000^2 &= 1\ 009801^2 \\
12\ 0990199^2 + 2178000^2 &= 121\ 009801^2 \\
1232\ 0990199^2 + 21978000^2 &= 12321\ 009801^2 \\
123432\ 0990199^2 + 219978000^2 &= 1234321\ 009801^2 \quad (5.99)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0990000^2 + 200000^2 &= 1\ 010000^2 \\
12\ 0990000^2 + 2200000^2 &= 121\ 010000^2 \\
1232\ 0990000^2 + 22200000^2 &= 12321\ 010000^2 \\
123432\ 0990000^2 + 222200000^2 &= 1234321\ 010000^2 \quad (5.100)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0988764^2 + 212000^2 &= 1\ 011236^2 \\
12\ 0988764^2 + 2332000^2 &= 121\ 011236^2 \\
1232\ 0988764^2 + 23532000^2 &= 12321\ 011236^2 \\
123432\ 0988764^2 + 235532000^2 &= 1234321\ 011236^2 \quad (5.106)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0989799^2 + 202000^2 &= 1\ 010201^2 \\
12\ 0989799^2 + 2222000^2 &= 121\ 010201^2 \\
1232\ 0989799^2 + 22422000^2 &= 12321\ 010201^2 \\
123432\ 0989799^2 + 224422000^2 &= 1234321\ 010201^2 \quad (5.101)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0988551^2 + 214000^2 &= 1\ 011449^2 \\
12\ 0988551^2 + 2354000^2 &= 121\ 011449^2 \\
1232\ 0988551^2 + 23754000^2 &= 12321\ 011449^2 \\
123432\ 0988551^2 + 237754000^2 &= 1234321\ 011449^2 \quad (5.107)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0989596^2 + 204000^2 &= 1\ 010404^2 \\
12\ 0989596^2 + 2244000^2 &= 121\ 010404^2 \\
1232\ 0989596^2 + 22644000^2 &= 12321\ 010404^2 \\
123432\ 0989596^2 + 226644000^2 &= 1234321\ 010404^2 \quad (5.102)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0988336^2 + 216000^2 &= 1\ 011664^2 \\
12\ 0988336^2 + 2376000^2 &= 121\ 011664^2 \\
1232\ 0988336^2 + 23976000^2 &= 12321\ 011664^2 \\
123432\ 0988336^2 + 239976000^2 &= 1234321\ 011664^2 \quad (5.108)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0989391^2 + 206000^2 &= 1\ 010609^2 \\
12\ 0989391^2 + 2266000^2 &= 121\ 010609^2 \\
1232\ 0989391^2 + 22866000^2 &= 12321\ 010609^2 \\
123432\ 0989391^2 + 228866000^2 &= 1234321\ 010609^2 \quad (5.103)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0988119^2 + 218000^2 &= 1\ 011881^2 \\
12\ 0988119^2 + 2398000^2 &= 121\ 011881^2 \\
1232\ 0988119^2 + 24198000^2 &= 12321\ 011881^2 \\
123432\ 0988119^2 + 242198000^2 &= 1234321\ 011881^2 \quad (5.109)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0989184^2 + 208000^2 &= 1\ 010816^2 \\
12\ 0989184^2 + 2288000^2 &= 121\ 010816^2 \\
1232\ 0989184^2 + 23088000^2 &= 12321\ 010816^2 \\
123432\ 0989184^2 + 231088000^2 &= 1234321\ 010816^2 \quad (5.104)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0987900^2 + 220000^2 &= 1\ 012100^2 \\
12\ 0987900^2 + 2420000^2 &= 121\ 012100^2 \\
1232\ 0987900^2 + 24420000^2 &= 12321\ 012100^2 \\
123432\ 0987900^2 + 244420000^2 &= 1234321\ 012100^2 \quad (5.110)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0988975^2 + 210000^2 &= 1\ 011025^2 \\
12\ 0988975^2 + 2310000^2 &= 121\ 011025^2 \\
1232\ 0988975^2 + 23310000^2 &= 12321\ 011025^2 \\
123432\ 0988975^2 + 233310000^2 &= 1234321\ 011025^2 \quad (5.105)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0987679^2 + 222000^2 &= 1\ 012321^2 \\
12\ 0987679^2 + 2442000^2 &= 121\ 012321^2 \\
1232\ 0987679^2 + 24642000^2 &= 12321\ 012321^2 \\
123432\ 0987679^2 + 246642000^2 &= 1234321\ 012321^2 \quad (5.111)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0987456^2 + 224000^2 &= 1\ 012544^2 & 0985359^2 + 242000^2 &= 1\ 014641^2 \\
12\ 0987456^2 + 2464000^2 &= 121\ 012544^2 & 12\ 0985359^2 + 2662000^2 &= 121\ 014641^2 \\
1232\ 0987456^2 + 24864000^2 &= 12321\ 012544^2 & 1232\ 0985359^2 + 26862000^2 &= 12321\ 014641^2 \\
123432\ 0987456^2 + 248864000^2 &= 1234321\ 012544^2 & 123432\ 0985359^2 + 268862000^2 &= 1234321\ 014641^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.112} \tag{5.121}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0987231^2 + 226000^2 &= 1\ 012769^2 & 0985116^2 + 244000^2 &= 1\ 014884^2 \\
12\ 0987231^2 + 2486000^2 &= 121\ 012769^2 & 12\ 0985116^2 + 2684000^2 &= 121\ 014884^2 \\
1232\ 0987231^2 + 25086000^2 &= 12321\ 012769^2 & 1232\ 0985116^2 + 27084000^2 &= 12321\ 014884^2 \\
123432\ 0987231^2 + 251086000^2 &= 1234321\ 012769^2 & 123432\ 0985116^2 + 271084000^2 &= 1234321\ 014884^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.113} \tag{5.122}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0987004^2 + 228000^2 &= 1\ 012996^2 & 0984871^2 + 246000^2 &= 1\ 015129^2 \\
12\ 0987004^2 + 2508000^2 &= 121\ 012996^2 & 12\ 0984871^2 + 2706000^2 &= 121\ 015129^2 \\
1232\ 0987004^2 + 25308000^2 &= 12321\ 012996^2 & 1232\ 0984871^2 + 27306000^2 &= 12321\ 015129^2 \\
123432\ 0987004^2 + 253308000^2 &= 1234321\ 012996^2 & 123432\ 0984871^2 + 273306000^2 &= 1234321\ 015129^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.114} \tag{5.123}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0986775^2 + 230000^2 &= 1\ 013225^2 & 0984624^2 + 248000^2 &= 1\ 015376^2 \\
12\ 0986775^2 + 2530000^2 &= 121\ 013225^2 & 12\ 0984624^2 + 2728000^2 &= 121\ 015376^2 \\
1232\ 0986775^2 + 25530000^2 &= 12321\ 013225^2 & 1232\ 0984624^2 + 27528000^2 &= 12321\ 015376^2 \\
123432\ 0986775^2 + 255530000^2 &= 1234321\ 013225^2 & 123432\ 0984624^2 + 275528000^2 &= 1234321\ 015376^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.115} \tag{5.124}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0986544^2 + 232000^2 &= 1\ 013456^2 & 0984375^2 + 250000^2 &= 1\ 015625^2 \\
12\ 0986544^2 + 2552000^2 &= 121\ 013456^2 & 12\ 0984375^2 + 2750000^2 &= 121\ 015625^2 \\
1232\ 0986544^2 + 25752000^2 &= 12321\ 013456^2 & 1232\ 0984375^2 + 27750000^2 &= 12321\ 015625^2 \\
123432\ 0986544^2 + 257752000^2 &= 1234321\ 013456^2 & 123432\ 0984375^2 + 277750000^2 &= 1234321\ 015625^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.116} \tag{5.125}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0986311^2 + 234000^2 &= 1\ 013689^2 & 0984124^2 + 252000^2 &= 1\ 015876^2 \\
12\ 0986311^2 + 2574000^2 &= 121\ 013689^2 & 12\ 0984124^2 + 2772000^2 &= 121\ 015876^2 \\
1232\ 0986311^2 + 25974000^2 &= 12321\ 013689^2 & 1232\ 0984124^2 + 27972000^2 &= 12321\ 015876^2 \\
123432\ 0986311^2 + 259974000^2 &= 1234321\ 013689^2 & 123432\ 0984124^2 + 279972000^2 &= 1234321\ 015876^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.117} \tag{5.126}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0986076^2 + 236000^2 &= 1\ 013924^2 & 0983871^2 + 254000^2 &= 1\ 016129^2 \\
12\ 0986076^2 + 2596000^2 &= 121\ 013924^2 & 12\ 0983871^2 + 2794000^2 &= 121\ 016129^2 \\
1232\ 0986076^2 + 26196000^2 &= 12321\ 013924^2 & 1232\ 0983871^2 + 28194000^2 &= 12321\ 016129^2 \\
123432\ 0986076^2 + 262196000^2 &= 1234321\ 013924^2 & 123432\ 0983871^2 + 282194000^2 &= 1234321\ 016129^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.118} \tag{5.127}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0985839^2 + 238000^2 &= 1\ 014161^2 & 0983616^2 + 256000^2 &= 1\ 016384^2 \\
12\ 0985839^2 + 2618000^2 &= 121\ 014161^2 & 12\ 0983616^2 + 2816000^2 &= 121\ 016384^2 \\
1232\ 0985839^2 + 26418000^2 &= 12321\ 014161^2 & 1232\ 0983616^2 + 28416000^2 &= 12321\ 016384^2 \\
123432\ 0985839^2 + 264418000^2 &= 1234321\ 014161^2 & 123432\ 0983616^2 + 284416000^2 &= 1234321\ 016384^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.119} \tag{5.128}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0985600^2 + 240000^2 &= 1\ 014400^2 & 0983359^2 + 258000^2 &= 1\ 016641^2 \\
12\ 0985600^2 + 2640000^2 &= 121\ 014400^2 & 12\ 0983359^2 + 2838000^2 &= 121\ 016641^2 \\
1232\ 0985600^2 + 26640000^2 &= 12321\ 014400^2 & 1232\ 0983359^2 + 28638000^2 &= 12321\ 016641^2 \\
123432\ 0985600^2 + 266640000^2 &= 1234321\ 014400^2 & 123432\ 0983359^2 + 286638000^2 &= 1234321\ 016641^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.120} \tag{5.129}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0983100^2 + 260000^2 &= 1\ 016900^2 & 0980679^2 + 278000^2 &= 1\ 019321^2 \\
12\ 0983100^2 + 2860000^2 &= 121\ 016900^2 & 12\ 0980679^2 + 3058000^2 &= 121\ 019321^2 \\
1232\ 0983100^2 + 28860000^2 &= 12321\ 016900^2 & 1232\ 0980679^2 + 30858000^2 &= 12321\ 019321^2 \\
123432\ 0983100^2 + 288860000^2 &= 1234321\ 016900^2 & 123432\ 0980679^2 + 308858000^2 &= 1234321\ 019321^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.130} \tag{5.139}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0982839^2 + 262000^2 &= 1\ 017161^2 & 0980400^2 + 280000^2 &= 1\ 019600^2 \\
12\ 0982839^2 + 2882000^2 &= 121\ 017161^2 & 12\ 0980400^2 + 3080000^2 &= 121\ 019600^2 \\
1232\ 0982839^2 + 29082000^2 &= 12321\ 017161^2 & 1232\ 0980400^2 + 31080000^2 &= 12321\ 019600^2 \\
123432\ 0982839^2 + 291082000^2 &= 1234321\ 017161^2 & 123432\ 0980400^2 + 311080000^2 &= 1234321\ 019600^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.131} \tag{5.140}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0982576^2 + 264000^2 &= 1\ 017424^2 & 0980119^2 + 282000^2 &= 1\ 019881^2 \\
12\ 0982576^2 + 2904000^2 &= 121\ 017424^2 & 12\ 0980119^2 + 3102000^2 &= 121\ 019881^2 \\
1232\ 0982576^2 + 29304000^2 &= 12321\ 017424^2 & 1232\ 0980119^2 + 31302000^2 &= 12321\ 019881^2 \\
123432\ 0982576^2 + 293304000^2 &= 1234321\ 017424^2 & 123432\ 0980119^2 + 313302000^2 &= 1234321\ 019881^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.132} \tag{5.141}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0982311^2 + 266000^2 &= 1\ 017689^2 & 0979836^2 + 284000^2 &= 1\ 020164^2 \\
12\ 0982311^2 + 2926000^2 &= 121\ 017689^2 & 12\ 0979836^2 + 3124000^2 &= 121\ 020164^2 \\
1232\ 0982311^2 + 29526000^2 &= 12321\ 017689^2 & 1232\ 0979836^2 + 31524000^2 &= 12321\ 020164^2 \\
123432\ 0982311^2 + 295526000^2 &= 1234321\ 017689^2 & 123432\ 0979836^2 + 315524000^2 &= 1234321\ 020164^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.133} \tag{5.142}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0982044^2 + 268000^2 &= 1\ 017956^2 & 0979551^2 + 286000^2 &= 1\ 020449^2 \\
12\ 0982044^2 + 2948000^2 &= 121\ 017956^2 & 12\ 0979551^2 + 3146000^2 &= 121\ 020449^2 \\
1232\ 0982044^2 + 29748000^2 &= 12321\ 017956^2 & 1232\ 0979551^2 + 31746000^2 &= 12321\ 020449^2 \\
123432\ 0982044^2 + 297748000^2 &= 1234321\ 017956^2 & 123432\ 0979551^2 + 317746000^2 &= 1234321\ 020449^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.134} \tag{5.143}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0981775^2 + 270000^2 &= 1\ 018225^2 & 0979264^2 + 288000^2 &= 1\ 020736^2 \\
12\ 0981775^2 + 2970000^2 &= 121\ 018225^2 & 12\ 0979264^2 + 3168000^2 &= 121\ 020736^2 \\
1232\ 0981775^2 + 29970000^2 &= 12321\ 018225^2 & 1232\ 0979264^2 + 31968000^2 &= 12321\ 020736^2 \\
123432\ 0981775^2 + 299970000^2 &= 1234321\ 018225^2 & 123432\ 0979264^2 + 319968000^2 &= 1234321\ 020736^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.135} \tag{5.144}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0981504^2 + 272000^2 &= 1\ 018496^2 & 0978975^2 + 290000^2 &= 1\ 021025^2 \\
12\ 0981504^2 + 2992000^2 &= 121\ 018496^2 & 12\ 0978975^2 + 3190000^2 &= 121\ 021025^2 \\
1232\ 0981504^2 + 30192000^2 &= 12321\ 018496^2 & 1232\ 0978975^2 + 32190000^2 &= 12321\ 021025^2 \\
123432\ 0981504^2 + 302192000^2 &= 1234321\ 018496^2 & 123432\ 0978975^2 + 322190000^2 &= 1234321\ 021025^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.136} \tag{5.145}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0981231^2 + 274000^2 &= 1\ 018769^2 & 0978684^2 + 292000^2 &= 1\ 021316^2 \\
12\ 0981231^2 + 3014000^2 &= 121\ 018769^2 & 12\ 0978684^2 + 3212000^2 &= 121\ 021316^2 \\
1232\ 0981231^2 + 30414000^2 &= 12321\ 018769^2 & 1232\ 0978684^2 + 32412000^2 &= 12321\ 021316^2 \\
123432\ 0981231^2 + 304414000^2 &= 1234321\ 018769^2 & 123432\ 0978684^2 + 324412000^2 &= 1234321\ 021316^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.137} \tag{5.146}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0980956^2 + 276000^2 &= 1\ 019044^2 & 0978391^2 + 294000^2 &= 1\ 021609^2 \\
12\ 0980956^2 + 3036000^2 &= 121\ 019044^2 & 12\ 0978391^2 + 3234000^2 &= 121\ 021609^2 \\
1232\ 0980956^2 + 30636000^2 &= 12321\ 019044^2 & 1232\ 0978391^2 + 32634000^2 &= 12321\ 021609^2 \\
123432\ 0980956^2 + 306636000^2 &= 1234321\ 019044^2 & 123432\ 0978391^2 + 326634000^2 &= 1234321\ 021609^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.138} \tag{5.147}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0978096^2 + 296000^2 &= 1\ 021904^2 & 0975351^2 + 314000^2 &= 1\ 024649^2 \\
12\ 0978096^2 + 3256000^2 &= 121\ 021904^2 & 12\ 0975351^2 + 3454000^2 &= 121\ 024649^2 \\
1232\ 0978096^2 + 32856000^2 &= 12321\ 021904^2 & 1232\ 0975351^2 + 34854000^2 &= 12321\ 024649^2 \\
123432\ 0978096^2 + 328856000^2 &= 1234321\ 021904^2 & 123432\ 0975351^2 + 348854000^2 &= 1234321\ 024649^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.148} \tag{5.157}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0977799^2 + 298000^2 &= 1\ 022201^2 & 0975036^2 + 316000^2 &= 1\ 024964^2 \\
12\ 0977799^2 + 3278000^2 &= 121\ 022201^2 & 12\ 0975036^2 + 3476000^2 &= 121\ 024964^2 \\
1232\ 0977799^2 + 33078000^2 &= 12321\ 022201^2 & 1232\ 0975036^2 + 35076000^2 &= 12321\ 024964^2 \\
123432\ 0977799^2 + 331078000^2 &= 1234321\ 022201^2 & 123432\ 0975036^2 + 351076000^2 &= 1234321\ 024964^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.149} \tag{5.158}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0977500^2 + 300000^2 &= 1\ 022500^2 & 0974719^2 + 318000^2 &= 1\ 025281^2 \\
12\ 0977500^2 + 3300000^2 &= 121\ 022500^2 & 12\ 0974719^2 + 3498000^2 &= 121\ 025281^2 \\
1232\ 0977500^2 + 33300000^2 &= 12321\ 022500^2 & 1232\ 0974719^2 + 35298000^2 &= 12321\ 025281^2 \\
123432\ 0977500^2 + 333300000^2 &= 1234321\ 022500^2 & 123432\ 0974719^2 + 353298000^2 &= 1234321\ 025281^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.150} \tag{5.159}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0977199^2 + 302000^2 &= 1\ 022801^2 & 0974400^2 + 320000^2 &= 1\ 025600^2 \\
12\ 0977199^2 + 3322000^2 &= 121\ 022801^2 & 12\ 0974400^2 + 3520000^2 &= 121\ 025600^2 \\
1232\ 0977199^2 + 33522000^2 &= 12321\ 022801^2 & 1232\ 0974400^2 + 35520000^2 &= 12321\ 025600^2 \\
123432\ 0977199^2 + 335522000^2 &= 1234321\ 022801^2 & 123432\ 0974400^2 + 355520000^2 &= 1234321\ 025600^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.151} \tag{5.160}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0976896^2 + 304000^2 &= 1\ 023104^2 & 0974079^2 + 322000^2 &= 1\ 025921^2 \\
12\ 0976896^2 + 3344000^2 &= 121\ 023104^2 & 12\ 0974079^2 + 3542000^2 &= 121\ 025921^2 \\
1232\ 0976896^2 + 33744000^2 &= 12321\ 023104^2 & 1232\ 0974079^2 + 35742000^2 &= 12321\ 025921^2 \\
123432\ 0976896^2 + 337744000^2 &= 1234321\ 023104^2 & 123432\ 0974079^2 + 357742000^2 &= 1234321\ 025921^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.152} \tag{5.161}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0976591^2 + 306000^2 &= 1\ 023409^2 & 0973756^2 + 324000^2 &= 1\ 026244^2 \\
12\ 0976591^2 + 3366000^2 &= 121\ 023409^2 & 12\ 0973756^2 + 3564000^2 &= 121\ 026244^2 \\
1232\ 0976591^2 + 33966000^2 &= 12321\ 023409^2 & 1232\ 0973756^2 + 35964000^2 &= 12321\ 026244^2 \\
123432\ 0976591^2 + 339966000^2 &= 1234321\ 023409^2 & 123432\ 0973756^2 + 359964000^2 &= 1234321\ 026244^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.153} \tag{5.162}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0976284^2 + 308000^2 &= 1\ 023716^2 & 0973431^2 + 326000^2 &= 1\ 026569^2 \\
12\ 0976284^2 + 3388000^2 &= 121\ 023716^2 & 12\ 0973431^2 + 3586000^2 &= 121\ 026569^2 \\
1232\ 0976284^2 + 34188000^2 &= 12321\ 023716^2 & 1232\ 0973431^2 + 36186000^2 &= 12321\ 026569^2 \\
123432\ 0976284^2 + 342188000^2 &= 1234321\ 023716^2 & 123432\ 0973431^2 + 362186000^2 &= 1234321\ 026569^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.154} \tag{5.163}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0975975^2 + 310000^2 &= 1\ 024025^2 & 0973104^2 + 328000^2 &= 1\ 026896^2 \\
12\ 0975975^2 + 3410000^2 &= 121\ 024025^2 & 12\ 0973104^2 + 3608000^2 &= 121\ 026896^2 \\
1232\ 0975975^2 + 34410000^2 &= 12321\ 024025^2 & 1232\ 0973104^2 + 36408000^2 &= 12321\ 026896^2 \\
123432\ 0975975^2 + 344410000^2 &= 1234321\ 024025^2 & 123432\ 0973104^2 + 364408000^2 &= 1234321\ 026896^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.155} \tag{5.164}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0975664^2 + 312000^2 &= 1\ 024336^2 & 0972775^2 + 330000^2 &= 1\ 027225^2 \\
12\ 0975664^2 + 3432000^2 &= 121\ 024336^2 & 12\ 0972775^2 + 3630000^2 &= 121\ 027225^2 \\
1232\ 0975664^2 + 34632000^2 &= 12321\ 024336^2 & 1232\ 0972775^2 + 36630000^2 &= 12321\ 027225^2 \\
123432\ 0975664^2 + 346632000^2 &= 1234321\ 024336^2 & 123432\ 0972775^2 + 366630000^2 &= 1234321\ 027225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.156} \tag{5.165}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0972444^2 + 332000^2 &= 1\ 027556^2 & 0969375^2 + 350000^2 &= 1\ 030625^2 \\
12\ 0972444^2 + 3652000^2 &= 121\ 027556^2 & 12\ 0969375^2 + 3850000^2 &= 121\ 030625^2 \\
1232\ 0972444^2 + 36852000^2 &= 12321\ 027556^2 & 1232\ 0969375^2 + 38850000^2 &= 12321\ 030625^2 \\
123432\ 0972444^2 + 368852000^2 &= 1234321\ 027556^2 & 123432\ 0969375^2 + 388850000^2 &= 1234321\ 030625^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.166} \tag{5.175}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0972111^2 + 334000^2 &= 1\ 027889^2 & 0969024^2 + 352000^2 &= 1\ 030976^2 \\
12\ 0972111^2 + 3674000^2 &= 121\ 027889^2 & 12\ 0969024^2 + 3872000^2 &= 121\ 030976^2 \\
1232\ 0972111^2 + 37074000^2 &= 12321\ 027889^2 & 1232\ 0969024^2 + 39072000^2 &= 12321\ 030976^2 \\
123432\ 0972111^2 + 371074000^2 &= 1234321\ 027889^2 & 123432\ 0969024^2 + 391072000^2 &= 1234321\ 030976^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.167} \tag{5.176}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0971776^2 + 336000^2 &= 1\ 028224^2 & 0968671^2 + 354000^2 &= 1\ 031329^2 \\
12\ 0971776^2 + 3696000^2 &= 121\ 028224^2 & 12\ 0968671^2 + 3894000^2 &= 121\ 031329^2 \\
1232\ 0971776^2 + 37296000^2 &= 12321\ 028224^2 & 1232\ 0968671^2 + 39294000^2 &= 12321\ 031329^2 \\
123432\ 0971776^2 + 373296000^2 &= 1234321\ 028224^2 & 123432\ 0968671^2 + 393294000^2 &= 1234321\ 031329^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.168} \tag{5.177}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0971439^2 + 338000^2 &= 1\ 028561^2 & 0968316^2 + 356000^2 &= 1\ 031684^2 \\
12\ 0971439^2 + 3718000^2 &= 121\ 028561^2 & 12\ 0968316^2 + 3916000^2 &= 121\ 031684^2 \\
1232\ 0971439^2 + 37518000^2 &= 12321\ 028561^2 & 1232\ 0968316^2 + 39516000^2 &= 12321\ 031684^2 \\
123432\ 0971439^2 + 375518000^2 &= 1234321\ 028561^2 & 123432\ 0968316^2 + 395516000^2 &= 1234321\ 031684^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.169} \tag{5.178}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0971100^2 + 340000^2 &= 1\ 028900^2 & 0967959^2 + 358000^2 &= 1\ 032041^2 \\
12\ 0971100^2 + 3740000^2 &= 121\ 028900^2 & 12\ 0967959^2 + 3938000^2 &= 121\ 032041^2 \\
1232\ 0971100^2 + 37740000^2 &= 12321\ 028900^2 & 1232\ 0967959^2 + 39738000^2 &= 12321\ 032041^2 \\
123432\ 0971100^2 + 377740000^2 &= 1234321\ 028900^2 & 123432\ 0967959^2 + 397738000^2 &= 1234321\ 032041^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.170} \tag{5.179}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0970759^2 + 342000^2 &= 1\ 029241^2 & 0967600^2 + 360000^2 &= 1\ 032400^2 \\
12\ 0970759^2 + 3762000^2 &= 121\ 029241^2 & 12\ 0967600^2 + 3960000^2 &= 121\ 032400^2 \\
1232\ 0970759^2 + 37962000^2 &= 12321\ 029241^2 & 1232\ 0967600^2 + 39960000^2 &= 12321\ 032400^2 \\
123432\ 0970759^2 + 379962000^2 &= 1234321\ 029241^2 & 123432\ 0967600^2 + 399960000^2 &= 1234321\ 032400^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.171} \tag{5.180}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0970416^2 + 344000^2 &= 1\ 029584^2 & 0967239^2 + 362000^2 &= 1\ 032761^2 \\
12\ 0970416^2 + 3784000^2 &= 121\ 029584^2 & 12\ 0967239^2 + 3982000^2 &= 121\ 032761^2 \\
1232\ 0970416^2 + 38184000^2 &= 12321\ 029584^2 & 1232\ 0967239^2 + 40182000^2 &= 12321\ 032761^2 \\
123432\ 0970416^2 + 382184000^2 &= 1234321\ 029584^2 & 123432\ 0967239^2 + 402182000^2 &= 1234321\ 032761^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.172} \tag{5.181}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0970071^2 + 346000^2 &= 1\ 029929^2 & 0966876^2 + 364000^2 &= 1\ 033124^2 \\
12\ 0970071^2 + 3806000^2 &= 121\ 029929^2 & 12\ 0966876^2 + 4004000^2 &= 121\ 033124^2 \\
1232\ 0970071^2 + 38406000^2 &= 12321\ 029929^2 & 1232\ 0966876^2 + 40404000^2 &= 12321\ 033124^2 \\
123432\ 0970071^2 + 384406000^2 &= 1234321\ 029929^2 & 123432\ 0966876^2 + 404404000^2 &= 1234321\ 033124^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.173} \tag{5.182}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0969724^2 + 348000^2 &= 1\ 030276^2 & 0966511^2 + 366000^2 &= 1\ 033489^2 \\
12\ 0969724^2 + 3828000^2 &= 121\ 030276^2 & 12\ 0966511^2 + 4026000^2 &= 121\ 033489^2 \\
1232\ 0969724^2 + 38628000^2 &= 12321\ 030276^2 & 1232\ 0966511^2 + 40626000^2 &= 12321\ 033489^2 \\
123432\ 0969724^2 + 386628000^2 &= 1234321\ 030276^2 & 123432\ 0966511^2 + 406626000^2 &= 1234321\ 033489^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.174} \tag{5.183}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0966144^2 + 368000^2 &= 1\ 033856^2 & 0963136^2 + 384000^2 &= 1\ 036864^2 \\
12\ 0966144^2 + 4048000^2 &= 121\ 033856^2 & 12\ 0963136^2 + 4224000^2 &= 121\ 036864^2 \\
1232\ 0966144^2 + 40848000^2 &= 12321\ 033856^2 & 1232\ 0963136^2 + 42624000^2 &= 12321\ 036864^2 \\
123432\ 0966144^2 + 408848000^2 &= 1234321\ 033856^2 & 123432\ 0963136^2 + 426624000^2 &= 1234321\ 036864^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.184} \tag{5.192}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0965775^2 + 370000^2 &= 1\ 034225^2 & 0962751^2 + 386000^2 &= 1\ 037249^2 \\
12\ 0965775^2 + 4070000^2 &= 121\ 034225^2 & 12\ 0962751^2 + 4246000^2 &= 121\ 037249^2 \\
1232\ 0965775^2 + 41070000^2 &= 12321\ 034225^2 & 1232\ 0962751^2 + 42846000^2 &= 12321\ 037249^2 \\
123432\ 0965775^2 + 411070000^2 &= 1234321\ 034225^2 & 123432\ 0962751^2 + 428846000^2 &= 1234321\ 037249^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.185} \tag{5.193}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0965404^2 + 372000^2 &= 1\ 034596^2 & 0962364^2 + 388000^2 &= 1\ 037636^2 \\
12\ 0965404^2 + 4092000^2 &= 121\ 034596^2 & 12\ 0962364^2 + 4268000^2 &= 121\ 037636^2 \\
1232\ 0965404^2 + 41292000^2 &= 12321\ 034596^2 & 1232\ 0962364^2 + 43068000^2 &= 12321\ 037636^2 \\
123432\ 0965404^2 + 413292000^2 &= 1234321\ 034596^2 & 123432\ 0962364^2 + 431068000^2 &= 1234321\ 037636^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.186} \tag{5.194}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0965031^2 + 374000^2 &= 1\ 034969^2 & 0961975^2 + 390000^2 &= 1\ 038025^2 \\
12\ 0965031^2 + 4114000^2 &= 121\ 034969^2 & 12\ 0961975^2 + 4290000^2 &= 121\ 038025^2 \\
1232\ 0965031^2 + 41514000^2 &= 12321\ 034969^2 & 1232\ 0961975^2 + 43290000^2 &= 12321\ 038025^2 \\
123432\ 0965031^2 + 415514000^2 &= 1234321\ 034969^2 & 123432\ 0961975^2 + 433290000^2 &= 1234321\ 038025^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.187} \tag{5.195}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0964656^2 + 376000^2 &= 1\ 035344^2 & 0961584^2 + 392000^2 &= 1\ 038416^2 \\
12\ 0964656^2 + 4136000^2 &= 121\ 035344^2 & 12\ 0961584^2 + 4312000^2 &= 121\ 038416^2 \\
1232\ 0964656^2 + 41736000^2 &= 12321\ 035344^2 & 1232\ 0961584^2 + 43512000^2 &= 12321\ 038416^2 \\
123432\ 0964656^2 + 417736000^2 &= 1234321\ 035344^2 & 123432\ 0961584^2 + 435512000^2 &= 1234321\ 038416^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.188} \tag{5.196}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0964279^2 + 378000^2 &= 1\ 035721^2 & 0961191^2 + 394000^2 &= 1\ 038809^2 \\
12\ 0964279^2 + 4158000^2 &= 121\ 035721^2 & 12\ 0961191^2 + 4334000^2 &= 121\ 038809^2 \\
1232\ 0964279^2 + 41958000^2 &= 12321\ 035721^2 & 1232\ 0961191^2 + 43734000^2 &= 12321\ 038809^2 \\
123432\ 0964279^2 + 419958000^2 &= 1234321\ 035721^2 & 123432\ 0961191^2 + 437734000^2 &= 1234321\ 038809^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.189} \tag{5.197}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0963900^2 + 380000^2 &= 1\ 036100^2 & 0960796^2 + 396000^2 &= 1\ 039204^2 \\
12\ 0963900^2 + 4180000^2 &= 121\ 036100^2 & 12\ 0960796^2 + 4356000^2 &= 121\ 039204^2 \\
1232\ 0963900^2 + 42180000^2 &= 12321\ 036100^2 & 1232\ 0960796^2 + 43956000^2 &= 12321\ 039204^2 \\
123432\ 0963900^2 + 422180000^2 &= 1234321\ 036100^2 & 123432\ 0960796^2 + 439956000^2 &= 1234321\ 039204^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.190} \tag{5.198}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0963519^2 + 382000^2 &= 1\ 036481^2 & 0960399^2 + 398000^2 &= 1\ 039601^2 \\
12\ 0963519^2 + 4202000^2 &= 121\ 036481^2 & 12\ 0960399^2 + 4378000^2 &= 121\ 039601^2 \\
1232\ 0963519^2 + 42402000^2 &= 12321\ 036481^2 & 1232\ 0960399^2 + 44178000^2 &= 12321\ 039601^2 \\
123432\ 0963519^2 + 424402000^2 &= 1234321\ 036481^2 & 123432\ 0960399^2 + 442178000^2 &= 1234321\ 039601^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.191} \tag{5.199}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0960000^2 + 400000^2 &= 1\ 040000^2 \\
12\ 0960000^2 + 4400000^2 &= 121\ 040000^2 \\
1232\ 0960000^2 + 44400000^2 &= 12321\ 040000^2 \\
123432\ 0960000^2 + 444400000^2 &= 1234321\ 040000^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.200}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0959599^2 + 402000^2 &= 1\ 040401^2 & 0955900^2 + 420000^2 &= 1\ 044100^2 \\
12\ 0959599^2 + 4422000^2 &= 121\ 040401^2 & 12\ 0955900^2 + 4620000^2 &= 121\ 044100^2 \\
1232\ 0959599^2 + 44622000^2 &= 12321\ 040401^2 & 1232\ 0955900^2 + 46620000^2 &= 12321\ 044100^2 \\
123432\ 0959599^2 + 446622000^2 &= 1234321\ 040401^2 & 123432\ 0955900^2 + 466620000^2 &= 1234321\ 044100^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.201} \tag{5.210}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0959196^2 + 404000^2 &= 1\ 040804^2 & 0955479^2 + 422000^2 &= 1\ 044521^2 \\
12\ 0959196^2 + 4444000^2 &= 121\ 040804^2 & 12\ 0955479^2 + 4642000^2 &= 121\ 044521^2 \\
1232\ 0959196^2 + 44844000^2 &= 12321\ 040804^2 & 1232\ 0955479^2 + 46842000^2 &= 12321\ 044521^2 \\
123432\ 0959196^2 + 448844000^2 &= 1234321\ 040804^2 & 123432\ 0955479^2 + 468842000^2 &= 1234321\ 044521^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.202} \tag{5.211}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0958791^2 + 406000^2 &= 1\ 041209^2 & 0955056^2 + 424000^2 &= 1\ 044944^2 \\
12\ 0958791^2 + 4466000^2 &= 121\ 041209^2 & 12\ 0955056^2 + 4664000^2 &= 121\ 044944^2 \\
1232\ 0958791^2 + 45066000^2 &= 12321\ 041209^2 & 1232\ 0955056^2 + 47064000^2 &= 12321\ 044944^2 \\
123432\ 0958791^2 + 451066000^2 &= 1234321\ 041209^2 & 123432\ 0955056^2 + 471064000^2 &= 1234321\ 044944^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.203} \tag{5.212}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0958384^2 + 408000^2 &= 1\ 041616^2 & 0954631^2 + 426000^2 &= 1\ 045369^2 \\
12\ 0958384^2 + 4488000^2 &= 121\ 041616^2 & 12\ 0954631^2 + 4686000^2 &= 121\ 045369^2 \\
1232\ 0958384^2 + 45288000^2 &= 12321\ 041616^2 & 1232\ 0954631^2 + 47286000^2 &= 12321\ 045369^2 \\
123432\ 0958384^2 + 453288000^2 &= 1234321\ 041616^2 & 123432\ 0954631^2 + 473286000^2 &= 1234321\ 045369^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.204} \tag{5.213}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0957975^2 + 410000^2 &= 1\ 042025^2 & 0954204^2 + 428000^2 &= 1\ 045796^2 \\
12\ 0957975^2 + 4510000^2 &= 121\ 042025^2 & 12\ 0954204^2 + 4708000^2 &= 121\ 045796^2 \\
1232\ 0957975^2 + 45510000^2 &= 12321\ 042025^2 & 1232\ 0954204^2 + 47508000^2 &= 12321\ 045796^2 \\
123432\ 0957975^2 + 455510000^2 &= 1234321\ 042025^2 & 123432\ 0954204^2 + 475508000^2 &= 1234321\ 045796^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.205} \tag{5.214}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0957564^2 + 412000^2 &= 1\ 042436^2 & 0953775^2 + 430000^2 &= 1\ 046225^2 \\
12\ 0957564^2 + 4532000^2 &= 121\ 042436^2 & 12\ 0953775^2 + 4730000^2 &= 121\ 046225^2 \\
1232\ 0957564^2 + 45732000^2 &= 12321\ 042436^2 & 1232\ 0953775^2 + 47730000^2 &= 12321\ 046225^2 \\
123432\ 0957564^2 + 457732000^2 &= 1234321\ 042436^2 & 123432\ 0953775^2 + 477730000^2 &= 1234321\ 046225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.206} \tag{5.215}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0957151^2 + 414000^2 &= 1\ 042849^2 & 0953344^2 + 432000^2 &= 1\ 046656^2 \\
12\ 0957151^2 + 4554000^2 &= 121\ 042849^2 & 12\ 0953344^2 + 4752000^2 &= 121\ 046656^2 \\
1232\ 0957151^2 + 45954000^2 &= 12321\ 042849^2 & 1232\ 0953344^2 + 47952000^2 &= 12321\ 046656^2 \\
123432\ 0957151^2 + 459954000^2 &= 1234321\ 042849^2 & 123432\ 0953344^2 + 479952000^2 &= 1234321\ 046656^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.207} \tag{5.216}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0956736^2 + 416000^2 &= 1\ 043264^2 & 0952911^2 + 434000^2 &= 1\ 047089^2 \\
12\ 0956736^2 + 4576000^2 &= 121\ 043264^2 & 12\ 0952911^2 + 4774000^2 &= 121\ 047089^2 \\
1232\ 0956736^2 + 46176000^2 &= 12321\ 043264^2 & 1232\ 0952911^2 + 48174000^2 &= 12321\ 047089^2 \\
123432\ 0956736^2 + 462176000^2 &= 1234321\ 043264^2 & 123432\ 0952911^2 + 482174000^2 &= 1234321\ 047089^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.208} \tag{5.217}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0956319^2 + 418000^2 &= 1\ 043681^2 & 0952476^2 + 436000^2 &= 1\ 047524^2 \\
12\ 0956319^2 + 4598000^2 &= 121\ 043681^2 & 12\ 0952476^2 + 4796000^2 &= 121\ 047524^2 \\
1232\ 0956319^2 + 46398000^2 &= 12321\ 043681^2 & 1232\ 0952476^2 + 48396000^2 &= 12321\ 047524^2 \\
123432\ 0956319^2 + 464398000^2 &= 1234321\ 043681^2 & 123432\ 0952476^2 + 484396000^2 &= 1234321\ 047524^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.209} \tag{5.218}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0952039^2 + 438000^2 &= 1\ 047961^2 & 0948016^2 + 456000^2 &= 1\ 051984^2 \\
12\ 0952039^2 + 4818000^2 &= 121\ 047961^2 & 12\ 0948016^2 + 5016000^2 &= 121\ 051984^2 \\
1232\ 0952039^2 + 48618000^2 &= 12321\ 047961^2 & 1232\ 0948016^2 + 50616000^2 &= 12321\ 051984^2 \\
123432\ 0952039^2 + 486618000^2 &= 1234321\ 047961^2 & 123432\ 0948016^2 + 506616000^2 &= 1234321\ 051984^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.219} \tag{5.228}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0951600^2 + 440000^2 &= 1\ 048400^2 & 0947559^2 + 458000^2 &= 1\ 052441^2 \\
12\ 0951600^2 + 4840000^2 &= 121\ 048400^2 & 12\ 0947559^2 + 5038000^2 &= 121\ 052441^2 \\
1232\ 0951600^2 + 48840000^2 &= 12321\ 048400^2 & 1232\ 0947559^2 + 50838000^2 &= 12321\ 052441^2 \\
123432\ 0951600^2 + 488840000^2 &= 1234321\ 048400^2 & 123432\ 0947559^2 + 508838000^2 &= 1234321\ 052441^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.220} \tag{5.229}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0951159^2 + 442000^2 &= 1\ 048841^2 & 0947100^2 + 460000^2 &= 1\ 052900^2 \\
12\ 0951159^2 + 4862000^2 &= 121\ 048841^2 & 12\ 0947100^2 + 5060000^2 &= 121\ 052900^2 \\
1232\ 0951159^2 + 49062000^2 &= 12321\ 048841^2 & 1232\ 0947100^2 + 51060000^2 &= 12321\ 052900^2 \\
123432\ 0951159^2 + 491062000^2 &= 1234321\ 048841^2 & 123432\ 0947100^2 + 511060000^2 &= 1234321\ 052900^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.221} \tag{5.230}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0950716^2 + 444000^2 &= 1\ 049284^2 & 0946639^2 + 462000^2 &= 1\ 053361^2 \\
12\ 0950716^2 + 4884000^2 &= 121\ 049284^2 & 12\ 0946639^2 + 5082000^2 &= 121\ 053361^2 \\
1232\ 0950716^2 + 49284000^2 &= 12321\ 049284^2 & 1232\ 0946639^2 + 51282000^2 &= 12321\ 053361^2 \\
123432\ 0950716^2 + 493284000^2 &= 1234321\ 049284^2 & 123432\ 0946639^2 + 513282000^2 &= 1234321\ 053361^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.222} \tag{5.231}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0950271^2 + 446000^2 &= 1\ 049729^2 & 0946176^2 + 464000^2 &= 1\ 053824^2 \\
12\ 0950271^2 + 4906000^2 &= 121\ 049729^2 & 12\ 0946176^2 + 5104000^2 &= 121\ 053824^2 \\
1232\ 0950271^2 + 49506000^2 &= 12321\ 049729^2 & 1232\ 0946176^2 + 51504000^2 &= 12321\ 053824^2 \\
123432\ 0950271^2 + 495506000^2 &= 1234321\ 049729^2 & 123432\ 0946176^2 + 515504000^2 &= 1234321\ 053824^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.223} \tag{5.232}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0949824^2 + 448000^2 &= 1\ 050176^2 & 0945711^2 + 466000^2 &= 1\ 054289^2 \\
12\ 0949824^2 + 4928000^2 &= 121\ 050176^2 & 12\ 0945711^2 + 5126000^2 &= 121\ 054289^2 \\
1232\ 0949824^2 + 49728000^2 &= 12321\ 050176^2 & 1232\ 0945711^2 + 51726000^2 &= 12321\ 054289^2 \\
123432\ 0949824^2 + 497728000^2 &= 1234321\ 050176^2 & 123432\ 0945711^2 + 517726000^2 &= 1234321\ 054289^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.224} \tag{5.233}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0949375^2 + 450000^2 &= 1\ 050625^2 & 0945244^2 + 468000^2 &= 1\ 054756^2 \\
12\ 0949375^2 + 4950000^2 &= 121\ 050625^2 & 12\ 0945244^2 + 5148000^2 &= 121\ 054756^2 \\
1232\ 0949375^2 + 49950000^2 &= 12321\ 050625^2 & 1232\ 0945244^2 + 51948000^2 &= 12321\ 054756^2 \\
123432\ 0949375^2 + 499950000^2 &= 1234321\ 050625^2 & 123432\ 0945244^2 + 519948000^2 &= 1234321\ 054756^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.225} \tag{5.234}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0948924^2 + 452000^2 &= 1\ 051076^2 & 0944775^2 + 470000^2 &= 1\ 055225^2 \\
12\ 0948924^2 + 4972000^2 &= 121\ 051076^2 & 12\ 0944775^2 + 5170000^2 &= 121\ 055225^2 \\
1232\ 0948924^2 + 50172000^2 &= 12321\ 051076^2 & 1232\ 0944775^2 + 52170000^2 &= 12321\ 055225^2 \\
123432\ 0948924^2 + 502172000^2 &= 1234321\ 051076^2 & 123432\ 0944775^2 + 522170000^2 &= 1234321\ 055225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.226} \tag{5.235}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0948471^2 + 454000^2 &= 1\ 051529^2 & 0944304^2 + 472000^2 &= 1\ 055696^2 \\
12\ 0948471^2 + 4994000^2 &= 121\ 051529^2 & 12\ 0944304^2 + 5192000^2 &= 121\ 055696^2 \\
1232\ 0948471^2 + 50394000^2 &= 12321\ 051529^2 & 1232\ 0944304^2 + 52392000^2 &= 12321\ 055696^2 \\
123432\ 0948471^2 + 504394000^2 &= 1234321\ 051529^2 & 123432\ 0944304^2 + 524392000^2 &= 1234321\ 055696^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.227} \tag{5.236}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0943831^2 + 474000^2 &= 1\ 056169^2 & 0939484^2 + 492000^2 &= 1\ 060516^2 \\
12\ 0943831^2 + 5214000^2 &= 121\ 056169^2 & 12\ 0939484^2 + 5412000^2 &= 121\ 060516^2 \\
1232\ 0943831^2 + 52614000^2 &= 12321\ 056169^2 & 1232\ 0939484^2 + 54612000^2 &= 12321\ 060516^2 \\
123432\ 0943831^2 + 526614000^2 &= 1234321\ 056169^2 & 123432\ 0939484^2 + 546612000^2 &= 1234321\ 060516^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.237} \tag{5.246}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0943356^2 + 476000^2 &= 1\ 056644^2 & 0938991^2 + 494000^2 &= 1\ 061009^2 \\
12\ 0943356^2 + 5236000^2 &= 121\ 056644^2 & 12\ 0938991^2 + 5434000^2 &= 121\ 061009^2 \\
1232\ 0943356^2 + 52836000^2 &= 12321\ 056644^2 & 1232\ 0938991^2 + 54834000^2 &= 12321\ 061009^2 \\
123432\ 0943356^2 + 528836000^2 &= 1234321\ 056644^2 & 123432\ 0938991^2 + 548834000^2 &= 1234321\ 061009^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.238} \tag{5.247}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0942879^2 + 478000^2 &= 1\ 057121^2 & 0938496^2 + 496000^2 &= 1\ 061504^2 \\
12\ 0942879^2 + 5258000^2 &= 121\ 057121^2 & 12\ 0938496^2 + 5456000^2 &= 121\ 061504^2 \\
1232\ 0942879^2 + 53058000^2 &= 12321\ 057121^2 & 1232\ 0938496^2 + 55056000^2 &= 12321\ 061504^2 \\
123432\ 0942879^2 + 531058000^2 &= 1234321\ 057121^2 & 123432\ 0938496^2 + 551056000^2 &= 1234321\ 061504^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.239} \tag{5.248}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0942400^2 + 480000^2 &= 1\ 057600^2 & 0937999^2 + 498000^2 &= 1\ 062001^2 \\
12\ 0942400^2 + 5280000^2 &= 121\ 057600^2 & 12\ 0937999^2 + 5478000^2 &= 121\ 062001^2 \\
1232\ 0942400^2 + 53280000^2 &= 12321\ 057600^2 & 1232\ 0937999^2 + 55278000^2 &= 12321\ 062001^2 \\
123432\ 0942400^2 + 533280000^2 &= 1234321\ 057600^2 & 123432\ 0937999^2 + 553278000^2 &= 1234321\ 062001^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.240} \tag{5.249}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0941919^2 + 482000^2 &= 1\ 058081^2 & 0937500^2 + 500000^2 &= 1\ 062500^2 \\
12\ 0941919^2 + 5302000^2 &= 121\ 058081^2 & 12\ 0937500^2 + 5500000^2 &= 121\ 062500^2 \\
1232\ 0941919^2 + 53502000^2 &= 12321\ 058081^2 & 1232\ 0937500^2 + 55500000^2 &= 12321\ 062500^2 \\
123432\ 0941919^2 + 535502000^2 &= 1234321\ 058081^2 & 123432\ 0937500^2 + 555500000^2 &= 1234321\ 062500^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.241} \tag{5.250}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0941436^2 + 484000^2 &= 1\ 058564^2 & 0936999^2 + 502000^2 &= 1\ 063001^2 \\
12\ 0941436^2 + 5324000^2 &= 121\ 058564^2 & 12\ 0936999^2 + 5522000^2 &= 121\ 063001^2 \\
1232\ 0941436^2 + 53724000^2 &= 12321\ 058564^2 & 1232\ 0936999^2 + 55722000^2 &= 12321\ 063001^2 \\
123432\ 0941436^2 + 537724000^2 &= 1234321\ 058564^2 & 123432\ 0936999^2 + 557722000^2 &= 1234321\ 063001^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.242} \tag{5.251}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0940951^2 + 486000^2 &= 1\ 059049^2 & 0936496^2 + 504000^2 &= 1\ 063504^2 \\
12\ 0940951^2 + 5346000^2 &= 121\ 059049^2 & 12\ 0936496^2 + 5544000^2 &= 121\ 063504^2 \\
1232\ 0940951^2 + 53946000^2 &= 12321\ 059049^2 & 1232\ 0936496^2 + 55944000^2 &= 12321\ 063504^2 \\
123432\ 0940951^2 + 539946000^2 &= 1234321\ 059049^2 & 123432\ 0936496^2 + 559944000^2 &= 1234321\ 063504^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.243} \tag{5.252}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0940464^2 + 488000^2 &= 1\ 059536^2 & 0935991^2 + 506000^2 &= 1\ 064009^2 \\
12\ 0940464^2 + 5368000^2 &= 121\ 059536^2 & 12\ 0935991^2 + 5566000^2 &= 121\ 064009^2 \\
1232\ 0940464^2 + 54168000^2 &= 12321\ 059536^2 & 1232\ 0935991^2 + 56166000^2 &= 12321\ 064009^2 \\
123432\ 0940464^2 + 542168000^2 &= 1234321\ 059536^2 & 123432\ 0935991^2 + 562166000^2 &= 1234321\ 064009^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.244} \tag{5.253}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0939975^2 + 490000^2 &= 1\ 060025^2 & 0935484^2 + 508000^2 &= 1\ 064516^2 \\
12\ 0939975^2 + 5390000^2 &= 121\ 060025^2 & 12\ 0935484^2 + 5588000^2 &= 121\ 064516^2 \\
1232\ 0939975^2 + 54390000^2 &= 12321\ 060025^2 & 1232\ 0935484^2 + 56388000^2 &= 12321\ 064516^2 \\
123432\ 0939975^2 + 544390000^2 &= 1234321\ 060025^2 & 123432\ 0935484^2 + 564388000^2 &= 1234321\ 064516^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.245} \tag{5.254}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0934975^2 + 510000^2 &= 1\ 065025^2 & 0930304^2 + 528000^2 &= 1\ 069696^2 \\
12\ 0934975^2 + 5610000^2 &= 121\ 065025^2 & 12\ 0930304^2 + 5808000^2 &= 121\ 069696^2 \\
1232\ 0934975^2 + 56610000^2 &= 12321\ 065025^2 & 1232\ 0930304^2 + 58608000^2 &= 12321\ 069696^2 \\
123432\ 0934975^2 + 566610000^2 &= 1234321\ 065025^2 & 123432\ 0930304^2 + 586608000^2 &= 1234321\ 069696^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.255} \tag{5.264}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0934464^2 + 512000^2 &= 1\ 065536^2 & 0929775^2 + 530000^2 &= 1\ 070225^2 \\
12\ 0934464^2 + 5632000^2 &= 121\ 065536^2 & 12\ 0929775^2 + 5830000^2 &= 121\ 070225^2 \\
1232\ 0934464^2 + 56832000^2 &= 12321\ 065536^2 & 1232\ 0929775^2 + 58830000^2 &= 12321\ 070225^2 \\
123432\ 0934464^2 + 568832000^2 &= 1234321\ 065536^2 & 123432\ 0929775^2 + 588830000^2 &= 1234321\ 070225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.256} \tag{5.265}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0933951^2 + 514000^2 &= 1\ 066049^2 & 0929244^2 + 532000^2 &= 1\ 070756^2 \\
12\ 0933951^2 + 5654000^2 &= 121\ 066049^2 & 12\ 0929244^2 + 5852000^2 &= 121\ 070756^2 \\
1232\ 0933951^2 + 57054000^2 &= 12321\ 066049^2 & 1232\ 0929244^2 + 59052000^2 &= 12321\ 070756^2 \\
123432\ 0933951^2 + 571054000^2 &= 1234321\ 066049^2 & 123432\ 0929244^2 + 591052000^2 &= 1234321\ 070756^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.257} \tag{5.266}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0933436^2 + 516000^2 &= 1\ 066564^2 & 0928711^2 + 534000^2 &= 1\ 071289^2 \\
12\ 0933436^2 + 5676000^2 &= 121\ 066564^2 & 12\ 0928711^2 + 5874000^2 &= 121\ 071289^2 \\
1232\ 0933436^2 + 57276000^2 &= 12321\ 066564^2 & 1232\ 0928711^2 + 59274000^2 &= 12321\ 071289^2 \\
123432\ 0933436^2 + 573276000^2 &= 1234321\ 066564^2 & 123432\ 0928711^2 + 593274000^2 &= 1234321\ 071289^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.258} \tag{5.267}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0932919^2 + 518000^2 &= 1\ 067081^2 & 0928176^2 + 536000^2 &= 1\ 071824^2 \\
12\ 0932919^2 + 5698000^2 &= 121\ 067081^2 & 12\ 0928176^2 + 5896000^2 &= 121\ 071824^2 \\
1232\ 0932919^2 + 57498000^2 &= 12321\ 067081^2 & 1232\ 0928176^2 + 59496000^2 &= 12321\ 071824^2 \\
123432\ 0932919^2 + 575498000^2 &= 1234321\ 067081^2 & 123432\ 0928176^2 + 595496000^2 &= 1234321\ 071824^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.259} \tag{5.268}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0932400^2 + 520000^2 &= 1\ 067600^2 & 0927639^2 + 538000^2 &= 1\ 072361^2 \\
12\ 0932400^2 + 5720000^2 &= 121\ 067600^2 & 12\ 0927639^2 + 5918000^2 &= 121\ 072361^2 \\
1232\ 0932400^2 + 57720000^2 &= 12321\ 067600^2 & 1232\ 0927639^2 + 59718000^2 &= 12321\ 072361^2 \\
123432\ 0932400^2 + 577720000^2 &= 1234321\ 067600^2 & 123432\ 0927639^2 + 597718000^2 &= 1234321\ 072361^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.260} \tag{5.269}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0931879^2 + 522000^2 &= 1\ 068121^2 & 0927100^2 + 540000^2 &= 1\ 072900^2 \\
12\ 0931879^2 + 5742000^2 &= 121\ 068121^2 & 12\ 0927100^2 + 5940000^2 &= 121\ 072900^2 \\
1232\ 0931879^2 + 57942000^2 &= 12321\ 068121^2 & 1232\ 0927100^2 + 59940000^2 &= 12321\ 072900^2 \\
123432\ 0931879^2 + 579942000^2 &= 1234321\ 068121^2 & 123432\ 0927100^2 + 599940000^2 &= 1234321\ 072900^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.261} \tag{5.270}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0931356^2 + 524000^2 &= 1\ 068644^2 & 0926559^2 + 542000^2 &= 1\ 073441^2 \\
12\ 0931356^2 + 5764000^2 &= 121\ 068644^2 & 12\ 0926559^2 + 5962000^2 &= 121\ 073441^2 \\
1232\ 0931356^2 + 58164000^2 &= 12321\ 068644^2 & 1232\ 0926559^2 + 60162000^2 &= 12321\ 073441^2 \\
123432\ 0931356^2 + 582164000^2 &= 1234321\ 068644^2 & 123432\ 0926559^2 + 602162000^2 &= 1234321\ 073441^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.262} \tag{5.271}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0930831^2 + 526000^2 &= 1\ 069169^2 & 0926016^2 + 544000^2 &= 1\ 073984^2 \\
12\ 0930831^2 + 5786000^2 &= 121\ 069169^2 & 12\ 0926016^2 + 5984000^2 &= 121\ 073984^2 \\
1232\ 0930831^2 + 58386000^2 &= 12321\ 069169^2 & 1232\ 0926016^2 + 60384000^2 &= 12321\ 073984^2 \\
123432\ 0930831^2 + 584386000^2 &= 1234321\ 069169^2 & 123432\ 0926016^2 + 604384000^2 &= 1234321\ 073984^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.263} \tag{5.272}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0925471^2 + 546000^2 &= 1\ 074529^2 & 0920476^2 + 564000^2 &= 1\ 079524^2 \\
12\ 0925471^2 + 6006000^2 &= 121\ 074529^2 & 12\ 0920476^2 + 6204000^2 &= 121\ 079524^2 \\
1232\ 0925471^2 + 60606000^2 &= 12321\ 074529^2 & 1232\ 0920476^2 + 62604000^2 &= 12321\ 079524^2 \\
123432\ 0925471^2 + 606606000^2 &= 1234321\ 074529^2 & 123432\ 0920476^2 + 626604000^2 &= 1234321\ 079524^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.273} \tag{5.282}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0924924^2 + 548000^2 &= 1\ 075076^2 & 0919911^2 + 566000^2 &= 1\ 080089^2 \\
12\ 0924924^2 + 6028000^2 &= 121\ 075076^2 & 12\ 0919911^2 + 6226000^2 &= 121\ 080089^2 \\
1232\ 0924924^2 + 60828000^2 &= 12321\ 075076^2 & 1232\ 0919911^2 + 62826000^2 &= 12321\ 080089^2 \\
123432\ 0924924^2 + 608828000^2 &= 1234321\ 075076^2 & 123432\ 0919911^2 + 628826000^2 &= 1234321\ 080089^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.274} \tag{5.283}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0924375^2 + 550000^2 &= 1\ 075625^2 & 0919344^2 + 568000^2 &= 1\ 080656^2 \\
12\ 0924375^2 + 6050000^2 &= 121\ 075625^2 & 12\ 0919344^2 + 6248000^2 &= 121\ 080656^2 \\
1232\ 0924375^2 + 61050000^2 &= 12321\ 075625^2 & 1232\ 0919344^2 + 63048000^2 &= 12321\ 080656^2 \\
123432\ 0924375^2 + 611050000^2 &= 1234321\ 075625^2 & 123432\ 0919344^2 + 631048000^2 &= 1234321\ 080656^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.275} \tag{5.284}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0923824^2 + 552000^2 &= 1\ 076176^2 & 0918775^2 + 570000^2 &= 1\ 081225^2 \\
12\ 0923824^2 + 6072000^2 &= 121\ 076176^2 & 12\ 0918775^2 + 6270000^2 &= 121\ 081225^2 \\
1232\ 0923824^2 + 61272000^2 &= 12321\ 076176^2 & 1232\ 0918775^2 + 63270000^2 &= 12321\ 081225^2 \\
123432\ 0923824^2 + 613272000^2 &= 1234321\ 076176^2 & 123432\ 0918775^2 + 633270000^2 &= 1234321\ 081225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.276} \tag{5.285}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0923271^2 + 554000^2 &= 1\ 076729^2 & 0918204^2 + 572000^2 &= 1\ 081796^2 \\
12\ 0923271^2 + 6094000^2 &= 121\ 076729^2 & 12\ 0918204^2 + 6292000^2 &= 121\ 081796^2 \\
1232\ 0923271^2 + 61494000^2 &= 12321\ 076729^2 & 1232\ 0918204^2 + 63492000^2 &= 12321\ 081796^2 \\
123432\ 0923271^2 + 615494000^2 &= 1234321\ 076729^2 & 123432\ 0918204^2 + 635492000^2 &= 1234321\ 081796^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.277} \tag{5.286}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0922716^2 + 556000^2 &= 1\ 077284^2 & 0917631^2 + 574000^2 &= 1\ 082369^2 \\
12\ 0922716^2 + 6116000^2 &= 121\ 077284^2 & 12\ 0917631^2 + 6314000^2 &= 121\ 082369^2 \\
1232\ 0922716^2 + 61716000^2 &= 12321\ 077284^2 & 1232\ 0917631^2 + 63714000^2 &= 12321\ 082369^2 \\
123432\ 0922716^2 + 617716000^2 &= 1234321\ 077284^2 & 123432\ 0917631^2 + 637714000^2 &= 1234321\ 082369^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.278} \tag{5.287}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0922159^2 + 558000^2 &= 1\ 077841^2 & 0917056^2 + 576000^2 &= 1\ 082944^2 \\
12\ 0922159^2 + 6138000^2 &= 121\ 077841^2 & 12\ 0917056^2 + 6336000^2 &= 121\ 082944^2 \\
1232\ 0922159^2 + 61938000^2 &= 12321\ 077841^2 & 1232\ 0917056^2 + 63936000^2 &= 12321\ 082944^2 \\
123432\ 0922159^2 + 619938000^2 &= 1234321\ 077841^2 & 123432\ 0917056^2 + 639936000^2 &= 1234321\ 082944^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.279} \tag{5.288}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0921600^2 + 560000^2 &= 1\ 078400^2 & 0916479^2 + 578000^2 &= 1\ 083521^2 \\
12\ 0921600^2 + 6160000^2 &= 121\ 078400^2 & 12\ 0916479^2 + 6358000^2 &= 121\ 083521^2 \\
1232\ 0921600^2 + 62160000^2 &= 12321\ 078400^2 & 1232\ 0916479^2 + 64158000^2 &= 12321\ 083521^2 \\
123432\ 0921600^2 + 622160000^2 &= 1234321\ 078400^2 & 123432\ 0916479^2 + 642158000^2 &= 1234321\ 083521^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.280} \tag{5.289}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0921039^2 + 562000^2 &= 1\ 078961^2 & 0915900^2 + 580000^2 &= 1\ 084100^2 \\
12\ 0921039^2 + 6182000^2 &= 121\ 078961^2 & 12\ 0915900^2 + 6380000^2 &= 121\ 084100^2 \\
1232\ 0921039^2 + 62382000^2 &= 12321\ 078961^2 & 1232\ 0915900^2 + 64380000^2 &= 12321\ 084100^2 \\
123432\ 0921039^2 + 624382000^2 &= 1234321\ 078961^2 & 123432\ 0915900^2 + 644380000^2 &= 1234321\ 084100^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.281} \tag{5.290}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0915319^2 + 582000^2 = 1084681^2 \\
120915319^2 + 6402000^2 = 121084681^2 \\
12320915319^2 + 64602000^2 = 12321084681^2 \\
1234320915319^2 + 646602000^2 = 1234321084681^2 \quad (5.291)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0912384^2 + 592000^2 = 1087616^2 \\
120912384^2 + 6512000^2 = 121087616^2 \\
12320912384^2 + 65712000^2 = 12321087616^2 \\
1234320912384^2 + 657712000^2 = 1234321087616^2 \quad (5.296)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0914736^2 + 584000^2 = 1085264^2 \\
120914736^2 + 6424000^2 = 121085264^2 \\
12320914736^2 + 64824000^2 = 12321085264^2 \\
1234320914736^2 + 648824000^2 = 1234321085264^2 \quad (5.292)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0911791^2 + 594000^2 = 1088209^2 \\
120911791^2 + 6534000^2 = 121088209^2 \\
12320911791^2 + 65934000^2 = 12321088209^2 \\
1234320911791^2 + 659934000^2 = 1234321088209^2 \quad (5.297)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0914151^2 + 586000^2 = 1085849^2 \\
120914151^2 + 6446000^2 = 121085849^2 \\
12320914151^2 + 65046000^2 = 12321085849^2 \\
1234320914151^2 + 651046000^2 = 1234321085849^2 \quad (5.293)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0911196^2 + 596000^2 = 1088804^2 \\
120911196^2 + 6556000^2 = 121088804^2 \\
12320911196^2 + 66156000^2 = 12321088804^2 \\
1234320911196^2 + 662156000^2 = 1234321088804^2 \quad (5.298)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0913564^2 + 588000^2 = 1086436^2 \\
120913564^2 + 6468000^2 = 121086436^2 \\
12320913564^2 + 65268000^2 = 12321086436^2 \\
1234320913564^2 + 653268000^2 = 1234321086436^2 \quad (5.294)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0910599^2 + 598000^2 = 1089401^2 \\
120910599^2 + 6578000^2 = 121089401^2 \\
12320910599^2 + 66378000^2 = 12321089401^2 \\
1234320910599^2 + 664378000^2 = 1234321089401^2 \quad (5.299)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0912975^2 + 590000^2 = 1087025^2 \\
120912975^2 + 6490000^2 = 121087025^2 \\
12320912975^2 + 65490000^2 = 12321087025^2 \\
1234320912975^2 + 655490000^2 = 1234321087025^2 \quad (5.295)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0910000^2 + 600000^2 = 1090000^2 \\
120910000^2 + 6600000^2 = 121090000^2 \\
12320910000^2 + 66600000^2 = 12321090000^2 \\
1234320910000^2 + 666600000^2 = 1234321090000^2 \quad (5.300)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0907584^2 + 608000^2 = 1092416^2 \\
120907584^2 + 6688000^2 = 121092416^2 \\
12320907584^2 + 67488000^2 = 12321092416^2 \\
1234320907584^2 + 675488000^2 = 1234321092416^2 \quad (5.304)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0909399^2 + 602000^2 = 1090601^2 \\
120909399^2 + 6622000^2 = 121090601^2 \\
12320909399^2 + 66822000^2 = 12321090601^2 \\
1234320909399^2 + 668822000^2 = 1234321090601^2 \quad (5.301)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0906975^2 + 610000^2 = 1093025^2 \\
120906975^2 + 6710000^2 = 121093025^2 \\
12320906975^2 + 67710000^2 = 12321093025^2 \\
1234320906975^2 + 677710000^2 = 1234321093025^2 \quad (5.305)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0908796^2 + 604000^2 = 1091204^2 \\
120908796^2 + 6644000^2 = 121091204^2 \\
12320908796^2 + 67044000^2 = 12321091204^2 \\
1234320908796^2 + 671044000^2 = 1234321091204^2 \quad (5.302)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0906364^2 + 612000^2 = 1093636^2 \\
120906364^2 + 6732000^2 = 121093636^2 \\
12320906364^2 + 67932000^2 = 12321093636^2 \\
1234320906364^2 + 679932000^2 = 1234321093636^2 \quad (5.306)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0908191^2 + 606000^2 = 1091809^2 \\
120908191^2 + 6666000^2 = 121091809^2 \\
12320908191^2 + 67266000^2 = 12321091809^2 \\
1234320908191^2 + 673266000^2 = 1234321091809^2 \quad (5.303)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0905751^2 + 614000^2 = 1094249^2 \\
120905751^2 + 6754000^2 = 121094249^2 \\
12320905751^2 + 68154000^2 = 12321094249^2 \\
1234320905751^2 + 682154000^2 = 1234321094249^2 \quad (5.307)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0905136^2 + 616000^2 &= 1\ 094864^2 & 0899511^2 + 634000^2 &= 1\ 100489^2 \\
12\ 0905136^2 + 6776000^2 &= 121\ 094864^2 & 12\ 0899511^2 + 6974000^2 &= 121\ 100489^2 \\
1232\ 0905136^2 + 68376000^2 &= 12321\ 094864^2 & 1232\ 0899511^2 + 70374000^2 &= 12321\ 100489^2 \\
123432\ 0905136^2 + 684376000^2 &= 1234321\ 094864^2 & 123432\ 0899511^2 + 704374000^2 &= 1234321\ 100489^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.308} \tag{5.317}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0904519^2 + 618000^2 &= 1\ 095481^2 & 0898876^2 + 636000^2 &= 1\ 101124^2 \\
12\ 0904519^2 + 6798000^2 &= 121\ 095481^2 & 12\ 0898876^2 + 6996000^2 &= 121\ 101124^2 \\
1232\ 0904519^2 + 68598000^2 &= 12321\ 095481^2 & 1232\ 0898876^2 + 70596000^2 &= 12321\ 101124^2 \\
123432\ 0904519^2 + 686598000^2 &= 1234321\ 095481^2 & 123432\ 0898876^2 + 706596000^2 &= 1234321\ 101124^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.309} \tag{5.318}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0903900^2 + 620000^2 &= 1\ 096100^2 & 0898239^2 + 638000^2 &= 1\ 101761^2 \\
12\ 0903900^2 + 6820000^2 &= 121\ 096100^2 & 12\ 0898239^2 + 7018000^2 &= 121\ 101761^2 \\
1232\ 0903900^2 + 68820000^2 &= 12321\ 096100^2 & 1232\ 0898239^2 + 70818000^2 &= 12321\ 101761^2 \\
123432\ 0903900^2 + 688820000^2 &= 1234321\ 096100^2 & 123432\ 0898239^2 + 708818000^2 &= 1234321\ 101761^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.310} \tag{5.319}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0903279^2 + 622000^2 &= 1\ 096721^2 & 0897600^2 + 640000^2 &= 1\ 102400^2 \\
12\ 0903279^2 + 6842000^2 &= 121\ 096721^2 & 12\ 0897600^2 + 7040000^2 &= 121\ 102400^2 \\
1232\ 0903279^2 + 69042000^2 &= 12321\ 096721^2 & 1232\ 0897600^2 + 71040000^2 &= 12321\ 102400^2 \\
123432\ 0903279^2 + 691042000^2 &= 1234321\ 096721^2 & 123432\ 0897600^2 + 711040000^2 &= 1234321\ 102400^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.311} \tag{5.320}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0902656^2 + 624000^2 &= 1\ 097344^2 & 0896959^2 + 642000^2 &= 1\ 103041^2 \\
12\ 0902656^2 + 6864000^2 &= 121\ 097344^2 & 12\ 0896959^2 + 7062000^2 &= 121\ 103041^2 \\
1232\ 0902656^2 + 69264000^2 &= 12321\ 097344^2 & 1232\ 0896959^2 + 71262000^2 &= 12321\ 103041^2 \\
123432\ 0902656^2 + 693264000^2 &= 1234321\ 097344^2 & 123432\ 0896959^2 + 713262000^2 &= 1234321\ 103041^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.312} \tag{5.321}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0902031^2 + 626000^2 &= 1\ 097969^2 & 0896316^2 + 644000^2 &= 1\ 103684^2 \\
12\ 0902031^2 + 6886000^2 &= 121\ 097969^2 & 12\ 0896316^2 + 7084000^2 &= 121\ 103684^2 \\
1232\ 0902031^2 + 69486000^2 &= 12321\ 097969^2 & 1232\ 0896316^2 + 71484000^2 &= 12321\ 103684^2 \\
123432\ 0902031^2 + 695486000^2 &= 1234321\ 097969^2 & 123432\ 0896316^2 + 715484000^2 &= 1234321\ 103684^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.313} \tag{5.322}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0901404^2 + 628000^2 &= 1\ 098596^2 & 0895671^2 + 646000^2 &= 1\ 104329^2 \\
12\ 0901404^2 + 6908000^2 &= 121\ 098596^2 & 12\ 0895671^2 + 7106000^2 &= 121\ 104329^2 \\
1232\ 0901404^2 + 69708000^2 &= 12321\ 098596^2 & 1232\ 0895671^2 + 71706000^2 &= 12321\ 104329^2 \\
123432\ 0901404^2 + 697708000^2 &= 1234321\ 098596^2 & 123432\ 0895671^2 + 717706000^2 &= 1234321\ 104329^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.314} \tag{5.323}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0900775^2 + 630000^2 &= 1\ 099225^2 & 0895024^2 + 648000^2 &= 1\ 104976^2 \\
12\ 0900775^2 + 6930000^2 &= 121\ 099225^2 & 12\ 0895024^2 + 7128000^2 &= 121\ 104976^2 \\
1232\ 0900775^2 + 69930000^2 &= 12321\ 099225^2 & 1232\ 0895024^2 + 71928000^2 &= 12321\ 104976^2 \\
123432\ 0900775^2 + 699930000^2 &= 1234321\ 099225^2 & 123432\ 0895024^2 + 719928000^2 &= 1234321\ 104976^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.315} \tag{5.324}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0900144^2 + 632000^2 &= 1\ 099856^2 & 0894375^2 + 650000^2 &= 1\ 105625^2 \\
12\ 0900144^2 + 6952000^2 &= 121\ 099856^2 & 12\ 0894375^2 + 7150000^2 &= 121\ 105625^2 \\
1232\ 0900144^2 + 70152000^2 &= 12321\ 099856^2 & 1232\ 0894375^2 + 72150000^2 &= 12321\ 105625^2 \\
123432\ 0900144^2 + 702152000^2 &= 1234321\ 099856^2 & 123432\ 0894375^2 + 722150000^2 &= 1234321\ 105625^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.316} \tag{5.325}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0893724^2 + 652000^2 &= 1\ 106276^2 & 0887775^2 + 670000^2 &= 1\ 112225^2 \\
12\ 0893724^2 + 7172000^2 &= 121\ 106276^2 & 12\ 0887775^2 + 7370000^2 &= 121\ 112225^2 \\
1232\ 0893724^2 + 72372000^2 &= 12321\ 106276^2 & 1232\ 0887775^2 + 74370000^2 &= 12321\ 112225^2 \\
123432\ 0893724^2 + 724372000^2 &= 1234321\ 106276^2 & 123432\ 0887775^2 + 744370000^2 &= 1234321\ 112225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.326} \tag{5.335}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0893071^2 + 654000^2 &= 1\ 106929^2 & 0887104^2 + 672000^2 &= 1\ 112896^2 \\
12\ 0893071^2 + 7194000^2 &= 121\ 106929^2 & 12\ 0887104^2 + 7392000^2 &= 121\ 112896^2 \\
1232\ 0893071^2 + 72594000^2 &= 12321\ 106929^2 & 1232\ 0887104^2 + 74592000^2 &= 12321\ 112896^2 \\
123432\ 0893071^2 + 726594000^2 &= 1234321\ 106929^2 & 123432\ 0887104^2 + 746592000^2 &= 1234321\ 112896^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.327} \tag{5.336}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0892416^2 + 656000^2 &= 1\ 107584^2 & 0886431^2 + 674000^2 &= 1\ 113569^2 \\
12\ 0892416^2 + 7216000^2 &= 121\ 107584^2 & 12\ 0886431^2 + 7414000^2 &= 121\ 113569^2 \\
1232\ 0892416^2 + 72816000^2 &= 12321\ 107584^2 & 1232\ 0886431^2 + 74814000^2 &= 12321\ 113569^2 \\
123432\ 0892416^2 + 728816000^2 &= 1234321\ 107584^2 & 123432\ 0886431^2 + 748814000^2 &= 1234321\ 113569^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.328} \tag{5.337}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0891759^2 + 658000^2 &= 1\ 108241^2 & 0885756^2 + 676000^2 &= 1\ 114244^2 \\
12\ 0891759^2 + 7238000^2 &= 121\ 108241^2 & 12\ 0885756^2 + 7436000^2 &= 121\ 114244^2 \\
1232\ 0891759^2 + 73038000^2 &= 12321\ 108241^2 & 1232\ 0885756^2 + 75036000^2 &= 12321\ 114244^2 \\
123432\ 0891759^2 + 731038000^2 &= 1234321\ 108241^2 & 123432\ 0885756^2 + 751036000^2 &= 1234321\ 114244^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.329} \tag{5.338}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0891100^2 + 660000^2 &= 1\ 108900^2 & 0885079^2 + 678000^2 &= 1\ 114921^2 \\
12\ 0891100^2 + 7260000^2 &= 121\ 108900^2 & 12\ 0885079^2 + 7458000^2 &= 121\ 114921^2 \\
1232\ 0891100^2 + 73260000^2 &= 12321\ 108900^2 & 1232\ 0885079^2 + 75258000^2 &= 12321\ 114921^2 \\
123432\ 0891100^2 + 733260000^2 &= 1234321\ 108900^2 & 123432\ 0885079^2 + 753258000^2 &= 1234321\ 114921^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.330} \tag{5.339}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0890439^2 + 662000^2 &= 1\ 109561^2 & 0884400^2 + 680000^2 &= 1\ 115600^2 \\
12\ 0890439^2 + 7282000^2 &= 121\ 109561^2 & 12\ 0884400^2 + 7480000^2 &= 121\ 115600^2 \\
1232\ 0890439^2 + 73482000^2 &= 12321\ 109561^2 & 1232\ 0884400^2 + 75480000^2 &= 12321\ 115600^2 \\
123432\ 0890439^2 + 735482000^2 &= 1234321\ 109561^2 & 123432\ 0884400^2 + 755480000^2 &= 1234321\ 115600^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.331} \tag{5.340}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0889776^2 + 664000^2 &= 1\ 110224^2 & 0883719^2 + 682000^2 &= 1\ 116281^2 \\
12\ 0889776^2 + 7304000^2 &= 121\ 110224^2 & 12\ 0883719^2 + 7502000^2 &= 121\ 116281^2 \\
1232\ 0889776^2 + 73704000^2 &= 12321\ 110224^2 & 1232\ 0883719^2 + 75702000^2 &= 12321\ 116281^2 \\
123432\ 0889776^2 + 737704000^2 &= 1234321\ 110224^2 & 123432\ 0883719^2 + 757702000^2 &= 1234321\ 116281^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.332} \tag{5.341}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0889111^2 + 666000^2 &= 1\ 110889^2 & 0883036^2 + 684000^2 &= 1\ 116964^2 \\
12\ 0889111^2 + 7326000^2 &= 121\ 110889^2 & 12\ 0883036^2 + 7524000^2 &= 121\ 116964^2 \\
1232\ 0889111^2 + 73926000^2 &= 12321\ 110889^2 & 1232\ 0883036^2 + 75924000^2 &= 12321\ 116964^2 \\
123432\ 0889111^2 + 739926000^2 &= 1234321\ 110889^2 & 123432\ 0883036^2 + 759924000^2 &= 1234321\ 116964^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.333} \tag{5.342}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0888444^2 + 668000^2 &= 1\ 111556^2 & 0882351^2 + 686000^2 &= 1\ 117649^2 \\
12\ 0888444^2 + 7348000^2 &= 121\ 111556^2 & 12\ 0882351^2 + 7546000^2 &= 121\ 117649^2 \\
1232\ 0888444^2 + 74148000^2 &= 12321\ 111556^2 & 1232\ 0882351^2 + 76146000^2 &= 12321\ 117649^2 \\
123432\ 0888444^2 + 742148000^2 &= 1234321\ 111556^2 & 123432\ 0882351^2 + 762146000^2 &= 1234321\ 117649^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.334} \tag{5.343}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0881664^2 + 688000^2 &= 1\ 118336^2 & 0875391^2 + 706000^2 &= 1\ 124609^2 \\
12\ 0881664^2 + 7568000^2 &= 121\ 118336^2 & 12\ 0875391^2 + 7766000^2 &= 121\ 124609^2 \\
1232\ 0881664^2 + 76368000^2 &= 12321\ 118336^2 & 1232\ 0875391^2 + 78366000^2 &= 12321\ 124609^2 \\
123432\ 0881664^2 + 764368000^2 &= 1234321\ 118336^2 & 123432\ 0875391^2 + 784366000^2 &= 1234321\ 124609^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.344} \tag{5.353}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0880975^2 + 690000^2 &= 1\ 119025^2 & 0874684^2 + 708000^2 &= 1\ 125316^2 \\
12\ 0880975^2 + 7590000^2 &= 121\ 119025^2 & 12\ 0874684^2 + 7788000^2 &= 121\ 125316^2 \\
1232\ 0880975^2 + 76590000^2 &= 12321\ 119025^2 & 1232\ 0874684^2 + 78588000^2 &= 12321\ 125316^2 \\
123432\ 0880975^2 + 766590000^2 &= 1234321\ 119025^2 & 123432\ 0874684^2 + 786588000^2 &= 1234321\ 125316^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.345} \tag{5.354}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0880284^2 + 692000^2 &= 1\ 119716^2 & 0873975^2 + 710000^2 &= 1\ 126025^2 \\
12\ 0880284^2 + 7612000^2 &= 121\ 119716^2 & 12\ 0873975^2 + 7810000^2 &= 121\ 126025^2 \\
1232\ 0880284^2 + 76812000^2 &= 12321\ 119716^2 & 1232\ 0873975^2 + 78810000^2 &= 12321\ 126025^2 \\
123432\ 0880284^2 + 768812000^2 &= 1234321\ 119716^2 & 123432\ 0873975^2 + 788810000^2 &= 1234321\ 126025^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.346} \tag{5.355}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0879591^2 + 694000^2 &= 1\ 120409^2 & 0873264^2 + 712000^2 &= 1\ 126736^2 \\
12\ 0879591^2 + 7634000^2 &= 121\ 120409^2 & 12\ 0873264^2 + 7832000^2 &= 121\ 126736^2 \\
1232\ 0879591^2 + 77034000^2 &= 12321\ 120409^2 & 1232\ 0873264^2 + 79032000^2 &= 12321\ 126736^2 \\
123432\ 0879591^2 + 771034000^2 &= 1234321\ 120409^2 & 123432\ 0873264^2 + 791032000^2 &= 1234321\ 126736^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.347} \tag{5.356}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0878896^2 + 696000^2 &= 1\ 121104^2 & 0872551^2 + 714000^2 &= 1\ 127449^2 \\
12\ 0878896^2 + 7656000^2 &= 121\ 121104^2 & 12\ 0872551^2 + 7854000^2 &= 121\ 127449^2 \\
1232\ 0878896^2 + 77256000^2 &= 12321\ 121104^2 & 1232\ 0872551^2 + 79254000^2 &= 12321\ 127449^2 \\
123432\ 0878896^2 + 773256000^2 &= 1234321\ 121104^2 & 123432\ 0872551^2 + 793254000^2 &= 1234321\ 127449^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.348} \tag{5.357}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0878199^2 + 698000^2 &= 1\ 121801^2 & 0871836^2 + 716000^2 &= 1\ 128164^2 \\
12\ 0878199^2 + 7678000^2 &= 121\ 121801^2 & 12\ 0871836^2 + 7876000^2 &= 121\ 128164^2 \\
1232\ 0878199^2 + 77478000^2 &= 12321\ 121801^2 & 1232\ 0871836^2 + 79476000^2 &= 12321\ 128164^2 \\
123432\ 0878199^2 + 775478000^2 &= 1234321\ 121801^2 & 123432\ 0871836^2 + 795476000^2 &= 1234321\ 128164^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.349} \tag{5.358}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0877500^2 + 700000^2 &= 1\ 122500^2 & 0871119^2 + 718000^2 &= 1\ 128881^2 \\
12\ 0877500^2 + 7700000^2 &= 121\ 122500^2 & 12\ 0871119^2 + 7898000^2 &= 121\ 128881^2 \\
1232\ 0877500^2 + 77700000^2 &= 12321\ 122500^2 & 1232\ 0871119^2 + 79698000^2 &= 12321\ 128881^2 \\
123432\ 0877500^2 + 777700000^2 &= 1234321\ 122500^2 & 123432\ 0871119^2 + 797698000^2 &= 1234321\ 128881^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.350} \tag{5.359}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0876799^2 + 702000^2 &= 1\ 123201^2 & 0870400^2 + 720000^2 &= 1\ 129600^2 \\
12\ 0876799^2 + 7722000^2 &= 121\ 123201^2 & 12\ 0870400^2 + 7920000^2 &= 121\ 129600^2 \\
1232\ 0876799^2 + 77922000^2 &= 12321\ 123201^2 & 1232\ 0870400^2 + 79920000^2 &= 12321\ 129600^2 \\
123432\ 0876799^2 + 779922000^2 &= 1234321\ 123201^2 & 123432\ 0870400^2 + 799920000^2 &= 1234321\ 129600^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.351} \tag{5.360}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0876096^2 + 704000^2 &= 1\ 123904^2 & 0869679^2 + 722000^2 &= 1\ 130321^2 \\
12\ 0876096^2 + 7744000^2 &= 121\ 123904^2 & 12\ 0869679^2 + 7942000^2 &= 121\ 130321^2 \\
1232\ 0876096^2 + 78144000^2 &= 12321\ 123904^2 & 1232\ 0869679^2 + 80142000^2 &= 12321\ 130321^2 \\
123432\ 0876096^2 + 782144000^2 &= 1234321\ 123904^2 & 123432\ 0869679^2 + 802142000^2 &= 1234321\ 130321^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.352} \tag{5.361}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0868956^2 + 724000^2 &= 1\ 131044^2 & 0862359^2 + 742000^2 &= 1\ 137641^2 \\
12\ 0868956^2 + 7964000^2 &= 121\ 131044^2 & 12\ 0862359^2 + 8162000^2 &= 121\ 137641^2 \\
1232\ 0868956^2 + 80364000^2 &= 12321\ 131044^2 & 1232\ 0862359^2 + 82362000^2 &= 12321\ 137641^2 \\
123432\ 0868956^2 + 804364000^2 &= 1234321\ 131044^2 & 123432\ 0862359^2 + 824362000^2 &= 1234321\ 137641^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.362} \tag{5.371}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0868231^2 + 726000^2 &= 1\ 131769^2 & 0861616^2 + 744000^2 &= 1\ 138384^2 \\
12\ 0868231^2 + 7986000^2 &= 121\ 131769^2 & 12\ 0861616^2 + 8184000^2 &= 121\ 138384^2 \\
1232\ 0868231^2 + 80586000^2 &= 12321\ 131769^2 & 1232\ 0861616^2 + 82584000^2 &= 12321\ 138384^2 \\
123432\ 0868231^2 + 806586000^2 &= 1234321\ 131769^2 & 123432\ 0861616^2 + 826584000^2 &= 1234321\ 138384^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.363} \tag{5.372}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0867504^2 + 728000^2 &= 1\ 132496^2 & 0860871^2 + 746000^2 &= 1\ 139129^2 \\
12\ 0867504^2 + 8008000^2 &= 121\ 132496^2 & 12\ 0860871^2 + 8206000^2 &= 121\ 139129^2 \\
1232\ 0867504^2 + 80808000^2 &= 12321\ 132496^2 & 1232\ 0860871^2 + 82806000^2 &= 12321\ 139129^2 \\
123432\ 0867504^2 + 808808000^2 &= 1234321\ 132496^2 & 123432\ 0860871^2 + 828806000^2 &= 1234321\ 139129^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.364} \tag{5.373}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0866775^2 + 730000^2 &= 1\ 133225^2 & 0860124^2 + 748000^2 &= 1\ 139876^2 \\
12\ 0866775^2 + 8030000^2 &= 121\ 133225^2 & 12\ 0860124^2 + 8228000^2 &= 121\ 139876^2 \\
1232\ 0866775^2 + 81030000^2 &= 12321\ 133225^2 & 1232\ 0860124^2 + 83028000^2 &= 12321\ 139876^2 \\
123432\ 0866775^2 + 811030000^2 &= 1234321\ 133225^2 & 123432\ 0860124^2 + 831028000^2 &= 1234321\ 139876^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.365} \tag{5.374}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0866044^2 + 732000^2 &= 1\ 133956^2 & 0859375^2 + 750000^2 &= 1\ 140625^2 \\
12\ 0866044^2 + 8052000^2 &= 121\ 133956^2 & 12\ 0859375^2 + 8250000^2 &= 121\ 140625^2 \\
1232\ 0866044^2 + 81252000^2 &= 12321\ 133956^2 & 1232\ 0859375^2 + 83250000^2 &= 12321\ 140625^2 \\
123432\ 0866044^2 + 813252000^2 &= 1234321\ 133956^2 & 123432\ 0859375^2 + 833250000^2 &= 1234321\ 140625^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.366} \tag{5.375}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0865311^2 + 734000^2 &= 1\ 134689^2 & 0858624^2 + 752000^2 &= 1\ 141376^2 \\
12\ 0865311^2 + 8074000^2 &= 121\ 134689^2 & 12\ 0858624^2 + 8272000^2 &= 121\ 141376^2 \\
1232\ 0865311^2 + 81474000^2 &= 12321\ 134689^2 & 1232\ 0858624^2 + 83472000^2 &= 12321\ 141376^2 \\
123432\ 0865311^2 + 815474000^2 &= 1234321\ 134689^2 & 123432\ 0858624^2 + 835472000^2 &= 1234321\ 141376^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.367} \tag{5.376}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0864576^2 + 736000^2 &= 1\ 135424^2 & 0857871^2 + 754000^2 &= 1\ 142129^2 \\
12\ 0864576^2 + 8096000^2 &= 121\ 135424^2 & 12\ 0857871^2 + 8294000^2 &= 121\ 142129^2 \\
1232\ 0864576^2 + 81696000^2 &= 12321\ 135424^2 & 1232\ 0857871^2 + 83694000^2 &= 12321\ 142129^2 \\
123432\ 0864576^2 + 817696000^2 &= 1234321\ 135424^2 & 123432\ 0857871^2 + 837694000^2 &= 1234321\ 142129^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.368} \tag{5.377}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0863839^2 + 738000^2 &= 1\ 136161^2 & 0857116^2 + 756000^2 &= 1\ 142884^2 \\
12\ 0863839^2 + 8118000^2 &= 121\ 136161^2 & 12\ 0857116^2 + 8316000^2 &= 121\ 142884^2 \\
1232\ 0863839^2 + 81918000^2 &= 12321\ 136161^2 & 1232\ 0857116^2 + 83916000^2 &= 12321\ 142884^2 \\
123432\ 0863839^2 + 819918000^2 &= 1234321\ 136161^2 & 123432\ 0857116^2 + 839916000^2 &= 1234321\ 142884^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.369} \tag{5.378}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0863100^2 + 740000^2 &= 1\ 136900^2 & 0856359^2 + 758000^2 &= 1\ 143641^2 \\
12\ 0863100^2 + 8140000^2 &= 121\ 136900^2 & 12\ 0856359^2 + 8338000^2 &= 121\ 143641^2 \\
1232\ 0863100^2 + 82140000^2 &= 12321\ 136900^2 & 1232\ 0856359^2 + 84138000^2 &= 12321\ 143641^2 \\
123432\ 0863100^2 + 822140000^2 &= 1234321\ 136900^2 & 123432\ 0856359^2 + 842138000^2 &= 1234321\ 143641^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.370} \tag{5.379}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0855600^2 + 760000^2 = 1\ 144400^2 \\
12\ 0855600^2 + 8360000^2 = 121\ 144400^2 \\
1232\ 0855600^2 + 84360000^2 = 12321\ 144400^2 \\
123432\ 0855600^2 + 844360000^2 = 1234321\ 144400^2 \quad (5.380)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0847900^2 + 780000^2 = 1\ 152100^2 \\
12\ 0847900^2 + 8580000^2 = 121\ 152100^2 \\
1232\ 0847900^2 + 86580000^2 = 12321\ 152100^2 \\
123432\ 0847900^2 + 866580000^2 = 1234321\ 152100^2 \quad (5.390)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0854839^2 + 762000^2 = 1\ 145161^2 \\
12\ 0854839^2 + 8382000^2 = 121\ 145161^2 \\
1232\ 0854839^2 + 84582000^2 = 12321\ 145161^2 \\
123432\ 0854839^2 + 846582000^2 = 1234321\ 145161^2 \quad (5.381)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0847119^2 + 782000^2 = 1\ 152881^2 \\
12\ 0847119^2 + 8602000^2 = 121\ 152881^2 \\
1232\ 0847119^2 + 86802000^2 = 12321\ 152881^2 \\
123432\ 0847119^2 + 868802000^2 = 1234321\ 152881^2 \quad (5.391)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0854076^2 + 764000^2 = 1\ 145924^2 \\
12\ 0854076^2 + 8404000^2 = 121\ 145924^2 \\
1232\ 0854076^2 + 84804000^2 = 12321\ 145924^2 \\
123432\ 0854076^2 + 848804000^2 = 1234321\ 145924^2 \quad (5.382)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0846336^2 + 784000^2 = 1\ 153664^2 \\
12\ 0846336^2 + 8624000^2 = 121\ 153664^2 \\
1232\ 0846336^2 + 87024000^2 = 12321\ 153664^2 \\
123432\ 0846336^2 + 871024000^2 = 1234321\ 153664^2 \quad (5.392)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0853311^2 + 766000^2 = 1\ 146689^2 \\
12\ 0853311^2 + 8426000^2 = 121\ 146689^2 \\
1232\ 0853311^2 + 85026000^2 = 12321\ 146689^2 \\
123432\ 0853311^2 + 851026000^2 = 1234321\ 146689^2 \quad (5.383)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0845551^2 + 786000^2 = 1\ 154449^2 \\
12\ 0845551^2 + 8646000^2 = 121\ 154449^2 \\
1232\ 0845551^2 + 87246000^2 = 12321\ 154449^2 \\
123432\ 0845551^2 + 873246000^2 = 1234321\ 154449^2 \quad (5.393)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0852544^2 + 768000^2 = 1\ 147456^2 \\
12\ 0852544^2 + 8448000^2 = 121\ 147456^2 \\
1232\ 0852544^2 + 85248000^2 = 12321\ 147456^2 \\
123432\ 0852544^2 + 853248000^2 = 1234321\ 147456^2 \quad (5.384)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0844764^2 + 788000^2 = 1\ 155236^2 \\
12\ 0844764^2 + 8668000^2 = 121\ 155236^2 \\
1232\ 0844764^2 + 87468000^2 = 12321\ 155236^2 \\
123432\ 0844764^2 + 875468000^2 = 1234321\ 155236^2 \quad (5.394)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0851775^2 + 770000^2 = 1\ 148225^2 \\
12\ 0851775^2 + 8470000^2 = 121\ 148225^2 \\
1232\ 0851775^2 + 85470000^2 = 12321\ 148225^2 \\
123432\ 0851775^2 + 855470000^2 = 1234321\ 148225^2 \quad (5.385)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0843975^2 + 790000^2 = 1\ 156025^2 \\
12\ 0843975^2 + 8690000^2 = 121\ 156025^2 \\
1232\ 0843975^2 + 87690000^2 = 12321\ 156025^2 \\
123432\ 0843975^2 + 877690000^2 = 1234321\ 156025^2 \quad (5.395)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0851004^2 + 772000^2 = 1\ 148996^2 \\
12\ 0851004^2 + 8492000^2 = 121\ 148996^2 \\
1232\ 0851004^2 + 85692000^2 = 12321\ 148996^2 \\
123432\ 0851004^2 + 857692000^2 = 1234321\ 148996^2 \quad (5.386)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0843184^2 + 792000^2 = 1\ 156816^2 \\
12\ 0843184^2 + 8712000^2 = 121\ 156816^2 \\
1232\ 0843184^2 + 87912000^2 = 12321\ 156816^2 \\
123432\ 0843184^2 + 879912000^2 = 1234321\ 156816^2 \quad (5.396)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0850231^2 + 774000^2 = 1\ 149769^2 \\
12\ 0850231^2 + 8514000^2 = 121\ 149769^2 \\
1232\ 0850231^2 + 85914000^2 = 12321\ 149769^2 \\
123432\ 0850231^2 + 859914000^2 = 1234321\ 149769^2 \quad (5.387)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0842391^2 + 794000^2 = 1\ 157609^2 \\
12\ 0842391^2 + 8734000^2 = 121\ 157609^2 \\
1232\ 0842391^2 + 88134000^2 = 12321\ 157609^2 \\
123432\ 0842391^2 + 882134000^2 = 1234321\ 157609^2 \quad (5.397)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0849456^2 + 776000^2 = 1\ 150544^2 \\
12\ 0849456^2 + 8536000^2 = 121\ 150544^2 \\
1232\ 0849456^2 + 86136000^2 = 12321\ 150544^2 \\
123432\ 0849456^2 + 862136000^2 = 1234321\ 150544^2 \quad (5.388)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0841596^2 + 796000^2 = 1\ 158404^2 \\
12\ 0841596^2 + 8756000^2 = 121\ 158404^2 \\
1232\ 0841596^2 + 88356000^2 = 12321\ 158404^2 \\
123432\ 0841596^2 + 884356000^2 = 1234321\ 158404^2 \quad (5.398)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0848679^2 + 778000^2 = 1\ 151321^2 \\
12\ 0848679^2 + 8558000^2 = 121\ 151321^2 \\
1232\ 0848679^2 + 86358000^2 = 12321\ 151321^2 \\
123432\ 0848679^2 + 864358000^2 = 1234321\ 151321^2 \quad (5.389)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0840799^2 + 798000^2 = 1\ 159201^2 \\
12\ 0840799^2 + 8778000^2 = 121\ 159201^2 \\
1232\ 0840799^2 + 88578000^2 = 12321\ 159201^2 \\
123432\ 0840799^2 + 886578000^2 = 1234321\ 159201^2 \quad (5.399)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0840000^2 + 800000^2 &= 1\ 160000^2 & 0832719^2 + 818000^2 &= 1\ 167281^2 \\
12\ 0840000^2 + 8800000^2 &= 121\ 160000^2 & 12\ 0832719^2 + 8998000^2 &= 121\ 167281^2 \\
1232\ 0840000^2 + 88800000^2 &= 12321\ 160000^2 & 1232\ 0832719^2 + 90798000^2 &= 12321\ 167281^2 \\
123432\ 0840000^2 + 888800000^2 &= 1234321\ 160000^2 & 123432\ 0832719^2 + 908798000^2 &= 1234321\ 167281^2 \quad (5.409)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.400)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0839199^2 + 802000^2 &= 1\ 160801^2 & 0831900^2 + 820000^2 &= 1\ 168100^2 \\
12\ 0839199^2 + 8822000^2 &= 121\ 160801^2 & 12\ 0831900^2 + 9020000^2 &= 121\ 168100^2 \\
1232\ 0839199^2 + 89022000^2 &= 12321\ 160801^2 & 1232\ 0831900^2 + 91020000^2 &= 12321\ 168100^2 \\
123432\ 0839199^2 + 891022000^2 &= 1234321\ 160801^2 & 123432\ 0831900^2 + 911020000^2 &= 1234321\ 168100^2 \quad (5.410)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.401)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0838396^2 + 804000^2 &= 1\ 161604^2 & 0831079^2 + 822000^2 &= 1\ 168921^2 \\
12\ 0838396^2 + 8844000^2 &= 121\ 161604^2 & 12\ 0831079^2 + 9042000^2 &= 121\ 168921^2 \\
1232\ 0838396^2 + 89244000^2 &= 12321\ 161604^2 & 1232\ 0831079^2 + 91242000^2 &= 12321\ 168921^2 \\
123432\ 0838396^2 + 893244000^2 &= 1234321\ 161604^2 & 123432\ 0831079^2 + 913242000^2 &= 1234321\ 168921^2 \quad (5.411)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.402)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0837591^2 + 806000^2 &= 1\ 162409^2 & 0830256^2 + 824000^2 &= 1\ 169744^2 \\
12\ 0837591^2 + 8866000^2 &= 121\ 162409^2 & 12\ 0830256^2 + 9064000^2 &= 121\ 169744^2 \\
1232\ 0837591^2 + 89466000^2 &= 12321\ 162409^2 & 1232\ 0830256^2 + 91464000^2 &= 12321\ 169744^2 \\
123432\ 0837591^2 + 895466000^2 &= 1234321\ 162409^2 & 123432\ 0830256^2 + 915464000^2 &= 1234321\ 169744^2 \quad (5.412)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.403)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0836784^2 + 808000^2 &= 1\ 163216^2 & 0829431^2 + 826000^2 &= 1\ 170569^2 \\
12\ 0836784^2 + 8888000^2 &= 121\ 163216^2 & 12\ 0829431^2 + 9086000^2 &= 121\ 170569^2 \\
1232\ 0836784^2 + 89688000^2 &= 12321\ 163216^2 & 1232\ 0829431^2 + 91686000^2 &= 12321\ 170569^2 \\
123432\ 0836784^2 + 897688000^2 &= 1234321\ 163216^2 & 123432\ 0829431^2 + 917686000^2 &= 1234321\ 170569^2 \quad (5.413)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.404)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0835975^2 + 810000^2 &= 1\ 164025^2 & 0828604^2 + 828000^2 &= 1\ 171396^2 \\
12\ 0835975^2 + 8910000^2 &= 121\ 164025^2 & 12\ 0828604^2 + 9108000^2 &= 121\ 171396^2 \\
1232\ 0835975^2 + 89910000^2 &= 12321\ 164025^2 & 1232\ 0828604^2 + 91908000^2 &= 12321\ 171396^2 \\
123432\ 0835975^2 + 899910000^2 &= 1234321\ 164025^2 & 123432\ 0828604^2 + 919908000^2 &= 1234321\ 171396^2 \quad (5.414)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.405)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0835164^2 + 812000^2 &= 1\ 164836^2 & 0827775^2 + 830000^2 &= 1\ 172225^2 \\
12\ 0835164^2 + 8932000^2 &= 121\ 164836^2 & 12\ 0827775^2 + 9130000^2 &= 121\ 172225^2 \\
1232\ 0835164^2 + 90132000^2 &= 12321\ 164836^2 & 1232\ 0827775^2 + 92130000^2 &= 12321\ 172225^2 \\
123432\ 0835164^2 + 902132000^2 &= 1234321\ 164836^2 & 123432\ 0827775^2 + 922130000^2 &= 1234321\ 172225^2 \quad (5.415)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.406)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0834351^2 + 814000^2 &= 1\ 165649^2 & 0826944^2 + 832000^2 &= 1\ 173056^2 \\
12\ 0834351^2 + 8954000^2 &= 121\ 165649^2 & 12\ 0826944^2 + 9152000^2 &= 121\ 173056^2 \\
1232\ 0834351^2 + 90354000^2 &= 12321\ 165649^2 & 1232\ 0826944^2 + 92352000^2 &= 12321\ 173056^2 \\
123432\ 0834351^2 + 904354000^2 &= 1234321\ 165649^2 & 123432\ 0826944^2 + 924352000^2 &= 1234321\ 173056^2 \quad (5.416)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.407)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0833536^2 + 816000^2 &= 1\ 166464^2 & 0826111^2 + 834000^2 &= 1\ 173889^2 \\
12\ 0833536^2 + 8976000^2 &= 121\ 166464^2 & 12\ 0826111^2 + 9174000^2 &= 121\ 173889^2 \\
1232\ 0833536^2 + 90576000^2 &= 12321\ 166464^2 & 1232\ 0826111^2 + 92574000^2 &= 12321\ 173889^2 \\
123432\ 0833536^2 + 906576000^2 &= 1234321\ 166464^2 & 123432\ 0826111^2 + 926574000^2 &= 1234321\ 173889^2 \quad (5.417)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.408)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0825276^2 + 836000^2 &= 1\ 174724^2 & 0817671^2 + 854000^2 &= 1\ 182329^2 \\
12\ 0825276^2 + 9196000^2 &= 121\ 174724^2 & 12\ 0817671^2 + 9394000^2 &= 121\ 182329^2 \\
1232\ 0825276^2 + 92796000^2 &= 12321\ 174724^2 & 1232\ 0817671^2 + 94794000^2 &= 12321\ 182329^2 \\
123432\ 0825276^2 + 928796000^2 &= 1234321\ 174724^2 & 123432\ 0817671^2 + 948794000^2 &= 1234321\ 182329^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.418} \tag{5.427}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0824439^2 + 838000^2 &= 1\ 175561^2 & 0816816^2 + 856000^2 &= 1\ 183184^2 \\
12\ 0824439^2 + 9218000^2 &= 121\ 175561^2 & 12\ 0816816^2 + 9416000^2 &= 121\ 183184^2 \\
1232\ 0824439^2 + 93018000^2 &= 12321\ 175561^2 & 1232\ 0816816^2 + 95016000^2 &= 12321\ 183184^2 \\
123432\ 0824439^2 + 931018000^2 &= 1234321\ 175561^2 & 123432\ 0816816^2 + 951016000^2 &= 1234321\ 183184^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.419} \tag{5.428}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0823600^2 + 840000^2 &= 1\ 176400^2 & 0815959^2 + 858000^2 &= 1\ 184041^2 \\
12\ 0823600^2 + 9240000^2 &= 121\ 176400^2 & 12\ 0815959^2 + 9438000^2 &= 121\ 184041^2 \\
1232\ 0823600^2 + 93240000^2 &= 12321\ 176400^2 & 1232\ 0815959^2 + 95238000^2 &= 12321\ 184041^2 \\
123432\ 0823600^2 + 933240000^2 &= 1234321\ 176400^2 & 123432\ 0815959^2 + 953238000^2 &= 1234321\ 184041^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.420} \tag{5.429}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0822759^2 + 842000^2 &= 1\ 177241^2 & 0815100^2 + 860000^2 &= 1\ 184900^2 \\
12\ 0822759^2 + 9262000^2 &= 121\ 177241^2 & 12\ 0815100^2 + 9460000^2 &= 121\ 184900^2 \\
1232\ 0822759^2 + 93462000^2 &= 12321\ 177241^2 & 1232\ 0815100^2 + 95460000^2 &= 12321\ 184900^2 \\
123432\ 0822759^2 + 935462000^2 &= 1234321\ 177241^2 & 123432\ 0815100^2 + 955460000^2 &= 1234321\ 184900^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.421} \tag{5.430}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0821916^2 + 844000^2 &= 1\ 178084^2 & 0814239^2 + 862000^2 &= 1\ 185761^2 \\
12\ 0821916^2 + 9284000^2 &= 121\ 178084^2 & 12\ 0814239^2 + 9482000^2 &= 121\ 185761^2 \\
1232\ 0821916^2 + 93684000^2 &= 12321\ 178084^2 & 1232\ 0814239^2 + 95682000^2 &= 12321\ 185761^2 \\
123432\ 0821916^2 + 937684000^2 &= 1234321\ 178084^2 & 123432\ 0814239^2 + 957682000^2 &= 1234321\ 185761^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.422} \tag{5.431}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0821071^2 + 846000^2 &= 1\ 178929^2 & 0813376^2 + 864000^2 &= 1\ 186624^2 \\
12\ 0821071^2 + 9306000^2 &= 121\ 178929^2 & 12\ 0813376^2 + 9504000^2 &= 121\ 186624^2 \\
1232\ 0821071^2 + 93906000^2 &= 12321\ 178929^2 & 1232\ 0813376^2 + 95904000^2 &= 12321\ 186624^2 \\
123432\ 0821071^2 + 939906000^2 &= 1234321\ 178929^2 & 123432\ 0813376^2 + 959904000^2 &= 1234321\ 186624^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.423} \tag{5.432}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0820224^2 + 848000^2 &= 1\ 179776^2 & 0812511^2 + 866000^2 &= 1\ 187489^2 \\
12\ 0820224^2 + 9328000^2 &= 121\ 179776^2 & 12\ 0812511^2 + 9526000^2 &= 121\ 187489^2 \\
1232\ 0820224^2 + 94128000^2 &= 12321\ 179776^2 & 1232\ 0812511^2 + 96126000^2 &= 12321\ 187489^2 \\
123432\ 0820224^2 + 942128000^2 &= 1234321\ 179776^2 & 123432\ 0812511^2 + 962126000^2 &= 1234321\ 187489^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.424} \tag{5.433}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0819375^2 + 850000^2 &= 1\ 180625^2 & 0811644^2 + 868000^2 &= 1\ 188356^2 \\
12\ 0819375^2 + 9350000^2 &= 121\ 180625^2 & 12\ 0811644^2 + 9548000^2 &= 121\ 188356^2 \\
1232\ 0819375^2 + 94350000^2 &= 12321\ 180625^2 & 1232\ 0811644^2 + 96348000^2 &= 12321\ 188356^2 \\
123432\ 0819375^2 + 944350000^2 &= 1234321\ 180625^2 & 123432\ 0811644^2 + 964348000^2 &= 1234321\ 188356^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.425} \tag{5.434}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0818524^2 + 852000^2 &= 1\ 181476^2 & 0810775^2 + 870000^2 &= 1\ 189225^2 \\
12\ 0818524^2 + 9372000^2 &= 121\ 181476^2 & 12\ 0810775^2 + 9570000^2 &= 121\ 189225^2 \\
1232\ 0818524^2 + 94572000^2 &= 12321\ 181476^2 & 1232\ 0810775^2 + 96570000^2 &= 12321\ 189225^2 \\
123432\ 0818524^2 + 946572000^2 &= 1234321\ 181476^2 & 123432\ 0810775^2 + 966570000^2 &= 1234321\ 189225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.426} \tag{5.435}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0809904^2 + 872000^2 &= 1\ 190096^2 & 0801975^2 + 890000^2 &= 1\ 198025^2 \\
12\ 0809904^2 + 9592000^2 &= 121\ 190096^2 & 12\ 0801975^2 + 9790000^2 &= 121\ 198025^2 \\
1232\ 0809904^2 + 96792000^2 &= 12321\ 190096^2 & 1232\ 0801975^2 + 98790000^2 &= 12321\ 198025^2 \\
123432\ 0809904^2 + 968792000^2 &= 1234321\ 190096^2 & 123432\ 0801975^2 + 988790000^2 &= 1234321\ 198025^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.436} \tag{5.445}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0809031^2 + 874000^2 &= 1\ 190969^2 & 0801084^2 + 892000^2 &= 1\ 198916^2 \\
12\ 0809031^2 + 9614000^2 &= 121\ 190969^2 & 12\ 0801084^2 + 9812000^2 &= 121\ 198916^2 \\
1232\ 0809031^2 + 97014000^2 &= 12321\ 190969^2 & 1232\ 0801084^2 + 99012000^2 &= 12321\ 198916^2 \\
123432\ 0809031^2 + 971014000^2 &= 1234321\ 190969^2 & 123432\ 0801084^2 + 991012000^2 &= 1234321\ 198916^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.437} \tag{5.446}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0808156^2 + 876000^2 &= 1\ 191844^2 & 0800191^2 + 894000^2 &= 1\ 199809^2 \\
12\ 0808156^2 + 9636000^2 &= 121\ 191844^2 & 12\ 0800191^2 + 9834000^2 &= 121\ 199809^2 \\
1232\ 0808156^2 + 97236000^2 &= 12321\ 191844^2 & 1232\ 0800191^2 + 99234000^2 &= 12321\ 199809^2 \\
123432\ 0808156^2 + 973236000^2 &= 1234321\ 191844^2 & 123432\ 0800191^2 + 993234000^2 &= 1234321\ 199809^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.438} \tag{5.447}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0807279^2 + 878000^2 &= 1\ 192721^2 & 0799296^2 + 896000^2 &= 1\ 200704^2 \\
12\ 0807279^2 + 9658000^2 &= 121\ 192721^2 & 12\ 0799296^2 + 9856000^2 &= 121\ 200704^2 \\
1232\ 0807279^2 + 97458000^2 &= 12321\ 192721^2 & 1232\ 0799296^2 + 99456000^2 &= 12321\ 200704^2 \\
123432\ 0807279^2 + 975458000^2 &= 1234321\ 192721^2 & 123432\ 0799296^2 + 995456000^2 &= 1234321\ 200704^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.439} \tag{5.448}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0806400^2 + 880000^2 &= 1\ 193600^2 & 0798399^2 + 898000^2 &= 1\ 201601^2 \\
12\ 0806400^2 + 9680000^2 &= 121\ 193600^2 & 12\ 0798399^2 + 9878000^2 &= 121\ 201601^2 \\
1232\ 0806400^2 + 97680000^2 &= 12321\ 193600^2 & 1232\ 0798399^2 + 99678000^2 &= 12321\ 201601^2 \\
123432\ 0806400^2 + 977680000^2 &= 1234321\ 193600^2 & 123432\ 0798399^2 + 997678000^2 &= 1234321\ 201601^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.440} \tag{5.449}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0805519^2 + 882000^2 &= 1\ 194481^2 & 0797500^2 + 900000^2 &= 1\ 202500^2 \\
12\ 0805519^2 + 9702000^2 &= 121\ 194481^2 & 12\ 0797500^2 + 9900000^2 &= 121\ 202500^2 \\
1232\ 0805519^2 + 97902000^2 &= 12321\ 194481^2 & 1232\ 0797500^2 + 99900000^2 &= 12321\ 202500^2 \\
123432\ 0805519^2 + 979902000^2 &= 1234321\ 194481^2 & 123432\ 0797500^2 + 999900000^2 &= 1234321\ 202500^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.441} \tag{5.450}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0804636^2 + 884000^2 &= 1\ 195364^2 & 0796599^2 + 902000^2 &= 1\ 203401^2 \\
12\ 0804636^2 + 9724000^2 &= 121\ 195364^2 & 12\ 0796599^2 + 9922000^2 &= 121\ 203401^2 \\
1232\ 0804636^2 + 98124000^2 &= 12321\ 195364^2 & 1232\ 0796599^2 + 100122000^2 &= 12321\ 203401^2 \\
123432\ 0804636^2 + 982124000^2 &= 1234321\ 195364^2 & 123432\ 0796599^2 + 1002122000^2 &= 1234321\ 203401^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.442} \tag{5.451}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0803751^2 + 886000^2 &= 1\ 196249^2 & 0795696^2 + 904000^2 &= 1\ 204304^2 \\
12\ 0803751^2 + 9746000^2 &= 121\ 196249^2 & 12\ 0795696^2 + 9944000^2 &= 121\ 204304^2 \\
1232\ 0803751^2 + 98346000^2 &= 12321\ 196249^2 & 1232\ 0795696^2 + 100344000^2 &= 12321\ 204304^2 \\
123432\ 0803751^2 + 984346000^2 &= 1234321\ 196249^2 & 123432\ 0795696^2 + 1004344000^2 &= 1234321\ 204304^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.443} \tag{5.452}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0802864^2 + 888000^2 &= 1\ 197136^2 & 0794791^2 + 906000^2 &= 1\ 205209^2 \\
12\ 0802864^2 + 9768000^2 &= 121\ 197136^2 & 12\ 0794791^2 + 9966000^2 &= 121\ 205209^2 \\
1232\ 0802864^2 + 98568000^2 &= 12321\ 197136^2 & 1232\ 0794791^2 + 100566000^2 &= 12321\ 205209^2 \\
123432\ 0802864^2 + 986568000^2 &= 1234321\ 197136^2 & 123432\ 0794791^2 + 1006566000^2 &= 1234321\ 205209^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.444} \tag{5.453}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0793884^2 + 908000^2 &= 1\ 206116^2 & 0785631^2 + 926000^2 &= 1\ 214369^2 \\
12\ 0793884^2 + 9988000^2 &= 121\ 206116^2 & 12\ 0785631^2 + 10186000^2 &= 121\ 214369^2 \\
1232\ 0793884^2 + 100788000^2 &= 12321\ 206116^2 & 1232\ 0785631^2 + 102786000^2 &= 12321\ 214369^2 \\
123432\ 0793884^2 + 1008788000^2 &= 1234321\ 206116^2 & 123432\ 0785631^2 + 1028786000^2 &= 1234321\ 214369^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.454} \tag{5.463}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0792975^2 + 910000^2 &= 1\ 207025^2 & 0784704^2 + 928000^2 &= 1\ 215296^2 \\
12\ 0792975^2 + 10010000^2 &= 121\ 207025^2 & 12\ 0784704^2 + 10208000^2 &= 121\ 215296^2 \\
1232\ 0792975^2 + 101010000^2 &= 12321\ 207025^2 & 1232\ 0784704^2 + 103008000^2 &= 12321\ 215296^2 \\
123432\ 0792975^2 + 1011010000^2 &= 1234321\ 207025^2 & 123432\ 0784704^2 + 1031008000^2 &= 1234321\ 215296^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.455} \tag{5.464}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0792064^2 + 912000^2 &= 1\ 207936^2 & 0783775^2 + 930000^2 &= 1\ 216225^2 \\
12\ 0792064^2 + 10032000^2 &= 121\ 207936^2 & 12\ 0783775^2 + 10230000^2 &= 121\ 216225^2 \\
1232\ 0792064^2 + 101232000^2 &= 12321\ 207936^2 & 1232\ 0783775^2 + 103230000^2 &= 12321\ 216225^2 \\
123432\ 0792064^2 + 1013232000^2 &= 1234321\ 207936^2 & 123432\ 0783775^2 + 1033230000^2 &= 1234321\ 216225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.456} \tag{5.465}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0791151^2 + 914000^2 &= 1\ 208849^2 & 0782844^2 + 932000^2 &= 1\ 217156^2 \\
12\ 0791151^2 + 10054000^2 &= 121\ 208849^2 & 12\ 0782844^2 + 10252000^2 &= 121\ 217156^2 \\
1232\ 0791151^2 + 101454000^2 &= 12321\ 208849^2 & 1232\ 0782844^2 + 103452000^2 &= 12321\ 217156^2 \\
123432\ 0791151^2 + 1015454000^2 &= 1234321\ 208849^2 & 123432\ 0782844^2 + 1035452000^2 &= 1234321\ 217156^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.457} \tag{5.466}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0790236^2 + 916000^2 &= 1\ 209764^2 & 0781911^2 + 934000^2 &= 1\ 218089^2 \\
12\ 0790236^2 + 10076000^2 &= 121\ 209764^2 & 12\ 0781911^2 + 10274000^2 &= 121\ 218089^2 \\
1232\ 0790236^2 + 101676000^2 &= 12321\ 209764^2 & 1232\ 0781911^2 + 103674000^2 &= 12321\ 218089^2 \\
123432\ 0790236^2 + 1017676000^2 &= 1234321\ 209764^2 & 123432\ 0781911^2 + 1037674000^2 &= 1234321\ 218089^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.458} \tag{5.467}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0789319^2 + 918000^2 &= 1\ 210681^2 & 0780976^2 + 936000^2 &= 1\ 219024^2 \\
12\ 0789319^2 + 10098000^2 &= 121\ 210681^2 & 12\ 0780976^2 + 10296000^2 &= 121\ 219024^2 \\
1232\ 0789319^2 + 101898000^2 &= 12321\ 210681^2 & 1232\ 0780976^2 + 103896000^2 &= 12321\ 219024^2 \\
123432\ 0789319^2 + 1019898000^2 &= 1234321\ 210681^2 & 123432\ 0780976^2 + 1039896000^2 &= 1234321\ 219024^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.459} \tag{5.468}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0788400^2 + 920000^2 &= 1\ 211600^2 & 0780039^2 + 938000^2 &= 1\ 219961^2 \\
12\ 0788400^2 + 10120000^2 &= 121\ 211600^2 & 12\ 0780039^2 + 10318000^2 &= 121\ 219961^2 \\
1232\ 0788400^2 + 102120000^2 &= 12321\ 211600^2 & 1232\ 0780039^2 + 104118000^2 &= 12321\ 219961^2 \\
123432\ 0788400^2 + 1022120000^2 &= 1234321\ 211600^2 & 123432\ 0780039^2 + 1042118000^2 &= 1234321\ 219961^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.460} \tag{5.469}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0787479^2 + 922000^2 &= 1\ 212521^2 & 0779100^2 + 940000^2 &= 1\ 220900^2 \\
12\ 0787479^2 + 10142000^2 &= 121\ 212521^2 & 12\ 0779100^2 + 10340000^2 &= 121\ 220900^2 \\
1232\ 0787479^2 + 102342000^2 &= 12321\ 212521^2 & 1232\ 0779100^2 + 104340000^2 &= 12321\ 220900^2 \\
123432\ 0787479^2 + 1024342000^2 &= 1234321\ 212521^2 & 123432\ 0779100^2 + 1044340000^2 &= 1234321\ 220900^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.461} \tag{5.470}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0786556^2 + 924000^2 &= 1\ 213444^2 & 0778159^2 + 942000^2 &= 1\ 221841^2 \\
12\ 0786556^2 + 10164000^2 &= 121\ 213444^2 & 12\ 0778159^2 + 10362000^2 &= 121\ 221841^2 \\
1232\ 0786556^2 + 102564000^2 &= 12321\ 213444^2 & 1232\ 0778159^2 + 104562000^2 &= 12321\ 221841^2 \\
123432\ 0786556^2 + 1026564000^2 &= 1234321\ 213444^2 & 123432\ 0778159^2 + 1046562000^2 &= 1234321\ 221841^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.462} \tag{5.471}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0777216^2 + 944000^2 &= 1\ 222784^2 & 0768639^2 + 962000^2 &= 1\ 231361^2 \\
12\ 0777216^2 + 10384000^2 &= 121\ 222784^2 & 12\ 0768639^2 + 10582000^2 &= 121\ 231361^2 \\
1232\ 0777216^2 + 104784000^2 &= 12321\ 222784^2 & 1232\ 0768639^2 + 106782000^2 &= 12321\ 231361^2 \\
123432\ 0777216^2 + 1048784000^2 &= 1234321\ 222784^2 & 123432\ 0768639^2 + 1068782000^2 &= 1234321\ 231361^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.472} \tag{5.481}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0776271^2 + 946000^2 &= 1\ 223729^2 & 0767676^2 + 964000^2 &= 1\ 232324^2 \\
12\ 0776271^2 + 10406000^2 &= 121\ 223729^2 & 12\ 0767676^2 + 10604000^2 &= 121\ 232324^2 \\
1232\ 0776271^2 + 105006000^2 &= 12321\ 223729^2 & 1232\ 0767676^2 + 107004000^2 &= 12321\ 232324^2 \\
123432\ 0776271^2 + 1051006000^2 &= 1234321\ 223729^2 & 123432\ 0767676^2 + 1071004000^2 &= 1234321\ 232324^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.473} \tag{5.482}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0775324^2 + 948000^2 &= 1\ 224676^2 & 0766711^2 + 966000^2 &= 1\ 233289^2 \\
12\ 0775324^2 + 10428000^2 &= 121\ 224676^2 & 12\ 0766711^2 + 10626000^2 &= 121\ 233289^2 \\
1232\ 0775324^2 + 105228000^2 &= 12321\ 224676^2 & 1232\ 0766711^2 + 107226000^2 &= 12321\ 233289^2 \\
123432\ 0775324^2 + 1053228000^2 &= 1234321\ 224676^2 & 123432\ 0766711^2 + 1073226000^2 &= 1234321\ 233289^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.474} \tag{5.483}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0774375^2 + 950000^2 &= 1\ 225625^2 & 0765744^2 + 968000^2 &= 1\ 234256^2 \\
12\ 0774375^2 + 10450000^2 &= 121\ 225625^2 & 12\ 0765744^2 + 10648000^2 &= 121\ 234256^2 \\
1232\ 0774375^2 + 105450000^2 &= 12321\ 225625^2 & 1232\ 0765744^2 + 107448000^2 &= 12321\ 234256^2 \\
123432\ 0774375^2 + 1055450000^2 &= 1234321\ 225625^2 & 123432\ 0765744^2 + 1075448000^2 &= 1234321\ 234256^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.475} \tag{5.484}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0773424^2 + 952000^2 &= 1\ 226576^2 & 0764775^2 + 970000^2 &= 1\ 235225^2 \\
12\ 0773424^2 + 10472000^2 &= 121\ 226576^2 & 12\ 0764775^2 + 10670000^2 &= 121\ 235225^2 \\
1232\ 0773424^2 + 105672000^2 &= 12321\ 226576^2 & 1232\ 0764775^2 + 107670000^2 &= 12321\ 235225^2 \\
123432\ 0773424^2 + 1057672000^2 &= 1234321\ 226576^2 & 123432\ 0764775^2 + 1077670000^2 &= 1234321\ 235225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.476} \tag{5.485}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0772471^2 + 954000^2 &= 1\ 227529^2 & 0763804^2 + 972000^2 &= 1\ 236196^2 \\
12\ 0772471^2 + 10494000^2 &= 121\ 227529^2 & 12\ 0763804^2 + 10692000^2 &= 121\ 236196^2 \\
1232\ 0772471^2 + 105894000^2 &= 12321\ 227529^2 & 1232\ 0763804^2 + 107892000^2 &= 12321\ 236196^2 \\
123432\ 0772471^2 + 1059894000^2 &= 1234321\ 227529^2 & 123432\ 0763804^2 + 1079892000^2 &= 1234321\ 236196^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.477} \tag{5.486}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0771516^2 + 956000^2 &= 1\ 228484^2 & 0762831^2 + 974000^2 &= 1\ 237169^2 \\
12\ 0771516^2 + 10516000^2 &= 121\ 228484^2 & 12\ 0762831^2 + 10714000^2 &= 121\ 237169^2 \\
1232\ 0771516^2 + 106116000^2 &= 12321\ 228484^2 & 1232\ 0762831^2 + 108114000^2 &= 12321\ 237169^2 \\
123432\ 0771516^2 + 1062116000^2 &= 1234321\ 228484^2 & 123432\ 0762831^2 + 1082114000^2 &= 1234321\ 237169^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.478} \tag{5.487}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0770559^2 + 958000^2 &= 1\ 229441^2 & 0761856^2 + 976000^2 &= 1\ 238144^2 \\
12\ 0770559^2 + 10538000^2 &= 121\ 229441^2 & 12\ 0761856^2 + 10736000^2 &= 121\ 238144^2 \\
1232\ 0770559^2 + 106338000^2 &= 12321\ 229441^2 & 1232\ 0761856^2 + 108336000^2 &= 12321\ 238144^2 \\
123432\ 0770559^2 + 1064338000^2 &= 1234321\ 229441^2 & 123432\ 0761856^2 + 1084336000^2 &= 1234321\ 238144^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.479} \tag{5.488}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0769600^2 + 960000^2 &= 1\ 230400^2 & 0760879^2 + 978000^2 &= 1\ 239121^2 \\
12\ 0769600^2 + 10560000^2 &= 121\ 230400^2 & 12\ 0760879^2 + 10758000^2 &= 121\ 239121^2 \\
1232\ 0769600^2 + 106560000^2 &= 12321\ 230400^2 & 1232\ 0760879^2 + 108558000^2 &= 12321\ 239121^2 \\
123432\ 0769600^2 + 1066560000^2 &= 1234321\ 230400^2 & 123432\ 0760879^2 + 1086558000^2 &= 1234321\ 239121^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.480} \tag{5.489}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0759900^2 + 980000^2 &= 1\,240100^2 & 0754975^2 + 990000^2 &= 1\,245025^2 \\
12\,0759900^2 + 10780000^2 &= 121\,240100^2 & 12\,0754975^2 + 10890000^2 &= 121\,245025^2 \\
1232\,0759900^2 + 108780000^2 &= 12321\,240100^2 & 1232\,0754975^2 + 109890000^2 &= 12321\,245025^2 \\
123432\,0759900^2 + 1088780000^2 &= 1234321\,240100^2 & 123432\,0754975^2 + 1099890000^2 &= 1234321\,245025^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.490} \tag{5.495}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0758919^2 + 982000^2 &= 1\,241081^2 & 0753984^2 + 992000^2 &= 1\,246016^2 \\
12\,0758919^2 + 10802000^2 &= 121\,241081^2 & 12\,0753984^2 + 10912000^2 &= 121\,246016^2 \\
1232\,0758919^2 + 109002000^2 &= 12321\,241081^2 & 1232\,0753984^2 + 110112000^2 &= 12321\,246016^2 \\
123432\,0758919^2 + 1091002000^2 &= 1234321\,241081^2 & 123432\,0753984^2 + 1102112000^2 &= 1234321\,246016^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.491} \tag{5.496}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0757936^2 + 984000^2 &= 1\,242064^2 & 0752991^2 + 994000^2 &= 1\,247009^2 \\
12\,0757936^2 + 10824000^2 &= 121\,242064^2 & 12\,0752991^2 + 10934000^2 &= 121\,247009^2 \\
1232\,0757936^2 + 109224000^2 &= 12321\,242064^2 & 1232\,0752991^2 + 110334000^2 &= 12321\,247009^2 \\
123432\,0757936^2 + 1093224000^2 &= 1234321\,242064^2 & 123432\,0752991^2 + 1104334000^2 &= 1234321\,247009^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.492} \tag{5.497}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0756951^2 + 986000^2 &= 1\,243049^2 & 0751996^2 + 996000^2 &= 1\,248004^2 \\
12\,0756951^2 + 10846000^2 &= 121\,243049^2 & 12\,0751996^2 + 10956000^2 &= 121\,248004^2 \\
1232\,0756951^2 + 109446000^2 &= 12321\,243049^2 & 1232\,0751996^2 + 110556000^2 &= 12321\,248004^2 \\
123432\,0756951^2 + 1095446000^2 &= 1234321\,243049^2 & 123432\,0751996^2 + 1106556000^2 &= 1234321\,248004^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.493} \tag{5.498}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0755964^2 + 988000^2 &= 1\,244036^2 & 0750999^2 + 998000^2 &= 1\,249001^2 \\
12\,0755964^2 + 10868000^2 &= 121\,244036^2 & 12\,0750999^2 + 10978000^2 &= 121\,249001^2 \\
1232\,0755964^2 + 109668000^2 &= 12321\,244036^2 & 1232\,0750999^2 + 110778000^2 &= 12321\,249001^2 \\
123432\,0755964^2 + 1097668000^2 &= 1234321\,244036^2 & 123432\,0750999^2 + 1108778000^2 &= 1234321\,249001^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.494} \tag{5.499}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0750000^2 + 1000000^2 &= 1\,250000^2 & 0745984^2 + 1008000^2 &= 1\,254016^2 \\
12\,0750000^2 + 11000000^2 &= 121\,250000^2 & 12\,0745984^2 + 11088000^2 &= 121\,254016^2 \\
1232\,0750000^2 + 111000000^2 &= 12321\,250000^2 & 1232\,0745984^2 + 111888000^2 &= 12321\,254016^2 \\
123432\,0750000^2 + 1111000000^2 &= 1234321\,250000^2 & 123432\,0745984^2 + 1119888000^2 &= 1234321\,254016^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.500} \tag{5.504}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0748999^2 + 1002000^2 &= 1\,251001^2 & 0744975^2 + 1010000^2 &= 1\,255025^2 \\
12\,0748999^2 + 11022000^2 &= 121\,251001^2 & 12\,0744975^2 + 11110000^2 &= 121\,255025^2 \\
1232\,0748999^2 + 111222000^2 &= 12321\,251001^2 & 1232\,0744975^2 + 112110000^2 &= 12321\,255025^2 \\
123432\,0748999^2 + 1113222000^2 &= 1234321\,251001^2 & 123432\,0744975^2 + 1122110000^2 &= 1234321\,255025^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.501} \tag{5.505}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0747996^2 + 1004000^2 &= 1\,252004^2 & 0743964^2 + 1012000^2 &= 1\,256036^2 \\
12\,0747996^2 + 11044000^2 &= 121\,252004^2 & 12\,0743964^2 + 11132000^2 &= 121\,256036^2 \\
1232\,0747996^2 + 111444000^2 &= 12321\,252004^2 & 1232\,0743964^2 + 112332000^2 &= 12321\,256036^2 \\
123432\,0747996^2 + 1115444000^2 &= 1234321\,252004^2 & 123432\,0743964^2 + 1124332000^2 &= 1234321\,256036^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.502} \tag{5.506}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0746991^2 + 1006000^2 &= 1\,253009^2 & 0742951^2 + 1014000^2 &= 1\,257049^2 \\
12\,0746991^2 + 11066000^2 &= 121\,253009^2 & 12\,0742951^2 + 11154000^2 &= 121\,257049^2 \\
1232\,0746991^2 + 111666000^2 &= 12321\,253009^2 & 1232\,0742951^2 + 112554000^2 &= 12321\,257049^2 \\
123432\,0746991^2 + 1117666000^2 &= 1234321\,253009^2 & 123432\,0742951^2 + 1126554000^2 &= 1234321\,257049^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.503} \tag{5.507}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0741936^2 + 1016000^2 &= 1\ 258064^2 & 0732711^2 + 1034000^2 &= 1\ 267289^2 \\
12\ 0741936^2 + 11176000^2 &= 121\ 258064^2 & 12\ 0732711^2 + 11374000^2 &= 121\ 267289^2 \\
1232\ 0741936^2 + 112776000^2 &= 12321\ 258064^2 & 1232\ 0732711^2 + 114774000^2 &= 12321\ 267289^2 \\
123432\ 0741936^2 + 1128776000^2 &= 1234321\ 258064^2 & 123432\ 0732711^2 + 1148774000^2 &= 1234321\ 267289^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.508} \tag{5.517}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0740919^2 + 1018000^2 &= 1\ 259081^2 & 0731676^2 + 1036000^2 &= 1\ 268324^2 \\
12\ 0740919^2 + 11198000^2 &= 121\ 259081^2 & 12\ 0731676^2 + 11396000^2 &= 121\ 268324^2 \\
1232\ 0740919^2 + 112998000^2 &= 12321\ 259081^2 & 1232\ 0731676^2 + 114996000^2 &= 12321\ 268324^2 \\
123432\ 0740919^2 + 1130998000^2 &= 1234321\ 259081^2 & 123432\ 0731676^2 + 1150996000^2 &= 1234321\ 268324^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.509} \tag{5.518}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0739900^2 + 1020000^2 &= 1\ 260100^2 & 0730639^2 + 1038000^2 &= 1\ 269361^2 \\
12\ 0739900^2 + 11220000^2 &= 121\ 260100^2 & 12\ 0730639^2 + 11418000^2 &= 121\ 269361^2 \\
1232\ 0739900^2 + 113220000^2 &= 12321\ 260100^2 & 1232\ 0730639^2 + 115218000^2 &= 12321\ 269361^2 \\
123432\ 0739900^2 + 1133220000^2 &= 1234321\ 260100^2 & 123432\ 0730639^2 + 1153218000^2 &= 1234321\ 269361^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.510} \tag{5.519}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0738879^2 + 1022000^2 &= 1\ 261121^2 & 0729600^2 + 1040000^2 &= 1\ 270400^2 \\
12\ 0738879^2 + 11242000^2 &= 121\ 261121^2 & 12\ 0729600^2 + 11440000^2 &= 121\ 270400^2 \\
1232\ 0738879^2 + 113442000^2 &= 12321\ 261121^2 & 1232\ 0729600^2 + 115440000^2 &= 12321\ 270400^2 \\
123432\ 0738879^2 + 1135442000^2 &= 1234321\ 261121^2 & 123432\ 0729600^2 + 1155440000^2 &= 1234321\ 270400^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.511} \tag{5.520}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0737856^2 + 1024000^2 &= 1\ 262144^2 & 0728559^2 + 1042000^2 &= 1\ 271441^2 \\
12\ 0737856^2 + 11264000^2 &= 121\ 262144^2 & 12\ 0728559^2 + 11462000^2 &= 121\ 271441^2 \\
1232\ 0737856^2 + 113664000^2 &= 12321\ 262144^2 & 1232\ 0728559^2 + 115662000^2 &= 12321\ 271441^2 \\
123432\ 0737856^2 + 1137664000^2 &= 1234321\ 262144^2 & 123432\ 0728559^2 + 1157662000^2 &= 1234321\ 271441^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.512} \tag{5.521}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0736831^2 + 1026000^2 &= 1\ 263169^2 & 0727516^2 + 1044000^2 &= 1\ 272484^2 \\
12\ 0736831^2 + 11286000^2 &= 121\ 263169^2 & 12\ 0727516^2 + 11484000^2 &= 121\ 272484^2 \\
1232\ 0736831^2 + 113886000^2 &= 12321\ 263169^2 & 1232\ 0727516^2 + 115884000^2 &= 12321\ 272484^2 \\
123432\ 0736831^2 + 1139886000^2 &= 1234321\ 263169^2 & 123432\ 0727516^2 + 1159884000^2 &= 1234321\ 272484^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.513} \tag{5.522}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0735804^2 + 1028000^2 &= 1\ 264196^2 & 0726471^2 + 1046000^2 &= 1\ 273529^2 \\
12\ 0735804^2 + 11308000^2 &= 121\ 264196^2 & 12\ 0726471^2 + 11506000^2 &= 121\ 273529^2 \\
1232\ 0735804^2 + 114108000^2 &= 12321\ 264196^2 & 1232\ 0726471^2 + 116106000^2 &= 12321\ 273529^2 \\
123432\ 0735804^2 + 1142108000^2 &= 1234321\ 264196^2 & 123432\ 0726471^2 + 1162106000^2 &= 1234321\ 273529^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.514} \tag{5.523}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0734775^2 + 1030000^2 &= 1\ 265225^2 & 0725424^2 + 1048000^2 &= 1\ 274576^2 \\
12\ 0734775^2 + 11330000^2 &= 121\ 265225^2 & 12\ 0725424^2 + 11528000^2 &= 121\ 274576^2 \\
1232\ 0734775^2 + 114330000^2 &= 12321\ 265225^2 & 1232\ 0725424^2 + 116328000^2 &= 12321\ 274576^2 \\
123432\ 0734775^2 + 1144330000^2 &= 1234321\ 265225^2 & 123432\ 0725424^2 + 1164328000^2 &= 1234321\ 274576^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.515} \tag{5.524}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0733744^2 + 1032000^2 &= 1\ 266256^2 & 0724375^2 + 1050000^2 &= 1\ 275625^2 \\
12\ 0733744^2 + 11352000^2 &= 121\ 266256^2 & 12\ 0724375^2 + 11550000^2 &= 121\ 275625^2 \\
1232\ 0733744^2 + 114552000^2 &= 12321\ 266256^2 & 1232\ 0724375^2 + 116550000^2 &= 12321\ 275625^2 \\
123432\ 0733744^2 + 1146552000^2 &= 1234321\ 266256^2 & 123432\ 0724375^2 + 1166550000^2 &= 1234321\ 275625^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.516} \tag{5.525}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0723324^2 + 1052000^2 &= 1\,276676^2 & 0713775^2 + 1070000^2 &= 1\,286225^2 \\
12\,0723324^2 + 11572000^2 &= 121\,276676^2 & 12\,0713775^2 + 11770000^2 &= 121\,286225^2 \\
1232\,0723324^2 + 116772000^2 &= 12321\,276676^2 & 1232\,0713775^2 + 118770000^2 &= 12321\,286225^2 \\
123432\,0723324^2 + 1168772000^2 &= 1234321\,276676^2 & 123432\,0713775^2 + 1188770000^2 &= 1234321\,286225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.526} \tag{5.535}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0722271^2 + 1054000^2 &= 1\,277729^2 & 0712704^2 + 1072000^2 &= 1\,287296^2 \\
12\,0722271^2 + 11594000^2 &= 121\,277729^2 & 12\,0712704^2 + 11792000^2 &= 121\,287296^2 \\
1232\,0722271^2 + 116994000^2 &= 12321\,277729^2 & 1232\,0712704^2 + 118992000^2 &= 12321\,287296^2 \\
123432\,0722271^2 + 1170994000^2 &= 1234321\,277729^2 & 123432\,0712704^2 + 1190992000^2 &= 1234321\,287296^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.527} \tag{5.536}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0721216^2 + 1056000^2 &= 1\,278784^2 & 0711631^2 + 1074000^2 &= 1\,288369^2 \\
12\,0721216^2 + 11616000^2 &= 121\,278784^2 & 12\,0711631^2 + 11814000^2 &= 121\,288369^2 \\
1232\,0721216^2 + 117216000^2 &= 12321\,278784^2 & 1232\,0711631^2 + 119214000^2 &= 12321\,288369^2 \\
123432\,0721216^2 + 1173216000^2 &= 1234321\,278784^2 & 123432\,0711631^2 + 1193214000^2 &= 1234321\,288369^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.528} \tag{5.537}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0720159^2 + 1058000^2 &= 1\,279841^2 & 0710556^2 + 1076000^2 &= 1\,289444^2 \\
12\,0720159^2 + 11638000^2 &= 121\,279841^2 & 12\,0710556^2 + 11836000^2 &= 121\,289444^2 \\
1232\,0720159^2 + 117438000^2 &= 12321\,279841^2 & 1232\,0710556^2 + 119436000^2 &= 12321\,289444^2 \\
123432\,0720159^2 + 1175438000^2 &= 1234321\,279841^2 & 123432\,0710556^2 + 1195436000^2 &= 1234321\,289444^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.529} \tag{5.538}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0719100^2 + 1060000^2 &= 1\,280900^2 & 0709479^2 + 1078000^2 &= 1\,290521^2 \\
12\,0719100^2 + 11660000^2 &= 121\,280900^2 & 12\,0709479^2 + 11858000^2 &= 121\,290521^2 \\
1232\,0719100^2 + 117660000^2 &= 12321\,280900^2 & 1232\,0709479^2 + 119658000^2 &= 12321\,290521^2 \\
123432\,0719100^2 + 1177660000^2 &= 1234321\,280900^2 & 123432\,0709479^2 + 1197658000^2 &= 1234321\,290521^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.530} \tag{5.539}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0718039^2 + 1062000^2 &= 1\,281961^2 & 0708400^2 + 1080000^2 &= 1\,291600^2 \\
12\,0718039^2 + 11682000^2 &= 121\,281961^2 & 12\,0708400^2 + 11880000^2 &= 121\,291600^2 \\
1232\,0718039^2 + 117882000^2 &= 12321\,281961^2 & 1232\,0708400^2 + 119880000^2 &= 12321\,291600^2 \\
123432\,0718039^2 + 1179882000^2 &= 1234321\,281961^2 & 123432\,0708400^2 + 1199880000^2 &= 1234321\,291600^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.531} \tag{5.540}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0716976^2 + 1064000^2 &= 1\,283024^2 & 0707319^2 + 1082000^2 &= 1\,292681^2 \\
12\,0716976^2 + 11704000^2 &= 121\,283024^2 & 12\,0707319^2 + 11902000^2 &= 121\,292681^2 \\
1232\,0716976^2 + 118104000^2 &= 12321\,283024^2 & 1232\,0707319^2 + 120102000^2 &= 12321\,292681^2 \\
123432\,0716976^2 + 1182104000^2 &= 1234321\,283024^2 & 123432\,0707319^2 + 1202102000^2 &= 1234321\,292681^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.532} \tag{5.541}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0715911^2 + 1066000^2 &= 1\,284089^2 & 0706236^2 + 1084000^2 &= 1\,293764^2 \\
12\,0715911^2 + 11726000^2 &= 121\,284089^2 & 12\,0706236^2 + 11924000^2 &= 121\,293764^2 \\
1232\,0715911^2 + 118326000^2 &= 12321\,284089^2 & 1232\,0706236^2 + 120324000^2 &= 12321\,293764^2 \\
123432\,0715911^2 + 1184326000^2 &= 1234321\,284089^2 & 123432\,0706236^2 + 1204324000^2 &= 1234321\,293764^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.533} \tag{5.542}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0714844^2 + 1068000^2 &= 1\,285156^2 & 0705151^2 + 1086000^2 &= 1\,294849^2 \\
12\,0714844^2 + 11748000^2 &= 121\,285156^2 & 12\,0705151^2 + 11946000^2 &= 121\,294849^2 \\
1232\,0714844^2 + 118548000^2 &= 12321\,285156^2 & 1232\,0705151^2 + 120546000^2 &= 12321\,294849^2 \\
123432\,0714844^2 + 1186548000^2 &= 1234321\,285156^2 & 123432\,0705151^2 + 1206546000^2 &= 1234321\,294849^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.534} \tag{5.543}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0704064^2 + 1088000^2 &= 1\ 295936^2 & 0694191^2 + 1106000^2 &= 1\ 305809^2 \\
12\ 0704064^2 + 11968000^2 &= 121\ 295936^2 & 12\ 0694191^2 + 12166000^2 &= 121\ 305809^2 \\
1232\ 0704064^2 + 120768000^2 &= 12321\ 295936^2 & 1232\ 0694191^2 + 122766000^2 &= 12321\ 305809^2 \\
123432\ 0704064^2 + 1208768000^2 &= 1234321\ 295936^2 & 123432\ 0694191^2 + 1228766000^2 &= 1234321\ 305809^2 \quad (5.553)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.544)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0702975^2 + 1090000^2 &= 1\ 297025^2 & 0693084^2 + 1108000^2 &= 1\ 306916^2 \\
12\ 0702975^2 + 11990000^2 &= 121\ 297025^2 & 12\ 0693084^2 + 12188000^2 &= 121\ 306916^2 \\
1232\ 0702975^2 + 120990000^2 &= 12321\ 297025^2 & 1232\ 0693084^2 + 122988000^2 &= 12321\ 306916^2 \\
123432\ 0702975^2 + 1210990000^2 &= 1234321\ 297025^2 & 123432\ 0693084^2 + 1230988000^2 &= 1234321\ 306916^2 \quad (5.554)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.545)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0701884^2 + 1092000^2 &= 1\ 298116^2 & 0691975^2 + 1110000^2 &= 1\ 308025^2 \\
12\ 0701884^2 + 12012000^2 &= 121\ 298116^2 & 12\ 0691975^2 + 12210000^2 &= 121\ 308025^2 \\
1232\ 0701884^2 + 121212000^2 &= 12321\ 298116^2 & 1232\ 0691975^2 + 123210000^2 &= 12321\ 308025^2 \\
123432\ 0701884^2 + 1213212000^2 &= 1234321\ 298116^2 & 123432\ 0691975^2 + 1233210000^2 &= 1234321\ 308025^2 \quad (5.555)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.546)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0700791^2 + 1094000^2 &= 1\ 299209^2 & 0690864^2 + 1112000^2 &= 1\ 309136^2 \\
12\ 0700791^2 + 12034000^2 &= 121\ 299209^2 & 12\ 0690864^2 + 12232000^2 &= 121\ 309136^2 \\
1232\ 0700791^2 + 121434000^2 &= 12321\ 299209^2 & 1232\ 0690864^2 + 123432000^2 &= 12321\ 309136^2 \\
123432\ 0700791^2 + 1215434000^2 &= 1234321\ 299209^2 & 123432\ 0690864^2 + 1235432000^2 &= 1234321\ 309136^2 \quad (5.556)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.547)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0699696^2 + 1096000^2 &= 1\ 300304^2 & 0689751^2 + 1114000^2 &= 1\ 310249^2 \\
12\ 0699696^2 + 12056000^2 &= 121\ 300304^2 & 12\ 0689751^2 + 12254000^2 &= 121\ 310249^2 \\
1232\ 0699696^2 + 121656000^2 &= 12321\ 300304^2 & 1232\ 0689751^2 + 123654000^2 &= 12321\ 310249^2 \\
123432\ 0699696^2 + 1217656000^2 &= 1234321\ 300304^2 & 123432\ 0689751^2 + 1237654000^2 &= 1234321\ 310249^2 \quad (5.557)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.548)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0698599^2 + 1098000^2 &= 1\ 301401^2 & 0688636^2 + 1116000^2 &= 1\ 311364^2 \\
12\ 0698599^2 + 12078000^2 &= 121\ 301401^2 & 12\ 0688636^2 + 12276000^2 &= 121\ 311364^2 \\
1232\ 0698599^2 + 121878000^2 &= 12321\ 301401^2 & 1232\ 0688636^2 + 123876000^2 &= 12321\ 311364^2 \\
123432\ 0698599^2 + 1219878000^2 &= 1234321\ 301401^2 & 123432\ 0688636^2 + 1239876000^2 &= 1234321\ 311364^2 \quad (5.558)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.549)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0697500^2 + 1100000^2 &= 1\ 302500^2 & 0687519^2 + 1118000^2 &= 1\ 312481^2 \\
12\ 0697500^2 + 12100000^2 &= 121\ 302500^2 & 12\ 0687519^2 + 12298000^2 &= 121\ 312481^2 \\
1232\ 0697500^2 + 122100000^2 &= 12321\ 302500^2 & 1232\ 0687519^2 + 124098000^2 &= 12321\ 312481^2 \\
123432\ 0697500^2 + 1222100000^2 &= 1234321\ 302500^2 & 123432\ 0687519^2 + 1242098000^2 &= 1234321\ 312481^2 \quad (5.559)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.550)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0696399^2 + 1102000^2 &= 1\ 303601^2 & 0686400^2 + 1120000^2 &= 1\ 313600^2 \\
12\ 0696399^2 + 12122000^2 &= 121\ 303601^2 & 12\ 0686400^2 + 12320000^2 &= 121\ 313600^2 \\
1232\ 0696399^2 + 122322000^2 &= 12321\ 303601^2 & 1232\ 0686400^2 + 124320000^2 &= 12321\ 313600^2 \\
123432\ 0696399^2 + 1224322000^2 &= 1234321\ 303601^2 & 123432\ 0686400^2 + 1244320000^2 &= 1234321\ 313600^2 \quad (5.560)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.551)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0695296^2 + 1104000^2 &= 1\ 304704^2 & 0685279^2 + 1122000^2 &= 1\ 314721^2 \\
12\ 0695296^2 + 12144000^2 &= 121\ 304704^2 & 12\ 0685279^2 + 12342000^2 &= 121\ 314721^2 \\
1232\ 0695296^2 + 122544000^2 &= 12321\ 304704^2 & 1232\ 0685279^2 + 124542000^2 &= 12321\ 314721^2 \\
123432\ 0695296^2 + 1226544000^2 &= 1234321\ 304704^2 & 123432\ 0685279^2 + 1246542000^2 &= 1234321\ 314721^2 \quad (5.561)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.552)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0684156^2 + 1124000^2 &= 1\ 315844^2 & 0673959^2 + 1142000^2 &= 1\ 326041^2 \\
12\ 0684156^2 + 12364000^2 &= 121\ 315844^2 & 12\ 0673959^2 + 12562000^2 &= 121\ 326041^2 \\
1232\ 0684156^2 + 124764000^2 &= 12321\ 315844^2 & 1232\ 0673959^2 + 126762000^2 &= 12321\ 326041^2 \\
123432\ 0684156^2 + 1248764000^2 &= 1234321\ 315844^2 & 123432\ 0673959^2 + 1268762000^2 &= 1234321\ 326041^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.562} \tag{5.571}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0683031^2 + 1126000^2 &= 1\ 316969^2 & 0672816^2 + 1144000^2 &= 1\ 327184^2 \\
12\ 0683031^2 + 12386000^2 &= 121\ 316969^2 & 12\ 0672816^2 + 12584000^2 &= 121\ 327184^2 \\
1232\ 0683031^2 + 124986000^2 &= 12321\ 316969^2 & 1232\ 0672816^2 + 126984000^2 &= 12321\ 327184^2 \\
123432\ 0683031^2 + 1250986000^2 &= 1234321\ 316969^2 & 123432\ 0672816^2 + 1270984000^2 &= 1234321\ 327184^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.563} \tag{5.572}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0681904^2 + 1128000^2 &= 1\ 318096^2 & 0671671^2 + 1146000^2 &= 1\ 328329^2 \\
12\ 0681904^2 + 12408000^2 &= 121\ 318096^2 & 12\ 0671671^2 + 12606000^2 &= 121\ 328329^2 \\
1232\ 0681904^2 + 125208000^2 &= 12321\ 318096^2 & 1232\ 0671671^2 + 127206000^2 &= 12321\ 328329^2 \\
123432\ 0681904^2 + 1253208000^2 &= 1234321\ 318096^2 & 123432\ 0671671^2 + 1273206000^2 &= 1234321\ 328329^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.564} \tag{5.573}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0680775^2 + 1130000^2 &= 1\ 319225^2 & 0670524^2 + 1148000^2 &= 1\ 329476^2 \\
12\ 0680775^2 + 12430000^2 &= 121\ 319225^2 & 12\ 0670524^2 + 12628000^2 &= 121\ 329476^2 \\
1232\ 0680775^2 + 125430000^2 &= 12321\ 319225^2 & 1232\ 0670524^2 + 127428000^2 &= 12321\ 329476^2 \\
123432\ 0680775^2 + 1255430000^2 &= 1234321\ 319225^2 & 123432\ 0670524^2 + 1275428000^2 &= 1234321\ 329476^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.565} \tag{5.574}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0679644^2 + 1132000^2 &= 1\ 320356^2 & 0669375^2 + 1150000^2 &= 1\ 330625^2 \\
12\ 0679644^2 + 12452000^2 &= 121\ 320356^2 & 12\ 0669375^2 + 12650000^2 &= 121\ 330625^2 \\
1232\ 0679644^2 + 125652000^2 &= 12321\ 320356^2 & 1232\ 0669375^2 + 127650000^2 &= 12321\ 330625^2 \\
123432\ 0679644^2 + 1257652000^2 &= 1234321\ 320356^2 & 123432\ 0669375^2 + 1277650000^2 &= 1234321\ 330625^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.566} \tag{5.575}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0678511^2 + 1134000^2 &= 1\ 321489^2 & 0668224^2 + 1152000^2 &= 1\ 331776^2 \\
12\ 0678511^2 + 12474000^2 &= 121\ 321489^2 & 12\ 0668224^2 + 12672000^2 &= 121\ 331776^2 \\
1232\ 0678511^2 + 125874000^2 &= 12321\ 321489^2 & 1232\ 0668224^2 + 127872000^2 &= 12321\ 331776^2 \\
123432\ 0678511^2 + 1259874000^2 &= 1234321\ 321489^2 & 123432\ 0668224^2 + 1279872000^2 &= 1234321\ 331776^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.567} \tag{5.576}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0677376^2 + 1136000^2 &= 1\ 322624^2 & 0667071^2 + 1154000^2 &= 1\ 332929^2 \\
12\ 0677376^2 + 12496000^2 &= 121\ 322624^2 & 12\ 0667071^2 + 12694000^2 &= 121\ 332929^2 \\
1232\ 0677376^2 + 126096000^2 &= 12321\ 322624^2 & 1232\ 0667071^2 + 128094000^2 &= 12321\ 332929^2 \\
123432\ 0677376^2 + 1262096000^2 &= 1234321\ 322624^2 & 123432\ 0667071^2 + 1282094000^2 &= 1234321\ 332929^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.568} \tag{5.577}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0676239^2 + 1138000^2 &= 1\ 323761^2 & 0665916^2 + 1156000^2 &= 1\ 334084^2 \\
12\ 0676239^2 + 12518000^2 &= 121\ 323761^2 & 12\ 0665916^2 + 12716000^2 &= 121\ 334084^2 \\
1232\ 0676239^2 + 126318000^2 &= 12321\ 323761^2 & 1232\ 0665916^2 + 128316000^2 &= 12321\ 334084^2 \\
123432\ 0676239^2 + 1264318000^2 &= 1234321\ 323761^2 & 123432\ 0665916^2 + 1284316000^2 &= 1234321\ 334084^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.569} \tag{5.578}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0675100^2 + 1140000^2 &= 1\ 324900^2 & 0664759^2 + 1158000^2 &= 1\ 335241^2 \\
12\ 0675100^2 + 12540000^2 &= 121\ 324900^2 & 12\ 0664759^2 + 12738000^2 &= 121\ 335241^2 \\
1232\ 0675100^2 + 126540000^2 &= 12321\ 324900^2 & 1232\ 0664759^2 + 128538000^2 &= 12321\ 335241^2 \\
123432\ 0675100^2 + 1266540000^2 &= 1234321\ 324900^2 & 123432\ 0664759^2 + 1286538000^2 &= 1234321\ 335241^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.570} \tag{5.579}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0663600^2 + 1160000^2 &= 1\ 336400^2 & 0651900^2 + 1180000^2 &= 1\ 348100^2 \\
12\ 0663600^2 + 12760000^2 &= 121\ 336400^2 & 12\ 0651900^2 + 12980000^2 &= 121\ 348100^2 \\
1232\ 0663600^2 + 128760000^2 &= 12321\ 336400^2 & 1232\ 0651900^2 + 130980000^2 &= 12321\ 348100^2 \\
123432\ 0663600^2 + 1288760000^2 &= 1234321\ 336400^2 & 123432\ 0651900^2 + 1310980000^2 &= 1234321\ 348100^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.580} \tag{5.590}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0662439^2 + 1162000^2 &= 1\ 337561^2 & 0650719^2 + 1182000^2 &= 1\ 349281^2 \\
12\ 0662439^2 + 12782000^2 &= 121\ 337561^2 & 12\ 0650719^2 + 13002000^2 &= 121\ 349281^2 \\
1232\ 0662439^2 + 128982000^2 &= 12321\ 337561^2 & 1232\ 0650719^2 + 131202000^2 &= 12321\ 349281^2 \\
123432\ 0662439^2 + 1290982000^2 &= 1234321\ 337561^2 & 123432\ 0650719^2 + 1313202000^2 &= 1234321\ 349281^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.581} \tag{5.591}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0661276^2 + 1164000^2 &= 1\ 338724^2 & 0649536^2 + 1184000^2 &= 1\ 350464^2 \\
12\ 0661276^2 + 12804000^2 &= 121\ 338724^2 & 12\ 0649536^2 + 13024000^2 &= 121\ 350464^2 \\
1232\ 0661276^2 + 129204000^2 &= 12321\ 338724^2 & 1232\ 0649536^2 + 131424000^2 &= 12321\ 350464^2 \\
123432\ 0661276^2 + 1293204000^2 &= 1234321\ 338724^2 & 123432\ 0649536^2 + 1315424000^2 &= 1234321\ 350464^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.582} \tag{5.592}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0660111^2 + 1166000^2 &= 1\ 339889^2 & 0648351^2 + 1186000^2 &= 1\ 351649^2 \\
12\ 0660111^2 + 12826000^2 &= 121\ 339889^2 & 12\ 0648351^2 + 13046000^2 &= 121\ 351649^2 \\
1232\ 0660111^2 + 129426000^2 &= 12321\ 339889^2 & 1232\ 0648351^2 + 131646000^2 &= 12321\ 351649^2 \\
123432\ 0660111^2 + 1295426000^2 &= 1234321\ 339889^2 & 123432\ 0648351^2 + 1317646000^2 &= 1234321\ 351649^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.583} \tag{5.593}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0658944^2 + 1168000^2 &= 1\ 341056^2 & 0647164^2 + 1188000^2 &= 1\ 352836^2 \\
12\ 0658944^2 + 12848000^2 &= 121\ 341056^2 & 12\ 0647164^2 + 13068000^2 &= 121\ 352836^2 \\
1232\ 0658944^2 + 129648000^2 &= 12321\ 341056^2 & 1232\ 0647164^2 + 131868000^2 &= 12321\ 352836^2 \\
123432\ 0658944^2 + 1297648000^2 &= 1234321\ 341056^2 & 123432\ 0647164^2 + 1319868000^2 &= 1234321\ 352836^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.584} \tag{5.594}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0657775^2 + 1170000^2 &= 1\ 342225^2 & 0645975^2 + 1190000^2 &= 1\ 354025^2 \\
12\ 0657775^2 + 12870000^2 &= 121\ 342225^2 & 12\ 0645975^2 + 13090000^2 &= 121\ 354025^2 \\
1232\ 0657775^2 + 129870000^2 &= 12321\ 342225^2 & 1232\ 0645975^2 + 132090000^2 &= 12321\ 354025^2 \\
123432\ 0657775^2 + 1299870000^2 &= 1234321\ 342225^2 & 123432\ 0645975^2 + 1322090000^2 &= 1234321\ 354025^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.585} \tag{5.595}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0656604^2 + 1172000^2 &= 1\ 343396^2 & 0644784^2 + 1192000^2 &= 1\ 355216^2 \\
12\ 0656604^2 + 12892000^2 &= 121\ 343396^2 & 12\ 0644784^2 + 13112000^2 &= 121\ 355216^2 \\
1232\ 0656604^2 + 130092000^2 &= 12321\ 343396^2 & 1232\ 0644784^2 + 132312000^2 &= 12321\ 355216^2 \\
123432\ 0656604^2 + 1302092000^2 &= 1234321\ 343396^2 & 123432\ 0644784^2 + 1324312000^2 &= 1234321\ 355216^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.586} \tag{5.596}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0655431^2 + 1174000^2 &= 1\ 344569^2 & 0643591^2 + 1194000^2 &= 1\ 356409^2 \\
12\ 0655431^2 + 12914000^2 &= 121\ 344569^2 & 12\ 0643591^2 + 13134000^2 &= 121\ 356409^2 \\
1232\ 0655431^2 + 130314000^2 &= 12321\ 344569^2 & 1232\ 0643591^2 + 132534000^2 &= 12321\ 356409^2 \\
123432\ 0655431^2 + 1304314000^2 &= 1234321\ 344569^2 & 123432\ 0643591^2 + 1326534000^2 &= 1234321\ 356409^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.587} \tag{5.597}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0654256^2 + 1176000^2 &= 1\ 345744^2 & 0642396^2 + 1196000^2 &= 1\ 357604^2 \\
12\ 0654256^2 + 12936000^2 &= 121\ 345744^2 & 12\ 0642396^2 + 13156000^2 &= 121\ 357604^2 \\
1232\ 0654256^2 + 130536000^2 &= 12321\ 345744^2 & 1232\ 0642396^2 + 132756000^2 &= 12321\ 357604^2 \\
123432\ 0654256^2 + 1306536000^2 &= 1234321\ 345744^2 & 123432\ 0642396^2 + 1328756000^2 &= 1234321\ 357604^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.588} \tag{5.598}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0653079^2 + 1178000^2 &= 1\ 346921^2 & 0641199^2 + 1198000^2 &= 1\ 358801^2 \\
12\ 0653079^2 + 12958000^2 &= 121\ 346921^2 & 12\ 0641199^2 + 13178000^2 &= 121\ 358801^2 \\
1232\ 0653079^2 + 130758000^2 &= 12321\ 346921^2 & 1232\ 0641199^2 + 132978000^2 &= 12321\ 358801^2 \\
123432\ 0653079^2 + 1308758000^2 &= 1234321\ 346921^2 & 123432\ 0641199^2 + 1330978000^2 &= 1234321\ 358801^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.589} \tag{5.599}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0640000^2 + 1200000^2 &= 1\ 360000^2 & 0629119^2 + 1218000^2 &= 1\ 370881^2 \\
12\ 0640000^2 + 13200000^2 &= 121\ 360000^2 & 12\ 0629119^2 + 13398000^2 &= 121\ 370881^2 \\
1232\ 0640000^2 + 133200000^2 &= 12321\ 360000^2 & 1232\ 0629119^2 + 135198000^2 &= 12321\ 370881^2 \\
123432\ 0640000^2 + 1333200000^2 &= 1234321\ 360000^2 & 123432\ 0629119^2 + 1353198000^2 &= 1234321\ 370881^2 \quad (5.609)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.600)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0638799^2 + 1202000^2 &= 1\ 361201^2 & 0627900^2 + 1220000^2 &= 1\ 372100^2 \\
12\ 0638799^2 + 13222000^2 &= 121\ 361201^2 & 12\ 0627900^2 + 13420000^2 &= 121\ 372100^2 \\
1232\ 0638799^2 + 133422000^2 &= 12321\ 361201^2 & 1232\ 0627900^2 + 135420000^2 &= 12321\ 372100^2 \\
123432\ 0638799^2 + 1335422000^2 &= 1234321\ 361201^2 & 123432\ 0627900^2 + 1355420000^2 &= 1234321\ 372100^2 \quad (5.610)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.601)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0637596^2 + 1204000^2 &= 1\ 362404^2 & 0626679^2 + 1222000^2 &= 1\ 373321^2 \\
12\ 0637596^2 + 13244000^2 &= 121\ 362404^2 & 12\ 0626679^2 + 13442000^2 &= 121\ 373321^2 \\
1232\ 0637596^2 + 133644000^2 &= 12321\ 362404^2 & 1232\ 0626679^2 + 135642000^2 &= 12321\ 373321^2 \\
123432\ 0637596^2 + 1337644000^2 &= 1234321\ 362404^2 & 123432\ 0626679^2 + 1357642000^2 &= 1234321\ 373321^2 \quad (5.611)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.602)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0636391^2 + 1206000^2 &= 1\ 363609^2 & 0625456^2 + 1224000^2 &= 1\ 374544^2 \\
12\ 0636391^2 + 13266000^2 &= 121\ 363609^2 & 12\ 0625456^2 + 13464000^2 &= 121\ 374544^2 \\
1232\ 0636391^2 + 133866000^2 &= 12321\ 363609^2 & 1232\ 0625456^2 + 135864000^2 &= 12321\ 374544^2 \\
123432\ 0636391^2 + 1339866000^2 &= 1234321\ 363609^2 & 123432\ 0625456^2 + 1359864000^2 &= 1234321\ 374544^2 \quad (5.612)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.603)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0635184^2 + 1208000^2 &= 1\ 364816^2 & 0624231^2 + 1226000^2 &= 1\ 375769^2 \\
12\ 0635184^2 + 13288000^2 &= 121\ 364816^2 & 12\ 0624231^2 + 13486000^2 &= 121\ 375769^2 \\
1232\ 0635184^2 + 134088000^2 &= 12321\ 364816^2 & 1232\ 0624231^2 + 136086000^2 &= 12321\ 375769^2 \\
123432\ 0635184^2 + 1342088000^2 &= 1234321\ 364816^2 & 123432\ 0624231^2 + 1362086000^2 &= 1234321\ 375769^2 \quad (5.613)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.604)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0633975^2 + 1210000^2 &= 1\ 366025^2 & 0623004^2 + 1228000^2 &= 1\ 376996^2 \\
12\ 0633975^2 + 13310000^2 &= 121\ 366025^2 & 12\ 0623004^2 + 13508000^2 &= 121\ 376996^2 \\
1232\ 0633975^2 + 134310000^2 &= 12321\ 366025^2 & 1232\ 0623004^2 + 136308000^2 &= 12321\ 376996^2 \\
123432\ 0633975^2 + 1344310000^2 &= 1234321\ 366025^2 & 123432\ 0623004^2 + 1364308000^2 &= 1234321\ 376996^2 \quad (5.614)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.605)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0632764^2 + 1212000^2 &= 1\ 367236^2 & 0621775^2 + 1230000^2 &= 1\ 378225^2 \\
12\ 0632764^2 + 13332000^2 &= 121\ 367236^2 & 12\ 0621775^2 + 13530000^2 &= 121\ 378225^2 \\
1232\ 0632764^2 + 134532000^2 &= 12321\ 367236^2 & 1232\ 0621775^2 + 136530000^2 &= 12321\ 378225^2 \\
123432\ 0632764^2 + 1346532000^2 &= 1234321\ 367236^2 & 123432\ 0621775^2 + 1366530000^2 &= 1234321\ 378225^2 \quad (5.615)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.606)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0631551^2 + 1214000^2 &= 1\ 368449^2 & 0620544^2 + 1232000^2 &= 1\ 379456^2 \\
12\ 0631551^2 + 13354000^2 &= 121\ 368449^2 & 12\ 0620544^2 + 13552000^2 &= 121\ 379456^2 \\
1232\ 0631551^2 + 134754000^2 &= 12321\ 368449^2 & 1232\ 0620544^2 + 136752000^2 &= 12321\ 379456^2 \\
123432\ 0631551^2 + 1348754000^2 &= 1234321\ 368449^2 & 123432\ 0620544^2 + 1368752000^2 &= 1234321\ 379456^2 \quad (5.616)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.607)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0630336^2 + 1216000^2 &= 1\ 369664^2 & 0619311^2 + 1234000^2 &= 1\ 380689^2 \\
12\ 0630336^2 + 13376000^2 &= 121\ 369664^2 & 12\ 0619311^2 + 13574000^2 &= 121\ 380689^2 \\
1232\ 0630336^2 + 134976000^2 &= 12321\ 369664^2 & 1232\ 0619311^2 + 136974000^2 &= 12321\ 380689^2 \\
123432\ 0630336^2 + 1350976000^2 &= 1234321\ 369664^2 & 123432\ 0619311^2 + 1370974000^2 &= 1234321\ 380689^2 \quad (5.617)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.608)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0618076^2 + 1236000^2 &= 1381924^2 & 0606871^2 + 1254000^2 &= 1393129^2 \\
120618076^2 + 13596000^2 &= 121381924^2 & 120606871^2 + 13794000^2 &= 121393129^2 \\
12320618076^2 + 137196000^2 &= 12321381924^2 & 12320606871^2 + 139194000^2 &= 12321393129^2 \\
1234320618076^2 + 1373196000^2 &= 1234321381924^2 & 1234320606871^2 + 1393194000^2 &= 1234321393129^2 \quad (5.627)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.618)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0616839^2 + 1238000^2 &= 1383161^2 & 0605616^2 + 1256000^2 &= 1394384^2 \\
120616839^2 + 13618000^2 &= 121383161^2 & 120605616^2 + 13816000^2 &= 121394384^2 \\
12320616839^2 + 137418000^2 &= 12321383161^2 & 12320605616^2 + 139416000^2 &= 12321394384^2 \\
1234320616839^2 + 1375418000^2 &= 1234321383161^2 & 1234320605616^2 + 1395416000^2 &= 1234321394384^2 \quad (5.628)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.619)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0615600^2 + 1240000^2 &= 1384400^2 & 0604359^2 + 1258000^2 &= 1395641^2 \\
120615600^2 + 13640000^2 &= 121384400^2 & 120604359^2 + 13838000^2 &= 121395641^2 \\
12320615600^2 + 137640000^2 &= 12321384400^2 & 12320604359^2 + 139638000^2 &= 12321395641^2 \\
1234320615600^2 + 1377640000^2 &= 1234321384400^2 & 1234320604359^2 + 1397638000^2 &= 1234321395641^2 \quad (5.629)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.620)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0614359^2 + 1242000^2 &= 1385641^2 & 0603100^2 + 1260000^2 &= 1396900^2 \\
120614359^2 + 13662000^2 &= 121385641^2 & 120603100^2 + 13860000^2 &= 121396900^2 \\
12320614359^2 + 137862000^2 &= 12321385641^2 & 12320603100^2 + 139860000^2 &= 12321396900^2 \\
1234320614359^2 + 1379862000^2 &= 1234321385641^2 & 1234320603100^2 + 1399860000^2 &= 1234321396900^2 \quad (5.630)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.621)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0613116^2 + 1244000^2 &= 1386884^2 & 0601839^2 + 1262000^2 &= 1398161^2 \\
120613116^2 + 13684000^2 &= 121386884^2 & 120601839^2 + 13882000^2 &= 121398161^2 \\
12320613116^2 + 138084000^2 &= 12321386884^2 & 12320601839^2 + 140082000^2 &= 12321398161^2 \\
1234320613116^2 + 1382084000^2 &= 1234321386884^2 & 1234320601839^2 + 1402082000^2 &= 1234321398161^2 \quad (5.631)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.622)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0611871^2 + 1246000^2 &= 1388129^2 & 0600576^2 + 1264000^2 &= 1399424^2 \\
120611871^2 + 13706000^2 &= 121388129^2 & 120600576^2 + 13904000^2 &= 121399424^2 \\
12320611871^2 + 138306000^2 &= 12321388129^2 & 12320600576^2 + 140304000^2 &= 12321399424^2 \\
1234320611871^2 + 1384306000^2 &= 1234321388129^2 & 1234320600576^2 + 1404304000^2 &= 1234321399424^2 \quad (5.632)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.623)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0610624^2 + 1248000^2 &= 1389376^2 & 0599311^2 + 1266000^2 &= 1400689^2 \\
120610624^2 + 13728000^2 &= 121389376^2 & 120599311^2 + 13926000^2 &= 121400689^2 \\
12320610624^2 + 138528000^2 &= 12321389376^2 & 12320599311^2 + 140526000^2 &= 12321400689^2 \\
1234320610624^2 + 1386528000^2 &= 1234321389376^2 & 1234320599311^2 + 1406526000^2 &= 1234321400689^2 \quad (5.633)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.624)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0609375^2 + 1250000^2 &= 1390625^2 & 0598044^2 + 1268000^2 &= 1401956^2 \\
120609375^2 + 13750000^2 &= 121390625^2 & 120598044^2 + 13948000^2 &= 121401956^2 \\
12320609375^2 + 138750000^2 &= 12321390625^2 & 12320598044^2 + 140748000^2 &= 12321401956^2 \\
1234320609375^2 + 1388750000^2 &= 1234321390625^2 & 1234320598044^2 + 1408748000^2 &= 1234321401956^2 \quad (5.634)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.625)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0608124^2 + 1252000^2 &= 1391876^2 & 0596775^2 + 1270000^2 &= 1403225^2 \\
120608124^2 + 13772000^2 &= 121391876^2 & 120596775^2 + 13970000^2 &= 121403225^2 \\
12320608124^2 + 138972000^2 &= 12321391876^2 & 12320596775^2 + 140970000^2 &= 12321403225^2 \\
1234320608124^2 + 1390972000^2 &= 1234321391876^2 & 1234320596775^2 + 1410970000^2 &= 1234321403225^2 \quad (5.635)
\end{aligned} \quad (5.626)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0595504^2 + 1272000^2 &= 1\ 404496^2 & 0583975^2 + 1290000^2 &= 1\ 416025^2 \\
12\ 0595504^2 + 13992000^2 &= 121\ 404496^2 & 12\ 0583975^2 + 14190000^2 &= 121\ 416025^2 \\
1232\ 0595504^2 + 141192000^2 &= 12321\ 404496^2 & 1232\ 0583975^2 + 143190000^2 &= 12321\ 416025^2 \\
123432\ 0595504^2 + 1413192000^2 &= 1234321\ 404496^2 & 123432\ 0583975^2 + 1433190000^2 &= 1234321\ 416025^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.636} \tag{5.645}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0594231^2 + 1274000^2 &= 1\ 405769^2 & 0582684^2 + 1292000^2 &= 1\ 417316^2 \\
12\ 0594231^2 + 14014000^2 &= 121\ 405769^2 & 12\ 0582684^2 + 14212000^2 &= 121\ 417316^2 \\
1232\ 0594231^2 + 141414000^2 &= 12321\ 405769^2 & 1232\ 0582684^2 + 143412000^2 &= 12321\ 417316^2 \\
123432\ 0594231^2 + 1415414000^2 &= 1234321\ 405769^2 & 123432\ 0582684^2 + 1435412000^2 &= 1234321\ 417316^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.637} \tag{5.646}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0592956^2 + 1276000^2 &= 1\ 407044^2 & 0581391^2 + 1294000^2 &= 1\ 418609^2 \\
12\ 0592956^2 + 14036000^2 &= 121\ 407044^2 & 12\ 0581391^2 + 14234000^2 &= 121\ 418609^2 \\
1232\ 0592956^2 + 141636000^2 &= 12321\ 407044^2 & 1232\ 0581391^2 + 143634000^2 &= 12321\ 418609^2 \\
123432\ 0592956^2 + 1417636000^2 &= 1234321\ 407044^2 & 123432\ 0581391^2 + 1437634000^2 &= 1234321\ 418609^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.638} \tag{5.647}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0591679^2 + 1278000^2 &= 1\ 408321^2 & 0580096^2 + 1296000^2 &= 1\ 419904^2 \\
12\ 0591679^2 + 14058000^2 &= 121\ 408321^2 & 12\ 0580096^2 + 14256000^2 &= 121\ 419904^2 \\
1232\ 0591679^2 + 141858000^2 &= 12321\ 408321^2 & 1232\ 0580096^2 + 143856000^2 &= 12321\ 419904^2 \\
123432\ 0591679^2 + 1419858000^2 &= 1234321\ 408321^2 & 123432\ 0580096^2 + 1439856000^2 &= 1234321\ 419904^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.639} \tag{5.648}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0590400^2 + 1280000^2 &= 1\ 409600^2 & 0578799^2 + 1298000^2 &= 1\ 421201^2 \\
12\ 0590400^2 + 14080000^2 &= 121\ 409600^2 & 12\ 0578799^2 + 14278000^2 &= 121\ 421201^2 \\
1232\ 0590400^2 + 142080000^2 &= 12321\ 409600^2 & 1232\ 0578799^2 + 144078000^2 &= 12321\ 421201^2 \\
123432\ 0590400^2 + 1422080000^2 &= 1234321\ 409600^2 & 123432\ 0578799^2 + 1442078000^2 &= 1234321\ 421201^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.640} \tag{5.649}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0589119^2 + 1282000^2 &= 1\ 410881^2 & 0577500^2 + 1300000^2 &= 1\ 422500^2 \\
12\ 0589119^2 + 14102000^2 &= 121\ 410881^2 & 12\ 0577500^2 + 14300000^2 &= 121\ 422500^2 \\
1232\ 0589119^2 + 142302000^2 &= 12321\ 410881^2 & 1232\ 0577500^2 + 144300000^2 &= 12321\ 422500^2 \\
123432\ 0589119^2 + 1424302000^2 &= 1234321\ 410881^2 & 123432\ 0577500^2 + 1444300000^2 &= 1234321\ 422500^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.641} \tag{5.650}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0587836^2 + 1284000^2 &= 1\ 412164^2 & 0576199^2 + 1302000^2 &= 1\ 423801^2 \\
12\ 0587836^2 + 14124000^2 &= 121\ 412164^2 & 12\ 0576199^2 + 14322000^2 &= 121\ 423801^2 \\
1232\ 0587836^2 + 142524000^2 &= 12321\ 412164^2 & 1232\ 0576199^2 + 144522000^2 &= 12321\ 423801^2 \\
123432\ 0587836^2 + 1426524000^2 &= 1234321\ 412164^2 & 123432\ 0576199^2 + 1446522000^2 &= 1234321\ 423801^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.642} \tag{5.651}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0586551^2 + 1286000^2 &= 1\ 413449^2 & 0574896^2 + 1304000^2 &= 1\ 425104^2 \\
12\ 0586551^2 + 14146000^2 &= 121\ 413449^2 & 12\ 0574896^2 + 14344000^2 &= 121\ 425104^2 \\
1232\ 0586551^2 + 142746000^2 &= 12321\ 413449^2 & 1232\ 0574896^2 + 144744000^2 &= 12321\ 425104^2 \\
123432\ 0586551^2 + 1428746000^2 &= 1234321\ 413449^2 & 123432\ 0574896^2 + 1448744000^2 &= 1234321\ 425104^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.643} \tag{5.652}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0585264^2 + 1288000^2 &= 1\ 414736^2 & 0573591^2 + 1306000^2 &= 1\ 426409^2 \\
12\ 0585264^2 + 14168000^2 &= 121\ 414736^2 & 12\ 0573591^2 + 14366000^2 &= 121\ 426409^2 \\
1232\ 0585264^2 + 142968000^2 &= 12321\ 414736^2 & 1232\ 0573591^2 + 144966000^2 &= 12321\ 426409^2 \\
123432\ 0585264^2 + 1430968000^2 &= 1234321\ 414736^2 & 123432\ 0573591^2 + 1450966000^2 &= 1234321\ 426409^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.644} \tag{5.653}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0572284^2 + 1308000^2 &= 1\ 427716^2 & 0560431^2 + 1326000^2 &= 1\ 439569^2 \\
12\ 0572284^2 + 14388000^2 &= 121\ 427716^2 & 12\ 0560431^2 + 14586000^2 &= 121\ 439569^2 \\
1232\ 0572284^2 + 145188000^2 &= 12321\ 427716^2 & 1232\ 0560431^2 + 147186000^2 &= 12321\ 439569^2 \\
123432\ 0572284^2 + 1453188000^2 &= 1234321\ 427716^2 & 123432\ 0560431^2 + 1473186000^2 &= 1234321\ 439569^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.654} \tag{5.663}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0570975^2 + 1310000^2 &= 1\ 429025^2 & 0559104^2 + 1328000^2 &= 1\ 440896^2 \\
12\ 0570975^2 + 14410000^2 &= 121\ 429025^2 & 12\ 0559104^2 + 14608000^2 &= 121\ 440896^2 \\
1232\ 0570975^2 + 145410000^2 &= 12321\ 429025^2 & 1232\ 0559104^2 + 147408000^2 &= 12321\ 440896^2 \\
123432\ 0570975^2 + 1455410000^2 &= 1234321\ 429025^2 & 123432\ 0559104^2 + 1475408000^2 &= 1234321\ 440896^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.655} \tag{5.664}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0569664^2 + 1312000^2 &= 1\ 430336^2 & 0557775^2 + 1330000^2 &= 1\ 442225^2 \\
12\ 0569664^2 + 14432000^2 &= 121\ 430336^2 & 12\ 0557775^2 + 14630000^2 &= 121\ 442225^2 \\
1232\ 0569664^2 + 145632000^2 &= 12321\ 430336^2 & 1232\ 0557775^2 + 147630000^2 &= 12321\ 442225^2 \\
123432\ 0569664^2 + 1457632000^2 &= 1234321\ 430336^2 & 123432\ 0557775^2 + 1477630000^2 &= 1234321\ 442225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.656} \tag{5.665}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0568351^2 + 1314000^2 &= 1\ 431649^2 & 0556444^2 + 1332000^2 &= 1\ 443556^2 \\
12\ 0568351^2 + 14454000^2 &= 121\ 431649^2 & 12\ 0556444^2 + 14652000^2 &= 121\ 443556^2 \\
1232\ 0568351^2 + 145854000^2 &= 12321\ 431649^2 & 1232\ 0556444^2 + 147852000^2 &= 12321\ 443556^2 \\
123432\ 0568351^2 + 1459854000^2 &= 1234321\ 431649^2 & 123432\ 0556444^2 + 1479852000^2 &= 1234321\ 443556^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.657} \tag{5.666}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0567036^2 + 1316000^2 &= 1\ 432964^2 & 0555111^2 + 1334000^2 &= 1\ 444889^2 \\
12\ 0567036^2 + 14476000^2 &= 121\ 432964^2 & 12\ 0555111^2 + 14674000^2 &= 121\ 444889^2 \\
1232\ 0567036^2 + 146076000^2 &= 12321\ 432964^2 & 1232\ 0555111^2 + 148074000^2 &= 12321\ 444889^2 \\
123432\ 0567036^2 + 1462076000^2 &= 1234321\ 432964^2 & 123432\ 0555111^2 + 1482074000^2 &= 1234321\ 444889^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.658} \tag{5.667}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0565719^2 + 1318000^2 &= 1\ 434281^2 & 0553776^2 + 1336000^2 &= 1\ 446224^2 \\
12\ 0565719^2 + 14498000^2 &= 121\ 434281^2 & 12\ 0553776^2 + 14696000^2 &= 121\ 446224^2 \\
1232\ 0565719^2 + 146298000^2 &= 12321\ 434281^2 & 1232\ 0553776^2 + 148296000^2 &= 12321\ 446224^2 \\
123432\ 0565719^2 + 1464298000^2 &= 1234321\ 434281^2 & 123432\ 0553776^2 + 1484296000^2 &= 1234321\ 446224^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.659} \tag{5.668}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0564400^2 + 1320000^2 &= 1\ 435600^2 & 0552439^2 + 1338000^2 &= 1\ 447561^2 \\
12\ 0564400^2 + 14520000^2 &= 121\ 435600^2 & 12\ 0552439^2 + 14718000^2 &= 121\ 447561^2 \\
1232\ 0564400^2 + 146520000^2 &= 12321\ 435600^2 & 1232\ 0552439^2 + 148518000^2 &= 12321\ 447561^2 \\
123432\ 0564400^2 + 1466520000^2 &= 1234321\ 435600^2 & 123432\ 0552439^2 + 1486518000^2 &= 1234321\ 447561^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.660} \tag{5.669}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0563079^2 + 1322000^2 &= 1\ 436921^2 & 0551100^2 + 1340000^2 &= 1\ 448900^2 \\
12\ 0563079^2 + 14542000^2 &= 121\ 436921^2 & 12\ 0551100^2 + 14740000^2 &= 121\ 448900^2 \\
1232\ 0563079^2 + 146742000^2 &= 12321\ 436921^2 & 1232\ 0551100^2 + 148740000^2 &= 12321\ 448900^2 \\
123432\ 0563079^2 + 1468742000^2 &= 1234321\ 436921^2 & 123432\ 0551100^2 + 1488740000^2 &= 1234321\ 448900^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.661} \tag{5.670}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0561756^2 + 1324000^2 &= 1\ 438244^2 & 0549759^2 + 1342000^2 &= 1\ 450241^2 \\
12\ 0561756^2 + 14564000^2 &= 121\ 438244^2 & 12\ 0549759^2 + 14762000^2 &= 121\ 450241^2 \\
1232\ 0561756^2 + 146964000^2 &= 12321\ 438244^2 & 1232\ 0549759^2 + 148962000^2 &= 12321\ 450241^2 \\
123432\ 0561756^2 + 1470964000^2 &= 1234321\ 438244^2 & 123432\ 0549759^2 + 1490962000^2 &= 1234321\ 450241^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.662} \tag{5.671}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0548416^2 + 1344000^2 &= 1451584^2 & 0536239^2 + 1362000^2 &= 1463761^2 \\
120548416^2 + 14784000^2 &= 121451584^2 & 120536239^2 + 14982000^2 &= 121463761^2 \\
12320548416^2 + 149184000^2 &= 12321451584^2 & 12320536239^2 + 151182000^2 &= 12321463761^2 \\
1234320548416^2 + 1493184000^2 &= 1234321451584^2 & 1234320536239^2 + 1513182000^2 &= 1234321463761^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.672} \tag{5.681}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0547071^2 + 1346000^2 &= 1452929^2 & 0534876^2 + 1364000^2 &= 1465124^2 \\
120547071^2 + 14806000^2 &= 121452929^2 & 120534876^2 + 15004000^2 &= 121465124^2 \\
12320547071^2 + 149406000^2 &= 12321452929^2 & 12320534876^2 + 151404000^2 &= 12321465124^2 \\
1234320547071^2 + 1495406000^2 &= 1234321452929^2 & 1234320534876^2 + 1515404000^2 &= 1234321465124^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.673} \tag{5.682}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0545724^2 + 1348000^2 &= 1454276^2 & 0533511^2 + 1366000^2 &= 1466489^2 \\
120545724^2 + 14828000^2 &= 121454276^2 & 120533511^2 + 15026000^2 &= 121466489^2 \\
12320545724^2 + 149628000^2 &= 12321454276^2 & 12320533511^2 + 151626000^2 &= 12321466489^2 \\
1234320545724^2 + 1497628000^2 &= 1234321454276^2 & 1234320533511^2 + 1517626000^2 &= 1234321466489^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.674} \tag{5.683}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0544375^2 + 1350000^2 &= 1455625^2 & 0532144^2 + 1368000^2 &= 1467856^2 \\
120544375^2 + 14850000^2 &= 121455625^2 & 120532144^2 + 15048000^2 &= 121467856^2 \\
12320544375^2 + 149850000^2 &= 12321455625^2 & 12320532144^2 + 151848000^2 &= 12321467856^2 \\
1234320544375^2 + 1499850000^2 &= 1234321455625^2 & 1234320532144^2 + 1519848000^2 &= 1234321467856^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.675} \tag{5.684}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0543024^2 + 1352000^2 &= 1456976^2 & 0530775^2 + 1370000^2 &= 1469225^2 \\
120543024^2 + 14872000^2 &= 121456976^2 & 120530775^2 + 15070000^2 &= 121469225^2 \\
12320543024^2 + 150072000^2 &= 12321456976^2 & 12320530775^2 + 152070000^2 &= 12321469225^2 \\
1234320543024^2 + 1502072000^2 &= 1234321456976^2 & 1234320530775^2 + 1522070000^2 &= 1234321469225^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.676} \tag{5.685}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0541671^2 + 1354000^2 &= 1458329^2 & 0529404^2 + 1372000^2 &= 1470596^2 \\
120541671^2 + 14894000^2 &= 121458329^2 & 120529404^2 + 15092000^2 &= 121470596^2 \\
12320541671^2 + 150294000^2 &= 12321458329^2 & 12320529404^2 + 152292000^2 &= 12321470596^2 \\
1234320541671^2 + 1504294000^2 &= 1234321458329^2 & 1234320529404^2 + 1524292000^2 &= 1234321470596^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.677} \tag{5.686}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0540316^2 + 1356000^2 &= 1459684^2 & 0528031^2 + 1374000^2 &= 1471969^2 \\
120540316^2 + 14916000^2 &= 121459684^2 & 120528031^2 + 15114000^2 &= 121471969^2 \\
12320540316^2 + 150516000^2 &= 12321459684^2 & 12320528031^2 + 152514000^2 &= 12321471969^2 \\
1234320540316^2 + 1506516000^2 &= 1234321459684^2 & 1234320528031^2 + 1526514000^2 &= 1234321471969^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.678} \tag{5.687}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0538959^2 + 1358000^2 &= 1461041^2 & 0526656^2 + 1376000^2 &= 1473344^2 \\
120538959^2 + 14938000^2 &= 121461041^2 & 120526656^2 + 15136000^2 &= 121473344^2 \\
12320538959^2 + 150738000^2 &= 12321461041^2 & 12320526656^2 + 152736000^2 &= 12321473344^2 \\
1234320538959^2 + 1508738000^2 &= 1234321461041^2 & 1234320526656^2 + 1528736000^2 &= 1234321473344^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.679} \tag{5.688}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0537600^2 + 1360000^2 &= 1462400^2 & 0525279^2 + 1378000^2 &= 1474721^2 \\
120537600^2 + 14960000^2 &= 121462400^2 & 120525279^2 + 15158000^2 &= 121474721^2 \\
12320537600^2 + 150960000^2 &= 12321462400^2 & 12320525279^2 + 152958000^2 &= 12321474721^2 \\
1234320537600^2 + 1510960000^2 &= 1234321462400^2 & 1234320525279^2 + 1530958000^2 &= 1234321474721^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.680} \tag{5.689}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0523900^2 + 1380000^2 &= 1\,476100^2 & 0516975^2 + 1390000^2 &= 1\,483025^2 \\
12\,0523900^2 + 15180000^2 &= 121\,476100^2 & 12\,0516975^2 + 15290000^2 &= 121\,483025^2 \\
1232\,0523900^2 + 153180000^2 &= 12321\,476100^2 & 1232\,0516975^2 + 154290000^2 &= 12321\,483025^2 \\
123432\,0523900^2 + 1533180000^2 &= 1234321\,476100^2 & 123432\,0516975^2 + 1544290000^2 &= 1234321\,483025^2 \quad (5.695)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0522519^2 + 1382000^2 &= 1\,477481^2 & 0515584^2 + 1392000^2 &= 1\,484416^2 \\
12\,0522519^2 + 15202000^2 &= 121\,477481^2 & 12\,0515584^2 + 15312000^2 &= 121\,484416^2 \\
1232\,0522519^2 + 153402000^2 &= 12321\,477481^2 & 1232\,0515584^2 + 154512000^2 &= 12321\,484416^2 \\
123432\,0522519^2 + 1535402000^2 &= 1234321\,477481^2 & 123432\,0515584^2 + 1546512000^2 &= 1234321\,484416^2 \quad (5.696)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0521136^2 + 1384000^2 &= 1\,478864^2 & 0514191^2 + 1394000^2 &= 1\,485809^2 \\
12\,0521136^2 + 15224000^2 &= 121\,478864^2 & 12\,0514191^2 + 15334000^2 &= 121\,485809^2 \\
1232\,0521136^2 + 153624000^2 &= 12321\,478864^2 & 1232\,0514191^2 + 154734000^2 &= 12321\,485809^2 \\
123432\,0521136^2 + 1537624000^2 &= 1234321\,478864^2 & 123432\,0514191^2 + 1548734000^2 &= 1234321\,485809^2 \quad (5.697)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0519751^2 + 1386000^2 &= 1\,480249^2 & 0512796^2 + 1396000^2 &= 1\,487204^2 \\
12\,0519751^2 + 15246000^2 &= 121\,480249^2 & 12\,0512796^2 + 15356000^2 &= 121\,487204^2 \\
1232\,0519751^2 + 153846000^2 &= 12321\,480249^2 & 1232\,0512796^2 + 154956000^2 &= 12321\,487204^2 \\
123432\,0519751^2 + 1539846000^2 &= 1234321\,480249^2 & 123432\,0512796^2 + 1550956000^2 &= 1234321\,487204^2 \quad (5.698)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0518364^2 + 1388000^2 &= 1\,481636^2 & 0511399^2 + 1398000^2 &= 1\,488601^2 \\
12\,0518364^2 + 15268000^2 &= 121\,481636^2 & 12\,0511399^2 + 15378000^2 &= 121\,488601^2 \\
1232\,0518364^2 + 154068000^2 &= 12321\,481636^2 & 1232\,0511399^2 + 155178000^2 &= 12321\,488601^2 \\
123432\,0518364^2 + 1542068000^2 &= 1234321\,481636^2 & 123432\,0511399^2 + 1553178000^2 &= 1234321\,488601^2 \quad (5.699)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0510000^2 + 1400000^2 &= 1\,490000^2 & 0504384^2 + 1408000^2 &= 1\,495616^2 \\
12\,0510000^2 + 15400000^2 &= 121\,490000^2 & 12\,0504384^2 + 15488000^2 &= 121\,495616^2 \\
1232\,0510000^2 + 155400000^2 &= 12321\,490000^2 & 1232\,0504384^2 + 156288000^2 &= 12321\,495616^2 \\
123432\,0510000^2 + 1555400000^2 &= 1234321\,490000^2 & 123432\,0504384^2 + 1564288000^2 &= 1234321\,495616^2 \quad (5.704)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0508599^2 + 1402000^2 &= 1\,491401^2 & 0502975^2 + 1410000^2 &= 1\,497025^2 \\
12\,0508599^2 + 15422000^2 &= 121\,491401^2 & 12\,0502975^2 + 15510000^2 &= 121\,497025^2 \\
1232\,0508599^2 + 155622000^2 &= 12321\,491401^2 & 1232\,0502975^2 + 156510000^2 &= 12321\,497025^2 \\
123432\,0508599^2 + 1557622000^2 &= 1234321\,491401^2 & 123432\,0502975^2 + 1566510000^2 &= 1234321\,497025^2 \quad (5.705)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0507196^2 + 1404000^2 &= 1\,492804^2 & 0501564^2 + 1412000^2 &= 1\,498436^2 \\
12\,0507196^2 + 15444000^2 &= 121\,492804^2 & 12\,0501564^2 + 15532000^2 &= 121\,498436^2 \\
1232\,0507196^2 + 155844000^2 &= 12321\,492804^2 & 1232\,0501564^2 + 156732000^2 &= 12321\,498436^2 \\
123432\,0507196^2 + 1559844000^2 &= 1234321\,492804^2 & 123432\,0501564^2 + 1568732000^2 &= 1234321\,498436^2 \quad (5.706)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0505791^2 + 1406000^2 &= 1\,494209^2 & 0500151^2 + 1414000^2 &= 1\,499849^2 \\
12\,0505791^2 + 15466000^2 &= 121\,494209^2 & 12\,0500151^2 + 15554000^2 &= 121\,499849^2 \\
1232\,0505791^2 + 156066000^2 &= 12321\,494209^2 & 1232\,0500151^2 + 156954000^2 &= 12321\,499849^2 \\
123432\,0505791^2 + 1562066000^2 &= 1234321\,494209^2 & 123432\,0500151^2 + 1570954000^2 &= 1234321\,499849^2 \quad (5.707)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0498736^2 + 1416000^2 &= 1\ 501264^2 & 0485911^2 + 1434000^2 &= 1\ 514089^2 \\
12\ 0498736^2 + 15576000^2 &= 121\ 501264^2 & 12\ 0485911^2 + 15774000^2 &= 121\ 514089^2 \\
1232\ 0498736^2 + 157176000^2 &= 12321\ 501264^2 & 1232\ 0485911^2 + 159174000^2 &= 12321\ 514089^2 \\
123432\ 0498736^2 + 1573176000^2 &= 1234321\ 501264^2 & 123432\ 0485911^2 + 1593174000^2 &= 1234321\ 514089^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.708} \tag{5.717}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0497319^2 + 1418000^2 &= 1\ 502681^2 & 0484476^2 + 1436000^2 &= 1\ 515524^2 \\
12\ 0497319^2 + 15598000^2 &= 121\ 502681^2 & 12\ 0484476^2 + 15796000^2 &= 121\ 515524^2 \\
1232\ 0497319^2 + 157398000^2 &= 12321\ 502681^2 & 1232\ 0484476^2 + 159396000^2 &= 12321\ 515524^2 \\
123432\ 0497319^2 + 1575398000^2 &= 1234321\ 502681^2 & 123432\ 0484476^2 + 1595396000^2 &= 1234321\ 515524^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.709} \tag{5.718}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0495900^2 + 1420000^2 &= 1\ 504100^2 & 0483039^2 + 1438000^2 &= 1\ 516961^2 \\
12\ 0495900^2 + 15620000^2 &= 121\ 504100^2 & 12\ 0483039^2 + 15818000^2 &= 121\ 516961^2 \\
1232\ 0495900^2 + 157620000^2 &= 12321\ 504100^2 & 1232\ 0483039^2 + 159618000^2 &= 12321\ 516961^2 \\
123432\ 0495900^2 + 1577620000^2 &= 1234321\ 504100^2 & 123432\ 0483039^2 + 1597618000^2 &= 1234321\ 516961^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.710} \tag{5.719}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0494479^2 + 1422000^2 &= 1\ 505521^2 & 0481600^2 + 1440000^2 &= 1\ 518400^2 \\
12\ 0494479^2 + 15642000^2 &= 121\ 505521^2 & 12\ 0481600^2 + 15840000^2 &= 121\ 518400^2 \\
1232\ 0494479^2 + 157842000^2 &= 12321\ 505521^2 & 1232\ 0481600^2 + 159840000^2 &= 12321\ 518400^2 \\
123432\ 0494479^2 + 1579842000^2 &= 1234321\ 505521^2 & 123432\ 0481600^2 + 1599840000^2 &= 1234321\ 518400^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.711} \tag{5.720}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0493056^2 + 1424000^2 &= 1\ 506944^2 & 0480159^2 + 1442000^2 &= 1\ 519841^2 \\
12\ 0493056^2 + 15664000^2 &= 121\ 506944^2 & 12\ 0480159^2 + 15862000^2 &= 121\ 519841^2 \\
1232\ 0493056^2 + 158064000^2 &= 12321\ 506944^2 & 1232\ 0480159^2 + 160062000^2 &= 12321\ 519841^2 \\
123432\ 0493056^2 + 1582064000^2 &= 1234321\ 506944^2 & 123432\ 0480159^2 + 1602062000^2 &= 1234321\ 519841^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.712} \tag{5.721}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0491631^2 + 1426000^2 &= 1\ 508369^2 & 0478716^2 + 1444000^2 &= 1\ 521284^2 \\
12\ 0491631^2 + 15686000^2 &= 121\ 508369^2 & 12\ 0478716^2 + 15884000^2 &= 121\ 521284^2 \\
1232\ 0491631^2 + 158286000^2 &= 12321\ 508369^2 & 1232\ 0478716^2 + 160284000^2 &= 12321\ 521284^2 \\
123432\ 0491631^2 + 1584286000^2 &= 1234321\ 508369^2 & 123432\ 0478716^2 + 1604284000^2 &= 1234321\ 521284^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.713} \tag{5.722}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0490204^2 + 1428000^2 &= 1\ 509796^2 & 0477271^2 + 1446000^2 &= 1\ 522729^2 \\
12\ 0490204^2 + 15708000^2 &= 121\ 509796^2 & 12\ 0477271^2 + 15906000^2 &= 121\ 522729^2 \\
1232\ 0490204^2 + 158508000^2 &= 12321\ 509796^2 & 1232\ 0477271^2 + 160506000^2 &= 12321\ 522729^2 \\
123432\ 0490204^2 + 1586508000^2 &= 1234321\ 509796^2 & 123432\ 0477271^2 + 1606506000^2 &= 1234321\ 522729^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.714} \tag{5.723}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0488775^2 + 1430000^2 &= 1\ 511225^2 & 0475824^2 + 1448000^2 &= 1\ 524176^2 \\
12\ 0488775^2 + 15730000^2 &= 121\ 511225^2 & 12\ 0475824^2 + 15928000^2 &= 121\ 524176^2 \\
1232\ 0488775^2 + 158730000^2 &= 12321\ 511225^2 & 1232\ 0475824^2 + 160728000^2 &= 12321\ 524176^2 \\
123432\ 0488775^2 + 1588730000^2 &= 1234321\ 511225^2 & 123432\ 0475824^2 + 1608728000^2 &= 1234321\ 524176^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.715} \tag{5.724}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0487344^2 + 1432000^2 &= 1\ 512656^2 & 0474375^2 + 1450000^2 &= 1\ 525625^2 \\
12\ 0487344^2 + 15752000^2 &= 121\ 512656^2 & 12\ 0474375^2 + 15950000^2 &= 121\ 525625^2 \\
1232\ 0487344^2 + 158952000^2 &= 12321\ 512656^2 & 1232\ 0474375^2 + 160950000^2 &= 12321\ 525625^2 \\
123432\ 0487344^2 + 1590952000^2 &= 1234321\ 512656^2 & 123432\ 0474375^2 + 1610950000^2 &= 1234321\ 525625^2
\end{aligned} \tag{5.716} \tag{5.725}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0472924^2 + 1452000^2 &= 1\ 527076^2 \\
12\ 0472924^2 + 15972000^2 &= 121\ 527076^2 \\
1232\ 0472924^2 + 161172000^2 &= 12321\ 527076^2 \\
123432\ 0472924^2 + 1613172000^2 &= 1234321\ 527076^2 \quad (5.726)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0471471^2 + 1454000^2 &= 1\ 528529^2 \\
12\ 0471471^2 + 15994000^2 &= 121\ 528529^2 \\
1232\ 0471471^2 + 161394000^2 &= 12321\ 528529^2 \\
123432\ 0471471^2 + 1615394000^2 &= 1234321\ 528529^2 \quad (5.727)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0470016^2 + 1456000^2 &= 1\ 529984^2 \\
12\ 0470016^2 + 16016000^2 &= 121\ 529984^2 \\
1232\ 0470016^2 + 161616000^2 &= 12321\ 529984^2 \\
123432\ 0470016^2 + 1617616000^2 &= 1234321\ 529984^2 \quad (5.728)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0468559^2 + 1458000^2 &= 1\ 531441^2 \\
12\ 0468559^2 + 16038000^2 &= 121\ 531441^2 \\
1232\ 0468559^2 + 161838000^2 &= 12321\ 531441^2 \\
123432\ 0468559^2 + 1619838000^2 &= 1234321\ 531441^2 \quad (5.729)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0467100^2 + 1460000^2 &= 1\ 532900^2 \\
12\ 0467100^2 + 16060000^2 &= 121\ 532900^2 \\
1232\ 0467100^2 + 162060000^2 &= 12321\ 532900^2 \\
123432\ 0467100^2 + 1622060000^2 &= 1234321\ 532900^2 \quad (5.730)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0465639^2 + 1462000^2 &= 1\ 534361^2 \\
12\ 0465639^2 + 16082000^2 &= 121\ 534361^2 \\
1232\ 0465639^2 + 162282000^2 &= 12321\ 534361^2 \\
123432\ 0465639^2 + 1624282000^2 &= 1234321\ 534361^2 \quad (5.731)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0464176^2 + 1464000^2 &= 1\ 535824^2 \\
12\ 0464176^2 + 16104000^2 &= 121\ 535824^2 \\
1232\ 0464176^2 + 162504000^2 &= 12321\ 535824^2 \\
123432\ 0464176^2 + 1626504000^2 &= 1234321\ 535824^2 \quad (5.732)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0462711^2 + 1466000^2 &= 1\ 537289^2 \\
12\ 0462711^2 + 16126000^2 &= 121\ 537289^2 \\
1232\ 0462711^2 + 162726000^2 &= 12321\ 537289^2 \\
123432\ 0462711^2 + 1628726000^2 &= 1234321\ 537289^2 \quad (5.733)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0461244^2 + 1468000^2 &= 1\ 538756^2 \\
12\ 0461244^2 + 16148000^2 &= 121\ 538756^2 \\
1232\ 0461244^2 + 162948000^2 &= 12321\ 538756^2 \\
123432\ 0461244^2 + 1630948000^2 &= 1234321\ 538756^2 \quad (5.734)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0459775^2 + 1470000^2 &= 1\ 540225^2 \\
12\ 0459775^2 + 16170000^2 &= 121\ 540225^2 \\
1232\ 0459775^2 + 163170000^2 &= 12321\ 540225^2 \\
123432\ 0459775^2 + 1633170000^2 &= 1234321\ 540225^2 \quad (5.735)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0458304^2 + 1472000^2 &= 1\ 541696^2 \\
12\ 0458304^2 + 16192000^2 &= 121\ 541696^2 \\
1232\ 0458304^2 + 163392000^2 &= 12321\ 541696^2 \\
123432\ 0458304^2 + 1635392000^2 &= 1234321\ 541696^2 \quad (5.736)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0456831^2 + 1474000^2 &= 1\ 543169^2 \\
12\ 0456831^2 + 16214000^2 &= 121\ 543169^2 \\
1232\ 0456831^2 + 163614000^2 &= 12321\ 543169^2 \\
123432\ 0456831^2 + 1637614000^2 &= 1234321\ 543169^2 \quad (5.737)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0455356^2 + 1476000^2 &= 1\ 544644^2 \\
12\ 0455356^2 + 16236000^2 &= 121\ 544644^2 \\
1232\ 0455356^2 + 163836000^2 &= 12321\ 544644^2 \\
123432\ 0455356^2 + 1639836000^2 &= 1234321\ 544644^2 \quad (5.738)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0453879^2 + 1478000^2 &= 1\ 546121^2 \\
12\ 0453879^2 + 16258000^2 &= 121\ 546121^2 \\
1232\ 0453879^2 + 164058000^2 &= 12321\ 546121^2 \\
123432\ 0453879^2 + 1642058000^2 &= 1234321\ 546121^2 \quad (5.739)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0452400^2 + 1480000^2 &= 1\ 547600^2 \\
12\ 0452400^2 + 16280000^2 &= 121\ 547600^2 \\
1232\ 0452400^2 + 164280000^2 &= 12321\ 547600^2 \\
123432\ 0452400^2 + 1644280000^2 &= 1234321\ 547600^2 \quad (5.740)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0450919^2 + 1482000^2 &= 1\ 549081^2 \\
12\ 0450919^2 + 16302000^2 &= 121\ 549081^2 \\
1232\ 0450919^2 + 164502000^2 &= 12321\ 549081^2 \\
123432\ 0450919^2 + 1646502000^2 &= 1234321\ 549081^2 \quad (5.741)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0449436^2 + 1484000^2 &= 1\ 550564^2 \\
12\ 0449436^2 + 16324000^2 &= 121\ 550564^2 \\
1232\ 0449436^2 + 164724000^2 &= 12321\ 550564^2 \\
123432\ 0449436^2 + 1648724000^2 &= 1234321\ 550564^2 \quad (5.742)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0447951^2 + 1486000^2 &= 1\ 552049^2 \\
12\ 0447951^2 + 16346000^2 &= 121\ 552049^2 \\
1232\ 0447951^2 + 164946000^2 &= 12321\ 552049^2 \\
123432\ 0447951^2 + 1650946000^2 &= 1234321\ 552049^2 \quad (5.743)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0446464^2 + 1488000^2 &= 1\ 553536^2 \\
12\ 0446464^2 + 16368000^2 &= 121\ 553536^2 \\
1232\ 0446464^2 + 165168000^2 &= 12321\ 553536^2 \\
123432\ 0446464^2 + 1653168000^2 &= 1234321\ 553536^2 \quad (5.744)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0444975^2 + 1490000^2 &= 1\ 555025^2 \\
12\ 0444975^2 + 16390000^2 &= 121\ 555025^2 \\
1232\ 0444975^2 + 165390000^2 &= 12321\ 555025^2 \\
123432\ 0444975^2 + 1655390000^2 &= 1234321\ 555025^2 \quad (5.745)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0443484^2 + 1492000^2 &= 1\ 556516^2 \\
12\ 0443484^2 + 16412000^2 &= 121\ 556516^2 \\
1232\ 0443484^2 + 165612000^2 &= 12321\ 556516^2 \\
123432\ 0443484^2 + 1657612000^2 &= 1234321\ 556516^2 \quad (5.746)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0441991^2 + 1494000^2 &= 1\ 558009^2 \\
12\ 0441991^2 + 16434000^2 &= 121\ 558009^2 \\
1232\ 0441991^2 + 165834000^2 &= 12321\ 558009^2 \\
123432\ 0441991^2 + 1659834000^2 &= 1234321\ 558009^2 \quad (5.747)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0440496^2 + 1496000^2 &= 1\ 559504^2 \\
12\ 0440496^2 + 16456000^2 &= 121\ 559504^2 \\
1232\ 0440496^2 + 166056000^2 &= 12321\ 559504^2 \\
123432\ 0440496^2 + 1662056000^2 &= 1234321\ 559504^2 \quad (5.748)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0438999^2 + 1498000^2 &= 1\ 561001^2 \\
12\ 0438999^2 + 16478000^2 &= 121\ 561001^2 \\
1232\ 0438999^2 + 166278000^2 &= 12321\ 561001^2 \\
123432\ 0438999^2 + 1664278000^2 &= 1234321\ 561001^2 \quad (5.749)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0437500^2 + 1500000^2 &= 1\ 562500^2 \\
12\ 0437500^2 + 16500000^2 &= 121\ 562500^2 \\
1232\ 0437500^2 + 166500000^2 &= 12321\ 562500^2 \\
123432\ 0437500^2 + 1666500000^2 &= 1234321\ 562500^2 \quad (5.750)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0435999^2 + 1502000^2 &= 1\ 564001^2 \\
12\ 0435999^2 + 16522000^2 &= 121\ 564001^2 \\
1232\ 0435999^2 + 166722000^2 &= 12321\ 564001^2 \\
123432\ 0435999^2 + 1668722000^2 &= 1234321\ 564001^2 \quad (5.751)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0434496^2 + 1504000^2 &= 1\ 565504^2 \\
12\ 0434496^2 + 16544000^2 &= 121\ 565504^2 \\
1232\ 0434496^2 + 166944000^2 &= 12321\ 565504^2 \\
123432\ 0434496^2 + 1670944000^2 &= 1234321\ 565504^2 \quad (5.752)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0432991^2 + 1506000^2 &= 1\ 567009^2 \\
12\ 0432991^2 + 16566000^2 &= 121\ 567009^2 \\
1232\ 0432991^2 + 167166000^2 &= 12321\ 567009^2 \\
123432\ 0432991^2 + 1673166000^2 &= 1234321\ 567009^2 \quad (5.753)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0431484^2 + 1508000^2 &= 1\ 568516^2 \\
12\ 0431484^2 + 16588000^2 &= 121\ 568516^2 \\
1232\ 0431484^2 + 167388000^2 &= 12321\ 568516^2 \\
123432\ 0431484^2 + 1675388000^2 &= 1234321\ 568516^2 \quad (5.754)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0429975^2 + 1510000^2 &= 1\ 570025^2 \\
12\ 0429975^2 + 16610000^2 &= 121\ 570025^2 \\
1232\ 0429975^2 + 167610000^2 &= 12321\ 570025^2 \\
123432\ 0429975^2 + 1677610000^2 &= 1234321\ 570025^2 \quad (5.755)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0428464^2 + 1512000^2 &= 1\ 571536^2 \\
12\ 0428464^2 + 16632000^2 &= 121\ 571536^2 \\
1232\ 0428464^2 + 167832000^2 &= 12321\ 571536^2 \\
123432\ 0428464^2 + 1679832000^2 &= 1234321\ 571536^2 \quad (5.756)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0426951^2 + 1514000^2 &= 1\ 573049^2 \\
12\ 0426951^2 + 16654000^2 &= 121\ 573049^2 \\
1232\ 0426951^2 + 168054000^2 &= 12321\ 573049^2 \\
123432\ 0426951^2 + 1682054000^2 &= 1234321\ 573049^2 \quad (5.757)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0425436^2 + 1516000^2 &= 1\ 574564^2 \\
12\ 0425436^2 + 16676000^2 &= 121\ 574564^2 \\
1232\ 0425436^2 + 168276000^2 &= 12321\ 574564^2 \\
123432\ 0425436^2 + 1684276000^2 &= 1234321\ 574564^2 \quad (5.758)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0423919^2 + 1518000^2 &= 1\ 576081^2 \\
12\ 0423919^2 + 16698000^2 &= 121\ 576081^2 \\
1232\ 0423919^2 + 168498000^2 &= 12321\ 576081^2 \\
123432\ 0423919^2 + 1686498000^2 &= 1234321\ 576081^2 \quad (5.759)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0422400^2 + 1520000^2 &= 1\ 577600^2 \\
12\ 0422400^2 + 16720000^2 &= 121\ 577600^2 \\
1232\ 0422400^2 + 168720000^2 &= 12321\ 577600^2 \\
123432\ 0422400^2 + 1688720000^2 &= 1234321\ 577600^2 \quad (5.760)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0420879^2 + 1522000^2 &= 1\ 579121^2 \\
12\ 0420879^2 + 16742000^2 &= 121\ 579121^2 \\
1232\ 0420879^2 + 168942000^2 &= 12321\ 579121^2 \\
123432\ 0420879^2 + 1690942000^2 &= 1234321\ 579121^2 \quad (5.761)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0419356^2 + 1524000^2 &= 1\ 580644^2 \\
12\ 0419356^2 + 16764000^2 &= 121\ 580644^2 \\
1232\ 0419356^2 + 169164000^2 &= 12321\ 580644^2 \\
123432\ 0419356^2 + 1693164000^2 &= 1234321\ 580644^2 \quad (5.762)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0417831^2 + 1526000^2 &= 1\ 582169^2 \\
12\ 0417831^2 + 16786000^2 &= 121\ 582169^2 \\
1232\ 0417831^2 + 169386000^2 &= 12321\ 582169^2 \\
123432\ 0417831^2 + 1695386000^2 &= 1234321\ 582169^2 \quad (5.763)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0416304^2 + 1528000^2 &= 1\ 583696^2 \\
12\ 0416304^2 + 16808000^2 &= 121\ 583696^2 \\
1232\ 0416304^2 + 169608000^2 &= 12321\ 583696^2 \\
123432\ 0416304^2 + 1697608000^2 &= 1234321\ 583696^2 \quad (5.764)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0414775^2 + 1530000^2 &= 1\ 585225^2 \\
12\ 0414775^2 + 16830000^2 &= 121\ 585225^2 \\
1232\ 0414775^2 + 169830000^2 &= 12321\ 585225^2 \\
123432\ 0414775^2 + 1699830000^2 &= 1234321\ 585225^2 \quad (5.765)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0413244^2 + 1532000^2 &= 1\ 586756^2 \\
12\ 0413244^2 + 16852000^2 &= 121\ 586756^2 \\
1232\ 0413244^2 + 170052000^2 &= 12321\ 586756^2 \\
123432\ 0413244^2 + 1702052000^2 &= 1234321\ 586756^2 \quad (5.766)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0411711^2 + 1534000^2 &= 1\ 588289^2 \\
12\ 0411711^2 + 16874000^2 &= 121\ 588289^2 \\
1232\ 0411711^2 + 170274000^2 &= 12321\ 588289^2 \\
123432\ 0411711^2 + 1704274000^2 &= 1234321\ 588289^2 \quad (5.767)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0410176^2 + 1536000^2 &= 1\ 589824^2 \\
12\ 0410176^2 + 16896000^2 &= 121\ 589824^2 \\
1232\ 0410176^2 + 170496000^2 &= 12321\ 589824^2 \\
123432\ 0410176^2 + 1706496000^2 &= 1234321\ 589824^2 \quad (5.768)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0408639^2 + 1538000^2 &= 1\ 591361^2 \\
12\ 0408639^2 + 16918000^2 &= 121\ 591361^2 \\
1232\ 0408639^2 + 170718000^2 &= 12321\ 591361^2 \\
123432\ 0408639^2 + 1708718000^2 &= 1234321\ 591361^2 \quad (5.769)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0407100^2 + 1540000^2 &= 1\ 592900^2 \\
12\ 0407100^2 + 16940000^2 &= 121\ 592900^2 \\
1232\ 0407100^2 + 170940000^2 &= 12321\ 592900^2 \\
123432\ 0407100^2 + 1710940000^2 &= 1234321\ 592900^2 \quad (5.770)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0405559^2 + 1542000^2 &= 1\ 594441^2 \\
12\ 0405559^2 + 16962000^2 &= 121\ 594441^2 \\
1232\ 0405559^2 + 171162000^2 &= 12321\ 594441^2 \\
123432\ 0405559^2 + 1713162000^2 &= 1234321\ 594441^2 \quad (5.771)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0404016^2 + 1544000^2 &= 1\ 595984^2 \\
12\ 0404016^2 + 16984000^2 &= 121\ 595984^2 \\
1232\ 0404016^2 + 171384000^2 &= 12321\ 595984^2 \\
123432\ 0404016^2 + 1715384000^2 &= 1234321\ 595984^2 \quad (5.772)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0402471^2 + 1546000^2 &= 1\ 597529^2 \\
12\ 0402471^2 + 17006000^2 &= 121\ 597529^2 \\
1232\ 0402471^2 + 171606000^2 &= 12321\ 597529^2 \\
123432\ 0402471^2 + 1717606000^2 &= 1234321\ 597529^2 \quad (5.773)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0400924^2 + 1548000^2 &= 1\ 599076^2 \\
12\ 0400924^2 + 17028000^2 &= 121\ 599076^2 \\
1232\ 0400924^2 + 171828000^2 &= 12321\ 599076^2 \\
123432\ 0400924^2 + 1719828000^2 &= 1234321\ 599076^2 \quad (5.774)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0399375^2 + 1550000^2 &= 1\ 600625^2 \\
12\ 0399375^2 + 17050000^2 &= 121\ 600625^2 \\
1232\ 0399375^2 + 172050000^2 &= 12321\ 600625^2 \\
123432\ 0399375^2 + 1722050000^2 &= 1234321\ 600625^2 \quad (5.775)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0397824^2 + 1552000^2 &= 1\ 602176^2 \\
12\ 0397824^2 + 17072000^2 &= 121\ 602176^2 \\
1232\ 0397824^2 + 172272000^2 &= 12321\ 602176^2 \\
123432\ 0397824^2 + 1724272000^2 &= 1234321\ 602176^2 \quad (5.776)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0396271^2 + 1554000^2 &= 1\ 603729^2 \\
12\ 0396271^2 + 17094000^2 &= 121\ 603729^2 \\
1232\ 0396271^2 + 172494000^2 &= 12321\ 603729^2 \\
123432\ 0396271^2 + 1726494000^2 &= 1234321\ 603729^2 \quad (5.777)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0394716^2 + 1556000^2 &= 1\ 605284^2 \\
12\ 0394716^2 + 17116000^2 &= 121\ 605284^2 \\
1232\ 0394716^2 + 172716000^2 &= 12321\ 605284^2 \\
123432\ 0394716^2 + 1728716000^2 &= 1234321\ 605284^2 \quad (5.778)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0393159^2 + 1558000^2 &= 1\ 606841^2 \\
12\ 0393159^2 + 17138000^2 &= 121\ 606841^2 \\
1232\ 0393159^2 + 172938000^2 &= 12321\ 606841^2 \\
123432\ 0393159^2 + 1730938000^2 &= 1234321\ 606841^2 \quad (5.779)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0391600^2 + 1560000^2 &= 1\ 608400^2 & 0375900^2 + 1580000^2 &= 1\ 624100^2 \\
12\ 0391600^2 + 17160000^2 &= 121\ 608400^2 & 12\ 0375900^2 + 17380000^2 &= 121\ 624100^2 \\
1232\ 0391600^2 + 173160000^2 &= 12321\ 608400^2 & 1232\ 0375900^2 + 175380000^2 &= 12321\ 624100^2 \\
123432\ 0391600^2 + 1733160000^2 &= 1234321\ 608400^2 & 123432\ 0375900^2 + 1755380000^2 &= 1234321\ 624100^2 & (5.790) & (5.790)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0390039^2 + 1562000^2 &= 1\ 609961^2 & 0374319^2 + 1582000^2 &= 1\ 625681^2 \\
12\ 0390039^2 + 17182000^2 &= 121\ 609961^2 & 12\ 0374319^2 + 17402000^2 &= 121\ 625681^2 \\
1232\ 0390039^2 + 173382000^2 &= 12321\ 609961^2 & 1232\ 0374319^2 + 175602000^2 &= 12321\ 625681^2 \\
123432\ 0390039^2 + 1735382000^2 &= 1234321\ 609961^2 & 123432\ 0374319^2 + 1757602000^2 &= 1234321\ 625681^2 & (5.781) & (5.791)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0388476^2 + 1564000^2 &= 1\ 611524^2 & 0372736^2 + 1584000^2 &= 1\ 627264^2 \\
12\ 0388476^2 + 17204000^2 &= 121\ 611524^2 & 12\ 0372736^2 + 17424000^2 &= 121\ 627264^2 \\
1232\ 0388476^2 + 173604000^2 &= 12321\ 611524^2 & 1232\ 0372736^2 + 175824000^2 &= 12321\ 627264^2 \\
123432\ 0388476^2 + 1737604000^2 &= 1234321\ 611524^2 & 123432\ 0372736^2 + 1759824000^2 &= 1234321\ 627264^2 & (5.782) & (5.792)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0386911^2 + 1566000^2 &= 1\ 613089^2 & 0371151^2 + 1586000^2 &= 1\ 628849^2 \\
12\ 0386911^2 + 17226000^2 &= 121\ 613089^2 & 12\ 0371151^2 + 17446000^2 &= 121\ 628849^2 \\
1232\ 0386911^2 + 173826000^2 &= 12321\ 613089^2 & 1232\ 0371151^2 + 176046000^2 &= 12321\ 628849^2 \\
123432\ 0386911^2 + 1739826000^2 &= 1234321\ 613089^2 & 123432\ 0371151^2 + 1762046000^2 &= 1234321\ 628849^2 & (5.783) & (5.793)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0385344^2 + 1568000^2 &= 1\ 614656^2 & 0369564^2 + 1588000^2 &= 1\ 630436^2 \\
12\ 0385344^2 + 17248000^2 &= 121\ 614656^2 & 12\ 0369564^2 + 17468000^2 &= 121\ 630436^2 \\
1232\ 0385344^2 + 174048000^2 &= 12321\ 614656^2 & 1232\ 0369564^2 + 176268000^2 &= 12321\ 630436^2 \\
123432\ 0385344^2 + 1742048000^2 &= 1234321\ 614656^2 & 123432\ 0369564^2 + 1764268000^2 &= 1234321\ 630436^2 & (5.784) & (5.794)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0383775^2 + 1570000^2 &= 1\ 616225^2 & 0367975^2 + 1590000^2 &= 1\ 632025^2 \\
12\ 0383775^2 + 17270000^2 &= 121\ 616225^2 & 12\ 0367975^2 + 17490000^2 &= 121\ 632025^2 \\
1232\ 0383775^2 + 174270000^2 &= 12321\ 616225^2 & 1232\ 0367975^2 + 176490000^2 &= 12321\ 632025^2 \\
123432\ 0383775^2 + 1744270000^2 &= 1234321\ 616225^2 & 123432\ 0367975^2 + 1766490000^2 &= 1234321\ 632025^2 & (5.785) & (5.795)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0382204^2 + 1572000^2 &= 1\ 617796^2 & 0366384^2 + 1592000^2 &= 1\ 633616^2 \\
12\ 0382204^2 + 17292000^2 &= 121\ 617796^2 & 12\ 0366384^2 + 17512000^2 &= 121\ 633616^2 \\
1232\ 0382204^2 + 174492000^2 &= 12321\ 617796^2 & 1232\ 0366384^2 + 176712000^2 &= 12321\ 633616^2 \\
123432\ 0382204^2 + 1746492000^2 &= 1234321\ 617796^2 & 123432\ 0366384^2 + 1768712000^2 &= 1234321\ 633616^2 & (5.786) & (5.796)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0380631^2 + 1574000^2 &= 1\ 619369^2 & 0364791^2 + 1594000^2 &= 1\ 635209^2 \\
12\ 0380631^2 + 17314000^2 &= 121\ 619369^2 & 12\ 0364791^2 + 17534000^2 &= 121\ 635209^2 \\
1232\ 0380631^2 + 174714000^2 &= 12321\ 619369^2 & 1232\ 0364791^2 + 176934000^2 &= 12321\ 635209^2 \\
123432\ 0380631^2 + 1748714000^2 &= 1234321\ 619369^2 & 123432\ 0364791^2 + 1770934000^2 &= 1234321\ 635209^2 & (5.787) & (5.797)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0379056^2 + 1576000^2 &= 1\ 620944^2 & 0363196^2 + 1596000^2 &= 1\ 636804^2 \\
12\ 0379056^2 + 17336000^2 &= 121\ 620944^2 & 12\ 0363196^2 + 17556000^2 &= 121\ 636804^2 \\
1232\ 0379056^2 + 174936000^2 &= 12321\ 620944^2 & 1232\ 0363196^2 + 177156000^2 &= 12321\ 636804^2 \\
123432\ 0379056^2 + 1750936000^2 &= 1234321\ 620944^2 & 123432\ 0363196^2 + 1773156000^2 &= 1234321\ 636804^2 & (5.788) & (5.798)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0377479^2 + 1578000^2 &= 1\ 622521^2 & 0361599^2 + 1598000^2 &= 1\ 638401^2 \\
12\ 0377479^2 + 17358000^2 &= 121\ 622521^2 & 12\ 0361599^2 + 17578000^2 &= 121\ 638401^2 \\
1232\ 0377479^2 + 175158000^2 &= 12321\ 622521^2 & 1232\ 0361599^2 + 177378000^2 &= 12321\ 638401^2 \\
123432\ 0377479^2 + 1753158000^2 &= 1234321\ 622521^2 & 123432\ 0361599^2 + 1775378000^2 &= 1234321\ 638401^2 & (5.789) & (5.799)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0360000^2 + 1600000^2 &= 1\ 640000^2 \\
12\ 0360000^2 + 17600000^2 &= 121\ 640000^2 \\
1232\ 0360000^2 + 177600000^2 &= 12321\ 640000^2 \\
123432\ 0360000^2 + 1777600000^2 &= 1234321\ 640000^2 \quad (5.800)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0358399^2 + 1602000^2 &= 1\ 641601^2 \\
12\ 0358399^2 + 17622000^2 &= 121\ 641601^2 \\
1232\ 0358399^2 + 177822000^2 &= 12321\ 641601^2 \\
123432\ 0358399^2 + 1779822000^2 &= 1234321\ 641601^2 \quad (5.801)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0356796^2 + 1604000^2 &= 1\ 643204^2 \\
12\ 0356796^2 + 17644000^2 &= 121\ 643204^2 \\
1232\ 0356796^2 + 178044000^2 &= 12321\ 643204^2 \\
123432\ 0356796^2 + 1782044000^2 &= 1234321\ 643204^2 \quad (5.802)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0355191^2 + 1606000^2 &= 1\ 644809^2 \\
12\ 0355191^2 + 17666000^2 &= 121\ 644809^2 \\
1232\ 0355191^2 + 178266000^2 &= 12321\ 644809^2 \\
123432\ 0355191^2 + 1784266000^2 &= 1234321\ 644809^2 \quad (5.803)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0353584^2 + 1608000^2 &= 1\ 646416^2 \\
12\ 0353584^2 + 17688000^2 &= 121\ 646416^2 \\
1232\ 0353584^2 + 178488000^2 &= 12321\ 646416^2 \\
123432\ 0353584^2 + 1786488000^2 &= 1234321\ 646416^2 \quad (5.804)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0351975^2 + 1610000^2 &= 1\ 648025^2 \\
12\ 0351975^2 + 17710000^2 &= 121\ 648025^2 \\
1232\ 0351975^2 + 178710000^2 &= 12321\ 648025^2 \\
123432\ 0351975^2 + 1788710000^2 &= 1234321\ 648025^2 \quad (5.805)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0350364^2 + 1612000^2 &= 1\ 649636^2 \\
12\ 0350364^2 + 17732000^2 &= 121\ 649636^2 \\
1232\ 0350364^2 + 178932000^2 &= 12321\ 649636^2 \\
123432\ 0350364^2 + 1790932000^2 &= 1234321\ 649636^2 \quad (5.806)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0348751^2 + 1614000^2 &= 1\ 651249^2 \\
12\ 0348751^2 + 17754000^2 &= 121\ 651249^2 \\
1232\ 0348751^2 + 179154000^2 &= 12321\ 651249^2 \\
123432\ 0348751^2 + 1793154000^2 &= 1234321\ 651249^2 \quad (5.807)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0347136^2 + 1616000^2 &= 1\ 652864^2 \\
12\ 0347136^2 + 17776000^2 &= 121\ 652864^2 \\
1232\ 0347136^2 + 179376000^2 &= 12321\ 652864^2 \\
123432\ 0347136^2 + 1795376000^2 &= 1234321\ 652864^2 \quad (5.808)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0345519^2 + 1618000^2 &= 1\ 654481^2 \\
12\ 0345519^2 + 17798000^2 &= 121\ 654481^2 \\
1232\ 0345519^2 + 179598000^2 &= 12321\ 654481^2 \\
123432\ 0345519^2 + 1797598000^2 &= 1234321\ 654481^2 \quad (5.809)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0343900^2 + 1620000^2 &= 1\ 656100^2 \\
12\ 0343900^2 + 17820000^2 &= 121\ 656100^2 \\
1232\ 0343900^2 + 179820000^2 &= 12321\ 656100^2 \\
123432\ 0343900^2 + 1799820000^2 &= 1234321\ 656100^2 \quad (5.810)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0342279^2 + 1622000^2 &= 1\ 657721^2 \\
12\ 0342279^2 + 17842000^2 &= 121\ 657721^2 \\
1232\ 0342279^2 + 180042000^2 &= 12321\ 657721^2 \\
123432\ 0342279^2 + 1802042000^2 &= 1234321\ 657721^2 \quad (5.811)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0340656^2 + 1624000^2 &= 1\ 659344^2 \\
12\ 0340656^2 + 17864000^2 &= 121\ 659344^2 \\
1232\ 0340656^2 + 180264000^2 &= 12321\ 659344^2 \\
123432\ 0340656^2 + 1804264000^2 &= 1234321\ 659344^2 \quad (5.812)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0339031^2 + 1626000^2 &= 1\ 660969^2 \\
12\ 0339031^2 + 17886000^2 &= 121\ 660969^2 \\
1232\ 0339031^2 + 180486000^2 &= 12321\ 660969^2 \\
123432\ 0339031^2 + 1806486000^2 &= 1234321\ 660969^2 \quad (5.813)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0337404^2 + 1628000^2 &= 1\ 662596^2 \\
12\ 0337404^2 + 17908000^2 &= 121\ 662596^2 \\
1232\ 0337404^2 + 180708000^2 &= 12321\ 662596^2 \\
123432\ 0337404^2 + 1808708000^2 &= 1234321\ 662596^2 \quad (5.814)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0335775^2 + 1630000^2 &= 1\ 664225^2 \\
12\ 0335775^2 + 17930000^2 &= 121\ 664225^2 \\
1232\ 0335775^2 + 180930000^2 &= 12321\ 664225^2 \\
123432\ 0335775^2 + 1810930000^2 &= 1234321\ 664225^2 \quad (5.815)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0334144^2 + 1632000^2 &= 1\ 665856^2 \\
12\ 0334144^2 + 17952000^2 &= 121\ 665856^2 \\
1232\ 0334144^2 + 181152000^2 &= 12321\ 665856^2 \\
123432\ 0334144^2 + 1813152000^2 &= 1234321\ 665856^2 \quad (5.816)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0332511^2 + 1634000^2 &= 1\ 667489^2 \\
12\ 0332511^2 + 17974000^2 &= 121\ 667489^2 \\
1232\ 0332511^2 + 181374000^2 &= 12321\ 667489^2 \\
123432\ 0332511^2 + 1815374000^2 &= 1234321\ 667489^2 \quad (5.817)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0330876^2 + 1636000^2 &= 1\ 669124^2 \\
12\ 0330876^2 + 17996000^2 &= 121\ 669124^2 \\
1232\ 0330876^2 + 181596000^2 &= 12321\ 669124^2 \\
123432\ 0330876^2 + 1817596000^2 &= 1234321\ 669124^2 \quad (5.818)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0329239^2 + 1638000^2 &= 1\ 670761^2 \\
12\ 0329239^2 + 18018000^2 &= 121\ 670761^2 \\
1232\ 0329239^2 + 181818000^2 &= 12321\ 670761^2 \\
123432\ 0329239^2 + 1819818000^2 &= 1234321\ 670761^2 \quad (5.819)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0327600^2 + 1640000^2 &= 1\ 672400^2 \\
12\ 0327600^2 + 18040000^2 &= 121\ 672400^2 \\
1232\ 0327600^2 + 182040000^2 &= 12321\ 672400^2 \\
123432\ 0327600^2 + 1822040000^2 &= 1234321\ 672400^2 \quad (5.820)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0325959^2 + 1642000^2 &= 1\ 674041^2 \\
12\ 0325959^2 + 18062000^2 &= 121\ 674041^2 \\
1232\ 0325959^2 + 182262000^2 &= 12321\ 674041^2 \\
123432\ 0325959^2 + 1824262000^2 &= 1234321\ 674041^2 \quad (5.821)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0324316^2 + 1644000^2 &= 1\ 675684^2 \\
12\ 0324316^2 + 18084000^2 &= 121\ 675684^2 \\
1232\ 0324316^2 + 182484000^2 &= 12321\ 675684^2 \\
123432\ 0324316^2 + 1826484000^2 &= 1234321\ 675684^2 \quad (5.822)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0322671^2 + 1646000^2 &= 1\ 677329^2 \\
12\ 0322671^2 + 18106000^2 &= 121\ 677329^2 \\
1232\ 0322671^2 + 182706000^2 &= 12321\ 677329^2 \\
123432\ 0322671^2 + 1828706000^2 &= 1234321\ 677329^2 \quad (5.823)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0321024^2 + 1648000^2 &= 1\ 678976^2 \\
12\ 0321024^2 + 18128000^2 &= 121\ 678976^2 \\
1232\ 0321024^2 + 182928000^2 &= 12321\ 678976^2 \\
123432\ 0321024^2 + 1830928000^2 &= 1234321\ 678976^2 \quad (5.824)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0319375^2 + 1650000^2 &= 1\ 680625^2 \\
12\ 0319375^2 + 18150000^2 &= 121\ 680625^2 \\
1232\ 0319375^2 + 183150000^2 &= 12321\ 680625^2 \\
123432\ 0319375^2 + 1833150000^2 &= 1234321\ 680625^2 \quad (5.825)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0317724^2 + 1652000^2 &= 1\ 682276^2 \\
12\ 0317724^2 + 18172000^2 &= 121\ 682276^2 \\
1232\ 0317724^2 + 183372000^2 &= 12321\ 682276^2 \\
123432\ 0317724^2 + 1835372000^2 &= 1234321\ 682276^2 \quad (5.826)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0316071^2 + 1654000^2 &= 1\ 683929^2 \\
12\ 0316071^2 + 18194000^2 &= 121\ 683929^2 \\
1232\ 0316071^2 + 183594000^2 &= 12321\ 683929^2 \\
123432\ 0316071^2 + 1837594000^2 &= 1234321\ 683929^2 \quad (5.827)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0314416^2 + 1656000^2 &= 1\ 685584^2 \\
12\ 0314416^2 + 18216000^2 &= 121\ 685584^2 \\
1232\ 0314416^2 + 183816000^2 &= 12321\ 685584^2 \\
123432\ 0314416^2 + 1839816000^2 &= 1234321\ 685584^2 \quad (5.828)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0312759^2 + 1658000^2 &= 1\ 687241^2 \\
12\ 0312759^2 + 18238000^2 &= 121\ 687241^2 \\
1232\ 0312759^2 + 184038000^2 &= 12321\ 687241^2 \\
123432\ 0312759^2 + 1842038000^2 &= 1234321\ 687241^2 \quad (5.829)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0311100^2 + 1660000^2 &= 1\ 688900^2 \\
12\ 0311100^2 + 18260000^2 &= 121\ 688900^2 \\
1232\ 0311100^2 + 184260000^2 &= 12321\ 688900^2 \\
123432\ 0311100^2 + 1844260000^2 &= 1234321\ 688900^2 \quad (5.830)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0309439^2 + 1662000^2 &= 1\ 690561^2 \\
12\ 0309439^2 + 18282000^2 &= 121\ 690561^2 \\
1232\ 0309439^2 + 184482000^2 &= 12321\ 690561^2 \\
123432\ 0309439^2 + 1846482000^2 &= 1234321\ 690561^2 \quad (5.831)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0307776^2 + 1664000^2 &= 1\ 692224^2 \\
12\ 0307776^2 + 18304000^2 &= 121\ 692224^2 \\
1232\ 0307776^2 + 184704000^2 &= 12321\ 692224^2 \\
123432\ 0307776^2 + 1848704000^2 &= 1234321\ 692224^2 \quad (5.832)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0306111^2 + 1666000^2 &= 1\ 693889^2 \\
12\ 0306111^2 + 18326000^2 &= 121\ 693889^2 \\
1232\ 0306111^2 + 184926000^2 &= 12321\ 693889^2 \\
123432\ 0306111^2 + 1850926000^2 &= 1234321\ 693889^2 \quad (5.833)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0304444^2 + 1668000^2 &= 1\ 695556^2 \\
12\ 0304444^2 + 18348000^2 &= 121\ 695556^2 \\
1232\ 0304444^2 + 185148000^2 &= 12321\ 695556^2 \\
123432\ 0304444^2 + 1853148000^2 &= 1234321\ 695556^2 \quad (5.834)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0302775^2 + 1670000^2 &= 1\ 697225^2 \\
12\ 0302775^2 + 18370000^2 &= 121\ 697225^2 \\
1232\ 0302775^2 + 185370000^2 &= 12321\ 697225^2 \\
123432\ 0302775^2 + 1855370000^2 &= 1234321\ 697225^2 \quad (5.835)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0301104^2 + 1672000^2 &= 1\ 698896^2 \\
12\ 0301104^2 + 18392000^2 &= 121\ 698896^2 \\
1232\ 0301104^2 + 185592000^2 &= 12321\ 698896^2 \\
123432\ 0301104^2 + 1857592000^2 &= 1234321\ 698896^2 \quad (5.836)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0299431^2 + 1674000^2 &= 1\ 700569^2 \\
12\ 0299431^2 + 18414000^2 &= 121\ 700569^2 \\
1232\ 0299431^2 + 185814000^2 &= 12321\ 700569^2 \\
123432\ 0299431^2 + 1859814000^2 &= 1234321\ 700569^2 \quad (5.837)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0297756^2 + 1676000^2 &= 1\ 702244^2 \\
12\ 0297756^2 + 18436000^2 &= 121\ 702244^2 \\
1232\ 0297756^2 + 186036000^2 &= 12321\ 702244^2 \\
123432\ 0297756^2 + 1862036000^2 &= 1234321\ 702244^2 \quad (5.838)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0296079^2 + 1678000^2 &= 1\ 703921^2 \\
12\ 0296079^2 + 18458000^2 &= 121\ 703921^2 \\
1232\ 0296079^2 + 186258000^2 &= 12321\ 703921^2 \\
123432\ 0296079^2 + 1864258000^2 &= 1234321\ 703921^2 \quad (5.839)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0294400^2 + 1680000^2 &= 1\ 705600^2 \\
12\ 0294400^2 + 18480000^2 &= 121\ 705600^2 \\
1232\ 0294400^2 + 186480000^2 &= 12321\ 705600^2 \\
123432\ 0294400^2 + 1866480000^2 &= 1234321\ 705600^2 \quad (5.840)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0292719^2 + 1682000^2 &= 1\ 707281^2 \\
12\ 0292719^2 + 18502000^2 &= 121\ 707281^2 \\
1232\ 0292719^2 + 186702000^2 &= 12321\ 707281^2 \\
123432\ 0292719^2 + 1868702000^2 &= 1234321\ 707281^2 \quad (5.841)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0291036^2 + 1684000^2 &= 1\ 708964^2 \\
12\ 0291036^2 + 18524000^2 &= 121\ 708964^2 \\
1232\ 0291036^2 + 186924000^2 &= 12321\ 708964^2 \\
123432\ 0291036^2 + 1870924000^2 &= 1234321\ 708964^2 \quad (5.842)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0289351^2 + 1686000^2 &= 1\ 710649^2 \\
12\ 0289351^2 + 18546000^2 &= 121\ 710649^2 \\
1232\ 0289351^2 + 187146000^2 &= 12321\ 710649^2 \\
123432\ 0289351^2 + 1873146000^2 &= 1234321\ 710649^2 \quad (5.843)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0287664^2 + 1688000^2 &= 1\ 712336^2 \\
12\ 0287664^2 + 18568000^2 &= 121\ 712336^2 \\
1232\ 0287664^2 + 187368000^2 &= 12321\ 712336^2 \\
123432\ 0287664^2 + 1875368000^2 &= 1234321\ 712336^2 \quad (5.844)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0285975^2 + 1690000^2 &= 1\ 714025^2 \\
12\ 0285975^2 + 18590000^2 &= 121\ 714025^2 \\
1232\ 0285975^2 + 187590000^2 &= 12321\ 714025^2 \\
123432\ 0285975^2 + 1877590000^2 &= 1234321\ 714025^2 \quad (5.845)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0284284^2 + 1692000^2 &= 1\ 715716^2 \\
12\ 0284284^2 + 18612000^2 &= 121\ 715716^2 \\
1232\ 0284284^2 + 187812000^2 &= 12321\ 715716^2 \\
123432\ 0284284^2 + 1879812000^2 &= 1234321\ 715716^2 \quad (5.846)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0282591^2 + 1694000^2 &= 1\ 717409^2 \\
12\ 0282591^2 + 18634000^2 &= 121\ 717409^2 \\
1232\ 0282591^2 + 188034000^2 &= 12321\ 717409^2 \\
123432\ 0282591^2 + 1882034000^2 &= 1234321\ 717409^2 \quad (5.847)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0280896^2 + 1696000^2 &= 1\ 719104^2 \\
12\ 0280896^2 + 18656000^2 &= 121\ 719104^2 \\
1232\ 0280896^2 + 188256000^2 &= 12321\ 719104^2 \\
123432\ 0280896^2 + 1884256000^2 &= 1234321\ 719104^2 \quad (5.848)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0279199^2 + 1698000^2 &= 1\ 720801^2 \\
12\ 0279199^2 + 18678000^2 &= 121\ 720801^2 \\
1232\ 0279199^2 + 188478000^2 &= 12321\ 720801^2 \\
123432\ 0279199^2 + 1886478000^2 &= 1234321\ 720801^2 \quad (5.849)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0277500^2 + 1700000^2 &= 1\ 722500^2 \\
12\ 0277500^2 + 18700000^2 &= 121\ 722500^2 \\
1232\ 0277500^2 + 188700000^2 &= 12321\ 722500^2 \\
123432\ 0277500^2 + 1888700000^2 &= 1234321\ 722500^2 \quad (5.850)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0275799^2 + 1702000^2 &= 1\ 724201^2 \\
12\ 0275799^2 + 18722000^2 &= 121\ 724201^2 \\
1232\ 0275799^2 + 188922000^2 &= 12321\ 724201^2 \\
123432\ 0275799^2 + 1890922000^2 &= 1234321\ 724201^2 \quad (5.851)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0274096^2 + 1704000^2 &= 1\ 725904^2 \\
12\ 0274096^2 + 18744000^2 &= 121\ 725904^2 \\
1232\ 0274096^2 + 189144000^2 &= 12321\ 725904^2 \\
123432\ 0274096^2 + 1893144000^2 &= 1234321\ 725904^2 \quad (5.852)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0272391^2 + 1706000^2 &= 1\ 727609^2 \\
12\ 0272391^2 + 18766000^2 &= 121\ 727609^2 \\
1232\ 0272391^2 + 189366000^2 &= 12321\ 727609^2 \\
123432\ 0272391^2 + 1895366000^2 &= 1234321\ 727609^2 \quad (5.853)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0270684^2 + 1708000^2 &= 1729316^2 \\
120270684^2 + 18788000^2 &= 121729316^2 \\
12320270684^2 + 189588000^2 &= 12321729316^2 \\
1234320270684^2 + 1897588000^2 &= 1234321729316^2 \quad (5.854)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0268975^2 + 1710000^2 &= 1731025^2 \\
120268975^2 + 18810000^2 &= 121731025^2 \\
12320268975^2 + 189810000^2 &= 12321731025^2 \\
1234320268975^2 + 1899810000^2 &= 1234321731025^2 \quad (5.855)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0267264^2 + 1712000^2 &= 1732736^2 \\
120267264^2 + 18832000^2 &= 121732736^2 \\
12320267264^2 + 190032000^2 &= 12321732736^2 \\
1234320267264^2 + 1902032000^2 &= 1234321732736^2 \quad (5.856)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0265551^2 + 1714000^2 &= 1734449^2 \\
120265551^2 + 18854000^2 &= 121734449^2 \\
12320265551^2 + 190254000^2 &= 12321734449^2 \\
1234320265551^2 + 1904254000^2 &= 1234321734449^2 \quad (5.857)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0263836^2 + 1716000^2 &= 1736164^2 \\
120263836^2 + 18876000^2 &= 121736164^2 \\
12320263836^2 + 190476000^2 &= 12321736164^2 \\
1234320263836^2 + 1906476000^2 &= 1234321736164^2 \quad (5.858)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0262119^2 + 1718000^2 &= 1737881^2 \\
120262119^2 + 18898000^2 &= 121737881^2 \\
12320262119^2 + 190698000^2 &= 12321737881^2 \\
1234320262119^2 + 1908698000^2 &= 1234321737881^2 \quad (5.859)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0260400^2 + 1720000^2 &= 1739600^2 \\
120260400^2 + 18920000^2 &= 121739600^2 \\
12320260400^2 + 190920000^2 &= 12321739600^2 \\
1234320260400^2 + 1910920000^2 &= 1234321739600^2 \quad (5.860)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0258679^2 + 1722000^2 &= 1741321^2 \\
120258679^2 + 18942000^2 &= 121741321^2 \\
12320258679^2 + 191142000^2 &= 12321741321^2 \\
1234320258679^2 + 1913142000^2 &= 1234321741321^2 \quad (5.861)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0256956^2 + 1724000^2 &= 1743044^2 \\
120256956^2 + 18964000^2 &= 121743044^2 \\
12320256956^2 + 191364000^2 &= 12321743044^2 \\
1234320256956^2 + 1915364000^2 &= 1234321743044^2 \quad (5.862)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0255231^2 + 1726000^2 &= 1744769^2 \\
120255231^2 + 18986000^2 &= 121744769^2 \\
12320255231^2 + 191586000^2 &= 12321744769^2 \\
1234320255231^2 + 1917586000^2 &= 1234321744769^2 \quad (5.863)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0253504^2 + 1728000^2 &= 1746496^2 \\
120253504^2 + 19008000^2 &= 121746496^2 \\
12320253504^2 + 191808000^2 &= 12321746496^2 \\
1234320253504^2 + 1919808000^2 &= 1234321746496^2 \quad (5.864)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0251775^2 + 1730000^2 &= 1748225^2 \\
120251775^2 + 19030000^2 &= 121748225^2 \\
12320251775^2 + 192030000^2 &= 12321748225^2 \\
1234320251775^2 + 1922030000^2 &= 1234321748225^2 \quad (5.865)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0250044^2 + 1732000^2 &= 1749956^2 \\
120250044^2 + 19052000^2 &= 121749956^2 \\
12320250044^2 + 192252000^2 &= 12321749956^2 \\
1234320250044^2 + 1924252000^2 &= 1234321749956^2 \quad (5.866)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0248311^2 + 1734000^2 &= 1751689^2 \\
120248311^2 + 19074000^2 &= 121751689^2 \\
12320248311^2 + 192474000^2 &= 12321751689^2 \\
1234320248311^2 + 1926474000^2 &= 1234321751689^2 \quad (5.867)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0246576^2 + 1736000^2 &= 1753424^2 \\
120246576^2 + 19096000^2 &= 121753424^2 \\
12320246576^2 + 192696000^2 &= 12321753424^2 \\
1234320246576^2 + 1928696000^2 &= 1234321753424^2 \quad (5.868)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0244839^2 + 1738000^2 &= 1755161^2 \\
120244839^2 + 19118000^2 &= 121755161^2 \\
12320244839^2 + 192918000^2 &= 12321755161^2 \\
1234320244839^2 + 1930918000^2 &= 1234321755161^2 \quad (5.869)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0243100^2 + 1740000^2 &= 1756900^2 \\
120243100^2 + 19140000^2 &= 121756900^2 \\
12320243100^2 + 193140000^2 &= 12321756900^2 \\
1234320243100^2 + 1933140000^2 &= 1234321756900^2 \quad (5.870)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0241359^2 + 1742000^2 &= 1758641^2 \\
120241359^2 + 19162000^2 &= 121758641^2 \\
12320241359^2 + 193362000^2 &= 12321758641^2 \\
1234320241359^2 + 1935362000^2 &= 1234321758641^2 \quad (5.871)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0239616^2 + 1744000^2 &= 1760384^2 \\
120239616^2 + 19184000^2 &= 121760384^2 \\
12320239616^2 + 193584000^2 &= 12321760384^2 \\
1234320239616^2 + 1937584000^2 &= 1234321760384^2 \quad (5.872)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0237871^2 + 1746000^2 &= 1762129^2 \\
120237871^2 + 19206000^2 &= 121762129^2 \\
12320237871^2 + 193806000^2 &= 12321762129^2 \\
1234320237871^2 + 1939806000^2 &= 1234321762129^2 \quad (5.873)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0236124^2 + 1748000^2 &= 1763876^2 \\
120236124^2 + 19228000^2 &= 121763876^2 \\
12320236124^2 + 194028000^2 &= 12321763876^2 \\
1234320236124^2 + 1942028000^2 &= 1234321763876^2 \quad (5.874)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0234375^2 + 1750000^2 &= 1765625^2 \\
120234375^2 + 19250000^2 &= 121765625^2 \\
12320234375^2 + 194250000^2 &= 12321765625^2 \\
1234320234375^2 + 1944250000^2 &= 1234321765625^2 \quad (5.875)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0232624^2 + 1752000^2 &= 1767376^2 \\
120232624^2 + 19272000^2 &= 121767376^2 \\
12320232624^2 + 194472000^2 &= 12321767376^2 \\
1234320232624^2 + 1946472000^2 &= 1234321767376^2 \quad (5.876)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0230871^2 + 1754000^2 &= 1769129^2 \\
120230871^2 + 19294000^2 &= 121769129^2 \\
12320230871^2 + 194694000^2 &= 12321769129^2 \\
1234320230871^2 + 1948694000^2 &= 1234321769129^2 \quad (5.877)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0229116^2 + 1756000^2 &= 1770884^2 \\
120229116^2 + 19316000^2 &= 121770884^2 \\
12320229116^2 + 194916000^2 &= 12321770884^2 \\
1234320229116^2 + 1950916000^2 &= 1234321770884^2 \quad (5.878)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0227359^2 + 1758000^2 &= 1772641^2 \\
120227359^2 + 19338000^2 &= 121772641^2 \\
12320227359^2 + 195138000^2 &= 12321772641^2 \\
1234320227359^2 + 1953138000^2 &= 1234321772641^2 \quad (5.879)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0225600^2 + 1760000^2 &= 1774400^2 \\
120225600^2 + 19360000^2 &= 121774400^2 \\
12320225600^2 + 195360000^2 &= 12321774400^2 \\
1234320225600^2 + 1955360000^2 &= 1234321774400^2 \quad (5.880)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0223839^2 + 1762000^2 &= 1776161^2 \\
120223839^2 + 19382000^2 &= 121776161^2 \\
12320223839^2 + 195582000^2 &= 12321776161^2 \\
1234320223839^2 + 1957582000^2 &= 1234321776161^2 \quad (5.881)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0222076^2 + 1764000^2 &= 1777924^2 \\
120222076^2 + 19404000^2 &= 121777924^2 \\
12320222076^2 + 195804000^2 &= 12321777924^2 \\
1234320222076^2 + 1959804000^2 &= 1234321777924^2 \quad (5.882)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0220311^2 + 1766000^2 &= 1779689^2 \\
120220311^2 + 19426000^2 &= 121779689^2 \\
12320220311^2 + 196026000^2 &= 12321779689^2 \\
1234320220311^2 + 1962026000^2 &= 1234321779689^2 \quad (5.883)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0218544^2 + 1768000^2 &= 1781456^2 \\
120218544^2 + 19448000^2 &= 121781456^2 \\
12320218544^2 + 196248000^2 &= 12321781456^2 \\
1234320218544^2 + 1964248000^2 &= 1234321781456^2 \quad (5.884)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0216775^2 + 1770000^2 &= 1783225^2 \\
120216775^2 + 19470000^2 &= 121783225^2 \\
12320216775^2 + 196470000^2 &= 12321783225^2 \\
1234320216775^2 + 1966470000^2 &= 1234321783225^2 \quad (5.885)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0215004^2 + 1772000^2 &= 1784996^2 \\
120215004^2 + 19492000^2 &= 121784996^2 \\
12320215004^2 + 196692000^2 &= 12321784996^2 \\
1234320215004^2 + 1968692000^2 &= 1234321784996^2 \quad (5.886)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0213231^2 + 1774000^2 &= 1786769^2 \\
120213231^2 + 19514000^2 &= 121786769^2 \\
12320213231^2 + 196914000^2 &= 12321786769^2 \\
1234320213231^2 + 1970914000^2 &= 1234321786769^2 \quad (5.887)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0211456^2 + 1776000^2 &= 1788544^2 \\
120211456^2 + 19536000^2 &= 121788544^2 \\
12320211456^2 + 197136000^2 &= 12321788544^2 \\
1234320211456^2 + 1973136000^2 &= 1234321788544^2 \quad (5.888)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0209679^2 + 1778000^2 &= 1790321^2 \\
120209679^2 + 19558000^2 &= 121790321^2 \\
12320209679^2 + 197358000^2 &= 12321790321^2 \\
1234320209679^2 + 1975358000^2 &= 1234321790321^2 \quad (5.889)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0207900^2 + 1780000^2 &= 1792100^2 & 0198975^2 + 1790000^2 &= 1801025^2 \\
120207900^2 + 19580000^2 &= 121792100^2 & 120198975^2 + 19690000^2 &= 121801025^2 \\
12320207900^2 + 197580000^2 &= 12321792100^2 & 12320198975^2 + 198690000^2 &= 12321801025^2 \\
1234320207900^2 + 1977580000^2 &= 1234321792100^2 & 1234320198975^2 + 1988690000^2 &= 1234321801025^2 \quad (5.895)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0206119^2 + 1782000^2 &= 1793881^2 & 0197184^2 + 1792000^2 &= 1802816^2 \\
120206119^2 + 19602000^2 &= 121793881^2 & 120197184^2 + 19712000^2 &= 121802816^2 \\
12320206119^2 + 197802000^2 &= 12321793881^2 & 12320197184^2 + 198912000^2 &= 12321802816^2 \\
1234320206119^2 + 1979802000^2 &= 1234321793881^2 & 1234320197184^2 + 1990912000^2 &= 1234321802816^2 \quad (5.896)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0204336^2 + 1784000^2 &= 1795664^2 & 0195391^2 + 1794000^2 &= 1804609^2 \\
120204336^2 + 19624000^2 &= 121795664^2 & 120195391^2 + 19734000^2 &= 121804609^2 \\
12320204336^2 + 198024000^2 &= 12321795664^2 & 12320195391^2 + 199134000^2 &= 12321804609^2 \\
1234320204336^2 + 1982024000^2 &= 1234321795664^2 & 1234320195391^2 + 1993134000^2 &= 1234321804609^2 \quad (5.897)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0202551^2 + 1786000^2 &= 1797449^2 & 0193596^2 + 1796000^2 &= 1806404^2 \\
120202551^2 + 19646000^2 &= 121797449^2 & 120193596^2 + 19756000^2 &= 121806404^2 \\
12320202551^2 + 198246000^2 &= 12321797449^2 & 12320193596^2 + 199356000^2 &= 12321806404^2 \\
1234320202551^2 + 1984246000^2 &= 1234321797449^2 & 1234320193596^2 + 1995356000^2 &= 1234321806404^2 \quad (5.898)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0200764^2 + 1788000^2 &= 1799236^2 & 0191799^2 + 1798000^2 &= 1808201^2 \\
120200764^2 + 19668000^2 &= 121799236^2 & 120191799^2 + 19778000^2 &= 121808201^2 \\
12320200764^2 + 198468000^2 &= 12321799236^2 & 12320191799^2 + 199578000^2 &= 12321808201^2 \\
1234320200764^2 + 1986468000^2 &= 1234321799236^2 & 1234320191799^2 + 1997578000^2 &= 1234321808201^2 \quad (5.899)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0190000^2 + 1800000^2 &= 1810000^2 & 0182784^2 + 1808000^2 &= 1817216^2 \\
120190000^2 + 19800000^2 &= 121810000^2 & 120182784^2 + 19888000^2 &= 121817216^2 \\
12320190000^2 + 199800000^2 &= 12321810000^2 & 12320182784^2 + 200688000^2 &= 12321817216^2 \\
1234320190000^2 + 1999800000^2 &= 1234321810000^2 & 1234320182784^2 + 2008688000^2 &= 1234321817216^2 \quad (5.904)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0188199^2 + 1802000^2 &= 1811801^2 & 0180975^2 + 1810000^2 &= 1819025^2 \\
120188199^2 + 19822000^2 &= 121811801^2 & 120180975^2 + 19910000^2 &= 121819025^2 \\
12320188199^2 + 200022000^2 &= 12321811801^2 & 12320180975^2 + 200910000^2 &= 12321819025^2 \\
1234320188199^2 + 2002022000^2 &= 1234321811801^2 & 1234320180975^2 + 2010910000^2 &= 1234321819025^2 \quad (5.905)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0186396^2 + 1804000^2 &= 1813604^2 & 0179164^2 + 1812000^2 &= 1820836^2 \\
120186396^2 + 19844000^2 &= 121813604^2 & 120179164^2 + 19932000^2 &= 121820836^2 \\
12320186396^2 + 200244000^2 &= 12321813604^2 & 12320179164^2 + 201132000^2 &= 12321820836^2 \\
1234320186396^2 + 2004244000^2 &= 1234321813604^2 & 1234320179164^2 + 2013132000^2 &= 1234321820836^2 \quad (5.906)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0184591^2 + 1806000^2 &= 1815409^2 & 0177351^2 + 1814000^2 &= 1822649^2 \\
120184591^2 + 19866000^2 &= 121815409^2 & 120177351^2 + 19954000^2 &= 121822649^2 \\
12320184591^2 + 200466000^2 &= 12321815409^2 & 12320177351^2 + 201354000^2 &= 12321822649^2 \\
1234320184591^2 + 2006466000^2 &= 1234321815409^2 & 1234320177351^2 + 2015354000^2 &= 1234321822649^2 \quad (5.907)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0175536^2 + 1816000^2 &= 1824464^2 & 0159111^2 + 1834000^2 &= 1840889^2 \\
120175536^2 + 19976000^2 &= 121824464^2 & 120159111^2 + 20174000^2 &= 121840889^2 \\
12320175536^2 + 201576000^2 &= 12321824464^2 & 12320159111^2 + 203574000^2 &= 12321840889^2 \\
1234320175536^2 + 2017576000^2 &= 1234321824464^2 & 1234320159111^2 + 2037574000^2 &= 1234321840889^2 & (5.917)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0173719^2 + 1818000^2 &= 1826281^2 & 0157276^2 + 1836000^2 &= 1842724^2 \\
120173719^2 + 19998000^2 &= 121826281^2 & 120157276^2 + 20196000^2 &= 121842724^2 \\
12320173719^2 + 201798000^2 &= 12321826281^2 & 12320157276^2 + 203796000^2 &= 12321842724^2 \\
1234320173719^2 + 2019798000^2 &= 1234321826281^2 & 1234320157276^2 + 2039796000^2 &= 1234321842724^2 & (5.918)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0171900^2 + 1820000^2 &= 1828100^2 & 0155439^2 + 1838000^2 &= 1844561^2 \\
120171900^2 + 20020000^2 &= 121828100^2 & 120155439^2 + 20218000^2 &= 121844561^2 \\
12320171900^2 + 202020000^2 &= 12321828100^2 & 12320155439^2 + 204018000^2 &= 12321844561^2 \\
1234320171900^2 + 2022020000^2 &= 1234321828100^2 & 1234320155439^2 + 2042018000^2 &= 1234321844561^2 & (5.919)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0170079^2 + 1822000^2 &= 1829921^2 & 0153600^2 + 1840000^2 &= 1846400^2 \\
120170079^2 + 20042000^2 &= 121829921^2 & 120153600^2 + 20240000^2 &= 121846400^2 \\
12320170079^2 + 202242000^2 &= 12321829921^2 & 12320153600^2 + 204240000^2 &= 12321846400^2 \\
1234320170079^2 + 2024242000^2 &= 1234321829921^2 & 1234320153600^2 + 2044240000^2 &= 1234321846400^2 & (5.920)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0168256^2 + 1824000^2 &= 1831744^2 & 0151759^2 + 1842000^2 &= 1848241^2 \\
120168256^2 + 20064000^2 &= 121831744^2 & 120151759^2 + 20262000^2 &= 121848241^2 \\
12320168256^2 + 202464000^2 &= 12321831744^2 & 12320151759^2 + 204462000^2 &= 12321848241^2 \\
1234320168256^2 + 2026464000^2 &= 1234321831744^2 & 1234320151759^2 + 2046462000^2 &= 1234321848241^2 & (5.921)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0166431^2 + 1826000^2 &= 1833569^2 & 0149916^2 + 1844000^2 &= 1850084^2 \\
120166431^2 + 20086000^2 &= 121833569^2 & 120149916^2 + 20284000^2 &= 121850084^2 \\
12320166431^2 + 202686000^2 &= 12321833569^2 & 12320149916^2 + 204684000^2 &= 12321850084^2 \\
1234320166431^2 + 2028686000^2 &= 1234321833569^2 & 1234320149916^2 + 2048684000^2 &= 1234321850084^2 & (5.922)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0164604^2 + 1828000^2 &= 1835396^2 & 0148071^2 + 1846000^2 &= 1851929^2 \\
120164604^2 + 20108000^2 &= 121835396^2 & 120148071^2 + 20306000^2 &= 121851929^2 \\
12320164604^2 + 202908000^2 &= 12321835396^2 & 12320148071^2 + 204906000^2 &= 12321851929^2 \\
1234320164604^2 + 2030908000^2 &= 1234321835396^2 & 1234320148071^2 + 2050906000^2 &= 1234321851929^2 & (5.923)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0162775^2 + 1830000^2 &= 1837225^2 & 0146224^2 + 1848000^2 &= 1853776^2 \\
120162775^2 + 20130000^2 &= 121837225^2 & 120146224^2 + 20328000^2 &= 121853776^2 \\
12320162775^2 + 203130000^2 &= 12321837225^2 & 12320146224^2 + 205128000^2 &= 12321853776^2 \\
1234320162775^2 + 2033130000^2 &= 1234321837225^2 & 1234320146224^2 + 2053128000^2 &= 1234321853776^2 & (5.924)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0160944^2 + 1832000^2 &= 1839056^2 & 0144375^2 + 1850000^2 &= 1855625^2 \\
120160944^2 + 20152000^2 &= 121839056^2 & 120144375^2 + 20350000^2 &= 121855625^2 \\
12320160944^2 + 203352000^2 &= 12321839056^2 & 12320144375^2 + 205350000^2 &= 12321855625^2 \\
1234320160944^2 + 2035352000^2 &= 1234321839056^2 & 1234320144375^2 + 2055350000^2 &= 1234321855625^2 & (5.925)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0142524^2 + 1852000^2 &= 1857476^2 \\
120142524^2 + 20372000^2 &= 121857476^2 \\
12320142524^2 + 205572000^2 &= 12321857476^2 \\
1234320142524^2 + 2057572000^2 &= 1234321857476^2 \quad (5.926)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0140671^2 + 1854000^2 &= 1859329^2 \\
120140671^2 + 20394000^2 &= 121859329^2 \\
12320140671^2 + 205794000^2 &= 12321859329^2 \\
1234320140671^2 + 2059794000^2 &= 1234321859329^2 \quad (5.927)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0138816^2 + 1856000^2 &= 1861184^2 \\
120138816^2 + 20416000^2 &= 121861184^2 \\
12320138816^2 + 206016000^2 &= 12321861184^2 \\
1234320138816^2 + 2062016000^2 &= 1234321861184^2 \quad (5.928)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0136959^2 + 1858000^2 &= 1863041^2 \\
120136959^2 + 20438000^2 &= 121863041^2 \\
12320136959^2 + 206238000^2 &= 12321863041^2 \\
1234320136959^2 + 2064238000^2 &= 1234321863041^2 \quad (5.929)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0135100^2 + 1860000^2 &= 1864900^2 \\
120135100^2 + 20460000^2 &= 121864900^2 \\
12320135100^2 + 206460000^2 &= 12321864900^2 \\
1234320135100^2 + 2066460000^2 &= 1234321864900^2 \quad (5.930)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0133239^2 + 1862000^2 &= 1866761^2 \\
120133239^2 + 20482000^2 &= 121866761^2 \\
12320133239^2 + 206682000^2 &= 12321866761^2 \\
1234320133239^2 + 2068682000^2 &= 1234321866761^2 \quad (5.931)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0131376^2 + 1864000^2 &= 1868624^2 \\
120131376^2 + 20504000^2 &= 121868624^2 \\
12320131376^2 + 206904000^2 &= 12321868624^2 \\
1234320131376^2 + 2070904000^2 &= 1234321868624^2 \quad (5.932)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00129511^2 + 1866000^2 &= 1870489^2 \\
120129511^2 + 20526000^2 &= 121870489^2 \\
12320129511^2 + 207126000^2 &= 12321870489^2 \\
1234320129511^2 + 2073126000^2 &= 1234321870489^2 \quad (5.933)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00127644^2 + 1868000^2 &= 1872356^2 \\
120127644^2 + 20548000^2 &= 121872356^2 \\
12320127644^2 + 207348000^2 &= 12321872356^2 \\
1234320127644^2 + 2075348000^2 &= 1234321872356^2 \quad (5.934)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00125775^2 + 1870000^2 &= 1874225^2 \\
120125775^2 + 20570000^2 &= 121874225^2 \\
12320125775^2 + 207570000^2 &= 12321874225^2 \\
1234320125775^2 + 2077570000^2 &= 1234321874225^2 \quad (5.935)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00123904^2 + 1872000^2 &= 1876096^2 \\
120123904^2 + 20592000^2 &= 121876096^2 \\
12320123904^2 + 207792000^2 &= 12321876096^2 \\
1234320123904^2 + 2079792000^2 &= 1234321876096^2 \quad (5.936)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00122031^2 + 1874000^2 &= 1877969^2 \\
120122031^2 + 20614000^2 &= 121877969^2 \\
12320122031^2 + 208014000^2 &= 12321877969^2 \\
1234320122031^2 + 2082014000^2 &= 1234321877969^2 \quad (5.937)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00120156^2 + 1876000^2 &= 1879844^2 \\
120120156^2 + 20636000^2 &= 121879844^2 \\
12320120156^2 + 208236000^2 &= 12321879844^2 \\
1234320120156^2 + 2084236000^2 &= 1234321879844^2 \quad (5.938)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00118279^2 + 1878000^2 &= 1881721^2 \\
120118279^2 + 20658000^2 &= 121881721^2 \\
12320118279^2 + 208458000^2 &= 12321881721^2 \\
1234320118279^2 + 2086458000^2 &= 1234321881721^2 \quad (5.939)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00116400^2 + 1880000^2 &= 1883600^2 \\
120116400^2 + 20680000^2 &= 121883600^2 \\
12320116400^2 + 208680000^2 &= 12321883600^2 \\
1234320116400^2 + 2088680000^2 &= 1234321883600^2 \quad (5.940)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00114519^2 + 1882000^2 &= 1885481^2 \\
120114519^2 + 20702000^2 &= 121885481^2 \\
12320114519^2 + 208902000^2 &= 12321885481^2 \\
1234320114519^2 + 2090902000^2 &= 1234321885481^2 \quad (5.941)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00112636^2 + 1884000^2 &= 1887364^2 \\
120112636^2 + 20724000^2 &= 121887364^2 \\
12320112636^2 + 209124000^2 &= 12321887364^2 \\
1234320112636^2 + 2093124000^2 &= 1234321887364^2 \quad (5.942)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00110751^2 + 1886000^2 &= 1889249^2 \\
120110751^2 + 20746000^2 &= 121889249^2 \\
12320110751^2 + 209346000^2 &= 12321889249^2 \\
1234320110751^2 + 2095346000^2 &= 1234321889249^2 \quad (5.943)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00108864^2 + 1888000^2 &= 1891136^2 \\
120108864^2 + 20768000^2 &= 121891136^2 \\
12320108864^2 + 209568000^2 &= 12321891136^2 \\
1234320108864^2 + 2097568000^2 &= 1234321891136^2 \quad (5.944)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00106975^2 + 1890000^2 &= 1893025^2 \\
120106975^2 + 20790000^2 &= 121893025^2 \\
12320106975^2 + 209790000^2 &= 12321893025^2 \\
1234320106975^2 + 2099790000^2 &= 1234321893025^2 \quad (5.945)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00105084^2 + 1892000^2 &= 1894916^2 \\
120105084^2 + 20812000^2 &= 121894916^2 \\
12320105084^2 + 210012000^2 &= 12321894916^2 \\
1234320105084^2 + 2102012000^2 &= 1234321894916^2 \quad (5.946)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00103191^2 + 1894000^2 &= 1896809^2 \\
120103191^2 + 20834000^2 &= 121896809^2 \\
12320103191^2 + 210234000^2 &= 12321896809^2 \\
1234320103191^2 + 2104234000^2 &= 1234321896809^2 \quad (5.947)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
00101296^2 + 1896000^2 &= 1898704^2 \\
120101296^2 + 20856000^2 &= 121898704^2 \\
12320101296^2 + 210456000^2 &= 12321898704^2 \\
1234320101296^2 + 2106456000^2 &= 1234321898704^2 \quad (5.948)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0099399^2 + 1898000^2 &= 1900601^2 \\
120099399^2 + 20878000^2 &= 121900601^2 \\
12320099399^2 + 210678000^2 &= 12321900601^2 \\
1234320099399^2 + 2108678000^2 &= 1234321900601^2 \quad (5.949)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0097500^2 + 1900000^2 &= 1902500^2 \\
120097500^2 + 20900000^2 &= 121902500^2 \\
12320097500^2 + 210900000^2 &= 12321902500^2 \\
1234320097500^2 + 2110900000^2 &= 1234321902500^2 \quad (5.950)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0095599^2 + 1902000^2 &= 1904401^2 \\
120095599^2 + 20922000^2 &= 121904401^2 \\
12320095599^2 + 211122000^2 &= 12321904401^2 \\
1234320095599^2 + 2113122000^2 &= 1234321904401^2 \quad (5.951)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0093696^2 + 1904000^2 &= 1906304^2 \\
120093696^2 + 20944000^2 &= 121906304^2 \\
12320093696^2 + 211344000^2 &= 12321906304^2 \\
1234320093696^2 + 2115344000^2 &= 1234321906304^2 \quad (5.952)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0091791^2 + 1906000^2 &= 1908209^2 \\
120091791^2 + 20966000^2 &= 121908209^2 \\
12320091791^2 + 211566000^2 &= 12321908209^2 \\
1234320091791^2 + 2117566000^2 &= 1234321908209^2 \quad (5.953)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0089884^2 + 1908000^2 &= 1910116^2 \\
120089884^2 + 20988000^2 &= 121910116^2 \\
12320089884^2 + 211788000^2 &= 12321910116^2 \\
1234320089884^2 + 2119788000^2 &= 1234321910116^2 \quad (5.954)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0087975^2 + 1910000^2 &= 1912025^2 \\
120087975^2 + 21010000^2 &= 121912025^2 \\
12320087975^2 + 212010000^2 &= 12321912025^2 \\
1234320087975^2 + 2122010000^2 &= 1234321912025^2 \quad (5.955)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0086064^2 + 1912000^2 &= 1913936^2 \\
120086064^2 + 21032000^2 &= 121913936^2 \\
12320086064^2 + 212232000^2 &= 12321913936^2 \\
1234320086064^2 + 2124232000^2 &= 1234321913936^2 \quad (5.956)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0084151^2 + 1914000^2 &= 1915849^2 \\
120084151^2 + 21054000^2 &= 121915849^2 \\
12320084151^2 + 212454000^2 &= 12321915849^2 \\
1234320084151^2 + 2126454000^2 &= 1234321915849^2 \quad (5.957)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0082236^2 + 1916000^2 &= 1917764^2 \\
120082236^2 + 21076000^2 &= 121917764^2 \\
12320082236^2 + 212676000^2 &= 12321917764^2 \\
1234320082236^2 + 2128676000^2 &= 1234321917764^2 \quad (5.958)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0080319^2 + 1918000^2 &= 1919681^2 \\
120080319^2 + 21098000^2 &= 121919681^2 \\
12320080319^2 + 212898000^2 &= 12321919681^2 \\
1234320080319^2 + 2130898000^2 &= 1234321919681^2 \quad (5.959)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0078400^2 + 1920000^2 &= 1921600^2 \\
120078400^2 + 21120000^2 &= 121921600^2 \\
12320078400^2 + 213120000^2 &= 12321921600^2 \\
1234320078400^2 + 2133120000^2 &= 1234321921600^2 \quad (5.960)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0076479^2 + 1922000^2 &= 1923521^2 \\
120076479^2 + 21142000^2 &= 121923521^2 \\
12320076479^2 + 213342000^2 &= 12321923521^2 \\
1234320076479^2 + 2135342000^2 &= 1234321923521^2 \quad (5.961)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0074556^2 + 1924000^2 &= 1\ 925444^2 \\
12\ 0074556^2 + 21164000^2 &= 121\ 925444^2 \\
1232\ 0074556^2 + 213564000^2 &= 12321\ 925444^2 \\
123432\ 0074556^2 + 2137564000^2 &= 1234321\ 925444^2 \quad (5.962)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0072631^2 + 1926000^2 &= 1\ 927369^2 \\
12\ 0072631^2 + 21186000^2 &= 121\ 927369^2 \\
1232\ 0072631^2 + 213786000^2 &= 12321\ 927369^2 \\
123432\ 0072631^2 + 2139786000^2 &= 1234321\ 927369^2 \quad (5.963)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0070704^2 + 1928000^2 &= 1\ 929296^2 \\
12\ 0070704^2 + 21208000^2 &= 121\ 929296^2 \\
1232\ 0070704^2 + 214008000^2 &= 12321\ 929296^2 \\
123432\ 0070704^2 + 2142008000^2 &= 1234321\ 929296^2 \quad (5.964)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0068775^2 + 1930000^2 &= 1\ 931225^2 \\
12\ 0068775^2 + 21230000^2 &= 121\ 931225^2 \\
1232\ 0068775^2 + 214230000^2 &= 12321\ 931225^2 \\
123432\ 0068775^2 + 2144230000^2 &= 1234321\ 931225^2 \quad (5.965)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0066844^2 + 1932000^2 &= 1\ 933156^2 \\
12\ 0066844^2 + 21252000^2 &= 121\ 933156^2 \\
1232\ 0066844^2 + 214452000^2 &= 12321\ 933156^2 \\
123432\ 0066844^2 + 2146452000^2 &= 1234321\ 933156^2 \quad (5.966)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0064911^2 + 1934000^2 &= 1\ 935089^2 \\
12\ 0064911^2 + 21274000^2 &= 121\ 935089^2 \\
1232\ 0064911^2 + 214674000^2 &= 12321\ 935089^2 \\
123432\ 0064911^2 + 2148674000^2 &= 1234321\ 935089^2 \quad (5.967)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0062976^2 + 1936000^2 &= 1\ 937024^2 \\
12\ 0062976^2 + 21296000^2 &= 121\ 937024^2 \\
1232\ 0062976^2 + 214896000^2 &= 12321\ 937024^2 \\
123432\ 0062976^2 + 2150896000^2 &= 1234321\ 937024^2 \quad (5.968)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0061039^2 + 1938000^2 &= 1\ 938961^2 \\
12\ 0061039^2 + 21318000^2 &= 121\ 938961^2 \\
1232\ 0061039^2 + 215118000^2 &= 12321\ 938961^2 \\
123432\ 0061039^2 + 2153118000^2 &= 1234321\ 938961^2 \quad (5.969)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0059100^2 + 1940000^2 &= 1\ 940900^2 \\
12\ 0059100^2 + 21340000^2 &= 121\ 940900^2 \\
1232\ 0059100^2 + 215340000^2 &= 12321\ 940900^2 \\
123432\ 0059100^2 + 2155340000^2 &= 1234321\ 940900^2 \quad (5.970)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0057159^2 + 1942000^2 &= 1\ 942841^2 \\
12\ 0057159^2 + 21362000^2 &= 121\ 942841^2 \\
1232\ 0057159^2 + 215562000^2 &= 12321\ 942841^2 \\
123432\ 0057159^2 + 2157562000^2 &= 1234321\ 942841^2 \quad (5.971)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0055216^2 + 1944000^2 &= 1\ 944784^2 \\
12\ 0055216^2 + 21384000^2 &= 121\ 944784^2 \\
1232\ 0055216^2 + 215784000^2 &= 12321\ 944784^2 \\
123432\ 0055216^2 + 2159784000^2 &= 1234321\ 944784^2 \quad (5.972)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0053271^2 + 1946000^2 &= 1\ 946729^2 \\
12\ 0053271^2 + 21406000^2 &= 121\ 946729^2 \\
1232\ 0053271^2 + 216006000^2 &= 12321\ 946729^2 \\
123432\ 0053271^2 + 2162006000^2 &= 1234321\ 946729^2 \quad (5.973)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0051324^2 + 1948000^2 &= 1\ 948676^2 \\
12\ 0051324^2 + 21428000^2 &= 121\ 948676^2 \\
1232\ 0051324^2 + 216228000^2 &= 12321\ 948676^2 \\
123432\ 0051324^2 + 2164228000^2 &= 1234321\ 948676^2 \quad (5.974)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0049375^2 + 1950000^2 &= 1\ 950625^2 \\
12\ 0049375^2 + 21450000^2 &= 121\ 950625^2 \\
1232\ 0049375^2 + 216450000^2 &= 12321\ 950625^2 \\
123432\ 0049375^2 + 2166450000^2 &= 1234321\ 950625^2 \quad (5.975)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0047424^2 + 1952000^2 &= 1\ 952576^2 \\
12\ 0047424^2 + 21472000^2 &= 121\ 952576^2 \\
1232\ 0047424^2 + 216672000^2 &= 12321\ 952576^2 \\
123432\ 0047424^2 + 2168672000^2 &= 1234321\ 952576^2 \quad (5.976)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0045471^2 + 1954000^2 &= 1\ 954529^2 \\
12\ 0045471^2 + 21494000^2 &= 121\ 954529^2 \\
1232\ 0045471^2 + 216894000^2 &= 12321\ 954529^2 \\
123432\ 0045471^2 + 2170894000^2 &= 1234321\ 954529^2 \quad (5.977)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0043516^2 + 1956000^2 &= 1\ 956484^2 \\
12\ 0043516^2 + 21516000^2 &= 121\ 956484^2 \\
1232\ 0043516^2 + 217116000^2 &= 12321\ 956484^2 \\
123432\ 0043516^2 + 2173116000^2 &= 1234321\ 956484^2 \quad (5.978)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
0041559^2 + 1958000^2 &= 1\ 958441^2 \\
12\ 0041559^2 + 21538000^2 &= 121\ 958441^2 \\
1232\ 0041559^2 + 217338000^2 &= 12321\ 958441^2 \\
123432\ 0041559^2 + 2175338000^2 &= 1234321\ 958441^2 \quad (5.979)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0039600^2 + 1960000^2 = 1\ 960400^2 \\
12\ 0039600^2 + 21560000^2 = 121\ 960400^2 \\
1232\ 0039600^2 + 217560000^2 = 12321\ 960400^2 \\
123432\ 0039600^2 + 2177560000^2 = 1234321\ 960400^2 \quad (5.980)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0019900^2 + 1980000^2 = 1\ 980100^2 \\
12\ 0019900^2 + 21780000^2 = 121\ 980100^2 \\
1232\ 0019900^2 + 219780000^2 = 12321\ 980100^2 \\
123432\ 0019900^2 + 2199780000^2 = 1234321\ 980100^2 \quad (5.990)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0037639^2 + 1962000^2 = 1\ 962361^2 \\
12\ 0037639^2 + 21582000^2 = 121\ 962361^2 \\
1232\ 0037639^2 + 217782000^2 = 12321\ 962361^2 \\
123432\ 0037639^2 + 2179782000^2 = 1234321\ 962361^2 \quad (5.981)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0017919^2 + 1982000^2 = 1\ 982081^2 \\
12\ 0017919^2 + 21802000^2 = 121\ 982081^2 \\
1232\ 0017919^2 + 220002000^2 = 12321\ 982081^2 \\
123432\ 0017919^2 + 2202002000^2 = 1234321\ 982081^2 \quad (5.991)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0035676^2 + 1964000^2 = 1\ 964324^2 \\
12\ 0035676^2 + 21604000^2 = 121\ 964324^2 \\
1232\ 0035676^2 + 218004000^2 = 12321\ 964324^2 \\
123432\ 0035676^2 + 2182004000^2 = 1234321\ 964324^2 \quad (5.982)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0015936^2 + 1984000^2 = 1\ 984064^2 \\
12\ 0015936^2 + 21824000^2 = 121\ 984064^2 \\
1232\ 0015936^2 + 220224000^2 = 12321\ 984064^2 \\
123432\ 0015936^2 + 2204224000^2 = 1234321\ 984064^2 \quad (5.992)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0033711^2 + 1966000^2 = 1\ 966289^2 \\
12\ 0033711^2 + 21626000^2 = 121\ 966289^2 \\
1232\ 0033711^2 + 218226000^2 = 12321\ 966289^2 \\
123432\ 0033711^2 + 2184226000^2 = 1234321\ 966289^2 \quad (5.983)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0013951^2 + 1986000^2 = 1\ 986049^2 \\
12\ 0013951^2 + 21846000^2 = 121\ 986049^2 \\
1232\ 0013951^2 + 220446000^2 = 12321\ 986049^2 \\
123432\ 0013951^2 + 2206446000^2 = 1234321\ 986049^2 \quad (5.993)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0031744^2 + 1968000^2 = 1\ 968256^2 \\
12\ 0031744^2 + 21648000^2 = 121\ 968256^2 \\
1232\ 0031744^2 + 218448000^2 = 12321\ 968256^2 \\
123432\ 0031744^2 + 2186448000^2 = 1234321\ 968256^2 \quad (5.984)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0011964^2 + 1988000^2 = 1\ 988036^2 \\
12\ 0011964^2 + 21868000^2 = 121\ 988036^2 \\
1232\ 0011964^2 + 220668000^2 = 12321\ 988036^2 \\
123432\ 0011964^2 + 2208668000^2 = 1234321\ 988036^2 \quad (5.994)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0029775^2 + 1970000^2 = 1\ 970225^2 \\
12\ 0029775^2 + 21670000^2 = 121\ 970225^2 \\
1232\ 0029775^2 + 218670000^2 = 12321\ 970225^2 \\
123432\ 0029775^2 + 2188670000^2 = 1234321\ 970225^2 \quad (5.985)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0009975^2 + 1990000^2 = 1\ 990025^2 \\
12\ 0009975^2 + 21890000^2 = 121\ 990025^2 \\
1232\ 0009975^2 + 220890000^2 = 12321\ 990025^2 \\
123432\ 0009975^2 + 2210890000^2 = 1234321\ 990025^2 \quad (5.995)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0027804^2 + 1972000^2 = 1\ 972196^2 \\
12\ 0027804^2 + 21692000^2 = 121\ 972196^2 \\
1232\ 0027804^2 + 218892000^2 = 12321\ 972196^2 \\
123432\ 0027804^2 + 2190892000^2 = 1234321\ 972196^2 \quad (5.986)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0007984^2 + 1992000^2 = 1\ 992016^2 \\
12\ 0007984^2 + 21912000^2 = 121\ 992016^2 \\
1232\ 0007984^2 + 221112000^2 = 12321\ 992016^2 \\
123432\ 0007984^2 + 2213112000^2 = 1234321\ 992016^2 \quad (5.996)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0025831^2 + 1974000^2 = 1\ 974169^2 \\
12\ 0025831^2 + 21714000^2 = 121\ 974169^2 \\
1232\ 0025831^2 + 219114000^2 = 12321\ 974169^2 \\
123432\ 0025831^2 + 2193114000^2 = 1234321\ 974169^2 \quad (5.987)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0005991^2 + 1994000^2 = 1\ 994009^2 \\
12\ 0005991^2 + 21934000^2 = 121\ 994009^2 \\
1232\ 0005991^2 + 221334000^2 = 12321\ 994009^2 \\
123432\ 0005991^2 + 2215334000^2 = 1234321\ 994009^2 \quad (5.997)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0023856^2 + 1976000^2 = 1\ 976144^2 \\
12\ 0023856^2 + 21736000^2 = 121\ 976144^2 \\
1232\ 0023856^2 + 219336000^2 = 12321\ 976144^2 \\
123432\ 0023856^2 + 2195336000^2 = 1234321\ 976144^2 \quad (5.988)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0003996^2 + 1996000^2 = 1\ 996004^2 \\
12\ 0003996^2 + 21956000^2 = 121\ 996004^2 \\
1232\ 0003996^2 + 221556000^2 = 12321\ 996004^2 \\
123432\ 0003996^2 + 2217556000^2 = 1234321\ 996004^2 \quad (5.998)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0021879^2 + 1978000^2 = 1\ 978121^2 \\
12\ 0021879^2 + 21758000^2 = 121\ 978121^2 \\
1232\ 0021879^2 + 219558000^2 = 12321\ 978121^2 \\
123432\ 0021879^2 + 2197558000^2 = 1234321\ 978121^2 \quad (5.989)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0001999^2 + 1998000^2 = 1\ 998001^2 \\
12\ 0001999^2 + 21978000^2 = 121\ 998001^2 \\
1232\ 0001999^2 + 221778000^2 = 12321\ 998001^2 \\
123432\ 0001999^2 + 2219778000^2 = 1234321\ 998001^2 \quad (5.999)
\end{array}$$

5.2 Second Type

- For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 997, 998, 999$:

This subsection is divided in two parts. The first part give first 19 results give complete patterns. The other 80 are with first four lines.

5.2.1 Second Part

- For $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 19$:

Let's consider

$$m = 1000, 101000, 10101000, 1010101000, 101010101000, 10101010101000, 1010101010101000, 101010101010101000, 10101010101010101000$$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17, 18, 19$; there are 19 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns** given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999999^2 + 2000^2 &&= 1\ 000001^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999999^2 + 202000^2 &&= 10201\ 000001^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999999^2 + 20202000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000001^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999999^2 + 2020202000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000001^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999999^2 + 202020202000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000001^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999999^2 + 20202020202000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000001^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999999^2 + 2020202020202000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000001^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999999^2 + 202020202020202000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000001^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999999^2 + 20202020202020202000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000001^2 \quad (5.1000)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999996^2 + 4000^2 &&= 1\ 000004^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999996^2 + 404000^2 &&= 10201\ 000004^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999996^2 + 40404000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000004^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999996^2 + 4040404000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000004^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999996^2 + 404040404000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000004^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999996^2 + 40404040404000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000004^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999996^2 + 4040404040404000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000004^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999996^2 + 404040404040404000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000004^2 \quad (5.1001)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999991^2 + 6000^2 &&= 1\ 000009^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999991^2 + 606000^2 &&= 10201\ 000009^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999991^2 + 60606000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000009^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999991^2 + 6060606000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000009^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999991^2 + 606060606000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000009^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999991^2 + 60606060606000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000009^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999991^2 + 6060606060606000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000009^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999991^2 + 606060606060606000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000009^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999991^2 + 60606060606060606000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000009^2 \quad (5.1002)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0999984^2 + 8000^2 &= 1\ 000016^2 \\
&1020\ 0999984^2 + 808000^2 &= 10201\ 000016^2 \\
&10203020\ 0999984^2 + 80808000^2 &= 102030201\ 000016^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0999984^2 + 8080808000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 000016^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 0999984^2 + 808080808000^2 &= 10203040504030201\ 000016^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 0999984^2 + 80808080808000^2 &= 102030405060504030201\ 000016^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 0999984^2 + 8080808080808000^2 &= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000016^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999984^2 + 808080808080808000^2 &= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000016^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999984^2 + 80808080808080808000^2 &= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000016^2 \quad (5.1003)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0999975^2 + 10000^2 &= 1\ 000025^2 \\
&1020\ 0999975^2 + 1010000^2 &= 10201\ 000025^2 \\
&10203020\ 0999975^2 + 101010000^2 &= 102030201\ 000025^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0999975^2 + 10101010000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 000025^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 0999975^2 + 1010101010000^2 &= 10203040504030201\ 000025^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 0999975^2 + 101010101010000^2 &= 102030405060504030201\ 000025^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 0999975^2 + 10101010101010000^2 &= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000025^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999975^2 + 1010101010101010000^2 &= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000025^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999975^2 + 101010101010101010000^2 &= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000025^2 \quad (5.1004)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0999964^2 + 12000^2 &= 1\ 000036^2 \\
&1020\ 0999964^2 + 1212000^2 &= 10201\ 000036^2 \\
&10203020\ 0999964^2 + 121212000^2 &= 102030201\ 000036^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0999964^2 + 12121212000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 000036^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 0999964^2 + 1212121212000^2 &= 10203040504030201\ 000036^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 0999964^2 + 121212121212000^2 &= 102030405060504030201\ 000036^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 0999964^2 + 12121212121212000^2 &= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000036^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999964^2 + 1212121212121212000^2 &= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000036^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999964^2 + 121212121212121212000^2 &= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000036^2 \quad (5.1005)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0999951^2 + 14000^2 &= 1\ 000049^2 \\
&1020\ 0999951^2 + 1414000^2 &= 10201\ 000049^2 \\
&10203020\ 0999951^2 + 141414000^2 &= 102030201\ 000049^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0999951^2 + 14141414000^2 &= 1020304030201\ 000049^2 \\
&1020304050403020\ 0999951^2 + 1414141414000^2 &= 10203040504030201\ 000049^2 \\
&10203040506050403020\ 0999951^2 + 141414141414000^2 &= 102030405060504030201\ 000049^2 \\
&102030405060706050403020\ 0999951^2 + 14141414141414000^2 &= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000049^2 \\
&1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999951^2 + 1414141414141414000^2 &= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000049^2 \\
&10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999951^2 + 141414141414141414000^2 &= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000049^2 \quad (5.1006)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999936^2 + 16000^2 &&= 1\ 000064^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999936^2 + 1616000^2 &&= 10201\ 000064^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999936^2 + 161616000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000064^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999936^2 + 16161616000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000064^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999936^2 + 1616161616000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000064^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999936^2 + 161616161616000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000064^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999936^2 + 16161616161616000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000064^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999936^2 + 1616161616161616000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000064^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999936^2 + 161616161616161616000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000064^2 \quad (5.1007)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999919^2 + 18000^2 &&= 1\ 000081^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999919^2 + 1818000^2 &&= 10201\ 000081^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999919^2 + 181818000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000081^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999919^2 + 18181818000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000081^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999919^2 + 1818181818000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000081^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999919^2 + 181818181818000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000081^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999919^2 + 18181818181818000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000081^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999919^2 + 1818181818181818000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000081^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999919^2 + 181818181818181818000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000081^2 \quad (5.1008)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999900^2 + 20000^2 &&= 1\ 000100^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999900^2 + 2020000^2 &&= 10201\ 000100^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999900^2 + 202020000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000100^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999900^2 + 20202020000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000100^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999900^2 + 2020202020000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000100^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999900^2 + 202020202020000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000100^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999900^2 + 20202020202020000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000100^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999900^2 + 2020202020202020000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000100^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999900^2 + 202020202020202020000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000100^2 \quad (5.1009)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999879^2 + 22000^2 &&= 1\ 000121^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999879^2 + 2222000^2 &&= 10201\ 000121^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999879^2 + 22222000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000121^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999879^2 + 222222000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000121^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999879^2 + 2222222000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000121^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999879^2 + 22222222000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000121^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999879^2 + 222222222000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000121^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999879^2 + 2222222222000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000121^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999879^2 + 22222222222000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000121^2 \quad (5.1010)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999856^2 + 24000^2 &&= 1\ 000144^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999856^2 + 2424000^2 &&= 10201\ 000144^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999856^2 + 242424000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000144^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999856^2 + 24242424000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000144^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999856^2 + 2424242424000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000144^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999856^2 + 242424242424000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000144^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999856^2 + 24242424242424000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000144^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999856^2 + 2424242424242424000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000144^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999856^2 + 242424242424242424000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000144^2 \quad (5.1011)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999831^2 + 26000^2 &&= 1\ 000169^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999831^2 + 2626000^2 &&= 10201\ 000169^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999831^2 + 262626000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000169^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999831^2 + 26262626000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000169^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999831^2 + 2626262626000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000169^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999831^2 + 262626262626000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000169^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999831^2 + 26262626262626000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000169^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999831^2 + 2626262626262626000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000169^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999831^2 + 262626262626262626000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000169^2 \quad (5.1012)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999804^2 + 28000^2 &&= 1\ 000196^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999804^2 + 2828000^2 &&= 10201\ 000196^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999804^2 + 282828000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000196^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999804^2 + 28282828000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000196^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999804^2 + 2828282828000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000196^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999804^2 + 282828282828000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000196^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999804^2 + 28282828282828000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000196^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999804^2 + 2828282828282828000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000196^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999804^2 + 282828282828282828000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000196^2 \quad (5.1013)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999775^2 + 30000^2 &&= 1\ 000225^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999775^2 + 3030000^2 &&= 10201\ 000225^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999775^2 + 303030000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000225^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999775^2 + 30303030000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000225^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999775^2 + 3030303030000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000225^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999775^2 + 303030303030000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000225^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999775^2 + 30303030303030000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000225^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999775^2 + 3030303030303030000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000225^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999775^2 + 303030303030303030000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000225^2 \quad (5.1014)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999744^2 + 32000^2 &&= 1\ 000256^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999744^2 + 3232000^2 &&= 10201\ 000256^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999744^2 + 323232000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000256^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999744^2 + 32323232000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000256^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999744^2 + 3232323232000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000256^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999744^2 + 323232323232000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000256^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999744^2 + 32323232323232000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000256^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999744^2 + 3232323232323232000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000256^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999744^2 + 323232323232323232000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000256^2 \quad (5.1015)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999711^2 + 34000^2 &&= 1\ 000289^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999711^2 + 3434000^2 &&= 10201\ 000289^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999711^2 + 343434000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000289^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999711^2 + 34343434000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000289^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999711^2 + 3434343434000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000289^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999711^2 + 343434343434000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000289^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999711^2 + 34343434343434000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000289^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999711^2 + 3434343434343434000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000289^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999711^2 + 343434343434343434000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000289^2 \quad (5.1016)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999676^2 + 36000^2 &&= 1\ 000324^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999676^2 + 3636000^2 &&= 10201\ 000324^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999676^2 + 363636000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000324^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999676^2 + 36363636000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000324^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999676^2 + 3636363636000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000324^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999676^2 + 363636363636000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000324^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999676^2 + 36363636363636000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000324^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999676^2 + 3636363636363636000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000324^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999676^2 + 363636363636363636000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000324^2 \quad (5.1017)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0999639^2 + 38000^2 &&= 1\ 000361^2 \\
 &1020\ 0999639^2 + 3838000^2 &&= 10201\ 000361^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0999639^2 + 383838000^2 &&= 102030201\ 000361^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0999639^2 + 38383838000^2 &&= 1020304030201\ 000361^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0999639^2 + 3838383838000^2 &&= 10203040504030201\ 000361^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0999639^2 + 383838383838000^2 &&= 102030405060504030201\ 000361^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0999639^2 + 38383838383838000^2 &&= 1020304050607060504030201\ 000361^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0999639^2 + 3838383838383838000^2 &&= 10203040506070807060504030201\ 000361^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0999639^2 + 383838383838383838000^2 &&= 102030405060708090807060504030201\ 000361^2 \quad (5.1018)
 \end{aligned}$$

5.2.2 Second Part

For $n = 20, 21, 22, \dots, 97, 98, 99 \dots, 997, 998, 999$:

Let's consider

$$m = 1000, 101000, 10101000, 1010101000, 101010101000, 10101010101000, 1010101010101000, 101010101010101000$$

in (1.1), then for each value of $n = 20, 21, 22, \dots, 97, 98, 99, \dots, 997, 998, 999$; there are 880 **palindromic-type pandigital Pythagorean patterns** given below. In each case, only first four values are written. The other 5 values can be written on similar lines.

$0999600^2 + 40000^2 = 1\ 000400^2$	$0999216^2 + 56000^2 = 1\ 000784^2$
$1020\ 0999600^2 + 4040000^2 = 10201\ 000400^2$	$1020\ 0999216^2 + 5656000^2 = 10201\ 000784^2$
$10203020\ 0999600^2 + 404040000^2 = 102030201\ 000400^2$	$10203020\ 0999216^2 + 565656000^2 = 102030201\ 000784^2$
$102030403020\ 0999600^2 + 40404040000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000400^2$ (5.1019)	$102030403020\ 0999216^2 + 56565656000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000784^2$ (5.1027)
$0999559^2 + 42000^2 = 1\ 000441^2$	$0999159^2 + 58000^2 = 1\ 000841^2$
$1020\ 0999559^2 + 4242000^2 = 10201\ 000441^2$	$1020\ 0999159^2 + 5858000^2 = 10201\ 000841^2$
$10203020\ 0999559^2 + 424242000^2 = 102030201\ 000441^2$	$10203020\ 0999159^2 + 585858000^2 = 102030201\ 000841^2$
$102030403020\ 0999559^2 + 42424242000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000441^2$ (5.1020)	$102030403020\ 0999159^2 + 58585858000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000841^2$ (5.1028)
$0999516^2 + 44000^2 = 1\ 000484^2$	$0999100^2 + 60000^2 = 1\ 000900^2$
$1020\ 0999516^2 + 4444000^2 = 10201\ 000484^2$	$1020\ 0999100^2 + 6060000^2 = 10201\ 000900^2$
$10203020\ 0999516^2 + 444444000^2 = 102030201\ 000484^2$	$10203020\ 0999100^2 + 606060000^2 = 102030201\ 000900^2$
$102030403020\ 0999516^2 + 44444444000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000484^2$ (5.1021)	$102030403020\ 0999100^2 + 60606060000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000900^2$ (5.1029)
$0999471^2 + 46000^2 = 1\ 000529^2$	$0999039^2 + 62000^2 = 1\ 000961^2$
$1020\ 0999471^2 + 4646000^2 = 10201\ 000529^2$	$1020\ 0999039^2 + 6262000^2 = 10201\ 000961^2$
$10203020\ 0999471^2 + 464646000^2 = 102030201\ 000529^2$	$10203020\ 0999039^2 + 626262000^2 = 102030201\ 000961^2$
$102030403020\ 0999471^2 + 46464646000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000529^2$ (5.1022)	$102030403020\ 0999039^2 + 62626262000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000961^2$ (5.1030)
$0999424^2 + 48000^2 = 1\ 000576^2$	$0998976^2 + 64000^2 = 1\ 001024^2$
$1020\ 0999424^2 + 4848000^2 = 10201\ 000576^2$	$1020\ 0998976^2 + 6464000^2 = 10201\ 001024^2$
$10203020\ 0999424^2 + 484848000^2 = 102030201\ 000576^2$	$10203020\ 0998976^2 + 646464000^2 = 102030201\ 001024^2$
$102030403020\ 0999424^2 + 48484848000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000576^2$ (5.1023)	$102030403020\ 0998976^2 + 64646464000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001024^2$ (5.1031)
$0999375^2 + 50000^2 = 1\ 000625^2$	$0998911^2 + 66000^2 = 1\ 001089^2$
$1020\ 0999375^2 + 5050000^2 = 10201\ 000625^2$	$1020\ 0998911^2 + 6666000^2 = 10201\ 001089^2$
$10203020\ 0999375^2 + 505050000^2 = 102030201\ 000625^2$	$10203020\ 0998911^2 + 666666000^2 = 102030201\ 001089^2$
$102030403020\ 0999375^2 + 50505050000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000625^2$ (5.1024)	$102030403020\ 0998911^2 + 66666666000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001089^2$ (5.1032)
$0999324^2 + 52000^2 = 1\ 000676^2$	$0998844^2 + 68000^2 = 1\ 001156^2$
$1020\ 0999324^2 + 5252000^2 = 10201\ 000676^2$	$1020\ 0998844^2 + 6868000^2 = 10201\ 001156^2$
$10203020\ 0999324^2 + 525252000^2 = 102030201\ 000676^2$	$10203020\ 0998844^2 + 686868000^2 = 102030201\ 001156^2$
$102030403020\ 0999324^2 + 52525252000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000676^2$ (5.1025)	$102030403020\ 0998844^2 + 68686868000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001156^2$ (5.1033)
$0999271^2 + 54000^2 = 1\ 000729^2$	$0998775^2 + 70000^2 = 1\ 001225^2$
$1020\ 0999271^2 + 5454000^2 = 10201\ 000729^2$	$1020\ 0998775^2 + 7070000^2 = 10201\ 001225^2$
$10203020\ 0999271^2 + 545454000^2 = 102030201\ 000729^2$	$10203020\ 0998775^2 + 707070000^2 = 102030201\ 001225^2$
$102030403020\ 0999271^2 + 54545454000^2 = 1020304030201\ 000729^2$ (5.1026)	$102030403020\ 0998775^2 + 70707070000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001225^2$ (5.1034)

$$\begin{aligned}
&0998704^2 + 72000^2 = 1\ 001296^2 \\
&1020\ 0998704^2 + 7272000^2 = 10201\ 001296^2 \\
&10203020\ 0998704^2 + 727272000^2 = 102030201\ 001296^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0998704^2 + 72727272000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001296^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1035)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0998631^2 + 74000^2 = 1\ 001369^2 \\
&1020\ 0998631^2 + 7474000^2 = 10201\ 001369^2 \\
&10203020\ 0998631^2 + 747474000^2 = 102030201\ 001369^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0998631^2 + 74747474000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001369^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1036)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0998556^2 + 76000^2 = 1\ 001444^2 \\
&1020\ 0998556^2 + 7676000^2 = 10201\ 001444^2 \\
&10203020\ 0998556^2 + 767676000^2 = 102030201\ 001444^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0998556^2 + 76767676000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001444^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1037)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0998479^2 + 78000^2 = 1\ 001521^2 \\
&1020\ 0998479^2 + 7878000^2 = 10201\ 001521^2 \\
&10203020\ 0998479^2 + 787878000^2 = 102030201\ 001521^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0998479^2 + 78787878000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001521^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1038)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0998400^2 + 80000^2 = 1\ 001600^2 \\
&1020\ 0998400^2 + 8080000^2 = 10201\ 001600^2 \\
&10203020\ 0998400^2 + 808080000^2 = 102030201\ 001600^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0998400^2 + 80808080000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001600^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1039)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0998319^2 + 82000^2 = 1\ 001681^2 \\
&1020\ 0998319^2 + 8282000^2 = 10201\ 001681^2 \\
&10203020\ 0998319^2 + 828282000^2 = 102030201\ 001681^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0998319^2 + 82828282000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001681^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1040)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0998236^2 + 84000^2 = 1\ 001764^2 \\
&1020\ 0998236^2 + 8484000^2 = 10201\ 001764^2 \\
&10203020\ 0998236^2 + 848484000^2 = 102030201\ 001764^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0998236^2 + 84848484000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001764^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1041)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0998151^2 + 86000^2 = 1\ 001849^2 \\
&1020\ 0998151^2 + 8686000^2 = 10201\ 001849^2 \\
&10203020\ 0998151^2 + 868686000^2 = 102030201\ 001849^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0998151^2 + 86868686000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001849^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1042)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0998064^2 + 88000^2 = 1\ 001936^2 \\
&1020\ 0998064^2 + 8888000^2 = 10201\ 001936^2 \\
&10203020\ 0998064^2 + 888888000^2 = 102030201\ 001936^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0998064^2 + 88888888000^2 = 1020304030201\ 001936^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1043)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0997975^2 + 90000^2 = 1\ 002025^2 \\
&1020\ 0997975^2 + 9090000^2 = 10201\ 002025^2 \\
&10203020\ 0997975^2 + 909090000^2 = 102030201\ 002025^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0997975^2 + 90909090000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002025^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1044)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0997884^2 + 92000^2 = 1\ 002116^2 \\
&1020\ 0997884^2 + 9292000^2 = 10201\ 002116^2 \\
&10203020\ 0997884^2 + 929292000^2 = 102030201\ 002116^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0997884^2 + 92929292000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002116^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1045)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0997791^2 + 94000^2 = 1\ 002209^2 \\
&1020\ 0997791^2 + 9494000^2 = 10201\ 002209^2 \\
&10203020\ 0997791^2 + 949494000^2 = 102030201\ 002209^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0997791^2 + 94949494000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002209^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1046)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0997696^2 + 96000^2 = 1\ 002304^2 \\
&1020\ 0997696^2 + 9696000^2 = 10201\ 002304^2 \\
&10203020\ 0997696^2 + 969696000^2 = 102030201\ 002304^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0997696^2 + 96969696000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002304^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1047)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0997599^2 + 98000^2 = 1\ 002401^2 \\
&1020\ 0997599^2 + 9898000^2 = 10201\ 002401^2 \\
&10203020\ 0997599^2 + 989898000^2 = 102030201\ 002401^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0997599^2 + 98989898000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002401^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1048)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0997500^2 + 100000^2 = 1\ 002500^2 \\
&1020\ 0997500^2 + 10100000^2 = 10201\ 002500^2 \\
&10203020\ 0997500^2 + 1010100000^2 = 102030201\ 002500^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0997500^2 + 101010100000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002500^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1049)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0997399^2 + 102000^2 = 1\ 002601^2 \\
&1020\ 0997399^2 + 10302000^2 = 10201\ 002601^2 \\
&10203020\ 0997399^2 + 1030302000^2 = 102030201\ 002601^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0997399^2 + 103030302000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002601^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1050)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0997296^2 + 104000^2 = 1\ 002704^2 \\
&1020\ 0997296^2 + 10504000^2 = 10201\ 002704^2 \\
&10203020\ 0997296^2 + 1050504000^2 = 102030201\ 002704^2 \\
&102030403020\ 0997296^2 + 105050504000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002704^2 \\
&\hspace{15em} (5.1051)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0997191^2 + 106000^2 = 1\ 002809^2 \\
1020\ 0997191^2 + 10706000^2 = 10201\ 002809^2 \\
10203020\ 0997191^2 + 1070706000^2 = 102030201\ 002809^2 \\
102030403020\ 0997191^2 + 107070706000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002809^2 \\
(5.1052)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0996156^2 + 124000^2 = 1\ 003844^2 \\
1020\ 0996156^2 + 12524000^2 = 10201\ 003844^2 \\
10203020\ 0996156^2 + 1252524000^2 = 102030201\ 003844^2 \\
102030403020\ 0996156^2 + 125252524000^2 = 1020304030201\ 003844^2 \\
(5.1061)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0997084^2 + 108000^2 = 1\ 002916^2 \\
1020\ 0997084^2 + 10908000^2 = 10201\ 002916^2 \\
10203020\ 0997084^2 + 1090908000^2 = 102030201\ 002916^2 \\
102030403020\ 0997084^2 + 109090908000^2 = 1020304030201\ 002916^2 \\
(5.1053)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0996031^2 + 126000^2 = 1\ 003969^2 \\
1020\ 0996031^2 + 12726000^2 = 10201\ 003969^2 \\
10203020\ 0996031^2 + 1272726000^2 = 102030201\ 003969^2 \\
102030403020\ 0996031^2 + 127272726000^2 = 1020304030201\ 003969^2 \\
(5.1062)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0996975^2 + 110000^2 = 1\ 003025^2 \\
1020\ 0996975^2 + 11110000^2 = 10201\ 003025^2 \\
10203020\ 0996975^2 + 1111110000^2 = 102030201\ 003025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0996975^2 + 111111110000^2 = 1020304030201\ 003025^2 \\
(5.1054)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0995904^2 + 128000^2 = 1\ 004096^2 \\
1020\ 0995904^2 + 12928000^2 = 10201\ 004096^2 \\
10203020\ 0995904^2 + 1292928000^2 = 102030201\ 004096^2 \\
102030403020\ 0995904^2 + 129292928000^2 = 1020304030201\ 004096^2 \\
(5.1063)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0996864^2 + 112000^2 = 1\ 003136^2 \\
1020\ 0996864^2 + 11312000^2 = 10201\ 003136^2 \\
10203020\ 0996864^2 + 1131312000^2 = 102030201\ 003136^2 \\
102030403020\ 0996864^2 + 113131312000^2 = 1020304030201\ 003136^2 \\
(5.1055)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0995775^2 + 130000^2 = 1\ 004225^2 \\
1020\ 0995775^2 + 13130000^2 = 10201\ 004225^2 \\
10203020\ 0995775^2 + 1313130000^2 = 102030201\ 004225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0995775^2 + 131313130000^2 = 1020304030201\ 004225^2 \\
(5.1064)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0996751^2 + 114000^2 = 1\ 003249^2 \\
1020\ 0996751^2 + 11514000^2 = 10201\ 003249^2 \\
10203020\ 0996751^2 + 1151514000^2 = 102030201\ 003249^2 \\
102030403020\ 0996751^2 + 115151514000^2 = 1020304030201\ 003249^2 \\
(5.1056)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0995644^2 + 132000^2 = 1\ 004356^2 \\
1020\ 0995644^2 + 13332000^2 = 10201\ 004356^2 \\
10203020\ 0995644^2 + 1333332000^2 = 102030201\ 004356^2 \\
102030403020\ 0995644^2 + 133333332000^2 = 1020304030201\ 004356^2 \\
(5.1065)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0996636^2 + 116000^2 = 1\ 003364^2 \\
1020\ 0996636^2 + 11716000^2 = 10201\ 003364^2 \\
10203020\ 0996636^2 + 1171716000^2 = 102030201\ 003364^2 \\
102030403020\ 0996636^2 + 117171716000^2 = 1020304030201\ 003364^2 \\
(5.1057)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0995511^2 + 134000^2 = 1\ 004489^2 \\
1020\ 0995511^2 + 13534000^2 = 10201\ 004489^2 \\
10203020\ 0995511^2 + 1353534000^2 = 102030201\ 004489^2 \\
102030403020\ 0995511^2 + 135353534000^2 = 1020304030201\ 004489^2 \\
(5.1066)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0996519^2 + 118000^2 = 1\ 003481^2 \\
1020\ 0996519^2 + 11918000^2 = 10201\ 003481^2 \\
10203020\ 0996519^2 + 1191918000^2 = 102030201\ 003481^2 \\
102030403020\ 0996519^2 + 119191918000^2 = 1020304030201\ 003481^2 \\
(5.1058)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0995376^2 + 136000^2 = 1\ 004624^2 \\
1020\ 0995376^2 + 13736000^2 = 10201\ 004624^2 \\
10203020\ 0995376^2 + 1373736000^2 = 102030201\ 004624^2 \\
102030403020\ 0995376^2 + 137373736000^2 = 1020304030201\ 004624^2 \\
(5.1067)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0996400^2 + 120000^2 = 1\ 003600^2 \\
1020\ 0996400^2 + 12120000^2 = 10201\ 003600^2 \\
10203020\ 0996400^2 + 1212120000^2 = 102030201\ 003600^2 \\
102030403020\ 0996400^2 + 121212120000^2 = 1020304030201\ 003600^2 \\
(5.1059)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0995239^2 + 138000^2 = 1\ 004761^2 \\
1020\ 0995239^2 + 13938000^2 = 10201\ 004761^2 \\
10203020\ 0995239^2 + 1393938000^2 = 102030201\ 004761^2 \\
102030403020\ 0995239^2 + 139393938000^2 = 1020304030201\ 004761^2 \\
(5.1068)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0996279^2 + 122000^2 = 1\ 003721^2 \\
1020\ 0996279^2 + 12322000^2 = 10201\ 003721^2 \\
10203020\ 0996279^2 + 1232322000^2 = 102030201\ 003721^2 \\
102030403020\ 0996279^2 + 123232322000^2 = 1020304030201\ 003721^2 \\
(5.1060)
\end{array}$$

$0995100^2 + 140000^2 = 1\ 004900^2$	$0993759^2 + 158000^2 = 1\ 006241^2$
$1020\ 0995100^2 + 14140000^2 = 10201\ 004900^2$	$1020\ 0993759^2 + 15958000^2 = 10201\ 006241^2$
$10203020\ 0995100^2 + 1414140000^2 = 102030201\ 004900^2$	$10203020\ 0993759^2 + 1595958000^2 = 102030201\ 006241^2$
$102030403020\ 0995100^2 + 141414140000^2 = 1020304030201\ 004900^2$ (5.1069)	$102030403020\ 0993759^2 + 159595958000^2 = 1020304030201\ 006241^2$ (5.1078)
$0994959^2 + 142000^2 = 1\ 005041^2$	$0993600^2 + 160000^2 = 1\ 006400^2$
$1020\ 0994959^2 + 14342000^2 = 10201\ 005041^2$	$1020\ 0993600^2 + 16160000^2 = 10201\ 006400^2$
$10203020\ 0994959^2 + 1434342000^2 = 102030201\ 005041^2$	$10203020\ 0993600^2 + 1616160000^2 = 102030201\ 006400^2$
$102030403020\ 0994959^2 + 143434342000^2 = 1020304030201\ 005041^2$ (5.1070)	$102030403020\ 0993600^2 + 161616160000^2 = 1020304030201\ 006400^2$ (5.1079)
$0994816^2 + 144000^2 = 1\ 005184^2$	$0993439^2 + 162000^2 = 1\ 006561^2$
$1020\ 0994816^2 + 14544000^2 = 10201\ 005184^2$	$1020\ 0993439^2 + 16362000^2 = 10201\ 006561^2$
$10203020\ 0994816^2 + 1454544000^2 = 102030201\ 005184^2$	$10203020\ 0993439^2 + 1636362000^2 = 102030201\ 006561^2$
$102030403020\ 0994816^2 + 145454544000^2 = 1020304030201\ 005184^2$ (5.1071)	$102030403020\ 0993439^2 + 163636362000^2 = 1020304030201\ 006561^2$ (5.1080)
$0994671^2 + 146000^2 = 1\ 005329^2$	$0993276^2 + 164000^2 = 1\ 006724^2$
$1020\ 0994671^2 + 14746000^2 = 10201\ 005329^2$	$1020\ 0993276^2 + 16564000^2 = 10201\ 006724^2$
$10203020\ 0994671^2 + 1474746000^2 = 102030201\ 005329^2$	$10203020\ 0993276^2 + 1656564000^2 = 102030201\ 006724^2$
$102030403020\ 0994671^2 + 147474746000^2 = 1020304030201\ 005329^2$ (5.1072)	$102030403020\ 0993276^2 + 165656564000^2 = 1020304030201\ 006724^2$ (5.1081)
$0994524^2 + 148000^2 = 1\ 005476^2$	$0993111^2 + 166000^2 = 1\ 006889^2$
$1020\ 0994524^2 + 14948000^2 = 10201\ 005476^2$	$1020\ 0993111^2 + 16766000^2 = 10201\ 006889^2$
$10203020\ 0994524^2 + 1494948000^2 = 102030201\ 005476^2$	$10203020\ 0993111^2 + 1676766000^2 = 102030201\ 006889^2$
$102030403020\ 0994524^2 + 149494948000^2 = 1020304030201\ 005476^2$ (5.1073)	$102030403020\ 0993111^2 + 167676766000^2 = 1020304030201\ 006889^2$ (5.1082)
$0994375^2 + 150000^2 = 1\ 005625^2$	$0992944^2 + 168000^2 = 1\ 007056^2$
$1020\ 0994375^2 + 15150000^2 = 10201\ 005625^2$	$1020\ 0992944^2 + 16968000^2 = 10201\ 007056^2$
$10203020\ 0994375^2 + 1515150000^2 = 102030201\ 005625^2$	$10203020\ 0992944^2 + 1696968000^2 = 102030201\ 007056^2$
$102030403020\ 0994375^2 + 151515150000^2 = 1020304030201\ 005625^2$ (5.1074)	$102030403020\ 0992944^2 + 169696968000^2 = 1020304030201\ 007056^2$ (5.1083)
$0994224^2 + 152000^2 = 1\ 005776^2$	$0992775^2 + 170000^2 = 1\ 007225^2$
$1020\ 0994224^2 + 15352000^2 = 10201\ 005776^2$	$1020\ 0992775^2 + 17170000^2 = 10201\ 007225^2$
$10203020\ 0994224^2 + 1535352000^2 = 102030201\ 005776^2$	$10203020\ 0992775^2 + 1717170000^2 = 102030201\ 007225^2$
$102030403020\ 0994224^2 + 153535352000^2 = 1020304030201\ 005776^2$ (5.1075)	$102030403020\ 0992775^2 + 171717170000^2 = 1020304030201\ 007225^2$ (5.1084)
$0994071^2 + 154000^2 = 1\ 005929^2$	$0992604^2 + 172000^2 = 1\ 007396^2$
$1020\ 0994071^2 + 15554000^2 = 10201\ 005929^2$	$1020\ 0992604^2 + 17372000^2 = 10201\ 007396^2$
$10203020\ 0994071^2 + 1555554000^2 = 102030201\ 005929^2$	$10203020\ 0992604^2 + 1737372000^2 = 102030201\ 007396^2$
$102030403020\ 0994071^2 + 155555554000^2 = 1020304030201\ 005929^2$ (5.1076)	$102030403020\ 0992604^2 + 173737372000^2 = 1020304030201\ 007396^2$ (5.1085)
$0993916^2 + 156000^2 = 1\ 006084^2$	
$1020\ 0993916^2 + 15756000^2 = 10201\ 006084^2$	
$10203020\ 0993916^2 + 1575756000^2 = 102030201\ 006084^2$	
$102030403020\ 0993916^2 + 157575756000^2 = 1020304030201\ 006084^2$ (5.1077)	

$0992431^2 + 174000^2 = 1\ 007569^2$	$0991164^2 + 188000^2 = 1\ 008836^2$
$1020\ 0992431^2 + 17574000^2 = 10201\ 007569^2$	$1020\ 0991164^2 + 18988000^2 = 10201\ 008836^2$
$10203020\ 0992431^2 + 1757574000^2 = 102030201\ 007569^2$	$10203020\ 0991164^2 + 1898988000^2 = 102030201\ 008836^2$
$102030403020\ 0992431^2 + 175757574000^2 = 1020304030201\ 007569^2$ (5.1086)	$102030403020\ 0991164^2 + 189898988000^2 = 1020304030201\ 008836^2$ (5.1093)
$0992256^2 + 176000^2 = 1\ 007744^2$	$0990975^2 + 190000^2 = 1\ 009025^2$
$1020\ 0992256^2 + 17776000^2 = 10201\ 007744^2$	$1020\ 0990975^2 + 19190000^2 = 10201\ 009025^2$
$10203020\ 0992256^2 + 1777776000^2 = 102030201\ 007744^2$	$10203020\ 0990975^2 + 1919190000^2 = 102030201\ 009025^2$
$102030403020\ 0992256^2 + 177777776000^2 = 1020304030201\ 007744^2$ (5.1087)	$102030403020\ 0990975^2 + 191919190000^2 = 1020304030201\ 009025^2$ (5.1094)
$0992079^2 + 178000^2 = 1\ 007921^2$	$0990784^2 + 192000^2 = 1\ 009216^2$
$1020\ 0992079^2 + 17978000^2 = 10201\ 007921^2$	$1020\ 0990784^2 + 19392000^2 = 10201\ 009216^2$
$10203020\ 0992079^2 + 1797978000^2 = 102030201\ 007921^2$	$10203020\ 0990784^2 + 1939392000^2 = 102030201\ 009216^2$
$102030403020\ 0992079^2 + 179797978000^2 = 1020304030201\ 007921^2$ (5.1088)	$102030403020\ 0990784^2 + 193939392000^2 = 1020304030201\ 009216^2$ (5.1095)
$0991900^2 + 180000^2 = 1\ 008100^2$	$0990591^2 + 194000^2 = 1\ 009409^2$
$1020\ 0991900^2 + 18180000^2 = 10201\ 008100^2$	$1020\ 0990591^2 + 19594000^2 = 10201\ 009409^2$
$10203020\ 0991900^2 + 1818180000^2 = 102030201\ 008100^2$	$10203020\ 0990591^2 + 1959594000^2 = 102030201\ 009409^2$
$102030403020\ 0991900^2 + 181818180000^2 = 1020304030201\ 008100^2$ (5.1089)	$102030403020\ 0990591^2 + 195959594000^2 = 1020304030201\ 009409^2$ (5.1096)
$0991719^2 + 182000^2 = 1\ 008281^2$	$0990396^2 + 196000^2 = 1\ 009604^2$
$1020\ 0991719^2 + 18382000^2 = 10201\ 008281^2$	$1020\ 0990396^2 + 19796000^2 = 10201\ 009604^2$
$10203020\ 0991719^2 + 1838382000^2 = 102030201\ 008281^2$	$10203020\ 0990396^2 + 1979796000^2 = 102030201\ 009604^2$
$102030403020\ 0991719^2 + 183838382000^2 = 1020304030201\ 008281^2$ (5.1090)	$102030403020\ 0990396^2 + 197979796000^2 = 1020304030201\ 009604^2$ (5.1097)
$0991536^2 + 184000^2 = 1\ 008464^2$	$0990199^2 + 198000^2 = 1\ 009801^2$
$1020\ 0991536^2 + 18584000^2 = 10201\ 008464^2$	$1020\ 0990199^2 + 19998000^2 = 10201\ 009801^2$
$10203020\ 0991536^2 + 1858584000^2 = 102030201\ 008464^2$	$10203020\ 0990199^2 + 1999998000^2 = 102030201\ 009801^2$
$102030403020\ 0991536^2 + 185858584000^2 = 1020304030201\ 008464^2$ (5.1091)	$102030403020\ 0990199^2 + 199999998000^2 = 1020304030201\ 009801^2$ (5.1098)
$0991351^2 + 186000^2 = 1\ 008649^2$	$0989799^2 + 202000^2 = 1\ 010201^2$
$1020\ 0991351^2 + 18786000^2 = 10201\ 008649^2$	$1020\ 0989799^2 + 20402000^2 = 10201\ 010201^2$
$10203020\ 0991351^2 + 1878786000^2 = 102030201\ 008649^2$	$10203020\ 0989799^2 + 2040402000^2 = 102030201\ 010201^2$
$102030403020\ 0991351^2 + 187878786000^2 = 1020304030201\ 008649^2$ (5.1092)	$102030403020\ 0989799^2 + 204040402000^2 = 1020304030201\ 010201^2$ (5.1100)
$0990000^2 + 200000^2 = 1\ 010000^2$	
$1020\ 0990000^2 + 20200000^2 = 10201\ 010000^2$	
$10203020\ 0990000^2 + 2020200000^2 = 102030201\ 010000^2$	
$102030403020\ 0990000^2 + 202020200000^2 = 1020304030201\ 010000^2$ (5.1099)	

$$\begin{array}{l}
0989596^2 + 204000^2 = 1\ 010404^2 \\
1020\ 0989596^2 + 20604000^2 = 10201\ 010404^2 \\
10203020\ 0989596^2 + 2060604000^2 = 102030201\ 010404^2 \\
102030403020\ 0989596^2 + 206060604000^2 = 1020304030201\ 010404^2 \\
(5.1101)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0987679^2 + 222000^2 = 1\ 012321^2 \\
1020\ 0987679^2 + 22422000^2 = 10201\ 012321^2 \\
10203020\ 0987679^2 + 2242422000^2 = 102030201\ 012321^2 \\
102030403020\ 0987679^2 + 224242422000^2 = 1020304030201\ 012321^2 \\
(5.1110)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0989391^2 + 206000^2 = 1\ 010609^2 \\
1020\ 0989391^2 + 20806000^2 = 10201\ 010609^2 \\
10203020\ 0989391^2 + 2080806000^2 = 102030201\ 010609^2 \\
102030403020\ 0989391^2 + 208080806000^2 = 1020304030201\ 010609^2 \\
(5.1102)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0987456^2 + 224000^2 = 1\ 012544^2 \\
1020\ 0987456^2 + 22624000^2 = 10201\ 012544^2 \\
10203020\ 0987456^2 + 2262624000^2 = 102030201\ 012544^2 \\
102030403020\ 0987456^2 + 226262624000^2 = 1020304030201\ 012544^2 \\
(5.1111)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0989184^2 + 208000^2 = 1\ 010816^2 \\
1020\ 0989184^2 + 21008000^2 = 10201\ 010816^2 \\
10203020\ 0989184^2 + 2101008000^2 = 102030201\ 010816^2 \\
102030403020\ 0989184^2 + 210101008000^2 = 1020304030201\ 010816^2 \\
(5.1103)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0987231^2 + 226000^2 = 1\ 012769^2 \\
1020\ 0987231^2 + 22826000^2 = 10201\ 012769^2 \\
10203020\ 0987231^2 + 2282826000^2 = 102030201\ 012769^2 \\
102030403020\ 0987231^2 + 228282826000^2 = 1020304030201\ 012769^2 \\
(5.1112)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0988975^2 + 210000^2 = 1\ 011025^2 \\
1020\ 0988975^2 + 21210000^2 = 10201\ 011025^2 \\
10203020\ 0988975^2 + 2121210000^2 = 102030201\ 011025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0988975^2 + 212121210000^2 = 1020304030201\ 011025^2 \\
(5.1104)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0987004^2 + 228000^2 = 1\ 012996^2 \\
1020\ 0987004^2 + 23028000^2 = 10201\ 012996^2 \\
10203020\ 0987004^2 + 2303028000^2 = 102030201\ 012996^2 \\
102030403020\ 0987004^2 + 230303028000^2 = 1020304030201\ 012996^2 \\
(5.1113)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0988764^2 + 212000^2 = 1\ 011236^2 \\
1020\ 0988764^2 + 21412000^2 = 10201\ 011236^2 \\
10203020\ 0988764^2 + 2141412000^2 = 102030201\ 011236^2 \\
102030403020\ 0988764^2 + 214141412000^2 = 1020304030201\ 011236^2 \\
(5.1105)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0986775^2 + 230000^2 = 1\ 013225^2 \\
1020\ 0986775^2 + 23230000^2 = 10201\ 013225^2 \\
10203020\ 0986775^2 + 2323230000^2 = 102030201\ 013225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0986775^2 + 232323230000^2 = 1020304030201\ 013225^2 \\
(5.1114)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0988551^2 + 214000^2 = 1\ 011449^2 \\
1020\ 0988551^2 + 21614000^2 = 10201\ 011449^2 \\
10203020\ 0988551^2 + 2161614000^2 = 102030201\ 011449^2 \\
102030403020\ 0988551^2 + 216161614000^2 = 1020304030201\ 011449^2 \\
(5.1106)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0986544^2 + 232000^2 = 1\ 013456^2 \\
1020\ 0986544^2 + 23432000^2 = 10201\ 013456^2 \\
10203020\ 0986544^2 + 2343432000^2 = 102030201\ 013456^2 \\
102030403020\ 0986544^2 + 234343432000^2 = 1020304030201\ 013456^2 \\
(5.1115)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0988336^2 + 216000^2 = 1\ 011664^2 \\
1020\ 0988336^2 + 21816000^2 = 10201\ 011664^2 \\
10203020\ 0988336^2 + 2181816000^2 = 102030201\ 011664^2 \\
102030403020\ 0988336^2 + 218181816000^2 = 1020304030201\ 011664^2 \\
(5.1107)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0986311^2 + 234000^2 = 1\ 013689^2 \\
1020\ 0986311^2 + 23634000^2 = 10201\ 013689^2 \\
10203020\ 0986311^2 + 2363634000^2 = 102030201\ 013689^2 \\
102030403020\ 0986311^2 + 236363634000^2 = 1020304030201\ 013689^2 \\
(5.1116)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0988119^2 + 218000^2 = 1\ 011881^2 \\
1020\ 0988119^2 + 22018000^2 = 10201\ 011881^2 \\
10203020\ 0988119^2 + 2202018000^2 = 102030201\ 011881^2 \\
102030403020\ 0988119^2 + 220202018000^2 = 1020304030201\ 011881^2 \\
(5.1108)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0986076^2 + 236000^2 = 1\ 013924^2 \\
1020\ 0986076^2 + 23836000^2 = 10201\ 013924^2 \\
10203020\ 0986076^2 + 2383836000^2 = 102030201\ 013924^2 \\
102030403020\ 0986076^2 + 238383836000^2 = 1020304030201\ 013924^2 \\
(5.1117)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0987900^2 + 220000^2 = 1\ 012100^2 \\
1020\ 0987900^2 + 22220000^2 = 10201\ 012100^2 \\
10203020\ 0987900^2 + 2222220000^2 = 102030201\ 012100^2 \\
102030403020\ 0987900^2 + 222222220000^2 = 1020304030201\ 012100^2 \\
(5.1109)
\end{array}$$

$0985839^2 + 238000^2 = 1\ 014161^2$	$0983616^2 + 256000^2 = 1\ 016384^2$
$1020\ 0985839^2 + 24038000^2 = 10201\ 014161^2$	$1020\ 0983616^2 + 25856000^2 = 10201\ 016384^2$
$10203020\ 0985839^2 + 2404038000^2 = 102030201\ 014161^2$	$10203020\ 0983616^2 + 2585856000^2 = 102030201\ 016384^2$
$102030403020\ 0985839^2 + 240404038000^2 = 1020304030201\ 014161^2$ (5.1118)	$102030403020\ 0983616^2 + 258585856000^2 = 1020304030201\ 016384^2$ (5.1127)
$0985600^2 + 240000^2 = 1\ 014400^2$	$0983359^2 + 258000^2 = 1\ 016641^2$
$1020\ 0985600^2 + 24240000^2 = 10201\ 014400^2$	$1020\ 0983359^2 + 26058000^2 = 10201\ 016641^2$
$10203020\ 0985600^2 + 2424240000^2 = 102030201\ 014400^2$	$10203020\ 0983359^2 + 2606058000^2 = 102030201\ 016641^2$
$102030403020\ 0985600^2 + 242424240000^2 = 1020304030201\ 014400^2$ (5.1119)	$102030403020\ 0983359^2 + 260606058000^2 = 1020304030201\ 016641^2$ (5.1128)
$0985359^2 + 242000^2 = 1\ 014641^2$	$0983100^2 + 260000^2 = 1\ 016900^2$
$1020\ 0985359^2 + 24442000^2 = 10201\ 014641^2$	$1020\ 0983100^2 + 26260000^2 = 10201\ 016900^2$
$10203020\ 0985359^2 + 2444442000^2 = 102030201\ 014641^2$	$10203020\ 0983100^2 + 2626260000^2 = 102030201\ 016900^2$
$102030403020\ 0985359^2 + 244444442000^2 = 1020304030201\ 014641^2$ (5.1120)	$102030403020\ 0983100^2 + 262626260000^2 = 1020304030201\ 016900^2$ (5.1129)
$0985116^2 + 244000^2 = 1\ 014884^2$	$0982839^2 + 262000^2 = 1\ 017161^2$
$1020\ 0985116^2 + 24644000^2 = 10201\ 014884^2$	$1020\ 0982839^2 + 26462000^2 = 10201\ 017161^2$
$10203020\ 0985116^2 + 2464644000^2 = 102030201\ 014884^2$	$10203020\ 0982839^2 + 2646462000^2 = 102030201\ 017161^2$
$102030403020\ 0985116^2 + 246464644000^2 = 1020304030201\ 014884^2$ (5.1121)	$102030403020\ 0982839^2 + 264646462000^2 = 1020304030201\ 017161^2$ (5.1130)
$0984871^2 + 246000^2 = 1\ 015129^2$	$0982576^2 + 264000^2 = 1\ 017424^2$
$1020\ 0984871^2 + 24846000^2 = 10201\ 015129^2$	$1020\ 0982576^2 + 26664000^2 = 10201\ 017424^2$
$10203020\ 0984871^2 + 2484846000^2 = 102030201\ 015129^2$	$10203020\ 0982576^2 + 2666664000^2 = 102030201\ 017424^2$
$102030403020\ 0984871^2 + 248484846000^2 = 1020304030201\ 015129^2$ (5.1122)	$102030403020\ 0982576^2 + 266666664000^2 = 1020304030201\ 017424^2$ (5.1131)
$0984624^2 + 248000^2 = 1\ 015376^2$	$0982311^2 + 266000^2 = 1\ 017689^2$
$1020\ 0984624^2 + 25048000^2 = 10201\ 015376^2$	$1020\ 0982311^2 + 26866000^2 = 10201\ 017689^2$
$10203020\ 0984624^2 + 2505048000^2 = 102030201\ 015376^2$	$10203020\ 0982311^2 + 2686866000^2 = 102030201\ 017689^2$
$102030403020\ 0984624^2 + 250505048000^2 = 1020304030201\ 015376^2$ (5.1123)	$102030403020\ 0982311^2 + 268686866000^2 = 1020304030201\ 017689^2$ (5.1132)
$0984375^2 + 250000^2 = 1\ 015625^2$	$0982044^2 + 268000^2 = 1\ 017956^2$
$1020\ 0984375^2 + 25250000^2 = 10201\ 015625^2$	$1020\ 0982044^2 + 27068000^2 = 10201\ 017956^2$
$10203020\ 0984375^2 + 2525250000^2 = 102030201\ 015625^2$	$10203020\ 0982044^2 + 2707068000^2 = 102030201\ 017956^2$
$102030403020\ 0984375^2 + 252525250000^2 = 1020304030201\ 015625^2$ (5.1124)	$102030403020\ 0982044^2 + 270707068000^2 = 1020304030201\ 017956^2$ (5.1133)
$0984124^2 + 252000^2 = 1\ 015876^2$	$0981775^2 + 270000^2 = 1\ 018225^2$
$1020\ 0984124^2 + 25452000^2 = 10201\ 015876^2$	$1020\ 0981775^2 + 27270000^2 = 10201\ 018225^2$
$10203020\ 0984124^2 + 2545452000^2 = 102030201\ 015876^2$	$10203020\ 0981775^2 + 2727270000^2 = 102030201\ 018225^2$
$102030403020\ 0984124^2 + 254545452000^2 = 1020304030201\ 015876^2$ (5.1125)	$102030403020\ 0981775^2 + 272727270000^2 = 1020304030201\ 018225^2$ (5.1134)
$0983871^2 + 254000^2 = 1\ 016129^2$	
$1020\ 0983871^2 + 25654000^2 = 10201\ 016129^2$	
$10203020\ 0983871^2 + 2565654000^2 = 102030201\ 016129^2$	
$102030403020\ 0983871^2 + 256565654000^2 = 1020304030201\ 016129^2$ (5.1126)	

$$\begin{array}{l}
0981504^2 + 272000^2 = 1\ 018496^2 \\
1020\ 0981504^2 + 27472000^2 = 10201\ 018496^2 \\
10203020\ 0981504^2 + 2747472000^2 = 102030201\ 018496^2 \\
102030403020\ 0981504^2 + 274747472000^2 = 1020304030201\ 018496^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1135) \\
0981231^2 + 274000^2 = 1\ 018769^2 \\
1020\ 0981231^2 + 27674000^2 = 10201\ 018769^2 \\
10203020\ 0981231^2 + 2767674000^2 = 102030201\ 018769^2 \\
102030403020\ 0981231^2 + 276767674000^2 = 1020304030201\ 018769^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1136) \\
0980956^2 + 276000^2 = 1\ 019044^2 \\
1020\ 0980956^2 + 27876000^2 = 10201\ 019044^2 \\
10203020\ 0980956^2 + 2787876000^2 = 102030201\ 019044^2 \\
102030403020\ 0980956^2 + 278787876000^2 = 1020304030201\ 019044^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1137) \\
0980679^2 + 278000^2 = 1\ 019321^2 \\
1020\ 0980679^2 + 28078000^2 = 10201\ 019321^2 \\
10203020\ 0980679^2 + 2808078000^2 = 102030201\ 019321^2 \\
102030403020\ 0980679^2 + 280808078000^2 = 1020304030201\ 019321^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1138) \\
0980400^2 + 280000^2 = 1\ 019600^2 \\
1020\ 0980400^2 + 28280000^2 = 10201\ 019600^2 \\
10203020\ 0980400^2 + 2828280000^2 = 102030201\ 019600^2 \\
102030403020\ 0980400^2 + 282828280000^2 = 1020304030201\ 019600^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1139) \\
0980119^2 + 282000^2 = 1\ 019881^2 \\
1020\ 0980119^2 + 28482000^2 = 10201\ 019881^2 \\
10203020\ 0980119^2 + 2848482000^2 = 102030201\ 019881^2 \\
102030403020\ 0980119^2 + 284848482000^2 = 1020304030201\ 019881^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1140) \\
0979836^2 + 284000^2 = 10201\ 64^2 \\
1020\ 0979836^2 + 28684000^2 = 10201\ 020164^2 \\
10203020\ 0979836^2 + 2868684000^2 = 102030201\ 020164^2 \\
102030403020\ 0979836^2 + 286868684000^2 = 1020304030201\ 020164^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1141) \\
0979551^2 + 286000^2 = 1\ 020449^2 \\
1020\ 0979551^2 + 28886000^2 = 10201\ 020449^2 \\
10203020\ 0979551^2 + 2888886000^2 = 102030201\ 020449^2 \\
102030403020\ 0979551^2 + 288888886000^2 = 1020304030201\ 020449^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1142) \\
0979264^2 + 288000^2 = 1\ 020736^2 \\
1020\ 0979264^2 + 29088000^2 = 10201\ 020736^2 \\
10203020\ 0979264^2 + 2909088000^2 = 102030201\ 020736^2 \\
102030403020\ 0979264^2 + 290909088000^2 = 1020304030201\ 020736^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1143) \\
0978975^2 + 290000^2 = 1\ 021025^2 \\
1020\ 0978975^2 + 29290000^2 = 10201\ 021025^2 \\
10203020\ 0978975^2 + 2929290000^2 = 102030201\ 021025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0978975^2 + 292929290000^2 = 1020304030201\ 021025^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1144) \\
0978684^2 + 292000^2 = 1\ 021316^2 \\
1020\ 0978684^2 + 29492000^2 = 10201\ 021316^2 \\
10203020\ 0978684^2 + 2949492000^2 = 102030201\ 021316^2 \\
102030403020\ 0978684^2 + 294949492000^2 = 1020304030201\ 021316^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1145) \\
0978391^2 + 294000^2 = 1\ 021609^2 \\
1020\ 0978391^2 + 29694000^2 = 10201\ 021609^2 \\
10203020\ 0978391^2 + 2969694000^2 = 102030201\ 021609^2 \\
102030403020\ 0978391^2 + 296969694000^2 = 1020304030201\ 021609^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1146) \\
0978096^2 + 296000^2 = 1\ 021904^2 \\
1020\ 0978096^2 + 29896000^2 = 10201\ 021904^2 \\
10203020\ 0978096^2 + 2989896000^2 = 102030201\ 021904^2 \\
102030403020\ 0978096^2 + 298989896000^2 = 1020304030201\ 021904^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1147) \\
0977799^2 + 298000^2 = 1\ 022201^2 \\
1020\ 0977799^2 + 30098000^2 = 10201\ 022201^2 \\
10203020\ 0977799^2 + 3010098000^2 = 102030201\ 022201^2 \\
102030403020\ 0977799^2 + 301010098000^2 = 1020304030201\ 022201^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1148) \\
0977500^2 + 300000^2 = 1\ 022500^2 \\
1020\ 0977500^2 + 30300000^2 = 10201\ 022500^2 \\
10203020\ 0977500^2 + 3030300000^2 = 102030201\ 022500^2 \\
102030403020\ 0977500^2 + 303030300000^2 = 1020304030201\ 022500^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1149) \\
0977199^2 + 302000^2 = 1\ 022801^2 \\
1020\ 0977199^2 + 30502000^2 = 10201\ 022801^2 \\
10203020\ 0977199^2 + 3050502000^2 = 102030201\ 022801^2 \\
102030403020\ 0977199^2 + 305050502000^2 = 1020304030201\ 022801^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1150) \\
0976896^2 + 304000^2 = 1\ 023104^2 \\
1020\ 0976896^2 + 30704000^2 = 10201\ 023104^2 \\
10203020\ 0976896^2 + 3070704000^2 = 102030201\ 023104^2 \\
102030403020\ 0976896^2 + 307070704000^2 = 1020304030201\ 023104^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1151)
\end{array}$$

$0976591^2 + 306000^2 = 1\ 023409^2$	$0973756^2 + 324000^2 = 1\ 026244^2$
$1020\ 0976591^2 + 30906000^2 = 10201\ 023409^2$	$1020\ 0973756^2 + 32724000^2 = 10201\ 026244^2$
$10203020\ 0976591^2 + 3090906000^2 = 102030201\ 023409^2$	$10203020\ 0973756^2 + 3272724000^2 = 102030201\ 026244^2$
$102030403020\ 0976591^2 + 309090906000^2 = 1020304030201\ 023409^2$ (5.1152)	$102030403020\ 0973756^2 + 327272724000^2 = 1020304030201\ 026244^2$ (5.1161)
$0976284^2 + 308000^2 = 1\ 023716^2$	$0973431^2 + 326000^2 = 1\ 026569^2$
$1020\ 0976284^2 + 31108000^2 = 10201\ 023716^2$	$1020\ 0973431^2 + 32926000^2 = 10201\ 026569^2$
$10203020\ 0976284^2 + 3111108000^2 = 102030201\ 023716^2$	$10203020\ 0973431^2 + 3292926000^2 = 102030201\ 026569^2$
$102030403020\ 0976284^2 + 311111108000^2 = 1020304030201\ 023716^2$ (5.1153)	$102030403020\ 0973431^2 + 329292926000^2 = 1020304030201\ 026569^2$ (5.1162)
$0975975^2 + 310000^2 = 1\ 024025^2$	$0973104^2 + 328000^2 = 1\ 026896^2$
$1020\ 0975975^2 + 31310000^2 = 10201\ 024025^2$	$1020\ 0973104^2 + 33128000^2 = 10201\ 026896^2$
$10203020\ 0975975^2 + 3131310000^2 = 102030201\ 024025^2$	$10203020\ 0973104^2 + 3313128000^2 = 102030201\ 026896^2$
$102030403020\ 0975975^2 + 313131310000^2 = 1020304030201\ 024025^2$ (5.1154)	$102030403020\ 0973104^2 + 331313128000^2 = 1020304030201\ 026896^2$ (5.1163)
$0975664^2 + 312000^2 = 1\ 024336^2$	$0972775^2 + 330000^2 = 1\ 027225^2$
$1020\ 0975664^2 + 31512000^2 = 10201\ 024336^2$	$1020\ 0972775^2 + 33330000^2 = 10201\ 027225^2$
$10203020\ 0975664^2 + 3151512000^2 = 102030201\ 024336^2$	$10203020\ 0972775^2 + 3333330000^2 = 102030201\ 027225^2$
$102030403020\ 0975664^2 + 315151512000^2 = 1020304030201\ 024336^2$ (5.1155)	$102030403020\ 0972775^2 + 33333330000^2 = 1020304030201\ 027225^2$ (5.1164)
$0975351^2 + 314000^2 = 1\ 024649^2$	$0972444^2 + 332000^2 = 1\ 027556^2$
$1020\ 0975351^2 + 31714000^2 = 10201\ 024649^2$	$1020\ 0972444^2 + 33532000^2 = 10201\ 027556^2$
$10203020\ 0975351^2 + 3171714000^2 = 102030201\ 024649^2$	$10203020\ 0972444^2 + 3353532000^2 = 102030201\ 027556^2$
$102030403020\ 0975351^2 + 317171714000^2 = 1020304030201\ 024649^2$ (5.1156)	$102030403020\ 0972444^2 + 335353532000^2 = 1020304030201\ 027556^2$ (5.1165)
$0975036^2 + 316000^2 = 1\ 024964^2$	$0972111^2 + 334000^2 = 1\ 027889^2$
$1020\ 0975036^2 + 31916000^2 = 10201\ 024964^2$	$1020\ 0972111^2 + 33734000^2 = 10201\ 027889^2$
$10203020\ 0975036^2 + 3191916000^2 = 102030201\ 024964^2$	$10203020\ 0972111^2 + 3373734000^2 = 102030201\ 027889^2$
$102030403020\ 0975036^2 + 319191916000^2 = 1020304030201\ 024964^2$ (5.1157)	$102030403020\ 0972111^2 + 337373734000^2 = 1020304030201\ 027889^2$ (5.1166)
$0974719^2 + 318000^2 = 1\ 025281^2$	$0971776^2 + 336000^2 = 1\ 028224^2$
$1020\ 0974719^2 + 32118000^2 = 10201\ 025281^2$	$1020\ 0971776^2 + 33936000^2 = 10201\ 028224^2$
$10203020\ 0974719^2 + 3212118000^2 = 102030201\ 025281^2$	$10203020\ 0971776^2 + 3393936000^2 = 102030201\ 028224^2$
$102030403020\ 0974719^2 + 321212118000^2 = 1020304030201\ 025281^2$ (5.1158)	$102030403020\ 0971776^2 + 339393936000^2 = 1020304030201\ 028224^2$ (5.1167)
$0974400^2 + 320000^2 = 1\ 025600^2$	$0971439^2 + 338000^2 = 1\ 028561^2$
$1020\ 0974400^2 + 32320000^2 = 10201\ 025600^2$	$1020\ 0971439^2 + 34138000^2 = 10201\ 028561^2$
$10203020\ 0974400^2 + 3232320000^2 = 102030201\ 025600^2$	$10203020\ 0971439^2 + 3414138000^2 = 102030201\ 028561^2$
$102030403020\ 0974400^2 + 323232320000^2 = 1020304030201\ 025600^2$ (5.1159)	$102030403020\ 0971439^2 + 341414138000^2 = 1020304030201\ 028561^2$ (5.1168)
$0974079^2 + 322000^2 = 1\ 025921^2$	
$1020\ 0974079^2 + 32522000^2 = 10201\ 025921^2$	
$10203020\ 0974079^2 + 3252522000^2 = 102030201\ 025921^2$	
$102030403020\ 0974079^2 + 325252522000^2 = 1020304030201\ 025921^2$ (5.1160)	

$0971100^2 + 340000^2 = 1\ 028900^2$	$0967959^2 + 358000^2 = 1\ 032041^2$
$1020\ 0971100^2 + 34340000^2 = 10201\ 028900^2$	$1020\ 0967959^2 + 36158000^2 = 10201\ 032041^2$
$10203020\ 0971100^2 + 3434340000^2 = 102030201\ 028900^2$	$10203020\ 0967959^2 + 3616158000^2 = 102030201\ 032041^2$
$102030403020\ 0971100^2 + 343434340000^2 = 1020304030201\ 028900^2$ (5.1169)	$102030403020\ 0967959^2 + 361616158000^2 = 1020304030201\ 032041^2$ (5.1178)
$0970759^2 + 342000^2 = 1\ 029241^2$	$0967600^2 + 360000^2 = 1\ 032400^2$
$1020\ 0970759^2 + 34542000^2 = 10201\ 029241^2$	$1020\ 0967600^2 + 36360000^2 = 10201\ 032400^2$
$10203020\ 0970759^2 + 3454542000^2 = 102030201\ 029241^2$	$10203020\ 0967600^2 + 3636360000^2 = 102030201\ 032400^2$
$102030403020\ 0970759^2 + 345454542000^2 = 1020304030201\ 029241^2$ (5.1170)	$102030403020\ 0967600^2 + 363636360000^2 = 1020304030201\ 032400^2$ (5.1179)
$0970416^2 + 344000^2 = 1\ 029584^2$	$0967239^2 + 362000^2 = 1\ 032761^2$
$1020\ 0970416^2 + 34744000^2 = 10201\ 029584^2$	$1020\ 0967239^2 + 36562000^2 = 10201\ 032761^2$
$10203020\ 0970416^2 + 3474744000^2 = 102030201\ 029584^2$	$10203020\ 0967239^2 + 3656562000^2 = 102030201\ 032761^2$
$102030403020\ 0970416^2 + 347474744000^2 = 1020304030201\ 029584^2$ (5.1171)	$102030403020\ 0967239^2 + 365656562000^2 = 1020304030201\ 032761^2$ (5.1180)
$0970071^2 + 346000^2 = 1\ 029929^2$	$0966876^2 + 364000^2 = 1\ 033124^2$
$1020\ 0970071^2 + 34946000^2 = 10201\ 029929^2$	$1020\ 0966876^2 + 36764000^2 = 10201\ 033124^2$
$10203020\ 0970071^2 + 3494946000^2 = 102030201\ 029929^2$	$10203020\ 0966876^2 + 3676764000^2 = 102030201\ 033124^2$
$102030403020\ 0970071^2 + 349494946000^2 = 1020304030201\ 029929^2$ (5.1172)	$102030403020\ 0966876^2 + 367676764000^2 = 1020304030201\ 033124^2$ (5.1181)
$0969724^2 + 348000^2 = 1\ 030276^2$	$0966511^2 + 366000^2 = 1\ 033489^2$
$1020\ 0969724^2 + 35148000^2 = 10201\ 030276^2$	$1020\ 0966511^2 + 36966000^2 = 10201\ 033489^2$
$10203020\ 0969724^2 + 3515148000^2 = 102030201\ 030276^2$	$10203020\ 0966511^2 + 3696966000^2 = 102030201\ 033489^2$
$102030403020\ 0969724^2 + 351515148000^2 = 1020304030201\ 030276^2$ (5.1173)	$102030403020\ 0966511^2 + 369696966000^2 = 1020304030201\ 033489^2$ (5.1182)
$0969375^2 + 350000^2 = 1\ 030625^2$	$0966144^2 + 368000^2 = 1\ 033856^2$
$1020\ 0969375^2 + 35350000^2 = 10201\ 030625^2$	$1020\ 0966144^2 + 37168000^2 = 10201\ 033856^2$
$10203020\ 0969375^2 + 3535350000^2 = 102030201\ 030625^2$	$10203020\ 0966144^2 + 3717168000^2 = 102030201\ 033856^2$
$102030403020\ 0969375^2 + 353535350000^2 = 1020304030201\ 030625^2$ (5.1174)	$102030403020\ 0966144^2 + 371717168000^2 = 1020304030201\ 033856^2$ (5.1183)
$0969024^2 + 352000^2 = 1\ 030976^2$	$0965775^2 + 370000^2 = 1\ 034225^2$
$1020\ 0969024^2 + 35552000^2 = 10201\ 030976^2$	$1020\ 0965775^2 + 37370000^2 = 10201\ 034225^2$
$10203020\ 0969024^2 + 3555552000^2 = 102030201\ 030976^2$	$10203020\ 0965775^2 + 3737370000^2 = 102030201\ 034225^2$
$102030403020\ 0969024^2 + 355555552000^2 = 1020304030201\ 030976^2$ (5.1175)	$102030403020\ 0965775^2 + 373737370000^2 = 1020304030201\ 034225^2$ (5.1184)
$0968671^2 + 354000^2 = 1\ 031329^2$	$0965404^2 + 372000^2 = 1\ 034596^2$
$1020\ 0968671^2 + 35754000^2 = 10201\ 031329^2$	$1020\ 0965404^2 + 37572000^2 = 10201\ 034596^2$
$10203020\ 0968671^2 + 3575754000^2 = 102030201\ 031329^2$	$10203020\ 0965404^2 + 3757572000^2 = 102030201\ 034596^2$
$102030403020\ 0968671^2 + 357575754000^2 = 1020304030201\ 031329^2$ (5.1176)	$102030403020\ 0965404^2 + 375757572000^2 = 1020304030201\ 034596^2$ (5.1185)
$0968316^2 + 356000^2 = 1\ 031684^2$	
$1020\ 0968316^2 + 35956000^2 = 10201\ 031684^2$	
$10203020\ 0968316^2 + 3595956000^2 = 102030201\ 031684^2$	
$102030403020\ 0968316^2 + 359595956000^2 = 1020304030201\ 031684^2$ (5.1177)	

$0965031^2 + 374000^2 = 1\ 034969^2$	$0962364^2 + 388000^2 = 1\ 037636^2$
$1020\ 0965031^2 + 37774000^2 = 10201\ 034969^2$	$1020\ 0962364^2 + 39188000^2 = 10201\ 037636^2$
$10203020\ 0965031^2 + 3777774000^2 = 102030201\ 034969^2$	$10203020\ 0962364^2 + 3919188000^2 = 102030201\ 037636^2$
$102030403020\ 0965031^2 + 377777774000^2 = 1020304030201\ 034969^2$ (5.1186)	$102030403020\ 0962364^2 + 391919188000^2 = 1020304030201\ 037636^2$ (5.1193)
$0964656^2 + 376000^2 = 1\ 035344^2$	$0961975^2 + 390000^2 = 1\ 038025^2$
$1020\ 0964656^2 + 37976000^2 = 10201\ 035344^2$	$1020\ 0961975^2 + 39390000^2 = 10201\ 038025^2$
$10203020\ 0964656^2 + 3797976000^2 = 102030201\ 035344^2$	$10203020\ 0961975^2 + 3939390000^2 = 102030201\ 038025^2$
$102030403020\ 0964656^2 + 379797976000^2 = 1020304030201\ 035344^2$ (5.1187)	$102030403020\ 0961975^2 + 393939390000^2 = 1020304030201\ 038025^2$ (5.1194)
$0964279^2 + 378000^2 = 1\ 035721^2$	$0961584^2 + 392000^2 = 1\ 038416^2$
$1020\ 0964279^2 + 38178000^2 = 10201\ 035721^2$	$1020\ 0961584^2 + 39592000^2 = 10201\ 038416^2$
$10203020\ 0964279^2 + 3818178000^2 = 102030201\ 035721^2$	$10203020\ 0961584^2 + 3959592000^2 = 102030201\ 038416^2$
$102030403020\ 0964279^2 + 381818178000^2 = 1020304030201\ 035721^2$ (5.1188)	$102030403020\ 0961584^2 + 395959592000^2 = 1020304030201\ 038416^2$ (5.1195)
$0963900^2 + 380000^2 = 1\ 036100^2$	$0961191^2 + 394000^2 = 1\ 038809^2$
$1020\ 0963900^2 + 38380000^2 = 10201\ 036100^2$	$1020\ 0961191^2 + 39794000^2 = 10201\ 038809^2$
$10203020\ 0963900^2 + 3838380000^2 = 102030201\ 036100^2$	$10203020\ 0961191^2 + 3979794000^2 = 102030201\ 038809^2$
$102030403020\ 0963900^2 + 383838380000^2 = 1020304030201\ 036100^2$ (5.1189)	$102030403020\ 0961191^2 + 397979794000^2 = 1020304030201\ 038809^2$ (5.1196)
$0963519^2 + 382000^2 = 1\ 036481^2$	$0960796^2 + 396000^2 = 1\ 039204^2$
$1020\ 0963519^2 + 38582000^2 = 10201\ 036481^2$	$1020\ 0960796^2 + 39996000^2 = 10201\ 039204^2$
$10203020\ 0963519^2 + 3858582000^2 = 102030201\ 036481^2$	$10203020\ 0960796^2 + 3999996000^2 = 102030201\ 039204^2$
$102030403020\ 0963519^2 + 385858582000^2 = 1020304030201\ 036481^2$ (5.1190)	$102030403020\ 0960796^2 + 399999996000^2 = 1020304030201\ 039204^2$ (5.1197)
$0963136^2 + 384000^2 = 1\ 036864^2$	$0960399^2 + 398000^2 = 1\ 039601^2$
$1020\ 0963136^2 + 38784000^2 = 10201\ 036864^2$	$1020\ 0960399^2 + 40198000^2 = 10201\ 039601^2$
$10203020\ 0963136^2 + 3878784000^2 = 102030201\ 036864^2$	$10203020\ 0960399^2 + 4020198000^2 = 102030201\ 039601^2$
$102030403020\ 0963136^2 + 387878784000^2 = 1020304030201\ 036864^2$ (5.1191)	$102030403020\ 0960399^2 + 402020198000^2 = 1020304030201\ 039601^2$ (5.1198)
$0962751^2 + 386000^2 = 1\ 037249^2$	$0960000^2 + 400000^2 = 1\ 040000^2$
$1020\ 0962751^2 + 38986000^2 = 10201\ 037249^2$	$1020\ 0960000^2 + 40400000^2 = 10201\ 040000^2$
$10203020\ 0962751^2 + 3898986000^2 = 102030201\ 037249^2$	$10203020\ 0960000^2 + 4040400000^2 = 102030201\ 040000^2$
$102030403020\ 0962751^2 + 389898986000^2 = 1020304030201\ 037249^2$ (5.1192)	$102030403020\ 0960000^2 + 404040400000^2 = 1020304030201\ 040000^2$ (5.1199)
$0960000^2 + 400000^2 = 1\ 040000^2$	$0959599^2 + 402000^2 = 1\ 040401^2$
$1020\ 0960000^2 + 40400000^2 = 10201\ 040000^2$	$1020\ 0959599^2 + 40602000^2 = 10201\ 040401^2$
$10203020\ 0960000^2 + 4040400000^2 = 102030201\ 040000^2$	$10203020\ 0959599^2 + 4060602000^2 = 102030201\ 040401^2$
$102030403020\ 0960000^2 + 404040400000^2 = 1020304030201\ 040000^2$ (5.1199)	$102030403020\ 0959599^2 + 406060602000^2 = 1020304030201\ 040401^2$ (5.1200)

$$\begin{array}{l}
0959196^2 + 404000^2 = 1\ 040804^2 \\
1020\ 0959196^2 + 40804000^2 = 10201\ 040804^2 \\
10203020\ 0959196^2 + 4080804000^2 = 102030201\ 040804^2 \\
102030403020\ 0959196^2 + 408080804000^2 = 1020304030201\ 040804^2 \\
(5.1201)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0955479^2 + 422000^2 = 1\ 044521^2 \\
1020\ 0955479^2 + 42622000^2 = 10201\ 044521^2 \\
10203020\ 0955479^2 + 4262622000^2 = 102030201\ 044521^2 \\
102030403020\ 0955479^2 + 426262622000^2 = 1020304030201\ 044521^2 \\
(5.1210)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0958791^2 + 406000^2 = 1\ 041209^2 \\
1020\ 0958791^2 + 41006000^2 = 10201\ 041209^2 \\
10203020\ 0958791^2 + 4101006000^2 = 102030201\ 041209^2 \\
102030403020\ 0958791^2 + 410101006000^2 = 1020304030201\ 041209^2 \\
(5.1202)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0955056^2 + 424000^2 = 1\ 044944^2 \\
1020\ 0955056^2 + 42824000^2 = 10201\ 044944^2 \\
10203020\ 0955056^2 + 4282824000^2 = 102030201\ 044944^2 \\
102030403020\ 0955056^2 + 428282824000^2 = 1020304030201\ 044944^2 \\
(5.1211)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0958384^2 + 408000^2 = 1\ 041616^2 \\
1020\ 0958384^2 + 41208000^2 = 10201\ 041616^2 \\
10203020\ 0958384^2 + 4121208000^2 = 102030201\ 041616^2 \\
102030403020\ 0958384^2 + 412121208000^2 = 1020304030201\ 041616^2 \\
(5.1203)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0954631^2 + 426000^2 = 1\ 045369^2 \\
1020\ 0954631^2 + 43026000^2 = 10201\ 045369^2 \\
10203020\ 0954631^2 + 4303026000^2 = 102030201\ 045369^2 \\
102030403020\ 0954631^2 + 430303026000^2 = 1020304030201\ 045369^2 \\
(5.1212)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0957975^2 + 410000^2 = 1\ 042025^2 \\
1020\ 0957975^2 + 41410000^2 = 10201\ 042025^2 \\
10203020\ 0957975^2 + 4141410000^2 = 102030201\ 042025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0957975^2 + 414141410000^2 = 1020304030201\ 042025^2 \\
(5.1204)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0954204^2 + 428000^2 = 1\ 045796^2 \\
1020\ 0954204^2 + 43228000^2 = 10201\ 045796^2 \\
10203020\ 0954204^2 + 4323228000^2 = 102030201\ 045796^2 \\
102030403020\ 0954204^2 + 432323228000^2 = 1020304030201\ 045796^2 \\
(5.1213)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0957564^2 + 412000^2 = 1\ 042436^2 \\
1020\ 0957564^2 + 41612000^2 = 10201\ 042436^2 \\
10203020\ 0957564^2 + 4161612000^2 = 102030201\ 042436^2 \\
102030403020\ 0957564^2 + 416161612000^2 = 1020304030201\ 042436^2 \\
(5.1205)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0953775^2 + 430000^2 = 1\ 046225^2 \\
1020\ 0953775^2 + 43430000^2 = 10201\ 046225^2 \\
10203020\ 0953775^2 + 4343430000^2 = 102030201\ 046225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0953775^2 + 434343430000^2 = 1020304030201\ 046225^2 \\
(5.1214)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0957151^2 + 414000^2 = 1\ 042849^2 \\
1020\ 0957151^2 + 41814000^2 = 10201\ 042849^2 \\
10203020\ 0957151^2 + 4181814000^2 = 102030201\ 042849^2 \\
102030403020\ 0957151^2 + 418181814000^2 = 1020304030201\ 042849^2 \\
(5.1206)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0953344^2 + 432000^2 = 1\ 046656^2 \\
1020\ 0953344^2 + 43632000^2 = 10201\ 046656^2 \\
10203020\ 0953344^2 + 4363632000^2 = 102030201\ 046656^2 \\
102030403020\ 0953344^2 + 436363632000^2 = 1020304030201\ 046656^2 \\
(5.1215)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0956736^2 + 416000^2 = 1\ 043264^2 \\
1020\ 0956736^2 + 42016000^2 = 10201\ 043264^2 \\
10203020\ 0956736^2 + 4202016000^2 = 102030201\ 043264^2 \\
102030403020\ 0956736^2 + 420202016000^2 = 1020304030201\ 043264^2 \\
(5.1207)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0952911^2 + 434000^2 = 1\ 047089^2 \\
1020\ 0952911^2 + 43834000^2 = 10201\ 047089^2 \\
10203020\ 0952911^2 + 4383834000^2 = 102030201\ 047089^2 \\
102030403020\ 0952911^2 + 438383834000^2 = 1020304030201\ 047089^2 \\
(5.1216)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0956319^2 + 418000^2 = 1\ 043681^2 \\
1020\ 0956319^2 + 42218000^2 = 10201\ 043681^2 \\
10203020\ 0956319^2 + 4222218000^2 = 102030201\ 043681^2 \\
102030403020\ 0956319^2 + 422222218000^2 = 1020304030201\ 043681^2 \\
(5.1208)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0952476^2 + 436000^2 = 1\ 047524^2 \\
1020\ 0952476^2 + 44036000^2 = 10201\ 047524^2 \\
10203020\ 0952476^2 + 4404036000^2 = 102030201\ 047524^2 \\
102030403020\ 0952476^2 + 440404036000^2 = 1020304030201\ 047524^2 \\
(5.1217)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0955900^2 + 420000^2 = 1\ 044100^2 \\
1020\ 0955900^2 + 42420000^2 = 10201\ 044100^2 \\
10203020\ 0955900^2 + 4242420000^2 = 102030201\ 044100^2 \\
102030403020\ 0955900^2 + 424242420000^2 = 1020304030201\ 044100^2 \\
(5.1209)
\end{array}$$

$0952039^2 + 438000^2 = 1\ 047961^2$	$0948016^2 + 456000^2 = 1\ 051984^2$
$1020\ 0952039^2 + 44238000^2 = 10201\ 047961^2$	$1020\ 0948016^2 + 46056000^2 = 10201\ 051984^2$
$10203020\ 0952039^2 + 4424238000^2 = 102030201\ 047961^2$	$10203020\ 0948016^2 + 4606056000^2 = 102030201\ 051984^2$
$102030403020\ 0952039^2 + 442424238000^2 = 1020304030201\ 047961^2$ (5.1218)	$102030403020\ 0948016^2 + 460606056000^2 = 1020304030201\ 051984^2$ (5.1227)
$0951600^2 + 440000^2 = 1\ 048400^2$	$0947559^2 + 458000^2 = 1\ 052441^2$
$1020\ 0951600^2 + 44440000^2 = 10201\ 048400^2$	$1020\ 0947559^2 + 46258000^2 = 10201\ 052441^2$
$10203020\ 0951600^2 + 4444440000^2 = 102030201\ 048400^2$	$10203020\ 0947559^2 + 4626258000^2 = 102030201\ 052441^2$
$102030403020\ 0951600^2 + 444444440000^2 = 1020304030201\ 048400^2$ (5.1219)	$102030403020\ 0947559^2 + 462626258000^2 = 1020304030201\ 052441^2$ (5.1228)
$0951159^2 + 442000^2 = 1\ 048841^2$	$0947100^2 + 460000^2 = 1\ 052900^2$
$1020\ 0951159^2 + 44642000^2 = 10201\ 048841^2$	$1020\ 0947100^2 + 46460000^2 = 10201\ 052900^2$
$10203020\ 0951159^2 + 4464642000^2 = 102030201\ 048841^2$	$10203020\ 0947100^2 + 4646460000^2 = 102030201\ 052900^2$
$102030403020\ 0951159^2 + 446464642000^2 = 1020304030201\ 048841^2$ (5.1220)	$102030403020\ 0947100^2 + 464646460000^2 = 1020304030201\ 052900^2$ (5.1229)
$0950716^2 + 444000^2 = 1\ 049284^2$	$0946639^2 + 462000^2 = 1\ 053361^2$
$1020\ 0950716^2 + 44844000^2 = 10201\ 049284^2$	$1020\ 0946639^2 + 46662000^2 = 10201\ 053361^2$
$10203020\ 0950716^2 + 4484844000^2 = 102030201\ 049284^2$	$10203020\ 0946639^2 + 4666662000^2 = 102030201\ 053361^2$
$102030403020\ 0950716^2 + 448484844000^2 = 1020304030201\ 049284^2$ (5.1221)	$102030403020\ 0946639^2 + 466666662000^2 = 1020304030201\ 053361^2$ (5.1230)
$0950271^2 + 446000^2 = 1\ 049729^2$	$0946176^2 + 464000^2 = 1\ 053824^2$
$1020\ 0950271^2 + 45046000^2 = 10201\ 049729^2$	$1020\ 0946176^2 + 46864000^2 = 10201\ 053824^2$
$10203020\ 0950271^2 + 4505046000^2 = 102030201\ 049729^2$	$10203020\ 0946176^2 + 4686864000^2 = 102030201\ 053824^2$
$102030403020\ 0950271^2 + 450505046000^2 = 1020304030201\ 049729^2$ (5.1222)	$102030403020\ 0946176^2 + 468686864000^2 = 1020304030201\ 053824^2$ (5.1231)
$0949824^2 + 448000^2 = 1\ 050176^2$	$0945711^2 + 466000^2 = 1\ 054289^2$
$1020\ 0949824^2 + 45248000^2 = 10201\ 050176^2$	$1020\ 0945711^2 + 47066000^2 = 10201\ 054289^2$
$10203020\ 0949824^2 + 4525248000^2 = 102030201\ 050176^2$	$10203020\ 0945711^2 + 4707066000^2 = 102030201\ 054289^2$
$102030403020\ 0949824^2 + 452525248000^2 = 1020304030201\ 050176^2$ (5.1223)	$102030403020\ 0945711^2 + 470707066000^2 = 1020304030201\ 054289^2$ (5.1232)
$0949375^2 + 450000^2 = 1\ 050625^2$	$0945244^2 + 468000^2 = 1\ 054756^2$
$1020\ 0949375^2 + 45450000^2 = 10201\ 050625^2$	$1020\ 0945244^2 + 47268000^2 = 10201\ 054756^2$
$10203020\ 0949375^2 + 4545450000^2 = 102030201\ 050625^2$	$10203020\ 0945244^2 + 4727268000^2 = 102030201\ 054756^2$
$102030403020\ 0949375^2 + 454545450000^2 = 1020304030201\ 050625^2$ (5.1224)	$102030403020\ 0945244^2 + 472727268000^2 = 1020304030201\ 054756^2$ (5.1233)
$0948924^2 + 452000^2 = 1\ 051076^2$	$0944775^2 + 470000^2 = 1\ 055225^2$
$1020\ 0948924^2 + 45652000^2 = 10201\ 051076^2$	$1020\ 0944775^2 + 47470000^2 = 10201\ 055225^2$
$10203020\ 0948924^2 + 4565652000^2 = 102030201\ 051076^2$	$10203020\ 0944775^2 + 4747470000^2 = 102030201\ 055225^2$
$102030403020\ 0948924^2 + 456565652000^2 = 1020304030201\ 051076^2$ (5.1225)	$102030403020\ 0944775^2 + 474747470000^2 = 1020304030201\ 055225^2$ (5.1234)
$0948471^2 + 454000^2 = 1\ 051529^2$	
$1020\ 0948471^2 + 45854000^2 = 10201\ 051529^2$	
$10203020\ 0948471^2 + 4585854000^2 = 102030201\ 051529^2$	
$102030403020\ 0948471^2 + 458585854000^2 = 1020304030201\ 051529^2$ (5.1226)	

$$\begin{array}{l}
0935991^2 + 506000^2 = 1\ 064009^2 \\
1020\ 0935991^2 + 51106000^2 = 10201\ 064009^2 \\
10203020\ 0935991^2 + 5111106000^2 = 102030201\ 064009^2 \\
102030403020\ 0935991^2 + 511111106000^2 = 1020304030201\ 064009^2 \\
(5.1252) \\
0935484^2 + 508000^2 = 1\ 064516^2 \\
1020\ 0935484^2 + 51308000^2 = 10201\ 064516^2 \\
10203020\ 0935484^2 + 5131308000^2 = 102030201\ 064516^2 \\
102030403020\ 0935484^2 + 513131308000^2 = 1020304030201\ 064516^2 \\
(5.1253) \\
0934975^2 + 510000^2 = 1\ 065025^2 \\
1020\ 0934975^2 + 51510000^2 = 10201\ 065025^2 \\
10203020\ 0934975^2 + 5151510000^2 = 102030201\ 065025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0934975^2 + 515151510000^2 = 1020304030201\ 065025^2 \\
(5.1254) \\
0934464^2 + 512000^2 = 1\ 065536^2 \\
1020\ 0934464^2 + 51712000^2 = 10201\ 065536^2 \\
10203020\ 0934464^2 + 5171712000^2 = 102030201\ 065536^2 \\
102030403020\ 0934464^2 + 517171712000^2 = 1020304030201\ 065536^2 \\
(5.1255) \\
0933951^2 + 514000^2 = 1\ 066049^2 \\
1020\ 0933951^2 + 51914000^2 = 10201\ 066049^2 \\
10203020\ 0933951^2 + 5191914000^2 = 102030201\ 066049^2 \\
102030403020\ 0933951^2 + 519191914000^2 = 1020304030201\ 066049^2 \\
(5.1256) \\
0933436^2 + 516000^2 = 1\ 066564^2 \\
1020\ 0933436^2 + 52116000^2 = 10201\ 066564^2 \\
10203020\ 0933436^2 + 5212116000^2 = 102030201\ 066564^2 \\
102030403020\ 0933436^2 + 521212116000^2 = 1020304030201\ 066564^2 \\
(5.1257) \\
0932919^2 + 518000^2 = 1\ 067081^2 \\
1020\ 0932919^2 + 52318000^2 = 10201\ 067081^2 \\
10203020\ 0932919^2 + 5232318000^2 = 102030201\ 067081^2 \\
102030403020\ 0932919^2 + 523232318000^2 = 1020304030201\ 067081^2 \\
(5.1258) \\
0932400^2 + 520000^2 = 1\ 067600^2 \\
1020\ 0932400^2 + 52520000^2 = 10201\ 067600^2 \\
10203020\ 0932400^2 + 5252520000^2 = 102030201\ 067600^2 \\
102030403020\ 0932400^2 + 525252520000^2 = 1020304030201\ 067600^2 \\
(5.1259) \\
0931879^2 + 522000^2 = 1\ 068121^2 \\
1020\ 0931879^2 + 52722000^2 = 10201\ 068121^2 \\
10203020\ 0931879^2 + 5272722000^2 = 102030201\ 068121^2 \\
102030403020\ 0931879^2 + 527272722000^2 = 1020304030201\ 068121^2 \\
(5.1260) \\
0931356^2 + 524000^2 = 1\ 068644^2 \\
1020\ 0931356^2 + 52924000^2 = 10201\ 068644^2 \\
10203020\ 0931356^2 + 5292924000^2 = 102030201\ 068644^2 \\
102030403020\ 0931356^2 + 529292924000^2 = 1020304030201\ 068644^2 \\
(5.1261) \\
0930831^2 + 526000^2 = 1\ 069169^2 \\
1020\ 0930831^2 + 53126000^2 = 10201\ 069169^2 \\
10203020\ 0930831^2 + 5313126000^2 = 102030201\ 069169^2 \\
102030403020\ 0930831^2 + 531313126000^2 = 1020304030201\ 069169^2 \\
(5.1262) \\
0930304^2 + 528000^2 = 1\ 069696^2 \\
1020\ 0930304^2 + 53328000^2 = 10201\ 069696^2 \\
10203020\ 0930304^2 + 5333328000^2 = 102030201\ 069696^2 \\
102030403020\ 0930304^2 + 533333328000^2 = 1020304030201\ 069696^2 \\
(5.1263) \\
0929775^2 + 530000^2 = 1\ 070225^2 \\
1020\ 0929775^2 + 53530000^2 = 10201\ 070225^2 \\
10203020\ 0929775^2 + 5353530000^2 = 102030201\ 070225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0929775^2 + 535353530000^2 = 1020304030201\ 070225^2 \\
(5.1264) \\
0929244^2 + 532000^2 = 1\ 070756^2 \\
1020\ 0929244^2 + 53732000^2 = 10201\ 070756^2 \\
10203020\ 0929244^2 + 5373732000^2 = 102030201\ 070756^2 \\
102030403020\ 0929244^2 + 537373732000^2 = 1020304030201\ 070756^2 \\
(5.1265) \\
0928711^2 + 534000^2 = 1\ 071289^2 \\
1020\ 0928711^2 + 53934000^2 = 10201\ 071289^2 \\
10203020\ 0928711^2 + 5393934000^2 = 102030201\ 071289^2 \\
102030403020\ 0928711^2 + 539393934000^2 = 1020304030201\ 071289^2 \\
(5.1266) \\
0928176^2 + 536000^2 = 1\ 071824^2 \\
1020\ 0928176^2 + 54136000^2 = 10201\ 071824^2 \\
10203020\ 0928176^2 + 5414136000^2 = 102030201\ 071824^2 \\
102030403020\ 0928176^2 + 541414136000^2 = 1020304030201\ 071824^2 \\
(5.1267) \\
0927639^2 + 538000^2 = 1\ 072361^2 \\
1020\ 0927639^2 + 54338000^2 = 10201\ 072361^2 \\
10203020\ 0927639^2 + 5434338000^2 = 102030201\ 072361^2 \\
102030403020\ 0927639^2 + 543434338000^2 = 1020304030201\ 072361^2 \\
(5.1268)
\end{array}$$

$0917631^2 + 574000^2 = 1\ 082369^2$	$0913564^2 + 588000^2 = 1\ 086436^2$
$1020\ 0917631^2 + 57974000^2 = 10201\ 082369^2$	$1020\ 0913564^2 + 59388000^2 = 10201\ 086436^2$
$10203020\ 0917631^2 + 5797974000^2 = 102030201\ 082369^2$	$10203020\ 0913564^2 + 5939388000^2 = 102030201\ 086436^2$
$102030403020\ 0917631^2 + 579797974000^2 = 1020304030201\ 082369^2$ (5.1286)	$102030403020\ 0913564^2 + 593939388000^2 = 1020304030201\ 086436^2$ (5.1293)
$0917056^2 + 576000^2 = 1\ 082944^2$	$0912975^2 + 590000^2 = 1\ 087025^2$
$1020\ 0917056^2 + 58176000^2 = 10201\ 082944^2$	$1020\ 0912975^2 + 59590000^2 = 10201\ 087025^2$
$10203020\ 0917056^2 + 5818176000^2 = 102030201\ 082944^2$	$10203020\ 0912975^2 + 5959590000^2 = 102030201\ 087025^2$
$102030403020\ 0917056^2 + 581818176000^2 = 1020304030201\ 082944^2$ (5.1287)	$102030403020\ 0912975^2 + 595959590000^2 = 1020304030201\ 087025^2$ (5.1294)
$0916479^2 + 578000^2 = 1\ 083521^2$	$0912384^2 + 592000^2 = 1\ 087616^2$
$1020\ 0916479^2 + 58378000^2 = 10201\ 083521^2$	$1020\ 0912384^2 + 59792000^2 = 10201\ 087616^2$
$10203020\ 0916479^2 + 5838378000^2 = 102030201\ 083521^2$	$10203020\ 0912384^2 + 5979792000^2 = 102030201\ 087616^2$
$102030403020\ 0916479^2 + 583838378000^2 = 1020304030201\ 083521^2$ (5.1288)	$102030403020\ 0912384^2 + 597979792000^2 = 1020304030201\ 087616^2$ (5.1295)
$0915900^2 + 580000^2 = 1\ 084100^2$	$0911791^2 + 594000^2 = 1\ 088209^2$
$1020\ 0915900^2 + 58580000^2 = 10201\ 084100^2$	$1020\ 0911791^2 + 59994000^2 = 10201\ 088209^2$
$10203020\ 0915900^2 + 5858580000^2 = 102030201\ 084100^2$	$10203020\ 0911791^2 + 5999994000^2 = 102030201\ 088209^2$
$102030403020\ 0915900^2 + 585858580000^2 = 1020304030201\ 084100^2$ (5.1289)	$102030403020\ 0911791^2 + 599999994000^2 = 1020304030201\ 088209^2$ (5.1296)
$0915319^2 + 582000^2 = 1\ 084681^2$	$0911196^2 + 596000^2 = 1\ 088804^2$
$1020\ 0915319^2 + 58782000^2 = 10201\ 084681^2$	$1020\ 0911196^2 + 60196000^2 = 10201\ 088804^2$
$10203020\ 0915319^2 + 5878782000^2 = 102030201\ 084681^2$	$10203020\ 0911196^2 + 6020196000^2 = 102030201\ 088804^2$
$102030403020\ 0915319^2 + 587878782000^2 = 1020304030201\ 084681^2$ (5.1290)	$102030403020\ 0911196^2 + 602020196000^2 = 1020304030201\ 088804^2$ (5.1297)
$0914736^2 + 584000^2 = 1\ 085264^2$	$0910599^2 + 598000^2 = 1\ 089401^2$
$1020\ 0914736^2 + 58984000^2 = 10201\ 085264^2$	$1020\ 0910599^2 + 60398000^2 = 10201\ 089401^2$
$10203020\ 0914736^2 + 5898984000^2 = 102030201\ 085264^2$	$10203020\ 0910599^2 + 6040398000^2 = 102030201\ 089401^2$
$102030403020\ 0914736^2 + 589898984000^2 = 1020304030201\ 085264^2$ (5.1291)	$102030403020\ 0910599^2 + 604040398000^2 = 1020304030201\ 089401^2$ (5.1298)
$0914151^2 + 586000^2 = 1\ 085849^2$	$0909399^2 + 602000^2 = 1\ 090601^2$
$1020\ 0914151^2 + 59186000^2 = 10201\ 085849^2$	$1020\ 0909399^2 + 60802000^2 = 10201\ 090601^2$
$10203020\ 0914151^2 + 5919186000^2 = 102030201\ 085849^2$	$10203020\ 0909399^2 + 6080802000^2 = 102030201\ 090601^2$
$102030403020\ 0914151^2 + 591919186000^2 = 1020304030201\ 085849^2$ (5.1292)	$102030403020\ 0909399^2 + 608080802000^2 = 1020304030201\ 090601^2$ (5.1300)
$0910000^2 + 600000^2 = 1\ 090000^2$	
$1020\ 0910000^2 + 60600000^2 = 10201\ 090000^2$	
$10203020\ 0910000^2 + 6060600000^2 = 102030201\ 090000^2$	
$102030403020\ 0910000^2 + 606060600000^2 = 1020304030201\ 090000^2$ (5.1299)	

$$\begin{array}{l}
0908796^2 + 604000^2 = 1\ 091204^2 \\
1020\ 0908796^2 + 61004000^2 = 10201\ 091204^2 \\
10203020\ 0908796^2 + 6101004000^2 = 102030201\ 091204^2 \\
102030403020\ 0908796^2 + 610101004000^2 = 1020304030201\ 091204^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1301) \\
0908191^2 + 606000^2 = 1\ 091809^2 \\
1020\ 0908191^2 + 61206000^2 = 10201\ 091809^2 \\
10203020\ 0908191^2 + 6121206000^2 = 102030201\ 091809^2 \\
102030403020\ 0908191^2 + 612121206000^2 = 1020304030201\ 091809^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1302) \\
0907584^2 + 608000^2 = 1\ 092416^2 \\
1020\ 0907584^2 + 61408000^2 = 10201\ 092416^2 \\
10203020\ 0907584^2 + 6141408000^2 = 102030201\ 092416^2 \\
102030403020\ 0907584^2 + 614141408000^2 = 1020304030201\ 092416^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1303) \\
0906975^2 + 610000^2 = 1\ 093025^2 \\
1020\ 0906975^2 + 61610000^2 = 10201\ 093025^2 \\
10203020\ 0906975^2 + 6161610000^2 = 102030201\ 093025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0906975^2 + 616161610000^2 = 1020304030201\ 093025^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1304) \\
0906364^2 + 612000^2 = 1\ 093636^2 \\
1020\ 0906364^2 + 61812000^2 = 10201\ 093636^2 \\
10203020\ 0906364^2 + 6181812000^2 = 102030201\ 093636^2 \\
102030403020\ 0906364^2 + 618181812000^2 = 1020304030201\ 093636^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1305) \\
0905751^2 + 614000^2 = 1\ 094249^2 \\
1020\ 0905751^2 + 62014000^2 = 10201\ 094249^2 \\
10203020\ 0905751^2 + 6202014000^2 = 102030201\ 094249^2 \\
102030403020\ 0905751^2 + 620202014000^2 = 1020304030201\ 094249^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1306) \\
0905136^2 + 616000^2 = 1\ 094864^2 \\
1020\ 0905136^2 + 62216000^2 = 10201\ 094864^2 \\
10203020\ 0905136^2 + 6222216000^2 = 102030201\ 094864^2 \\
102030403020\ 0905136^2 + 622222216000^2 = 1020304030201\ 094864^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1307) \\
0904519^2 + 618000^2 = 1\ 095481^2 \\
1020\ 0904519^2 + 62418000^2 = 10201\ 095481^2 \\
10203020\ 0904519^2 + 6242418000^2 = 102030201\ 095481^2 \\
102030403020\ 0904519^2 + 624242418000^2 = 1020304030201\ 095481^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1308) \\
0903900^2 + 620000^2 = 1\ 096100^2 \\
1020\ 0903900^2 + 62620000^2 = 10201\ 096100^2 \\
10203020\ 0903900^2 + 6262620000^2 = 102030201\ 096100^2 \\
102030403020\ 0903900^2 + 626262620000^2 = 1020304030201\ 096100^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1309) \\
0903279^2 + 622000^2 = 1\ 096721^2 \\
1020\ 0903279^2 + 62822000^2 = 10201\ 096721^2 \\
10203020\ 0903279^2 + 6282822000^2 = 102030201\ 096721^2 \\
102030403020\ 0903279^2 + 628282822000^2 = 1020304030201\ 096721^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1310) \\
0902656^2 + 624000^2 = 1\ 097344^2 \\
1020\ 0902656^2 + 63024000^2 = 10201\ 097344^2 \\
10203020\ 0902656^2 + 6303024000^2 = 102030201\ 097344^2 \\
102030403020\ 0902656^2 + 630303024000^2 = 1020304030201\ 097344^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1311) \\
0902031^2 + 626000^2 = 1\ 097969^2 \\
1020\ 0902031^2 + 63226000^2 = 10201\ 097969^2 \\
10203020\ 0902031^2 + 6323226000^2 = 102030201\ 097969^2 \\
102030403020\ 0902031^2 + 632323226000^2 = 1020304030201\ 097969^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1312) \\
0901404^2 + 628000^2 = 1\ 098596^2 \\
1020\ 0901404^2 + 63428000^2 = 10201\ 098596^2 \\
10203020\ 0901404^2 + 6343428000^2 = 102030201\ 098596^2 \\
102030403020\ 0901404^2 + 634343428000^2 = 1020304030201\ 098596^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1313) \\
0900775^2 + 630000^2 = 1\ 099225^2 \\
1020\ 0900775^2 + 63630000^2 = 10201\ 099225^2 \\
10203020\ 0900775^2 + 6363630000^2 = 102030201\ 099225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0900775^2 + 636363630000^2 = 1020304030201\ 099225^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1314) \\
0900144^2 + 632000^2 = 1\ 099856^2 \\
1020\ 0900144^2 + 63832000^2 = 10201\ 099856^2 \\
10203020\ 0900144^2 + 6383832000^2 = 102030201\ 099856^2 \\
102030403020\ 0900144^2 + 638383832000^2 = 1020304030201\ 099856^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1315) \\
0899511^2 + 634000^2 = 1\ 100489^2 \\
1020\ 0899511^2 + 64034000^2 = 10201\ 100489^2 \\
10203020\ 0899511^2 + 6404034000^2 = 102030201\ 100489^2 \\
102030403020\ 0899511^2 + 640404034000^2 = 1020304030201\ 100489^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1316) \\
0898876^2 + 636000^2 = 1\ 101124^2 \\
1020\ 0898876^2 + 64236000^2 = 10201\ 101124^2 \\
10203020\ 0898876^2 + 6424236000^2 = 102030201\ 101124^2 \\
102030403020\ 0898876^2 + 642424236000^2 = 1020304030201\ 101124^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1317)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0898239^2 + 638000^2 = 1\ 101761^2 \\
1020\ 0898239^2 + 64438000^2 = 10201\ 101761^2 \\
10203020\ 0898239^2 + 6444438000^2 = 102030201\ 101761^2 \\
102030403020\ 0898239^2 + 644444438000^2 = 1020304030201\ 101761^2 \\
(5.1318) \\
0897600^2 + 640000^2 = 1\ 102400^2 \\
1020\ 0897600^2 + 64640000^2 = 10201\ 102400^2 \\
10203020\ 0897600^2 + 6464640000^2 = 102030201\ 102400^2 \\
102030403020\ 0897600^2 + 646464640000^2 = 1020304030201\ 102400^2 \\
(5.1319) \\
0896959^2 + 642000^2 = 1\ 103041^2 \\
1020\ 0896959^2 + 64842000^2 = 10201\ 103041^2 \\
10203020\ 0896959^2 + 6484842000^2 = 102030201\ 103041^2 \\
102030403020\ 0896959^2 + 648484842000^2 = 1020304030201\ 103041^2 \\
(5.1320) \\
0896316^2 + 644000^2 = 1\ 103684^2 \\
1020\ 0896316^2 + 65044000^2 = 10201\ 103684^2 \\
10203020\ 0896316^2 + 6505044000^2 = 102030201\ 103684^2 \\
102030403020\ 0896316^2 + 650505044000^2 = 1020304030201\ 103684^2 \\
(5.1321) \\
0895671^2 + 646000^2 = 1\ 104329^2 \\
1020\ 0895671^2 + 65246000^2 = 10201\ 104329^2 \\
10203020\ 0895671^2 + 6525246000^2 = 102030201\ 104329^2 \\
102030403020\ 0895671^2 + 652525246000^2 = 1020304030201\ 104329^2 \\
(5.1322) \\
0895024^2 + 648000^2 = 1\ 104976^2 \\
1020\ 0895024^2 + 65448000^2 = 10201\ 104976^2 \\
10203020\ 0895024^2 + 6545448000^2 = 102030201\ 104976^2 \\
102030403020\ 0895024^2 + 654545448000^2 = 1020304030201\ 104976^2 \\
(5.1323) \\
0894375^2 + 650000^2 = 1\ 105625^2 \\
1020\ 0894375^2 + 65650000^2 = 10201\ 105625^2 \\
10203020\ 0894375^2 + 6565650000^2 = 102030201\ 105625^2 \\
102030403020\ 0894375^2 + 656565650000^2 = 1020304030201\ 105625^2 \\
(5.1324) \\
0893724^2 + 652000^2 = 1\ 106276^2 \\
1020\ 0893724^2 + 65852000^2 = 10201\ 106276^2 \\
10203020\ 0893724^2 + 6585852000^2 = 102030201\ 106276^2 \\
102030403020\ 0893724^2 + 658585852000^2 = 1020304030201\ 106276^2 \\
(5.1325) \\
0893071^2 + 654000^2 = 1\ 106929^2 \\
1020\ 0893071^2 + 66054000^2 = 10201\ 106929^2 \\
10203020\ 0893071^2 + 6606054000^2 = 102030201\ 106929^2 \\
102030403020\ 0893071^2 + 660606054000^2 = 1020304030201\ 106929^2 \\
(5.1326) \\
0892416^2 + 656000^2 = 1\ 107584^2 \\
1020\ 0892416^2 + 66256000^2 = 10201\ 107584^2 \\
10203020\ 0892416^2 + 6626256000^2 = 102030201\ 107584^2 \\
102030403020\ 0892416^2 + 662626256000^2 = 1020304030201\ 107584^2 \\
(5.1327) \\
0891759^2 + 658000^2 = 1\ 108241^2 \\
1020\ 0891759^2 + 66458000^2 = 10201\ 108241^2 \\
10203020\ 0891759^2 + 6646458000^2 = 102030201\ 108241^2 \\
102030403020\ 0891759^2 + 664646458000^2 = 1020304030201\ 108241^2 \\
(5.1328) \\
0891100^2 + 660000^2 = 1\ 108900^2 \\
1020\ 0891100^2 + 66660000^2 = 10201\ 108900^2 \\
10203020\ 0891100^2 + 6666660000^2 = 102030201\ 108900^2 \\
102030403020\ 0891100^2 + 666666660000^2 = 1020304030201\ 108900^2 \\
(5.1329) \\
0890439^2 + 662000^2 = 1\ 109561^2 \\
1020\ 0890439^2 + 66862000^2 = 10201\ 109561^2 \\
10203020\ 0890439^2 + 6686862000^2 = 102030201\ 109561^2 \\
102030403020\ 0890439^2 + 668686862000^2 = 1020304030201\ 109561^2 \\
(5.1330) \\
0889776^2 + 664000^2 = 1\ 110224^2 \\
1020\ 0889776^2 + 67064000^2 = 10201\ 110224^2 \\
10203020\ 0889776^2 + 6707064000^2 = 102030201\ 110224^2 \\
102030403020\ 0889776^2 + 670707064000^2 = 1020304030201\ 110224^2 \\
(5.1331) \\
0889111^2 + 666000^2 = 1\ 110889^2 \\
1020\ 0889111^2 + 67266000^2 = 10201\ 110889^2 \\
10203020\ 0889111^2 + 6727266000^2 = 102030201\ 110889^2 \\
102030403020\ 0889111^2 + 672727266000^2 = 1020304030201\ 110889^2 \\
(5.1332) \\
0888444^2 + 668000^2 = 1\ 111556^2 \\
1020\ 0888444^2 + 67468000^2 = 10201\ 111556^2 \\
10203020\ 0888444^2 + 6747468000^2 = 102030201\ 111556^2 \\
102030403020\ 0888444^2 + 674747468000^2 = 1020304030201\ 111556^2 \\
(5.1333) \\
0887775^2 + 670000^2 = 1\ 112225^2 \\
1020\ 0887775^2 + 67670000^2 = 10201\ 112225^2 \\
10203020\ 0887775^2 + 6767670000^2 = 102030201\ 112225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0887775^2 + 676767670000^2 = 1020304030201\ 112225^2 \\
(5.1334)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0887104^2 + 672000^2 = 1112896^2 \\
10200887104^2 + 67872000^2 = 10201112896^2 \\
102030200887104^2 + 6787872000^2 = 102030201112896^2 \\
1020304030200887104^2 + 678787872000^2 = 1020304030201112896^2 \quad (5.1335) \\
0886431^2 + 674000^2 = 1113569^2 \\
10200886431^2 + 68074000^2 = 10201113569^2 \\
102030200886431^2 + 6808074000^2 = 102030201113569^2 \\
1020304030200886431^2 + 680808074000^2 = 1020304030201113569^2 \quad (5.1336) \\
0885756^2 + 676000^2 = 1114244^2 \\
10200885756^2 + 68276000^2 = 10201114244^2 \\
102030200885756^2 + 6828276000^2 = 102030201114244^2 \\
1020304030200885756^2 + 682828276000^2 = 1020304030201114244^2 \quad (5.1337) \\
0885079^2 + 678000^2 = 1114921^2 \\
10200885079^2 + 68478000^2 = 10201114921^2 \\
102030200885079^2 + 6848478000^2 = 102030201114921^2 \\
1020304030200885079^2 + 684848478000^2 = 1020304030201114921^2 \quad (5.1338) \\
0884400^2 + 680000^2 = 1115600^2 \\
10200884400^2 + 68680000^2 = 10201115600^2 \\
102030200884400^2 + 6868680000^2 = 102030201115600^2 \\
1020304030200884400^2 + 686868680000^2 = 1020304030201115600^2 \quad (5.1339) \\
0883719^2 + 682000^2 = 1116281^2 \\
10200883719^2 + 68882000^2 = 10201116281^2 \\
102030200883719^2 + 6888882000^2 = 102030201116281^2 \\
1020304030200883719^2 + 68888882000^2 = 1020304030201116281^2 \quad (5.1340) \\
0883036^2 + 684000^2 = 1116964^2 \\
10200883036^2 + 69084000^2 = 10201116964^2 \\
102030200883036^2 + 6909084000^2 = 102030201116964^2 \\
1020304030200883036^2 + 690909084000^2 = 1020304030201116964^2 \quad (5.1341) \\
0882351^2 + 686000^2 = 1117649^2 \\
10200882351^2 + 69286000^2 = 10201117649^2 \\
102030200882351^2 + 6929286000^2 = 102030201117649^2 \\
1020304030200882351^2 + 692929286000^2 = 1020304030201117649^2 \quad (5.1342) \\
0881664^2 + 688000^2 = 1118336^2 \\
10200881664^2 + 69488000^2 = 10201118336^2 \\
102030200881664^2 + 6949488000^2 = 102030201118336^2 \\
1020304030200881664^2 + 694949488000^2 = 1020304030201118336^2 \quad (5.1343) \\
0880975^2 + 690000^2 = 1119025^2 \\
10200880975^2 + 69690000^2 = 10201119025^2 \\
102030200880975^2 + 6969690000^2 = 102030201119025^2 \\
1020304030200880975^2 + 696969690000^2 = 1020304030201119025^2 \quad (5.1344) \\
0880284^2 + 692000^2 = 1119716^2 \\
10200880284^2 + 69892000^2 = 10201119716^2 \\
102030200880284^2 + 6989892000^2 = 102030201119716^2 \\
1020304030200880284^2 + 698989892000^2 = 1020304030201119716^2 \quad (5.1345) \\
0879591^2 + 694000^2 = 1120409^2 \\
10200879591^2 + 70094000^2 = 10201120409^2 \\
102030200879591^2 + 7010094000^2 = 102030201120409^2 \\
1020304030200879591^2 + 701010094000^2 = 1020304030201120409^2 \quad (5.1346) \\
0878896^2 + 696000^2 = 1121104^2 \\
10200878896^2 + 70296000^2 = 10201121104^2 \\
102030200878896^2 + 7030296000^2 = 102030201121104^2 \\
1020304030200878896^2 + 703030296000^2 = 1020304030201121104^2 \quad (5.1347) \\
0878199^2 + 698000^2 = 1121801^2 \\
10200878199^2 + 70498000^2 = 10201121801^2 \\
102030200878199^2 + 7050498000^2 = 102030201121801^2 \\
1020304030200878199^2 + 705050498000^2 = 1020304030201121801^2 \quad (5.1348) \\
0877500^2 + 700000^2 = 1122500^2 \\
10200877500^2 + 70700000^2 = 10201122500^2 \\
102030200877500^2 + 7070700000^2 = 102030201122500^2 \\
1020304030200877500^2 + 707070700000^2 = 1020304030201122500^2 \quad (5.1349) \\
0876799^2 + 702000^2 = 1123201^2 \\
10200876799^2 + 70902000^2 = 10201123201^2 \\
102030200876799^2 + 7090902000^2 = 102030201123201^2 \\
1020304030200876799^2 + 709090902000^2 = 1020304030201123201^2 \quad (5.1350) \\
0876096^2 + 704000^2 = 1123904^2 \\
10200876096^2 + 71104000^2 = 10201123904^2 \\
102030200876096^2 + 7111104000^2 = 102030201123904^2 \\
1020304030200876096^2 + 711111104000^2 = 1020304030201123904^2 \quad (5.1351)
\end{array}$$

$0875391^2 + 706000^2 = 1\ 124609^2$	$0868956^2 + 724000^2 = 1\ 131044^2$
$1020\ 0875391^2 + 71306000^2 = 10201\ 124609^2$	$1020\ 0868956^2 + 73124000^2 = 10201\ 131044^2$
$10203020\ 0875391^2 + 7131306000^2 = 102030201\ 124609^2$	$10203020\ 0868956^2 + 7313124000^2 = 102030201\ 131044^2$
$102030403020\ 0875391^2 + 713131306000^2 = 1020304030201\ 124609^2$ (5.1352)	$102030403020\ 0868956^2 + 731313124000^2 = 1020304030201\ 131044^2$ (5.1361)
$0874684^2 + 708000^2 = 1\ 125316^2$	$0868231^2 + 726000^2 = 1\ 131769^2$
$1020\ 0874684^2 + 71508000^2 = 10201\ 125316^2$	$1020\ 0868231^2 + 73326000^2 = 10201\ 131769^2$
$10203020\ 0874684^2 + 7151508000^2 = 102030201\ 125316^2$	$10203020\ 0868231^2 + 7333326000^2 = 102030201\ 131769^2$
$102030403020\ 0874684^2 + 715151508000^2 = 1020304030201\ 125316^2$ (5.1353)	$102030403020\ 0868231^2 + 733333326000^2 = 1020304030201\ 131769^2$ (5.1362)
$0873975^2 + 710000^2 = 1\ 126025^2$	$0867504^2 + 728000^2 = 1\ 132496^2$
$1020\ 0873975^2 + 71710000^2 = 10201\ 126025^2$	$1020\ 0867504^2 + 73528000^2 = 10201\ 132496^2$
$10203020\ 0873975^2 + 7171710000^2 = 102030201\ 126025^2$	$10203020\ 0867504^2 + 7353528000^2 = 102030201\ 132496^2$
$102030403020\ 0873975^2 + 717171710000^2 = 1020304030201\ 126025^2$ (5.1354)	$102030403020\ 0867504^2 + 735353528000^2 = 1020304030201\ 132496^2$ (5.1363)
$0873264^2 + 712000^2 = 1\ 126736^2$	$0866775^2 + 730000^2 = 1\ 133225^2$
$1020\ 0873264^2 + 71912000^2 = 10201\ 126736^2$	$1020\ 0866775^2 + 73730000^2 = 10201\ 133225^2$
$10203020\ 0873264^2 + 7191912000^2 = 102030201\ 126736^2$	$10203020\ 0866775^2 + 7373730000^2 = 102030201\ 133225^2$
$102030403020\ 0873264^2 + 719191912000^2 = 1020304030201\ 126736^2$ (5.1355)	$102030403020\ 0866775^2 + 737373730000^2 = 1020304030201\ 133225^2$ (5.1364)
$0872551^2 + 714000^2 = 1\ 127449^2$	$0866044^2 + 732000^2 = 1\ 133956^2$
$1020\ 0872551^2 + 72114000^2 = 10201\ 127449^2$	$1020\ 0866044^2 + 73932000^2 = 10201\ 133956^2$
$10203020\ 0872551^2 + 7212114000^2 = 102030201\ 127449^2$	$10203020\ 0866044^2 + 7393932000^2 = 102030201\ 133956^2$
$102030403020\ 0872551^2 + 721212114000^2 = 1020304030201\ 127449^2$ (5.1356)	$102030403020\ 0866044^2 + 739393932000^2 = 1020304030201\ 133956^2$ (5.1365)
$0871836^2 + 716000^2 = 1\ 128164^2$	$0865311^2 + 734000^2 = 1\ 134689^2$
$1020\ 0871836^2 + 72316000^2 = 10201\ 128164^2$	$1020\ 0865311^2 + 74134000^2 = 10201\ 134689^2$
$10203020\ 0871836^2 + 7232316000^2 = 102030201\ 128164^2$	$10203020\ 0865311^2 + 7414134000^2 = 102030201\ 134689^2$
$102030403020\ 0871836^2 + 723232316000^2 = 1020304030201\ 128164^2$ (5.1357)	$102030403020\ 0865311^2 + 741414134000^2 = 1020304030201\ 134689^2$ (5.1366)
$0871119^2 + 718000^2 = 1\ 128881^2$	$0864576^2 + 736000^2 = 1\ 135424^2$
$1020\ 0871119^2 + 72518000^2 = 10201\ 128881^2$	$1020\ 0864576^2 + 74336000^2 = 10201\ 135424^2$
$10203020\ 0871119^2 + 7252518000^2 = 102030201\ 128881^2$	$10203020\ 0864576^2 + 7434336000^2 = 102030201\ 135424^2$
$102030403020\ 0871119^2 + 725252518000^2 = 1020304030201\ 128881^2$ (5.1358)	$102030403020\ 0864576^2 + 743434336000^2 = 1020304030201\ 135424^2$ (5.1367)
$0870400^2 + 720000^2 = 1\ 129600^2$	$0863839^2 + 738000^2 = 1\ 136161^2$
$1020\ 0870400^2 + 72720000^2 = 10201\ 129600^2$	$1020\ 0863839^2 + 74538000^2 = 10201\ 136161^2$
$10203020\ 0870400^2 + 7272720000^2 = 102030201\ 129600^2$	$10203020\ 0863839^2 + 7454538000^2 = 102030201\ 136161^2$
$102030403020\ 0870400^2 + 727272720000^2 = 1020304030201\ 129600^2$ (5.1359)	$102030403020\ 0863839^2 + 745454538000^2 = 1020304030201\ 136161^2$ (5.1368)
$0869679^2 + 722000^2 = 1\ 130321^2$	
$1020\ 0869679^2 + 72922000^2 = 10201\ 130321^2$	
$10203020\ 0869679^2 + 7292922000^2 = 102030201\ 130321^2$	
$102030403020\ 0869679^2 + 729292922000^2 = 1020304030201\ 130321^2$ (5.1360)	

$$\begin{array}{l}
0863100^2 + 740000^2 = 1\ 136900^2 \\
1020\ 0863100^2 + 74740000^2 = 10201\ 136900^2 \\
10203020\ 0863100^2 + 7474740000^2 = 102030201\ 136900^2 \\
102030403020\ 0863100^2 + 747474740000^2 = 1020304030201\ 136900^2 \\
(5.1369)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0856359^2 + 758000^2 = 1\ 143641^2 \\
1020\ 0856359^2 + 76558000^2 = 10201\ 143641^2 \\
10203020\ 0856359^2 + 7656558000^2 = 102030201\ 143641^2 \\
102030403020\ 0856359^2 + 765656558000^2 = 1020304030201\ 143641^2 \\
(5.1378)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0862359^2 + 742000^2 = 1\ 137641^2 \\
1020\ 0862359^2 + 74942000^2 = 10201\ 137641^2 \\
10203020\ 0862359^2 + 7494942000^2 = 102030201\ 137641^2 \\
102030403020\ 0862359^2 + 749494942000^2 = 1020304030201\ 137641^2 \\
(5.1370)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0855600^2 + 760000^2 = 1\ 144400^2 \\
1020\ 0855600^2 + 76760000^2 = 10201\ 144400^2 \\
10203020\ 0855600^2 + 7676760000^2 = 102030201\ 144400^2 \\
102030403020\ 0855600^2 + 767676760000^2 = 1020304030201\ 144400^2 \\
(5.1379)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0861616^2 + 744000^2 = 1\ 138384^2 \\
1020\ 0861616^2 + 75144000^2 = 10201\ 138384^2 \\
10203020\ 0861616^2 + 7515144000^2 = 102030201\ 138384^2 \\
102030403020\ 0861616^2 + 751515144000^2 = 1020304030201\ 138384^2 \\
(5.1371)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0854839^2 + 762000^2 = 1\ 145161^2 \\
1020\ 0854839^2 + 76962000^2 = 10201\ 145161^2 \\
10203020\ 0854839^2 + 7696962000^2 = 102030201\ 145161^2 \\
102030403020\ 0854839^2 + 769696962000^2 = 1020304030201\ 145161^2 \\
(5.1380)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0860871^2 + 746000^2 = 1\ 139129^2 \\
1020\ 0860871^2 + 75346000^2 = 10201\ 139129^2 \\
10203020\ 0860871^2 + 7535346000^2 = 102030201\ 139129^2 \\
102030403020\ 0860871^2 + 753535346000^2 = 1020304030201\ 139129^2 \\
(5.1372)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0854076^2 + 764000^2 = 1\ 145924^2 \\
1020\ 0854076^2 + 77164000^2 = 10201\ 145924^2 \\
10203020\ 0854076^2 + 7717164000^2 = 102030201\ 145924^2 \\
102030403020\ 0854076^2 + 771717164000^2 = 1020304030201\ 145924^2 \\
(5.1381)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0860124^2 + 748000^2 = 1\ 139876^2 \\
1020\ 0860124^2 + 75548000^2 = 10201\ 139876^2 \\
10203020\ 0860124^2 + 7555548000^2 = 102030201\ 139876^2 \\
102030403020\ 0860124^2 + 755555548000^2 = 1020304030201\ 139876^2 \\
(5.1373)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0853311^2 + 766000^2 = 1\ 146689^2 \\
1020\ 0853311^2 + 77366000^2 = 10201\ 146689^2 \\
10203020\ 0853311^2 + 7737366000^2 = 102030201\ 146689^2 \\
102030403020\ 0853311^2 + 773737366000^2 = 1020304030201\ 146689^2 \\
(5.1382)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0859375^2 + 750000^2 = 1\ 140625^2 \\
1020\ 0859375^2 + 75750000^2 = 10201\ 140625^2 \\
10203020\ 0859375^2 + 7575750000^2 = 102030201\ 140625^2 \\
102030403020\ 0859375^2 + 757575750000^2 = 1020304030201\ 140625^2 \\
(5.1374)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0852544^2 + 768000^2 = 1\ 147456^2 \\
1020\ 0852544^2 + 77568000^2 = 10201\ 147456^2 \\
10203020\ 0852544^2 + 7757568000^2 = 102030201\ 147456^2 \\
102030403020\ 0852544^2 + 775757568000^2 = 1020304030201\ 147456^2 \\
(5.1383)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0858624^2 + 752000^2 = 1\ 141376^2 \\
1020\ 0858624^2 + 75952000^2 = 10201\ 141376^2 \\
10203020\ 0858624^2 + 7595952000^2 = 102030201\ 141376^2 \\
102030403020\ 0858624^2 + 759595952000^2 = 1020304030201\ 141376^2 \\
(5.1375)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0851775^2 + 770000^2 = 1\ 148225^2 \\
1020\ 0851775^2 + 77770000^2 = 10201\ 148225^2 \\
10203020\ 0851775^2 + 7777770000^2 = 102030201\ 148225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0851775^2 + 777777770000^2 = 1020304030201\ 148225^2 \\
(5.1384)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0857871^2 + 754000^2 = 1\ 142129^2 \\
1020\ 0857871^2 + 76154000^2 = 10201\ 142129^2 \\
10203020\ 0857871^2 + 7616154000^2 = 102030201\ 142129^2 \\
102030403020\ 0857871^2 + 761616154000^2 = 1020304030201\ 142129^2 \\
(5.1376)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0851004^2 + 772000^2 = 1\ 148996^2 \\
1020\ 0851004^2 + 77972000^2 = 10201\ 148996^2 \\
10203020\ 0851004^2 + 7797972000^2 = 102030201\ 148996^2 \\
102030403020\ 0851004^2 + 779797972000^2 = 1020304030201\ 148996^2 \\
(5.1385)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0857116^2 + 756000^2 = 1\ 142884^2 \\
1020\ 0857116^2 + 76356000^2 = 10201\ 142884^2 \\
10203020\ 0857116^2 + 7636356000^2 = 102030201\ 142884^2 \\
102030403020\ 0857116^2 + 763636356000^2 = 1020304030201\ 142884^2 \\
(5.1377)
\end{array}$$

$0850231^2 + 774000^2 = 1\ 149769^2$	$0844764^2 + 788000^2 = 1\ 155236^2$
$1020\ 0850231^2 + 78174000^2 = 10201\ 149769^2$	$1020\ 0844764^2 + 79588000^2 = 10201\ 155236^2$
$10203020\ 0850231^2 + 7818174000^2 = 102030201\ 149769^2$	$10203020\ 0844764^2 + 7959588000^2 = 102030201\ 155236^2$
$102030403020\ 0850231^2 + 781818174000^2 = 1020304030201\ 149769^2$ (5.1386)	$102030403020\ 0844764^2 + 795959588000^2 = 1020304030201\ 155236^2$ (5.1393)
$0849456^2 + 776000^2 = 1\ 150544^2$	$0843975^2 + 790000^2 = 1\ 156025^2$
$1020\ 0849456^2 + 78376000^2 = 10201\ 150544^2$	$1020\ 0843975^2 + 79790000^2 = 10201\ 156025^2$
$10203020\ 0849456^2 + 7838376000^2 = 102030201\ 150544^2$	$10203020\ 0843975^2 + 7979790000^2 = 102030201\ 156025^2$
$102030403020\ 0849456^2 + 783838376000^2 = 1020304030201\ 150544^2$ (5.1387)	$102030403020\ 0843975^2 + 797979790000^2 = 1020304030201\ 156025^2$ (5.1394)
$0848679^2 + 778000^2 = 1\ 151321^2$	$0843184^2 + 792000^2 = 1\ 156816^2$
$1020\ 0848679^2 + 78578000^2 = 10201\ 151321^2$	$1020\ 0843184^2 + 79992000^2 = 10201\ 156816^2$
$10203020\ 0848679^2 + 7858578000^2 = 102030201\ 151321^2$	$10203020\ 0843184^2 + 7999992000^2 = 102030201\ 156816^2$
$102030403020\ 0848679^2 + 785858578000^2 = 1020304030201\ 151321^2$ (5.1388)	$102030403020\ 0843184^2 + 799999992000^2 = 1020304030201\ 156816^2$ (5.1395)
$0847900^2 + 780000^2 = 1\ 152100^2$	$0842391^2 + 794000^2 = 1\ 157609^2$
$1020\ 0847900^2 + 78780000^2 = 10201\ 152100^2$	$1020\ 0842391^2 + 80194000^2 = 10201\ 157609^2$
$10203020\ 0847900^2 + 7878780000^2 = 102030201\ 152100^2$	$10203020\ 0842391^2 + 8020194000^2 = 102030201\ 157609^2$
$102030403020\ 0847900^2 + 787878780000^2 = 1020304030201\ 152100^2$ (5.1389)	$102030403020\ 0842391^2 + 802020194000^2 = 1020304030201\ 157609^2$ (5.1396)
$0847119^2 + 782000^2 = 1\ 152881^2$	$0841596^2 + 796000^2 = 1\ 158404^2$
$1020\ 0847119^2 + 78982000^2 = 10201\ 152881^2$	$1020\ 0841596^2 + 80396000^2 = 10201\ 158404^2$
$10203020\ 0847119^2 + 7898982000^2 = 102030201\ 152881^2$	$10203020\ 0841596^2 + 8040396000^2 = 102030201\ 158404^2$
$102030403020\ 0847119^2 + 789898982000^2 = 1020304030201\ 152881^2$ (5.1390)	$102030403020\ 0841596^2 + 804040396000^2 = 1020304030201\ 158404^2$ (5.1397)
$0846336^2 + 784000^2 = 1\ 153664^2$	$0840799^2 + 798000^2 = 1\ 159201^2$
$1020\ 0846336^2 + 79184000^2 = 10201\ 153664^2$	$1020\ 0840799^2 + 80598000^2 = 10201\ 159201^2$
$10203020\ 0846336^2 + 7919184000^2 = 102030201\ 153664^2$	$10203020\ 0840799^2 + 8060598000^2 = 102030201\ 159201^2$
$102030403020\ 0846336^2 + 791919184000^2 = 1020304030201\ 153664^2$ (5.1391)	$102030403020\ 0840799^2 + 806060598000^2 = 1020304030201\ 159201^2$ (5.1398)
$0845551^2 + 786000^2 = 1\ 154449^2$	$0839199^2 + 802000^2 = 1\ 160801^2$
$1020\ 0845551^2 + 79386000^2 = 10201\ 154449^2$	$1020\ 0839199^2 + 81002000^2 = 10201\ 160801^2$
$10203020\ 0845551^2 + 7939386000^2 = 102030201\ 154449^2$	$10203020\ 0839199^2 + 8101002000^2 = 102030201\ 160801^2$
$102030403020\ 0845551^2 + 793939386000^2 = 1020304030201\ 154449^2$ (5.1392)	$102030403020\ 0839199^2 + 810101002000^2 = 1020304030201\ 160801^2$ (5.1400)
$0840000^2 + 800000^2 = 1\ 160000^2$	
$1020\ 0840000^2 + 80800000^2 = 10201\ 160000^2$	
$10203020\ 0840000^2 + 8080800000^2 = 102030201\ 160000^2$	
$102030403020\ 0840000^2 + 808080800000^2 = 1020304030201\ 160000^2$ (5.1399)	

$0838396^2 + 804000^2 = 1\ 161604^2$	$0831079^2 + 822000^2 = 1\ 168921^2$
$1020\ 0838396^2 + 81204000^2 = 10201\ 161604^2$	$1020\ 0831079^2 + 83022000^2 = 10201\ 168921^2$
$10203020\ 0838396^2 + 8121204000^2 = 102030201\ 161604^2$	$10203020\ 0831079^2 + 8303022000^2 = 102030201\ 168921^2$
$102030403020\ 0838396^2 + 812121204000^2 = 1020304030201\ 161604^2$ (5.1401)	$102030403020\ 0831079^2 + 830303022000^2 = 1020304030201\ 168921^2$ (5.1410)
$0837591^2 + 806000^2 = 1\ 162409^2$	$0830256^2 + 824000^2 = 1\ 169744^2$
$1020\ 0837591^2 + 81406000^2 = 10201\ 162409^2$	$1020\ 0830256^2 + 83224000^2 = 10201\ 169744^2$
$10203020\ 0837591^2 + 8141406000^2 = 102030201\ 162409^2$	$10203020\ 0830256^2 + 8323224000^2 = 102030201\ 169744^2$
$102030403020\ 0837591^2 + 814141406000^2 = 1020304030201\ 162409^2$ (5.1402)	$102030403020\ 0830256^2 + 832323224000^2 = 1020304030201\ 169744^2$ (5.1411)
$0836784^2 + 808000^2 = 1\ 163216^2$	$0829431^2 + 826000^2 = 1\ 170569^2$
$1020\ 0836784^2 + 81608000^2 = 10201\ 163216^2$	$1020\ 0829431^2 + 83426000^2 = 10201\ 170569^2$
$10203020\ 0836784^2 + 8161608000^2 = 102030201\ 163216^2$	$10203020\ 0829431^2 + 8343426000^2 = 102030201\ 170569^2$
$102030403020\ 0836784^2 + 816161608000^2 = 1020304030201\ 163216^2$ (5.1403)	$102030403020\ 0829431^2 + 834343426000^2 = 1020304030201\ 170569^2$ (5.1412)
$0835975^2 + 810000^2 = 1\ 164025^2$	$0828604^2 + 828000^2 = 1\ 171396^2$
$1020\ 0835975^2 + 81810000^2 = 10201\ 164025^2$	$1020\ 0828604^2 + 83628000^2 = 10201\ 171396^2$
$10203020\ 0835975^2 + 8181810000^2 = 102030201\ 164025^2$	$10203020\ 0828604^2 + 8363628000^2 = 102030201\ 171396^2$
$102030403020\ 0835975^2 + 818181810000^2 = 1020304030201\ 164025^2$ (5.1404)	$102030403020\ 0828604^2 + 836363628000^2 = 1020304030201\ 171396^2$ (5.1413)
$0835164^2 + 812000^2 = 1\ 164836^2$	$0827775^2 + 830000^2 = 1\ 172225^2$
$1020\ 0835164^2 + 82012000^2 = 10201\ 164836^2$	$1020\ 0827775^2 + 83830000^2 = 10201\ 172225^2$
$10203020\ 0835164^2 + 8202012000^2 = 102030201\ 164836^2$	$10203020\ 0827775^2 + 8383830000^2 = 102030201\ 172225^2$
$102030403020\ 0835164^2 + 820202012000^2 = 1020304030201\ 164836^2$ (5.1405)	$102030403020\ 0827775^2 + 838383830000^2 = 1020304030201\ 172225^2$ (5.1414)
$0834351^2 + 814000^2 = 1\ 165649^2$	$0826944^2 + 832000^2 = 1\ 173056^2$
$1020\ 0834351^2 + 82214000^2 = 10201\ 165649^2$	$1020\ 0826944^2 + 84032000^2 = 10201\ 173056^2$
$10203020\ 0834351^2 + 8222214000^2 = 102030201\ 165649^2$	$10203020\ 0826944^2 + 8404032000^2 = 102030201\ 173056^2$
$102030403020\ 0834351^2 + 822222214000^2 = 1020304030201\ 165649^2$ (5.1406)	$102030403020\ 0826944^2 + 840404032000^2 = 1020304030201\ 173056^2$ (5.1415)
$0833536^2 + 816000^2 = 1\ 166464^2$	$0826111^2 + 834000^2 = 1\ 173889^2$
$1020\ 0833536^2 + 82416000^2 = 10201\ 166464^2$	$1020\ 0826111^2 + 84234000^2 = 10201\ 173889^2$
$10203020\ 0833536^2 + 8242416000^2 = 102030201\ 166464^2$	$10203020\ 0826111^2 + 8424234000^2 = 102030201\ 173889^2$
$102030403020\ 0833536^2 + 824242416000^2 = 1020304030201\ 166464^2$ (5.1407)	$102030403020\ 0826111^2 + 842424234000^2 = 1020304030201\ 173889^2$ (5.1416)
$0832719^2 + 818000^2 = 1\ 167281^2$	$0825276^2 + 836000^2 = 1\ 174724^2$
$1020\ 0832719^2 + 82618000^2 = 10201\ 167281^2$	$1020\ 0825276^2 + 84436000^2 = 10201\ 174724^2$
$10203020\ 0832719^2 + 8262618000^2 = 102030201\ 167281^2$	$10203020\ 0825276^2 + 8444436000^2 = 102030201\ 174724^2$
$102030403020\ 0832719^2 + 826262618000^2 = 1020304030201\ 167281^2$ (5.1408)	$102030403020\ 0825276^2 + 844444436000^2 = 1020304030201\ 174724^2$ (5.1417)
$0831900^2 + 820000^2 = 1\ 168100^2$	
$1020\ 0831900^2 + 82820000^2 = 10201\ 168100^2$	
$10203020\ 0831900^2 + 8282820000^2 = 102030201\ 168100^2$	
$102030403020\ 0831900^2 + 828282820000^2 = 1020304030201\ 168100^2$ (5.1409)	

$0809904^2 + 872000^2 = 1\ 190096^2$	$0801975^2 + 890000^2 = 1\ 198025^2$
$1020\ 0809904^2 + 88072000^2 = 10201\ 190096^2$	$1020\ 0801975^2 + 89890000^2 = 10201\ 198025^2$
$10203020\ 0809904^2 + 8808072000^2 = 102030201\ 190096^2$	$10203020\ 0801975^2 + 8989890000^2 = 102030201\ 198025^2$
$102030403020\ 0809904^2 + 880808072000^2 = 1020304030201\ 190096^2$ (5.1435)	$102030403020\ 0801975^2 + 898989890000^2 = 1020304030201\ 198025^2$ (5.1444)
$0809031^2 + 874000^2 = 1\ 190969^2$	$0801084^2 + 892000^2 = 1\ 198916^2$
$1020\ 0809031^2 + 88274000^2 = 10201\ 190969^2$	$1020\ 0801084^2 + 90092000^2 = 10201\ 198916^2$
$10203020\ 0809031^2 + 8828274000^2 = 102030201\ 190969^2$	$10203020\ 0801084^2 + 9010092000^2 = 102030201\ 198916^2$
$102030403020\ 0809031^2 + 882828274000^2 = 1020304030201\ 190969^2$ (5.1436)	$102030403020\ 0801084^2 + 901010092000^2 = 1020304030201\ 198916^2$ (5.1445)
$0808156^2 + 876000^2 = 1\ 191844^2$	$0800191^2 + 894000^2 = 1\ 199809^2$
$1020\ 0808156^2 + 88476000^2 = 10201\ 191844^2$	$1020\ 0800191^2 + 90294000^2 = 10201\ 199809^2$
$10203020\ 0808156^2 + 8848476000^2 = 102030201\ 191844^2$	$10203020\ 0800191^2 + 9030294000^2 = 102030201\ 199809^2$
$102030403020\ 0808156^2 + 884848476000^2 = 1020304030201\ 191844^2$ (5.1437)	$102030403020\ 0800191^2 + 903030294000^2 = 1020304030201\ 199809^2$ (5.1446)
$0807279^2 + 878000^2 = 1\ 192721^2$	$0799296^2 + 896000^2 = 1\ 200704^2$
$1020\ 0807279^2 + 88678000^2 = 10201\ 192721^2$	$1020\ 0799296^2 + 90496000^2 = 10201\ 200704^2$
$10203020\ 0807279^2 + 8868678000^2 = 102030201\ 192721^2$	$10203020\ 0799296^2 + 9050496000^2 = 102030201\ 200704^2$
$102030403020\ 0807279^2 + 886868678000^2 = 1020304030201\ 192721^2$ (5.1438)	$102030403020\ 0799296^2 + 905050496000^2 = 1020304030201\ 200704^2$ (5.1447)
$0806400^2 + 880000^2 = 1\ 193600^2$	$0798399^2 + 898000^2 = 1\ 201601^2$
$1020\ 0806400^2 + 88880000^2 = 10201\ 193600^2$	$1020\ 0798399^2 + 90698000^2 = 10201\ 201601^2$
$10203020\ 0806400^2 + 8888880000^2 = 102030201\ 193600^2$	$10203020\ 0798399^2 + 9070698000^2 = 102030201\ 201601^2$
$102030403020\ 0806400^2 + 888888880000^2 = 1020304030201\ 193600^2$ (5.1439)	$102030403020\ 0798399^2 + 907070698000^2 = 1020304030201\ 201601^2$ (5.1448)
$0805519^2 + 882000^2 = 1\ 194481^2$	$0797500^2 + 900000^2 = 1\ 202500^2$
$1020\ 0805519^2 + 89082000^2 = 10201\ 194481^2$	$1020\ 0797500^2 + 90900000^2 = 10201\ 202500^2$
$10203020\ 0805519^2 + 8909082000^2 = 102030201\ 194481^2$	$10203020\ 0797500^2 + 9090900000^2 = 102030201\ 202500^2$
$102030403020\ 0805519^2 + 890909082000^2 = 1020304030201\ 194481^2$ (5.1440)	$102030403020\ 0797500^2 + 909090900000^2 = 1020304030201\ 202500^2$ (5.1449)
$0804636^2 + 884000^2 = 1\ 195364^2$	$0796599^2 + 902000^2 = 1\ 203401^2$
$1020\ 0804636^2 + 89284000^2 = 10201\ 195364^2$	$1020\ 0796599^2 + 91102000^2 = 10201\ 203401^2$
$10203020\ 0804636^2 + 8929284000^2 = 102030201\ 195364^2$	$10203020\ 0796599^2 + 9111102000^2 = 102030201\ 203401^2$
$102030403020\ 0804636^2 + 892929284000^2 = 1020304030201\ 195364^2$ (5.1441)	$102030403020\ 0796599^2 + 911111102000^2 = 1020304030201\ 203401^2$ (5.1450)
$0803751^2 + 886000^2 = 1\ 196249^2$	$0795696^2 + 904000^2 = 1\ 204304^2$
$1020\ 0803751^2 + 89486000^2 = 10201\ 196249^2$	$1020\ 0795696^2 + 91304000^2 = 10201\ 204304^2$
$10203020\ 0803751^2 + 8949486000^2 = 102030201\ 196249^2$	$10203020\ 0795696^2 + 9131304000^2 = 102030201\ 204304^2$
$102030403020\ 0803751^2 + 894949486000^2 = 1020304030201\ 196249^2$ (5.1442)	$102030403020\ 0795696^2 + 913131304000^2 = 1020304030201\ 204304^2$ (5.1451)
$0802864^2 + 888000^2 = 1\ 197136^2$	
$1020\ 0802864^2 + 89688000^2 = 10201\ 197136^2$	
$10203020\ 0802864^2 + 8969688000^2 = 102030201\ 197136^2$	
$102030403020\ 0802864^2 + 896969688000^2 = 1020304030201\ 197136^2$ (5.1443)	

$$\begin{array}{l}
0794791^2 + 906000^2 = 1\ 205209^2 \\
1020\ 0794791^2 + 91506000^2 = 10201\ 205209^2 \\
10203020\ 0794791^2 + 9151506000^2 = 102030201\ 205209^2 \\
102030403020\ 0794791^2 + 915151506000^2 = 1020304030201\ 205209^2 \\
(5.1452) \\
0793884^2 + 908000^2 = 1\ 206116^2 \\
1020\ 0793884^2 + 91708000^2 = 10201\ 206116^2 \\
10203020\ 0793884^2 + 9171708000^2 = 102030201\ 206116^2 \\
102030403020\ 0793884^2 + 917171708000^2 = 1020304030201\ 206116^2 \\
(5.1453) \\
0792975^2 + 910000^2 = 1\ 207025^2 \\
1020\ 0792975^2 + 91910000^2 = 10201\ 207025^2 \\
10203020\ 0792975^2 + 9191910000^2 = 102030201\ 207025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0792975^2 + 919191910000^2 = 1020304030201\ 207025^2 \\
(5.1454) \\
0792064^2 + 912000^2 = 1\ 207936^2 \\
1020\ 0792064^2 + 92112000^2 = 10201\ 207936^2 \\
10203020\ 0792064^2 + 9212112000^2 = 102030201\ 207936^2 \\
102030403020\ 0792064^2 + 921212112000^2 = 1020304030201\ 207936^2 \\
(5.1455) \\
0791151^2 + 914000^2 = 1\ 208849^2 \\
1020\ 0791151^2 + 92314000^2 = 10201\ 208849^2 \\
10203020\ 0791151^2 + 9232314000^2 = 102030201\ 208849^2 \\
102030403020\ 0791151^2 + 923232314000^2 = 1020304030201\ 208849^2 \\
(5.1456) \\
0790236^2 + 916000^2 = 1\ 209764^2 \\
1020\ 0790236^2 + 92516000^2 = 10201\ 209764^2 \\
10203020\ 0790236^2 + 9252516000^2 = 102030201\ 209764^2 \\
102030403020\ 0790236^2 + 925252516000^2 = 1020304030201\ 209764^2 \\
(5.1457) \\
0789319^2 + 918000^2 = 1\ 210681^2 \\
1020\ 0789319^2 + 92718000^2 = 10201\ 210681^2 \\
10203020\ 0789319^2 + 9272718000^2 = 102030201\ 210681^2 \\
102030403020\ 0789319^2 + 927272718000^2 = 1020304030201\ 210681^2 \\
(5.1458) \\
0788400^2 + 920000^2 = 1\ 211600^2 \\
1020\ 0788400^2 + 92920000^2 = 10201\ 211600^2 \\
10203020\ 0788400^2 + 9292920000^2 = 102030201\ 211600^2 \\
102030403020\ 0788400^2 + 929292920000^2 = 1020304030201\ 211600^2 \\
(5.1459) \\
0787479^2 + 922000^2 = 1\ 212521^2 \\
1020\ 0787479^2 + 93122000^2 = 10201\ 212521^2 \\
10203020\ 0787479^2 + 9313122000^2 = 102030201\ 212521^2 \\
102030403020\ 0787479^2 + 931313122000^2 = 1020304030201\ 212521^2 \\
(5.1460) \\
0786556^2 + 924000^2 = 1\ 213444^2 \\
1020\ 0786556^2 + 93324000^2 = 10201\ 213444^2 \\
10203020\ 0786556^2 + 9333324000^2 = 102030201\ 213444^2 \\
102030403020\ 0786556^2 + 933333324000^2 = 1020304030201\ 213444^2 \\
(5.1461) \\
0785631^2 + 926000^2 = 1\ 214369^2 \\
1020\ 0785631^2 + 93526000^2 = 10201\ 214369^2 \\
10203020\ 0785631^2 + 9353526000^2 = 102030201\ 214369^2 \\
102030403020\ 0785631^2 + 935353526000^2 = 1020304030201\ 214369^2 \\
(5.1462) \\
0784704^2 + 928000^2 = 1\ 215296^2 \\
1020\ 0784704^2 + 93728000^2 = 10201\ 215296^2 \\
10203020\ 0784704^2 + 9373728000^2 = 102030201\ 215296^2 \\
102030403020\ 0784704^2 + 937373728000^2 = 1020304030201\ 215296^2 \\
(5.1463) \\
0783775^2 + 930000^2 = 1\ 216225^2 \\
1020\ 0783775^2 + 93930000^2 = 10201\ 216225^2 \\
10203020\ 0783775^2 + 9393930000^2 = 102030201\ 216225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0783775^2 + 939393930000^2 = 1020304030201\ 216225^2 \\
(5.1464) \\
0782844^2 + 932000^2 = 1\ 217156^2 \\
1020\ 0782844^2 + 94132000^2 = 10201\ 217156^2 \\
10203020\ 0782844^2 + 9414132000^2 = 102030201\ 217156^2 \\
102030403020\ 0782844^2 + 941414132000^2 = 1020304030201\ 217156^2 \\
(5.1465) \\
0781911^2 + 934000^2 = 1\ 218089^2 \\
1020\ 0781911^2 + 94334000^2 = 10201\ 218089^2 \\
10203020\ 0781911^2 + 9434334000^2 = 102030201\ 218089^2 \\
102030403020\ 0781911^2 + 943434334000^2 = 1020304030201\ 218089^2 \\
(5.1466) \\
0780976^2 + 936000^2 = 1\ 219024^2 \\
1020\ 0780976^2 + 94536000^2 = 10201\ 219024^2 \\
10203020\ 0780976^2 + 9454536000^2 = 102030201\ 219024^2 \\
102030403020\ 0780976^2 + 945454536000^2 = 1020304030201\ 219024^2 \\
(5.1467) \\
0780039^2 + 938000^2 = 1\ 219961^2 \\
1020\ 0780039^2 + 94738000^2 = 10201\ 219961^2 \\
10203020\ 0780039^2 + 9474738000^2 = 102030201\ 219961^2 \\
102030403020\ 0780039^2 + 947474738000^2 = 1020304030201\ 219961^2 \\
(5.1468)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
0779100^2 + 940000^2 & = 1\ 220900^2 \\
1020\ 0779100^2 + 94940000^2 & = 10201\ 220900^2 \\
10203020\ 0779100^2 + 9494940000^2 & = 102030201\ 220900^2 \\
102030403020\ 0779100^2 + 949494940000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 220900^2 \\
& (5.1469) \\
0778159^2 + 942000^2 & = 1\ 221841^2 \\
1020\ 0778159^2 + 95142000^2 & = 10201\ 221841^2 \\
10203020\ 0778159^2 + 9515142000^2 & = 102030201\ 221841^2 \\
102030403020\ 0778159^2 + 951515142000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 221841^2 \\
& (5.1470) \\
0777216^2 + 944000^2 & = 1\ 222784^2 \\
1020\ 0777216^2 + 95344000^2 & = 10201\ 222784^2 \\
10203020\ 0777216^2 + 9535344000^2 & = 102030201\ 222784^2 \\
102030403020\ 0777216^2 + 953535344000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 222784^2 \\
& (5.1471) \\
0776271^2 + 946000^2 & = 1\ 223729^2 \\
1020\ 0776271^2 + 95546000^2 & = 10201\ 223729^2 \\
10203020\ 0776271^2 + 9555546000^2 & = 102030201\ 223729^2 \\
102030403020\ 0776271^2 + 955555546000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 223729^2 \\
& (5.1472) \\
0775324^2 + 948000^2 & = 1\ 224676^2 \\
1020\ 0775324^2 + 95748000^2 & = 10201\ 224676^2 \\
10203020\ 0775324^2 + 9575748000^2 & = 102030201\ 224676^2 \\
102030403020\ 0775324^2 + 957575748000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 224676^2 \\
& (5.1473) \\
0774375^2 + 950000^2 & = 1\ 225625^2 \\
1020\ 0774375^2 + 95950000^2 & = 10201\ 225625^2 \\
10203020\ 0774375^2 + 9595950000^2 & = 102030201\ 225625^2 \\
102030403020\ 0774375^2 + 959595950000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 225625^2 \\
& (5.1474) \\
0773424^2 + 952000^2 & = 1\ 226576^2 \\
1020\ 0773424^2 + 96152000^2 & = 10201\ 226576^2 \\
10203020\ 0773424^2 + 9616152000^2 & = 102030201\ 226576^2 \\
102030403020\ 0773424^2 + 961616152000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 226576^2 \\
& (5.1475) \\
0772471^2 + 954000^2 & = 1\ 227529^2 \\
1020\ 0772471^2 + 96354000^2 & = 10201\ 227529^2 \\
10203020\ 0772471^2 + 9636354000^2 & = 102030201\ 227529^2 \\
102030403020\ 0772471^2 + 963636354000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 227529^2 \\
& (5.1476) \\
0771516^2 + 956000^2 & = 1\ 228484^2 \\
1020\ 0771516^2 + 96556000^2 & = 10201\ 228484^2 \\
10203020\ 0771516^2 + 9656556000^2 & = 102030201\ 228484^2 \\
102030403020\ 0771516^2 + 965656556000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 228484^2 \\
& (5.1477) \\
0770559^2 + 958000^2 & = 1\ 229441^2 \\
1020\ 0770559^2 + 96758000^2 & = 10201\ 229441^2 \\
10203020\ 0770559^2 + 9676758000^2 & = 102030201\ 229441^2 \\
102030403020\ 0770559^2 + 967676758000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 229441^2 \\
& (5.1478) \\
0769600^2 + 960000^2 & = 1\ 230400^2 \\
1020\ 0769600^2 + 96960000^2 & = 10201\ 230400^2 \\
10203020\ 0769600^2 + 9696960000^2 & = 102030201\ 230400^2 \\
102030403020\ 0769600^2 + 969696960000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 230400^2 \\
& (5.1479) \\
0768639^2 + 962000^2 & = 1\ 231361^2 \\
1020\ 0768639^2 + 97162000^2 & = 10201\ 231361^2 \\
10203020\ 0768639^2 + 9717162000^2 & = 102030201\ 231361^2 \\
102030403020\ 0768639^2 + 971717162000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 231361^2 \\
& (5.1480) \\
0767676^2 + 964000^2 & = 1\ 232324^2 \\
1020\ 0767676^2 + 97364000^2 & = 10201\ 232324^2 \\
10203020\ 0767676^2 + 9737364000^2 & = 102030201\ 232324^2 \\
102030403020\ 0767676^2 + 973737364000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 232324^2 \\
& (5.1481) \\
0766711^2 + 966000^2 & = 1\ 233289^2 \\
1020\ 0766711^2 + 97566000^2 & = 10201\ 233289^2 \\
10203020\ 0766711^2 + 9757566000^2 & = 102030201\ 233289^2 \\
102030403020\ 0766711^2 + 975757566000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 233289^2 \\
& (5.1482) \\
0765744^2 + 968000^2 & = 1\ 234256^2 \\
1020\ 0765744^2 + 97768000^2 & = 10201\ 234256^2 \\
10203020\ 0765744^2 + 9777768000^2 & = 102030201\ 234256^2 \\
102030403020\ 0765744^2 + 977777768000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 234256^2 \\
& (5.1483) \\
0764775^2 + 970000^2 & = 1\ 235225^2 \\
1020\ 0764775^2 + 97970000^2 & = 10201\ 235225^2 \\
10203020\ 0764775^2 + 9797970000^2 & = 102030201\ 235225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0764775^2 + 979797970000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 235225^2 \\
& (5.1484) \\
0763804^2 + 972000^2 & = 1\ 236196^2 \\
1020\ 0763804^2 + 98172000^2 & = 10201\ 236196^2 \\
10203020\ 0763804^2 + 9818172000^2 & = 102030201\ 236196^2 \\
102030403020\ 0763804^2 + 981818172000^2 & = 1020304030201\ 236196^2 \\
& (5.1485)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0762831^2 + 974000^2 = 1\ 237169^2 \\
1020\ 0762831^2 + 98374000^2 = 10201\ 237169^2 \\
10203020\ 0762831^2 + 9838374000^2 = 102030201\ 237169^2 \\
102030403020\ 0762831^2 + 983838374000^2 = 1020304030201\ 237169^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1486) \\
0761856^2 + 976000^2 = 1\ 238144^2 \\
1020\ 0761856^2 + 98576000^2 = 10201\ 238144^2 \\
10203020\ 0761856^2 + 9858576000^2 = 102030201\ 238144^2 \\
102030403020\ 0761856^2 + 985858576000^2 = 1020304030201\ 238144^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1487) \\
0760879^2 + 978000^2 = 1\ 239121^2 \\
1020\ 0760879^2 + 98778000^2 = 10201\ 239121^2 \\
10203020\ 0760879^2 + 9878778000^2 = 102030201\ 239121^2 \\
102030403020\ 0760879^2 + 987878778000^2 = 1020304030201\ 239121^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1488) \\
0759900^2 + 980000^2 = 1\ 240100^2 \\
1020\ 0759900^2 + 98980000^2 = 10201\ 240100^2 \\
10203020\ 0759900^2 + 9898980000^2 = 102030201\ 240100^2 \\
102030403020\ 0759900^2 + 989898980000^2 = 1020304030201\ 240100^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1489) \\
0758919^2 + 982000^2 = 1\ 241081^2 \\
1020\ 0758919^2 + 99182000^2 = 10201\ 241081^2 \\
10203020\ 0758919^2 + 9919182000^2 = 102030201\ 241081^2 \\
102030403020\ 0758919^2 + 991919182000^2 = 1020304030201\ 241081^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1490) \\
0757936^2 + 984000^2 = 1\ 242064^2 \\
1020\ 0757936^2 + 99384000^2 = 10201\ 242064^2 \\
10203020\ 0757936^2 + 9939384000^2 = 102030201\ 242064^2 \\
102030403020\ 0757936^2 + 993939384000^2 = 1020304030201\ 242064^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1491) \\
0756951^2 + 986000^2 = 1\ 243049^2 \\
1020\ 0756951^2 + 99586000^2 = 10201\ 243049^2 \\
10203020\ 0756951^2 + 9959586000^2 = 102030201\ 243049^2 \\
102030403020\ 0756951^2 + 995959586000^2 = 1020304030201\ 243049^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1492) \\
0750000^2 + 1000000^2 = 1\ 250000^2 \\
1020\ 0750000^2 + 101000000^2 = 10201\ 250000^2 \\
10203020\ 0750000^2 + 10101000000^2 = 102030201\ 250000^2 \\
102030403020\ 0750000^2 + 1010101000000^2 = 1020304030201\ 250000^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1499) \\
0755964^2 + 988000^2 = 1\ 244036^2 \\
1020\ 0755964^2 + 99788000^2 = 10201\ 244036^2 \\
10203020\ 0755964^2 + 9979788000^2 = 102030201\ 244036^2 \\
102030403020\ 0755964^2 + 997979788000^2 = 1020304030201\ 244036^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1493) \\
0754975^2 + 990000^2 = 1\ 245025^2 \\
1020\ 0754975^2 + 99990000^2 = 10201\ 245025^2 \\
10203020\ 0754975^2 + 9999990000^2 = 102030201\ 245025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0754975^2 + 999999990000^2 = 1020304030201\ 245025^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1494) \\
0753984^2 + 992000^2 = 1\ 246016^2 \\
1020\ 0753984^2 + 100192000^2 = 10201\ 246016^2 \\
10203020\ 0753984^2 + 10020192000^2 = 102030201\ 246016^2 \\
102030403020\ 0753984^2 + 1002020192000^2 = 1020304030201\ 246016^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1495) \\
0752991^2 + 994000^2 = 1\ 247009^2 \\
1020\ 0752991^2 + 100394000^2 = 10201\ 247009^2 \\
10203020\ 0752991^2 + 10040394000^2 = 102030201\ 247009^2 \\
102030403020\ 0752991^2 + 1004040394000^2 = 1020304030201\ 247009^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1496) \\
0751996^2 + 996000^2 = 1\ 248004^2 \\
1020\ 0751996^2 + 100596000^2 = 10201\ 248004^2 \\
10203020\ 0751996^2 + 10060596000^2 = 102030201\ 248004^2 \\
102030403020\ 0751996^2 + 1006060596000^2 = 1020304030201\ 248004^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1497) \\
0750999^2 + 998000^2 = 1\ 249001^2 \\
1020\ 0750999^2 + 100798000^2 = 10201\ 249001^2 \\
10203020\ 0750999^2 + 10080798000^2 = 102030201\ 249001^2 \\
102030403020\ 0750999^2 + 1008080798000^2 = 1020304030201\ 249001^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1498) \\
0748999^2 + 1002000^2 = 1\ 251001^2 \\
1020\ 0748999^2 + 101202000^2 = 10201\ 251001^2 \\
10203020\ 0748999^2 + 10121202000^2 = 102030201\ 251001^2 \\
102030403020\ 0748999^2 + 1012121202000^2 = 1020304030201\ 251001^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1500)
\end{array}$$

$0747996^2 + 1004000^2 = 1\ 252004^2$	$0738879^2 + 1022000^2 = 1\ 261121^2$
$1020\ 0747996^2 + 101404000^2 = 10201\ 252004^2$	$1020\ 0738879^2 + 103222000^2 = 10201\ 261121^2$
$10203020\ 0747996^2 + 10141404000^2 = 102030201\ 252004^2$	$10203020\ 0738879^2 + 10323222000^2 = 102030201\ 261121^2$
$102030403020\ 0747996^2 + 1014141404000^2 = 1020304030201\ 252004^2$ (5.1501)	$102030403020\ 0738879^2 + 1032323222000^2 = 1020304030201\ 261121^2$ (5.1510)
$0746991^2 + 1006000^2 = 1\ 253009^2$	$0737856^2 + 1024000^2 = 1\ 262144^2$
$1020\ 0746991^2 + 101606000^2 = 10201\ 253009^2$	$1020\ 0737856^2 + 103424000^2 = 10201\ 262144^2$
$10203020\ 0746991^2 + 10161606000^2 = 102030201\ 253009^2$	$10203020\ 0737856^2 + 10343424000^2 = 102030201\ 262144^2$
$102030403020\ 0746991^2 + 1016161606000^2 = 1020304030201\ 253009^2$ (5.1502)	$102030403020\ 0737856^2 + 1034343424000^2 = 1020304030201\ 262144^2$ (5.1511)
$0745984^2 + 1008000^2 = 1\ 254016^2$	$0736831^2 + 1026000^2 = 1\ 263169^2$
$1020\ 0745984^2 + 101808000^2 = 10201\ 254016^2$	$1020\ 0736831^2 + 103626000^2 = 10201\ 263169^2$
$10203020\ 0745984^2 + 10181808000^2 = 102030201\ 254016^2$	$10203020\ 0736831^2 + 10363626000^2 = 102030201\ 263169^2$
$102030403020\ 0745984^2 + 1018181808000^2 = 1020304030201\ 254016^2$ (5.1503)	$102030403020\ 0736831^2 + 1036363626000^2 = 1020304030201\ 263169^2$ (5.1512)
$0744975^2 + 1010000^2 = 1\ 255025^2$	$0735804^2 + 1028000^2 = 1\ 264196^2$
$1020\ 0744975^2 + 102010000^2 = 10201\ 255025^2$	$1020\ 0735804^2 + 103828000^2 = 10201\ 264196^2$
$10203020\ 0744975^2 + 10202010000^2 = 102030201\ 255025^2$	$10203020\ 0735804^2 + 10383828000^2 = 102030201\ 264196^2$
$102030403020\ 0744975^2 + 1020202010000^2 = 1020304030201\ 255025^2$ (5.1504)	$102030403020\ 0735804^2 + 1038383828000^2 = 1020304030201\ 264196^2$ (5.1513)
$0743964^2 + 1012000^2 = 1\ 256036^2$	$0734775^2 + 1030000^2 = 1\ 265225^2$
$1020\ 0743964^2 + 102212000^2 = 10201\ 256036^2$	$1020\ 0734775^2 + 104030000^2 = 10201\ 265225^2$
$10203020\ 0743964^2 + 10222212000^2 = 102030201\ 256036^2$	$10203020\ 0734775^2 + 10404030000^2 = 102030201\ 265225^2$
$102030403020\ 0743964^2 + 1022222212000^2 = 1020304030201\ 256036^2$ (5.1505)	$102030403020\ 0734775^2 + 1040404030000^2 = 1020304030201\ 265225^2$ (5.1514)
$0742951^2 + 1014000^2 = 1\ 257049^2$	$0733744^2 + 1032000^2 = 1\ 266256^2$
$1020\ 0742951^2 + 102414000^2 = 10201\ 257049^2$	$1020\ 0733744^2 + 104232000^2 = 10201\ 266256^2$
$10203020\ 0742951^2 + 10242414000^2 = 102030201\ 257049^2$	$10203020\ 0733744^2 + 10424232000^2 = 102030201\ 266256^2$
$102030403020\ 0742951^2 + 1024242414000^2 = 1020304030201\ 257049^2$ (5.1506)	$102030403020\ 0733744^2 + 1042424232000^2 = 1020304030201\ 266256^2$ (5.1515)
$0741936^2 + 1016000^2 = 1\ 258064^2$	$0732711^2 + 1034000^2 = 1\ 267289^2$
$1020\ 0741936^2 + 102616000^2 = 10201\ 258064^2$	$1020\ 0732711^2 + 104434000^2 = 10201\ 267289^2$
$10203020\ 0741936^2 + 10262616000^2 = 102030201\ 258064^2$	$10203020\ 0732711^2 + 10444434000^2 = 102030201\ 267289^2$
$102030403020\ 0741936^2 + 1026262616000^2 = 1020304030201\ 258064^2$ (5.1507)	$102030403020\ 0732711^2 + 1044444434000^2 = 1020304030201\ 267289^2$ (5.1516)
$0740919^2 + 1018000^2 = 1\ 259081^2$	$0731676^2 + 1036000^2 = 1\ 268324^2$
$1020\ 0740919^2 + 102818000^2 = 10201\ 259081^2$	$1020\ 0731676^2 + 104636000^2 = 10201\ 268324^2$
$10203020\ 0740919^2 + 10282818000^2 = 102030201\ 259081^2$	$10203020\ 0731676^2 + 10464636000^2 = 102030201\ 268324^2$
$102030403020\ 0740919^2 + 1028282818000^2 = 1020304030201\ 259081^2$ (5.1508)	$102030403020\ 0731676^2 + 1046464636000^2 = 1020304030201\ 268324^2$ (5.1517)
$0739900^2 + 1020000^2 = 1\ 260100^2$	
$1020\ 0739900^2 + 103020000^2 = 10201\ 260100^2$	
$10203020\ 0739900^2 + 10303020000^2 = 102030201\ 260100^2$	
$102030403020\ 0739900^2 + 1030303020000^2 = 1020304030201\ 260100^2$ (5.1509)	

$0730639^2 + 1038000^2 = 1\ 269361^2$	$0721216^2 + 1056000^2 = 1\ 278784^2$
$1020\ 0730639^2 + 104838000^2 = 10201\ 269361^2$	$1020\ 0721216^2 + 106656000^2 = 10201\ 278784^2$
$10203020\ 0730639^2 + 10484838000^2 = 102030201\ 269361^2$	$10203020\ 0721216^2 + 10666656000^2 = 102030201\ 278784^2$
$102030403020\ 0730639^2 + 1048484838000^2 = 1020304030201\ 269361^2$ (5.1518)	$102030403020\ 0721216^2 + 1066666656000^2 = 1020304030201\ 278784^2$ (5.1527)
$0729600^2 + 1040000^2 = 1\ 270400^2$	$0720159^2 + 1058000^2 = 1\ 279841^2$
$1020\ 0729600^2 + 105040000^2 = 10201\ 270400^2$	$1020\ 0720159^2 + 106858000^2 = 10201\ 279841^2$
$10203020\ 0729600^2 + 10505040000^2 = 102030201\ 270400^2$	$10203020\ 0720159^2 + 10686858000^2 = 102030201\ 279841^2$
$102030403020\ 0729600^2 + 1050505040000^2 = 1020304030201\ 270400^2$ (5.1519)	$102030403020\ 0720159^2 + 1068686858000^2 = 1020304030201\ 279841^2$ (5.1528)
$0728559^2 + 1042000^2 = 1\ 271441^2$	$0719100^2 + 1060000^2 = 1\ 280900^2$
$1020\ 0728559^2 + 105242000^2 = 10201\ 271441^2$	$1020\ 0719100^2 + 107060000^2 = 10201\ 280900^2$
$10203020\ 0728559^2 + 10525242000^2 = 102030201\ 271441^2$	$10203020\ 0719100^2 + 10707060000^2 = 102030201\ 280900^2$
$102030403020\ 0728559^2 + 1052525242000^2 = 1020304030201\ 271441^2$ (5.1520)	$102030403020\ 0719100^2 + 1070707060000^2 = 1020304030201\ 280900^2$ (5.1529)
$0727516^2 + 1044000^2 = 1\ 272484^2$	$0718039^2 + 1062000^2 = 1\ 281961^2$
$1020\ 0727516^2 + 105444000^2 = 10201\ 272484^2$	$1020\ 0718039^2 + 107262000^2 = 10201\ 281961^2$
$10203020\ 0727516^2 + 10545444000^2 = 102030201\ 272484^2$	$10203020\ 0718039^2 + 10727262000^2 = 102030201\ 281961^2$
$102030403020\ 0727516^2 + 1054545444000^2 = 1020304030201\ 272484^2$ (5.1521)	$102030403020\ 0718039^2 + 1072727262000^2 = 1020304030201\ 281961^2$ (5.1530)
$0726471^2 + 1046000^2 = 1\ 273529^2$	$0716976^2 + 1064000^2 = 1\ 283024^2$
$1020\ 0726471^2 + 105646000^2 = 10201\ 273529^2$	$1020\ 0716976^2 + 107464000^2 = 10201\ 283024^2$
$10203020\ 0726471^2 + 10565646000^2 = 102030201\ 273529^2$	$10203020\ 0716976^2 + 10747464000^2 = 102030201\ 283024^2$
$102030403020\ 0726471^2 + 1056565646000^2 = 1020304030201\ 273529^2$ (5.1522)	$102030403020\ 0716976^2 + 1074747464000^2 = 1020304030201\ 283024^2$ (5.1531)
$0725424^2 + 1048000^2 = 1\ 274576^2$	$0715911^2 + 1066000^2 = 1\ 284089^2$
$1020\ 0725424^2 + 105848000^2 = 10201\ 274576^2$	$1020\ 0715911^2 + 107666000^2 = 10201\ 284089^2$
$10203020\ 0725424^2 + 10585848000^2 = 102030201\ 274576^2$	$10203020\ 0715911^2 + 10767666000^2 = 102030201\ 284089^2$
$102030403020\ 0725424^2 + 1058585848000^2 = 1020304030201\ 274576^2$ (5.1523)	$102030403020\ 0715911^2 + 1076767666000^2 = 1020304030201\ 284089^2$ (5.1532)
$0724375^2 + 1050000^2 = 1\ 275625^2$	$0714844^2 + 1068000^2 = 1\ 285156^2$
$1020\ 0724375^2 + 106050000^2 = 10201\ 275625^2$	$1020\ 0714844^2 + 107868000^2 = 10201\ 285156^2$
$10203020\ 0724375^2 + 10606050000^2 = 102030201\ 275625^2$	$10203020\ 0714844^2 + 10787868000^2 = 102030201\ 285156^2$
$102030403020\ 0724375^2 + 1060606050000^2 = 1020304030201\ 275625^2$ (5.1524)	$102030403020\ 0714844^2 + 1078787868000^2 = 1020304030201\ 285156^2$ (5.1533)
$0723324^2 + 1052000^2 = 1\ 276676^2$	$0713775^2 + 1070000^2 = 1\ 286225^2$
$1020\ 0723324^2 + 106252000^2 = 10201\ 276676^2$	$1020\ 0713775^2 + 108070000^2 = 10201\ 286225^2$
$10203020\ 0723324^2 + 10626252000^2 = 102030201\ 276676^2$	$10203020\ 0713775^2 + 10808070000^2 = 102030201\ 286225^2$
$102030403020\ 0723324^2 + 1062626252000^2 = 1020304030201\ 276676^2$ (5.1525)	$102030403020\ 0713775^2 + 1080808070000^2 = 1020304030201\ 286225^2$ (5.1534)
$0722271^2 + 1054000^2 = 1\ 277729^2$	
$1020\ 0722271^2 + 106454000^2 = 10201\ 277729^2$	
$10203020\ 0722271^2 + 10646454000^2 = 102030201\ 277729^2$	
$102030403020\ 0722271^2 + 1064646454000^2 = 1020304030201\ 277729^2$ (5.1526)	

$$\begin{array}{l}
0694191^2 + 1106000^2 = 1\ 305809^2 \\
1020\ 0694191^2 + 111706000^2 = 10201\ 305809^2 \\
10203020\ 0694191^2 + 11171706000^2 = 102030201\ 305809^2 \\
102030403020\ 0694191^2 + 1117171706000^2 = 1020304030201\ 305809^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1552)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0684156^2 + 1124000^2 = 1\ 315844^2 \\
1020\ 0684156^2 + 113524000^2 = 10201\ 315844^2 \\
10203020\ 0684156^2 + 11353524000^2 = 102030201\ 315844^2 \\
102030403020\ 0684156^2 + 1135353524000^2 = 1020304030201\ 315844^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1561)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0693084^2 + 1108000^2 = 1\ 306916^2 \\
1020\ 0693084^2 + 111908000^2 = 10201\ 306916^2 \\
10203020\ 0693084^2 + 11191908000^2 = 102030201\ 306916^2 \\
102030403020\ 0693084^2 + 1119191908000^2 = 1020304030201\ 306916^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1553)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0683031^2 + 1126000^2 = 1\ 316969^2 \\
1020\ 0683031^2 + 113726000^2 = 10201\ 316969^2 \\
10203020\ 0683031^2 + 11373726000^2 = 102030201\ 316969^2 \\
102030403020\ 0683031^2 + 1137373726000^2 = 1020304030201\ 316969^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1562)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0691975^2 + 1110000^2 = 1\ 308025^2 \\
1020\ 0691975^2 + 112110000^2 = 10201\ 308025^2 \\
10203020\ 0691975^2 + 11212110000^2 = 102030201\ 308025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0691975^2 + 1121212110000^2 = 1020304030201\ 308025^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1554)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0681904^2 + 1128000^2 = 1\ 318096^2 \\
1020\ 0681904^2 + 113928000^2 = 10201\ 318096^2 \\
10203020\ 0681904^2 + 11393928000^2 = 102030201\ 318096^2 \\
102030403020\ 0681904^2 + 1139393928000^2 = 1020304030201\ 318096^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1563)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0690864^2 + 1112000^2 = 1\ 309136^2 \\
1020\ 0690864^2 + 112312000^2 = 10201\ 309136^2 \\
10203020\ 0690864^2 + 11232312000^2 = 102030201\ 309136^2 \\
102030403020\ 0690864^2 + 1123232312000^2 = 1020304030201\ 309136^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1555)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0680775^2 + 1130000^2 = 1\ 319225^2 \\
1020\ 0680775^2 + 114130000^2 = 10201\ 319225^2 \\
10203020\ 0680775^2 + 11414130000^2 = 102030201\ 319225^2 \\
102030403020\ 0680775^2 + 1141414130000^2 = 1020304030201\ 319225^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1564)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0689751^2 + 1114000^2 = 1\ 310249^2 \\
1020\ 0689751^2 + 112514000^2 = 10201\ 310249^2 \\
10203020\ 0689751^2 + 11252514000^2 = 102030201\ 310249^2 \\
102030403020\ 0689751^2 + 1125252514000^2 = 1020304030201\ 310249^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1556)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0679644^2 + 1132000^2 = 1\ 320356^2 \\
1020\ 0679644^2 + 114332000^2 = 10201\ 320356^2 \\
10203020\ 0679644^2 + 11434332000^2 = 102030201\ 320356^2 \\
102030403020\ 0679644^2 + 1143434332000^2 = 1020304030201\ 320356^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1565)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0688636^2 + 1116000^2 = 1\ 311364^2 \\
1020\ 0688636^2 + 112716000^2 = 10201\ 311364^2 \\
10203020\ 0688636^2 + 11272716000^2 = 102030201\ 311364^2 \\
102030403020\ 0688636^2 + 1127272716000^2 = 1020304030201\ 311364^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1557)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0678511^2 + 1134000^2 = 1\ 321489^2 \\
1020\ 0678511^2 + 114534000^2 = 10201\ 321489^2 \\
10203020\ 0678511^2 + 11454534000^2 = 102030201\ 321489^2 \\
102030403020\ 0678511^2 + 1145454534000^2 = 1020304030201\ 321489^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1566)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0687519^2 + 1118000^2 = 1\ 312481^2 \\
1020\ 0687519^2 + 112918000^2 = 10201\ 312481^2 \\
10203020\ 0687519^2 + 11292918000^2 = 102030201\ 312481^2 \\
102030403020\ 0687519^2 + 1129292918000^2 = 1020304030201\ 312481^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1558)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0677376^2 + 1136000^2 = 1\ 322624^2 \\
1020\ 0677376^2 + 114736000^2 = 10201\ 322624^2 \\
10203020\ 0677376^2 + 11474736000^2 = 102030201\ 322624^2 \\
102030403020\ 0677376^2 + 1147474736000^2 = 1020304030201\ 322624^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1567)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0686400^2 + 1120000^2 = 1\ 313600^2 \\
1020\ 0686400^2 + 113120000^2 = 10201\ 313600^2 \\
10203020\ 0686400^2 + 11313120000^2 = 102030201\ 313600^2 \\
102030403020\ 0686400^2 + 1131313120000^2 = 1020304030201\ 313600^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1559)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0676239^2 + 1138000^2 = 1\ 323761^2 \\
1020\ 0676239^2 + 114938000^2 = 10201\ 323761^2 \\
10203020\ 0676239^2 + 11494938000^2 = 102030201\ 323761^2 \\
102030403020\ 0676239^2 + 1149494938000^2 = 1020304030201\ 323761^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1568)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0685279^2 + 1122000^2 = 1\ 314721^2 \\
1020\ 0685279^2 + 113322000^2 = 10201\ 314721^2 \\
10203020\ 0685279^2 + 11333322000^2 = 102030201\ 314721^2 \\
102030403020\ 0685279^2 + 1133333322000^2 = 1020304030201\ 314721^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1560)
\end{array}$$

$0675100^2 + 1140000^2 = 1\ 324900^2$	$0664759^2 + 1158000^2 = 1\ 335241^2$
$1020\ 0675100^2 + 115140000^2 = 10201\ 324900^2$	$1020\ 0664759^2 + 116958000^2 = 10201\ 335241^2$
$10203020\ 0675100^2 + 11515140000^2 = 102030201\ 324900^2$	$10203020\ 0664759^2 + 11696958000^2 = 102030201\ 335241^2$
$102030403020\ 0675100^2 + 1151515140000^2 = 1020304030201\ 324900^2$ (5.1569)	$102030403020\ 0664759^2 + 1169696958000^2 = 1020304030201\ 335241^2$ (5.1578)
$0673959^2 + 1142000^2 = 1\ 326041^2$	$0663600^2 + 1160000^2 = 1\ 336400^2$
$1020\ 0673959^2 + 115342000^2 = 10201\ 326041^2$	$1020\ 0663600^2 + 117160000^2 = 10201\ 336400^2$
$10203020\ 0673959^2 + 11535342000^2 = 102030201\ 326041^2$	$10203020\ 0663600^2 + 11717160000^2 = 102030201\ 336400^2$
$102030403020\ 0673959^2 + 1153535342000^2 = 1020304030201\ 326041^2$ (5.1570)	$102030403020\ 0663600^2 + 1171717160000^2 = 1020304030201\ 336400^2$ (5.1579)
$0672816^2 + 1144000^2 = 1\ 327184^2$	$0662439^2 + 1162000^2 = 1\ 337561^2$
$1020\ 0672816^2 + 115544000^2 = 10201\ 327184^2$	$1020\ 0662439^2 + 117362000^2 = 10201\ 337561^2$
$10203020\ 0672816^2 + 11555544000^2 = 102030201\ 327184^2$	$10203020\ 0662439^2 + 11737362000^2 = 102030201\ 337561^2$
$102030403020\ 0672816^2 + 1155555544000^2 = 1020304030201\ 327184^2$ (5.1571)	$102030403020\ 0662439^2 + 1173737362000^2 = 1020304030201\ 337561^2$ (5.1580)
$0671671^2 + 1146000^2 = 1\ 328329^2$	$0661276^2 + 1164000^2 = 1\ 338724^2$
$1020\ 0671671^2 + 115746000^2 = 10201\ 328329^2$	$1020\ 0661276^2 + 117564000^2 = 10201\ 338724^2$
$10203020\ 0671671^2 + 11575746000^2 = 102030201\ 328329^2$	$10203020\ 0661276^2 + 11757564000^2 = 102030201\ 338724^2$
$102030403020\ 0671671^2 + 1157575746000^2 = 1020304030201\ 328329^2$ (5.1572)	$102030403020\ 0661276^2 + 1175757564000^2 = 1020304030201\ 338724^2$ (5.1581)
$0670524^2 + 1148000^2 = 1\ 329476^2$	$0660111^2 + 1166000^2 = 1\ 339889^2$
$1020\ 0670524^2 + 115948000^2 = 10201\ 329476^2$	$1020\ 0660111^2 + 117766000^2 = 10201\ 339889^2$
$10203020\ 0670524^2 + 11595948000^2 = 102030201\ 329476^2$	$10203020\ 0660111^2 + 11777766000^2 = 102030201\ 339889^2$
$102030403020\ 0670524^2 + 1159595948000^2 = 1020304030201\ 329476^2$ (5.1573)	$102030403020\ 0660111^2 + 1177777766000^2 = 1020304030201\ 339889^2$ (5.1582)
$0669375^2 + 1150000^2 = 1\ 330625^2$	$0658944^2 + 1168000^2 = 1\ 341056^2$
$1020\ 0669375^2 + 116150000^2 = 10201\ 330625^2$	$1020\ 0658944^2 + 117968000^2 = 10201\ 341056^2$
$10203020\ 0669375^2 + 11616150000^2 = 102030201\ 330625^2$	$10203020\ 0658944^2 + 11797968000^2 = 102030201\ 341056^2$
$102030403020\ 0669375^2 + 1161616150000^2 = 1020304030201\ 330625^2$ (5.1574)	$102030403020\ 0658944^2 + 1179797968000^2 = 1020304030201\ 341056^2$ (5.1583)
$0668224^2 + 1152000^2 = 1\ 331776^2$	$0657775^2 + 1170000^2 = 1\ 342225^2$
$1020\ 0668224^2 + 116352000^2 = 10201\ 331776^2$	$1020\ 0657775^2 + 118170000^2 = 10201\ 342225^2$
$10203020\ 0668224^2 + 11636352000^2 = 102030201\ 331776^2$	$10203020\ 0657775^2 + 11818170000^2 = 102030201\ 342225^2$
$102030403020\ 0668224^2 + 1163636352000^2 = 1020304030201\ 331776^2$ (5.1575)	$102030403020\ 0657775^2 + 1181818170000^2 = 1020304030201\ 342225^2$ (5.1584)
$0667071^2 + 1154000^2 = 1\ 332929^2$	$0656604^2 + 1172000^2 = 1\ 343396^2$
$1020\ 0667071^2 + 116554000^2 = 10201\ 332929^2$	$1020\ 0656604^2 + 118372000^2 = 10201\ 343396^2$
$10203020\ 0667071^2 + 11656554000^2 = 102030201\ 332929^2$	$10203020\ 0656604^2 + 11838372000^2 = 102030201\ 343396^2$
$102030403020\ 0667071^2 + 1165656554000^2 = 1020304030201\ 332929^2$ (5.1576)	$102030403020\ 0656604^2 + 1183838372000^2 = 1020304030201\ 343396^2$ (5.1585)
$0665916^2 + 1156000^2 = 1\ 334084^2$	
$1020\ 0665916^2 + 116756000^2 = 10201\ 334084^2$	
$10203020\ 0665916^2 + 11676756000^2 = 102030201\ 334084^2$	
$102030403020\ 0665916^2 + 1167676756000^2 = 1020304030201\ 334084^2$ (5.1577)	

$0655431^2 + 1174000^2 = 1\ 344569^2$	$0647164^2 + 1188000^2 = 1\ 352836^2$
$1020\ 0655431^2 + 118574000^2 = 10201\ 344569^2$	$1020\ 0647164^2 + 119988000^2 = 10201\ 352836^2$
$10203020\ 0655431^2 + 11858574000^2 = 102030201\ 344569^2$	$10203020\ 0647164^2 + 11999988000^2 = 102030201\ 352836^2$
$102030403020\ 0655431^2 + 1185858574000^2 = 1020304030201\ 344569^2$ (5.1586)	$102030403020\ 0647164^2 + 1199999988000^2 = 1020304030201\ 352836^2$ (5.1593)
$0654256^2 + 1176000^2 = 1\ 345744^2$	$0645975^2 + 1190000^2 = 1\ 354025^2$
$1020\ 0654256^2 + 118776000^2 = 10201\ 345744^2$	$1020\ 0645975^2 + 120190000^2 = 10201\ 354025^2$
$10203020\ 0654256^2 + 11878776000^2 = 102030201\ 345744^2$	$10203020\ 0645975^2 + 12020190000^2 = 102030201\ 354025^2$
$102030403020\ 0654256^2 + 1187878776000^2 = 1020304030201\ 345744^2$ (5.1587)	$102030403020\ 0645975^2 + 1202020190000^2 = 1020304030201\ 354025^2$ (5.1594)
$0653079^2 + 1178000^2 = 1\ 346921^2$	$0644784^2 + 1192000^2 = 1\ 355216^2$
$1020\ 0653079^2 + 118978000^2 = 10201\ 346921^2$	$1020\ 0644784^2 + 120392000^2 = 10201\ 355216^2$
$10203020\ 0653079^2 + 11898978000^2 = 102030201\ 346921^2$	$10203020\ 0644784^2 + 12040392000^2 = 102030201\ 355216^2$
$102030403020\ 0653079^2 + 1189898978000^2 = 1020304030201\ 346921^2$ (5.1588)	$102030403020\ 0644784^2 + 1204040392000^2 = 1020304030201\ 355216^2$ (5.1595)
$0651900^2 + 1180000^2 = 1\ 348100^2$	$0643591^2 + 1194000^2 = 1\ 356409^2$
$1020\ 0651900^2 + 119180000^2 = 10201\ 348100^2$	$1020\ 0643591^2 + 120594000^2 = 10201\ 356409^2$
$10203020\ 0651900^2 + 11919180000^2 = 102030201\ 348100^2$	$10203020\ 0643591^2 + 12060594000^2 = 102030201\ 356409^2$
$102030403020\ 0651900^2 + 1191919180000^2 = 1020304030201\ 348100^2$ (5.1589)	$102030403020\ 0643591^2 + 1206060594000^2 = 1020304030201\ 356409^2$ (5.1596)
$0650719^2 + 1182000^2 = 1\ 349281^2$	$0642396^2 + 1196000^2 = 1\ 357604^2$
$1020\ 0650719^2 + 119382000^2 = 10201\ 349281^2$	$1020\ 0642396^2 + 120796000^2 = 10201\ 357604^2$
$10203020\ 0650719^2 + 11939382000^2 = 102030201\ 349281^2$	$10203020\ 0642396^2 + 12080796000^2 = 102030201\ 357604^2$
$102030403020\ 0650719^2 + 1193939382000^2 = 1020304030201\ 349281^2$ (5.1590)	$102030403020\ 0642396^2 + 1208080796000^2 = 1020304030201\ 357604^2$ (5.1597)
$0649536^2 + 1184000^2 = 1\ 350464^2$	$0641199^2 + 1198000^2 = 1\ 358801^2$
$1020\ 0649536^2 + 119584000^2 = 10201\ 350464^2$	$1020\ 0641199^2 + 120998000^2 = 10201\ 358801^2$
$10203020\ 0649536^2 + 11959584000^2 = 102030201\ 350464^2$	$10203020\ 0641199^2 + 12100998000^2 = 102030201\ 358801^2$
$102030403020\ 0649536^2 + 1195959584000^2 = 1020304030201\ 350464^2$ (5.1591)	$102030403020\ 0641199^2 + 1210100998000^2 = 1020304030201\ 358801^2$ (5.1598)
$0648351^2 + 1186000^2 = 1\ 351649^2$	$0638799^2 + 1202000^2 = 1\ 361201^2$
$1020\ 0648351^2 + 119786000^2 = 10201\ 351649^2$	$1020\ 0638799^2 + 121402000^2 = 10201\ 361201^2$
$10203020\ 0648351^2 + 11979786000^2 = 102030201\ 351649^2$	$10203020\ 0638799^2 + 12141402000^2 = 102030201\ 361201^2$
$102030403020\ 0648351^2 + 1197979786000^2 = 1020304030201\ 351649^2$ (5.1592)	$102030403020\ 0638799^2 + 1214141402000^2 = 1020304030201\ 361201^2$ (5.1600)
$0640000^2 + 1200000^2 = 1\ 360000^2$	
$1020\ 0640000^2 + 121200000^2 = 10201\ 360000^2$	
$10203020\ 0640000^2 + 12121200000^2 = 102030201\ 360000^2$	
$102030403020\ 0640000^2 + 1212121200000^2 = 1020304030201\ 360000^2$ (5.1599)	

$0637596^2 + 1204000^2 = 1\ 362404^2$	$0626679^2 + 1222000^2 = 1\ 373321^2$
$1020\ 0637596^2 + 121604000^2 = 10201\ 362404^2$	$1020\ 0626679^2 + 123422000^2 = 10201\ 373321^2$
$10203020\ 0637596^2 + 12161604000^2 = 102030201\ 362404^2$	$10203020\ 0626679^2 + 12343422000^2 = 102030201\ 373321^2$
$102030403020\ 0637596^2 + 1216161604000^2 = 1020304030201\ 362404^2$ (5.1601)	$102030403020\ 0626679^2 + 1234343422000^2 = 1020304030201\ 373321^2$ (5.1610)
$0636391^2 + 1206000^2 = 1\ 363609^2$	$0625456^2 + 1224000^2 = 1\ 374544^2$
$1020\ 0636391^2 + 121806000^2 = 10201\ 363609^2$	$1020\ 0625456^2 + 123624000^2 = 10201\ 374544^2$
$10203020\ 0636391^2 + 12181806000^2 = 102030201\ 363609^2$	$10203020\ 0625456^2 + 12363624000^2 = 102030201\ 374544^2$
$102030403020\ 0636391^2 + 1218181806000^2 = 1020304030201\ 363609^2$ (5.1602)	$102030403020\ 0625456^2 + 1236363624000^2 = 1020304030201\ 374544^2$ (5.1611)
$0635184^2 + 1208000^2 = 1\ 364816^2$	$0624231^2 + 1226000^2 = 1\ 375769^2$
$1020\ 0635184^2 + 122008000^2 = 10201\ 364816^2$	$1020\ 0624231^2 + 123826000^2 = 10201\ 375769^2$
$10203020\ 0635184^2 + 12202008000^2 = 102030201\ 364816^2$	$10203020\ 0624231^2 + 12383826000^2 = 102030201\ 375769^2$
$102030403020\ 0635184^2 + 1220202008000^2 = 1020304030201\ 364816^2$ (5.1603)	$102030403020\ 0624231^2 + 1238383826000^2 = 1020304030201\ 375769^2$ (5.1612)
$0633975^2 + 1210000^2 = 1\ 366025^2$	$0623004^2 + 1228000^2 = 1\ 376996^2$
$1020\ 0633975^2 + 122210000^2 = 10201\ 366025^2$	$1020\ 0623004^2 + 124028000^2 = 10201\ 376996^2$
$10203020\ 0633975^2 + 12222210000^2 = 102030201\ 366025^2$	$10203020\ 0623004^2 + 12404028000^2 = 102030201\ 376996^2$
$102030403020\ 0633975^2 + 1222222210000^2 = 1020304030201\ 366025^2$ (5.1604)	$102030403020\ 0623004^2 + 1240404028000^2 = 1020304030201\ 376996^2$ (5.1613)
$0632764^2 + 1212000^2 = 1\ 367236^2$	$0621775^2 + 1230000^2 = 1\ 378225^2$
$1020\ 0632764^2 + 122412000^2 = 10201\ 367236^2$	$1020\ 0621775^2 + 124230000^2 = 10201\ 378225^2$
$10203020\ 0632764^2 + 12242412000^2 = 102030201\ 367236^2$	$10203020\ 0621775^2 + 12424230000^2 = 102030201\ 378225^2$
$102030403020\ 0632764^2 + 1224242412000^2 = 1020304030201\ 367236^2$ (5.1605)	$102030403020\ 0621775^2 + 1242424230000^2 = 1020304030201\ 378225^2$ (5.1614)
$0631551^2 + 1214000^2 = 1\ 368449^2$	$0620544^2 + 1232000^2 = 1\ 379456^2$
$1020\ 0631551^2 + 122614000^2 = 10201\ 368449^2$	$1020\ 0620544^2 + 124432000^2 = 10201\ 379456^2$
$10203020\ 0631551^2 + 12262614000^2 = 102030201\ 368449^2$	$10203020\ 0620544^2 + 12444432000^2 = 102030201\ 379456^2$
$102030403020\ 0631551^2 + 1226262614000^2 = 1020304030201\ 368449^2$ (5.1606)	$102030403020\ 0620544^2 + 1244444432000^2 = 1020304030201\ 379456^2$ (5.1615)
$0630336^2 + 1216000^2 = 1\ 369664^2$	$0619311^2 + 1234000^2 = 1\ 380689^2$
$1020\ 0630336^2 + 122816000^2 = 10201\ 369664^2$	$1020\ 0619311^2 + 124634000^2 = 10201\ 380689^2$
$10203020\ 0630336^2 + 12282816000^2 = 102030201\ 369664^2$	$10203020\ 0619311^2 + 12464634000^2 = 102030201\ 380689^2$
$102030403020\ 0630336^2 + 1228282816000^2 = 1020304030201\ 369664^2$ (5.1607)	$102030403020\ 0619311^2 + 1246464634000^2 = 1020304030201\ 380689^2$ (5.1616)
$0629119^2 + 1218000^2 = 1\ 370881^2$	$0618076^2 + 1236000^2 = 1\ 381924^2$
$1020\ 0629119^2 + 123018000^2 = 10201\ 370881^2$	$1020\ 0618076^2 + 124836000^2 = 10201\ 381924^2$
$10203020\ 0629119^2 + 12303018000^2 = 102030201\ 370881^2$	$10203020\ 0618076^2 + 12484836000^2 = 102030201\ 381924^2$
$102030403020\ 0629119^2 + 1230303018000^2 = 1020304030201\ 370881^2$ (5.1608)	$102030403020\ 0618076^2 + 1248484836000^2 = 1020304030201\ 381924^2$ (5.1617)
$0627900^2 + 1220000^2 = 1\ 372100^2$	
$1020\ 0627900^2 + 123220000^2 = 10201\ 372100^2$	
$10203020\ 0627900^2 + 12323220000^2 = 102030201\ 372100^2$	
$102030403020\ 0627900^2 + 1232323220000^2 = 1020304030201\ 372100^2$ (5.1609)	

$0616839^2 + 1238000^2 = 1383161^2$	$0605616^2 + 1256000^2 = 1394384^2$
$10200616839^2 + 125038000^2 = 10201383161^2$	$10200605616^2 + 126856000^2 = 10201394384^2$
$102030200616839^2 + 12505038000^2 = 102030201383161^2$	$102030200605616^2 + 12686856000^2 = 102030201394384^2$
$1020304030200616839^2 + 1250505038000^2 = 1020304030201383161^2$ (5.1618)	$1020304030200605616^2 + 1268686856000^2 = 1020304030201394384^2$ (5.1627)
$0615600^2 + 1240000^2 = 1384400^2$	$0604359^2 + 1258000^2 = 1395641^2$
$10200615600^2 + 125240000^2 = 10201384400^2$	$10200604359^2 + 127058000^2 = 10201395641^2$
$102030200615600^2 + 12525240000^2 = 102030201384400^2$	$102030200604359^2 + 12707058000^2 = 102030201395641^2$
$1020304030200615600^2 + 1252525240000^2 = 1020304030201384400^2$ (5.1619)	$1020304030200604359^2 + 1270707058000^2 = 1020304030201395641^2$ (5.1628)
$0614359^2 + 1242000^2 = 1385641^2$	$0603100^2 + 1260000^2 = 1396900^2$
$10200614359^2 + 125442000^2 = 10201385641^2$	$10200603100^2 + 127260000^2 = 10201396900^2$
$102030200614359^2 + 12545442000^2 = 102030201385641^2$	$102030200603100^2 + 12727260000^2 = 102030201396900^2$
$1020304030200614359^2 + 1254545442000^2 = 1020304030201385641^2$ (5.1620)	$1020304030200603100^2 + 1272727260000^2 = 1020304030201396900^2$ (5.1629)
$0613116^2 + 1244000^2 = 1386884^2$	$0601839^2 + 1262000^2 = 1398161^2$
$10200613116^2 + 125644000^2 = 10201386884^2$	$10200601839^2 + 127462000^2 = 10201398161^2$
$102030200613116^2 + 12565644000^2 = 102030201386884^2$	$102030200601839^2 + 12747462000^2 = 102030201398161^2$
$1020304030200613116^2 + 1256565644000^2 = 1020304030201386884^2$ (5.1621)	$1020304030200601839^2 + 1274747462000^2 = 1020304030201398161^2$ (5.1630)
$0611871^2 + 1246000^2 = 1388129^2$	$0600576^2 + 1264000^2 = 1399424^2$
$10200611871^2 + 125846000^2 = 10201388129^2$	$10200600576^2 + 127664000^2 = 10201399424^2$
$102030200611871^2 + 12585846000^2 = 102030201388129^2$	$102030200600576^2 + 12767664000^2 = 102030201399424^2$
$1020304030200611871^2 + 1258585846000^2 = 1020304030201388129^2$ (5.1622)	$1020304030200600576^2 + 1276767664000^2 = 1020304030201399424^2$ (5.1631)
$0610624^2 + 1248000^2 = 1389376^2$	$0599311^2 + 1266000^2 = 1400689^2$
$10200610624^2 + 126048000^2 = 10201389376^2$	$10200599311^2 + 127866000^2 = 10201400689^2$
$102030200610624^2 + 12606048000^2 = 102030201389376^2$	$102030200599311^2 + 12787866000^2 = 102030201400689^2$
$1020304030200610624^2 + 1260606048000^2 = 1020304030201389376^2$ (5.1623)	$1020304030200599311^2 + 1278787866000^2 = 1020304030201400689^2$ (5.1632)
$0609375^2 + 1250000^2 = 1390625^2$	$0598044^2 + 1268000^2 = 1401956^2$
$10200609375^2 + 126250000^2 = 10201390625^2$	$10200598044^2 + 128068000^2 = 10201401956^2$
$102030200609375^2 + 12626250000^2 = 102030201390625^2$	$102030200598044^2 + 12808068000^2 = 102030201401956^2$
$1020304030200609375^2 + 1262626250000^2 = 1020304030201390625^2$ (5.1624)	$1020304030200598044^2 + 1280808068000^2 = 1020304030201401956^2$ (5.1633)
$0608124^2 + 1252000^2 = 1391876^2$	$0596775^2 + 1270000^2 = 1403225^2$
$10200608124^2 + 126452000^2 = 10201391876^2$	$10200596775^2 + 128270000^2 = 10201403225^2$
$102030200608124^2 + 12646452000^2 = 102030201391876^2$	$102030200596775^2 + 12828270000^2 = 102030201403225^2$
$1020304030200608124^2 + 1264646452000^2 = 1020304030201391876^2$ (5.1625)	$1020304030200596775^2 + 1282828270000^2 = 1020304030201403225^2$ (5.1634)
$0606871^2 + 1254000^2 = 1393129^2$	
$10200606871^2 + 126654000^2 = 10201393129^2$	
$102030200606871^2 + 12666654000^2 = 102030201393129^2$	
$1020304030200606871^2 + 1266666654000^2 = 1020304030201393129^2$ (5.1626)	

$0573591^2 + 1306000^2 = 1\ 426409^2$	$0561756^2 + 1324000^2 = 1\ 438244^2$
$1020\ 0573591^2 + 131906000^2 = 10201\ 426409^2$	$1020\ 0561756^2 + 133724000^2 = 10201\ 438244^2$
$10203020\ 0573591^2 + 13191906000^2 = 102030201\ 426409^2$	$10203020\ 0561756^2 + 13373724000^2 = 102030201\ 438244^2$
$102030403020\ 0573591^2 + 1319191906000^2 = 1020304030201\ 426409^2$ (5.1652)	$102030403020\ 0561756^2 + 1337373724000^2 = 1020304030201\ 438244^2$ (5.1661)
$0572284^2 + 1308000^2 = 1\ 427716^2$	$0560431^2 + 1326000^2 = 1\ 439569^2$
$1020\ 0572284^2 + 132108000^2 = 10201\ 427716^2$	$1020\ 0560431^2 + 133926000^2 = 10201\ 439569^2$
$10203020\ 0572284^2 + 13212108000^2 = 102030201\ 427716^2$	$10203020\ 0560431^2 + 13393926000^2 = 102030201\ 439569^2$
$102030403020\ 0572284^2 + 1321212108000^2 = 1020304030201\ 427716^2$ (5.1653)	$102030403020\ 0560431^2 + 1339393926000^2 = 1020304030201\ 439569^2$ (5.1662)
$0570975^2 + 1310000^2 = 1\ 429025^2$	$0559104^2 + 1328000^2 = 1\ 440896^2$
$1020\ 0570975^2 + 132310000^2 = 10201\ 429025^2$	$1020\ 0559104^2 + 134128000^2 = 10201\ 440896^2$
$10203020\ 0570975^2 + 13232310000^2 = 102030201\ 429025^2$	$10203020\ 0559104^2 + 13414128000^2 = 102030201\ 440896^2$
$102030403020\ 0570975^2 + 1323232310000^2 = 1020304030201\ 429025^2$ (5.1654)	$102030403020\ 0559104^2 + 1341414128000^2 = 1020304030201\ 440896^2$ (5.1663)
$0569664^2 + 1312000^2 = 1\ 430336^2$	$0557775^2 + 1330000^2 = 1\ 442225^2$
$1020\ 0569664^2 + 132512000^2 = 10201\ 430336^2$	$1020\ 0557775^2 + 134330000^2 = 10201\ 442225^2$
$10203020\ 0569664^2 + 13252512000^2 = 102030201\ 430336^2$	$10203020\ 0557775^2 + 13434330000^2 = 102030201\ 442225^2$
$102030403020\ 0569664^2 + 1325252512000^2 = 1020304030201\ 430336^2$ (5.1655)	$102030403020\ 0557775^2 + 1343434330000^2 = 1020304030201\ 442225^2$ (5.1664)
$0568351^2 + 1314000^2 = 1\ 431649^2$	$0556444^2 + 1332000^2 = 1\ 443556^2$
$1020\ 0568351^2 + 132714000^2 = 10201\ 431649^2$	$1020\ 0556444^2 + 134532000^2 = 10201\ 443556^2$
$10203020\ 0568351^2 + 13272714000^2 = 102030201\ 431649^2$	$10203020\ 0556444^2 + 13454532000^2 = 102030201\ 443556^2$
$102030403020\ 0568351^2 + 1327272714000^2 = 1020304030201\ 431649^2$ (5.1656)	$102030403020\ 0556444^2 + 1345454532000^2 = 1020304030201\ 443556^2$ (5.1665)
$0567036^2 + 1316000^2 = 1\ 432964^2$	$0555111^2 + 1334000^2 = 1\ 444889^2$
$1020\ 0567036^2 + 132916000^2 = 10201\ 432964^2$	$1020\ 0555111^2 + 134734000^2 = 10201\ 444889^2$
$10203020\ 0567036^2 + 13292916000^2 = 102030201\ 432964^2$	$10203020\ 0555111^2 + 13474734000^2 = 102030201\ 444889^2$
$102030403020\ 0567036^2 + 1329292916000^2 = 1020304030201\ 432964^2$ (5.1657)	$102030403020\ 0555111^2 + 1347474734000^2 = 1020304030201\ 444889^2$ (5.1666)
$0565719^2 + 1318000^2 = 1\ 434281^2$	$0553776^2 + 1336000^2 = 1\ 446224^2$
$1020\ 0565719^2 + 133118000^2 = 10201\ 434281^2$	$1020\ 0553776^2 + 134936000^2 = 10201\ 446224^2$
$10203020\ 0565719^2 + 13313118000^2 = 102030201\ 434281^2$	$10203020\ 0553776^2 + 13494936000^2 = 102030201\ 446224^2$
$102030403020\ 0565719^2 + 1331313118000^2 = 1020304030201\ 434281^2$ (5.1658)	$102030403020\ 0553776^2 + 1349494936000^2 = 1020304030201\ 446224^2$ (5.1667)
$0564400^2 + 1320000^2 = 1\ 435600^2$	$0552439^2 + 1338000^2 = 1\ 447561^2$
$1020\ 0564400^2 + 133320000^2 = 10201\ 435600^2$	$1020\ 0552439^2 + 135138000^2 = 10201\ 447561^2$
$10203020\ 0564400^2 + 13333320000^2 = 102030201\ 435600^2$	$10203020\ 0552439^2 + 13515138000^2 = 102030201\ 447561^2$
$102030403020\ 0564400^2 + 1333333320000^2 = 1020304030201\ 435600^2$ (5.1659)	$102030403020\ 0552439^2 + 1351515138000^2 = 1020304030201\ 447561^2$ (5.1668)
$0563079^2 + 1322000^2 = 1\ 436921^2$	
$1020\ 0563079^2 + 133522000^2 = 10201\ 436921^2$	
$10203020\ 0563079^2 + 13353522000^2 = 102030201\ 436921^2$	
$102030403020\ 0563079^2 + 1335353522000^2 = 1020304030201\ 436921^2$ (5.1660)	

$0551100^2 + 1340000^2 = 1\ 448900^2$	$0538959^2 + 1358000^2 = 1\ 461041^2$
$1020\ 0551100^2 + 135340000^2 = 10201\ 448900^2$	$1020\ 0538959^2 + 137158000^2 = 10201\ 461041^2$
$10203020\ 0551100^2 + 13535340000^2 = 102030201\ 448900^2$	$10203020\ 0538959^2 + 13717158000^2 = 102030201\ 461041^2$
$102030403020\ 0551100^2 + 1353535340000^2 = 1020304030201\ 448900^2$ (5.1669)	$102030403020\ 0538959^2 + 1371717158000^2 = 1020304030201\ 461041^2$ (5.1678)
$0549759^2 + 1342000^2 = 1\ 450241^2$	$0537600^2 + 1360000^2 = 1\ 462400^2$
$1020\ 0549759^2 + 135542000^2 = 10201\ 450241^2$	$1020\ 0537600^2 + 137360000^2 = 10201\ 462400^2$
$10203020\ 0549759^2 + 13555542000^2 = 102030201\ 450241^2$	$10203020\ 0537600^2 + 13737360000^2 = 102030201\ 462400^2$
$102030403020\ 0549759^2 + 1355555542000^2 = 1020304030201\ 450241^2$ (5.1670)	$102030403020\ 0537600^2 + 1373737360000^2 = 1020304030201\ 462400^2$ (5.1679)
$0548416^2 + 1344000^2 = 1\ 451584^2$	$0536239^2 + 1362000^2 = 1\ 463761^2$
$1020\ 0548416^2 + 135744000^2 = 10201\ 451584^2$	$1020\ 0536239^2 + 137562000^2 = 10201\ 463761^2$
$10203020\ 0548416^2 + 13575744000^2 = 102030201\ 451584^2$	$10203020\ 0536239^2 + 13757562000^2 = 102030201\ 463761^2$
$102030403020\ 0548416^2 + 1357575744000^2 = 1020304030201\ 451584^2$ (5.1671)	$102030403020\ 0536239^2 + 1375757562000^2 = 1020304030201\ 463761^2$ (5.1680)
$0547071^2 + 1346000^2 = 1\ 452929^2$	$0534876^2 + 1364000^2 = 1\ 465124^2$
$1020\ 0547071^2 + 135946000^2 = 10201\ 452929^2$	$1020\ 0534876^2 + 137764000^2 = 10201\ 465124^2$
$10203020\ 0547071^2 + 13595946000^2 = 102030201\ 452929^2$	$10203020\ 0534876^2 + 13777764000^2 = 102030201\ 465124^2$
$102030403020\ 0547071^2 + 1359595946000^2 = 1020304030201\ 452929^2$ (5.1672)	$102030403020\ 0534876^2 + 1377777764000^2 = 1020304030201\ 465124^2$ (5.1681)
$0545724^2 + 1348000^2 = 1\ 454276^2$	$0533511^2 + 1366000^2 = 1\ 466489^2$
$1020\ 0545724^2 + 136148000^2 = 10201\ 454276^2$	$1020\ 0533511^2 + 137966000^2 = 10201\ 466489^2$
$10203020\ 0545724^2 + 13616148000^2 = 102030201\ 454276^2$	$10203020\ 0533511^2 + 13797966000^2 = 102030201\ 466489^2$
$102030403020\ 0545724^2 + 1361616148000^2 = 1020304030201\ 454276^2$ (5.1673)	$102030403020\ 0533511^2 + 1379797966000^2 = 1020304030201\ 466489^2$ (5.1682)
$0544375^2 + 1350000^2 = 1\ 455625^2$	$0532144^2 + 1368000^2 = 1\ 467856^2$
$1020\ 0544375^2 + 136350000^2 = 10201\ 455625^2$	$1020\ 0532144^2 + 138168000^2 = 10201\ 467856^2$
$10203020\ 0544375^2 + 13636350000^2 = 102030201\ 455625^2$	$10203020\ 0532144^2 + 13818168000^2 = 102030201\ 467856^2$
$102030403020\ 0544375^2 + 1363636350000^2 = 1020304030201\ 455625^2$ (5.1674)	$102030403020\ 0532144^2 + 1381818168000^2 = 1020304030201\ 467856^2$ (5.1683)
$0543024^2 + 1352000^2 = 1\ 456976^2$	$0530775^2 + 1370000^2 = 1\ 469225^2$
$1020\ 0543024^2 + 136552000^2 = 10201\ 456976^2$	$1020\ 0530775^2 + 138370000^2 = 10201\ 469225^2$
$10203020\ 0543024^2 + 13656552000^2 = 102030201\ 456976^2$	$10203020\ 0530775^2 + 13838370000^2 = 102030201\ 469225^2$
$102030403020\ 0543024^2 + 1365656552000^2 = 1020304030201\ 456976^2$ (5.1675)	$102030403020\ 0530775^2 + 1383838370000^2 = 1020304030201\ 469225^2$ (5.1684)
$0541671^2 + 1354000^2 = 1\ 458329^2$	$0529404^2 + 1372000^2 = 1\ 470596^2$
$1020\ 0541671^2 + 136754000^2 = 10201\ 458329^2$	$1020\ 0529404^2 + 138572000^2 = 10201\ 470596^2$
$10203020\ 0541671^2 + 13676754000^2 = 102030201\ 458329^2$	$10203020\ 0529404^2 + 13858572000^2 = 102030201\ 470596^2$
$102030403020\ 0541671^2 + 1367676754000^2 = 1020304030201\ 458329^2$ (5.1676)	$102030403020\ 0529404^2 + 1385858572000^2 = 1020304030201\ 470596^2$ (5.1685)
$0540316^2 + 1356000^2 = 1\ 459684^2$	
$1020\ 0540316^2 + 136956000^2 = 10201\ 459684^2$	
$10203020\ 0540316^2 + 13696956000^2 = 102030201\ 459684^2$	
$102030403020\ 0540316^2 + 1369696956000^2 = 1020304030201\ 459684^2$ (5.1677)	

$0483039^2 + 1438000^2 = 1\ 516961^2$	$0470016^2 + 1456000^2 = 1\ 529984^2$
$1020\ 0483039^2 + 145238000^2 = 10201\ 516961^2$	$1020\ 0470016^2 + 147056000^2 = 10201\ 529984^2$
$10203020\ 0483039^2 + 14525238000^2 = 102030201\ 516961^2$	$10203020\ 0470016^2 + 14707056000^2 = 102030201\ 529984^2$
$102030403020\ 0483039^2 + 1452525238000^2 = 1020304030201\ 516961^2$ (5.1718)	$102030403020\ 0470016^2 + 1470707056000^2 = 1020304030201\ 529984^2$ (5.1727)
$0481600^2 + 1440000^2 = 1\ 518400^2$	$0468559^2 + 1458000^2 = 1\ 531441^2$
$1020\ 0481600^2 + 145440000^2 = 10201\ 518400^2$	$1020\ 0468559^2 + 147258000^2 = 10201\ 531441^2$
$10203020\ 0481600^2 + 14545440000^2 = 102030201\ 518400^2$	$10203020\ 0468559^2 + 14727258000^2 = 102030201\ 531441^2$
$102030403020\ 0481600^2 + 1454545440000^2 = 1020304030201\ 518400^2$ (5.1719)	$102030403020\ 0468559^2 + 1472727258000^2 = 1020304030201\ 531441^2$ (5.1728)
$0480159^2 + 1442000^2 = 1\ 519841^2$	$0467100^2 + 1460000^2 = 1\ 532900^2$
$1020\ 0480159^2 + 145642000^2 = 10201\ 519841^2$	$1020\ 0467100^2 + 147460000^2 = 10201\ 532900^2$
$10203020\ 0480159^2 + 14565642000^2 = 102030201\ 519841^2$	$10203020\ 0467100^2 + 14747460000^2 = 102030201\ 532900^2$
$102030403020\ 0480159^2 + 1456565642000^2 = 1020304030201\ 519841^2$ (5.1720)	$102030403020\ 0467100^2 + 1474747460000^2 = 1020304030201\ 532900^2$ (5.1729)
$0478716^2 + 1444000^2 = 1\ 521284^2$	$0465639^2 + 1462000^2 = 1\ 534361^2$
$1020\ 0478716^2 + 145844000^2 = 10201\ 521284^2$	$1020\ 0465639^2 + 147662000^2 = 10201\ 534361^2$
$10203020\ 0478716^2 + 14585844000^2 = 102030201\ 521284^2$	$10203020\ 0465639^2 + 14767662000^2 = 102030201\ 534361^2$
$102030403020\ 0478716^2 + 1458585844000^2 = 1020304030201\ 521284^2$ (5.1721)	$102030403020\ 0465639^2 + 1476767662000^2 = 1020304030201\ 534361^2$ (5.1730)
$0477271^2 + 1446000^2 = 1\ 522729^2$	$0464176^2 + 1464000^2 = 1\ 535824^2$
$1020\ 0477271^2 + 146046000^2 = 10201\ 522729^2$	$1020\ 0464176^2 + 147864000^2 = 10201\ 535824^2$
$10203020\ 0477271^2 + 14606046000^2 = 102030201\ 522729^2$	$10203020\ 0464176^2 + 14787864000^2 = 102030201\ 535824^2$
$102030403020\ 0477271^2 + 1460606046000^2 = 1020304030201\ 522729^2$ (5.1722)	$102030403020\ 0464176^2 + 1478787864000^2 = 1020304030201\ 535824^2$ (5.1731)
$0475824^2 + 1448000^2 = 1\ 524176^2$	$0462711^2 + 1466000^2 = 1\ 537289^2$
$1020\ 0475824^2 + 146248000^2 = 10201\ 524176^2$	$1020\ 0462711^2 + 148066000^2 = 10201\ 537289^2$
$10203020\ 0475824^2 + 14626248000^2 = 102030201\ 524176^2$	$10203020\ 0462711^2 + 14808066000^2 = 102030201\ 537289^2$
$102030403020\ 0475824^2 + 1462626248000^2 = 1020304030201\ 524176^2$ (5.1723)	$102030403020\ 0462711^2 + 1480808066000^2 = 1020304030201\ 537289^2$ (5.1732)
$0474375^2 + 1450000^2 = 1\ 525625^2$	$0461244^2 + 1468000^2 = 1\ 538756^2$
$1020\ 0474375^2 + 146450000^2 = 10201\ 525625^2$	$1020\ 0461244^2 + 148268000^2 = 10201\ 538756^2$
$10203020\ 0474375^2 + 14646450000^2 = 102030201\ 525625^2$	$10203020\ 0461244^2 + 14828268000^2 = 102030201\ 538756^2$
$102030403020\ 0474375^2 + 1464646450000^2 = 1020304030201\ 525625^2$ (5.1724)	$102030403020\ 0461244^2 + 1482828268000^2 = 1020304030201\ 538756^2$ (5.1733)
$0472924^2 + 1452000^2 = 1\ 527076^2$	$0459775^2 + 1470000^2 = 1\ 540225^2$
$1020\ 0472924^2 + 146652000^2 = 10201\ 527076^2$	$1020\ 0459775^2 + 148470000^2 = 10201\ 540225^2$
$10203020\ 0472924^2 + 14666652000^2 = 102030201\ 527076^2$	$10203020\ 0459775^2 + 14848470000^2 = 102030201\ 540225^2$
$102030403020\ 0472924^2 + 1466666652000^2 = 1020304030201\ 527076^2$ (5.1725)	$102030403020\ 0459775^2 + 1484848470000^2 = 1020304030201\ 540225^2$ (5.1734)
$0471471^2 + 1454000^2 = 1\ 528529^2$	
$1020\ 0471471^2 + 146854000^2 = 10201\ 528529^2$	
$10203020\ 0471471^2 + 14686854000^2 = 102030201\ 528529^2$	
$102030403020\ 0471471^2 + 1468686854000^2 = 1020304030201\ 528529^2$ (5.1726)	

$0458304^2 + 1472000^2 = 1\ 541696^2$	$0444975^2 + 1490000^2 = 1\ 555025^2$
$1020\ 0458304^2 + 148672000^2 = 10201\ 541696^2$	$1020\ 0444975^2 + 150490000^2 = 10201\ 555025^2$
$10203020\ 0458304^2 + 14868672000^2 = 102030201\ 541696^2$	$10203020\ 0444975^2 + 15050490000^2 = 102030201\ 555025^2$
$102030403020\ 0458304^2 + 1486868672000^2 = 1020304030201\ 541696^2$ (5.1735)	$102030403020\ 0444975^2 + 1505050490000^2 = 1020304030201\ 555025^2$ (5.1744)
$0456831^2 + 1474000^2 = 1\ 543169^2$	$0443484^2 + 1492000^2 = 1\ 556516^2$
$1020\ 0456831^2 + 148874000^2 = 10201\ 543169^2$	$1020\ 0443484^2 + 150692000^2 = 10201\ 556516^2$
$10203020\ 0456831^2 + 14888874000^2 = 102030201\ 543169^2$	$10203020\ 0443484^2 + 15070692000^2 = 102030201\ 556516^2$
$102030403020\ 0456831^2 + 1488888874000^2 = 1020304030201\ 543169^2$ (5.1736)	$102030403020\ 0443484^2 + 1507070692000^2 = 1020304030201\ 556516^2$ (5.1745)
$0455356^2 + 1476000^2 = 1\ 544644^2$	$0441991^2 + 1494000^2 = 1\ 558009^2$
$1020\ 0455356^2 + 149076000^2 = 10201\ 544644^2$	$1020\ 0441991^2 + 150894000^2 = 10201\ 558009^2$
$10203020\ 0455356^2 + 14909076000^2 = 102030201\ 544644^2$	$10203020\ 0441991^2 + 15090894000^2 = 102030201\ 558009^2$
$102030403020\ 0455356^2 + 1490909076000^2 = 1020304030201\ 544644^2$ (5.1737)	$102030403020\ 0441991^2 + 1509090894000^2 = 1020304030201\ 558009^2$ (5.1746)
$0453879^2 + 1478000^2 = 1\ 546121^2$	$0440496^2 + 1496000^2 = 1\ 559504^2$
$1020\ 0453879^2 + 149278000^2 = 10201\ 546121^2$	$1020\ 0440496^2 + 151096000^2 = 10201\ 559504^2$
$10203020\ 0453879^2 + 14929278000^2 = 102030201\ 546121^2$	$10203020\ 0440496^2 + 15111096000^2 = 102030201\ 559504^2$
$102030403020\ 0453879^2 + 1492929278000^2 = 1020304030201\ 546121^2$ (5.1738)	$102030403020\ 0440496^2 + 1511111096000^2 = 1020304030201\ 559504^2$ (5.1747)
$0452400^2 + 1480000^2 = 1\ 547600^2$	$0438999^2 + 1498000^2 = 1\ 561001^2$
$1020\ 0452400^2 + 149480000^2 = 10201\ 547600^2$	$1020\ 0438999^2 + 151298000^2 = 10201\ 561001^2$
$10203020\ 0452400^2 + 14949480000^2 = 102030201\ 547600^2$	$10203020\ 0438999^2 + 15131298000^2 = 102030201\ 561001^2$
$102030403020\ 0452400^2 + 1494949480000^2 = 1020304030201\ 547600^2$ (5.1739)	$102030403020\ 0438999^2 + 1513131298000^2 = 1020304030201\ 561001^2$ (5.1748)
$0450919^2 + 1482000^2 = 1\ 549081^2$	$0437500^2 + 1500000^2 = 1\ 562500^2$
$1020\ 0450919^2 + 149682000^2 = 10201\ 549081^2$	$1020\ 0437500^2 + 151500000^2 = 10201\ 562500^2$
$10203020\ 0450919^2 + 14969682000^2 = 102030201\ 549081^2$	$10203020\ 0437500^2 + 15151500000^2 = 102030201\ 562500^2$
$102030403020\ 0450919^2 + 1496969682000^2 = 1020304030201\ 549081^2$ (5.1740)	$102030403020\ 0437500^2 + 1515151500000^2 = 1020304030201\ 562500^2$ (5.1749)
$0449436^2 + 1484000^2 = 1\ 550564^2$	$0435999^2 + 1502000^2 = 1\ 564001^2$
$1020\ 0449436^2 + 149884000^2 = 10201\ 550564^2$	$1020\ 0435999^2 + 151702000^2 = 10201\ 564001^2$
$10203020\ 0449436^2 + 14989884000^2 = 102030201\ 550564^2$	$10203020\ 0435999^2 + 15171702000^2 = 102030201\ 564001^2$
$102030403020\ 0449436^2 + 1498989884000^2 = 1020304030201\ 550564^2$ (5.1741)	$102030403020\ 0435999^2 + 1517171702000^2 = 1020304030201\ 564001^2$ (5.1750)
$0447951^2 + 1486000^2 = 1\ 552049^2$	$0434496^2 + 1504000^2 = 1\ 565504^2$
$1020\ 0447951^2 + 150086000^2 = 10201\ 552049^2$	$1020\ 0434496^2 + 151904000^2 = 10201\ 565504^2$
$10203020\ 0447951^2 + 15010086000^2 = 102030201\ 552049^2$	$10203020\ 0434496^2 + 15191904000^2 = 102030201\ 565504^2$
$102030403020\ 0447951^2 + 1501010086000^2 = 1020304030201\ 552049^2$ (5.1742)	$102030403020\ 0434496^2 + 1519191904000^2 = 1020304030201\ 565504^2$ (5.1751)
$0446464^2 + 1488000^2 = 1\ 553536^2$	
$1020\ 0446464^2 + 150288000^2 = 10201\ 553536^2$	
$10203020\ 0446464^2 + 15030288000^2 = 102030201\ 553536^2$	
$102030403020\ 0446464^2 + 1503030288000^2 = 1020304030201\ 553536^2$ (5.1743)	

$0432991^2 + 1506000^2 = 1\ 567009^2$	$0419356^2 + 1524000^2 = 1\ 580644^2$
$1020\ 0432991^2 + 152106000^2 = 10201\ 567009^2$	$1020\ 0419356^2 + 153924000^2 = 10201\ 580644^2$
$10203020\ 0432991^2 + 15212106000^2 = 102030201\ 567009^2$	$10203020\ 0419356^2 + 15393924000^2 = 102030201\ 580644^2$
$102030403020\ 0432991^2 + 1521212106000^2 = 1020304030201\ 567009^2$ (5.1752)	$102030403020\ 0419356^2 + 1539393924000^2 = 1020304030201\ 580644^2$ (5.1761)
$0431484^2 + 1508000^2 = 1\ 568516^2$	$0417831^2 + 1526000^2 = 1\ 582169^2$
$1020\ 0431484^2 + 152308000^2 = 10201\ 568516^2$	$1020\ 0417831^2 + 154126000^2 = 10201\ 582169^2$
$10203020\ 0431484^2 + 15232308000^2 = 102030201\ 568516^2$	$10203020\ 0417831^2 + 15414126000^2 = 102030201\ 582169^2$
$102030403020\ 0431484^2 + 1523232308000^2 = 1020304030201\ 568516^2$ (5.1753)	$102030403020\ 0417831^2 + 1541414126000^2 = 1020304030201\ 582169^2$ (5.1762)
$0429975^2 + 1510000^2 = 1\ 570025^2$	$0416304^2 + 1528000^2 = 1\ 583696^2$
$1020\ 0429975^2 + 152510000^2 = 10201\ 570025^2$	$1020\ 0416304^2 + 154328000^2 = 10201\ 583696^2$
$10203020\ 0429975^2 + 15252510000^2 = 102030201\ 570025^2$	$10203020\ 0416304^2 + 15434328000^2 = 102030201\ 583696^2$
$102030403020\ 0429975^2 + 1525252510000^2 = 1020304030201\ 570025^2$ (5.1754)	$102030403020\ 0416304^2 + 1543434328000^2 = 1020304030201\ 583696^2$ (5.1763)
$0428464^2 + 1512000^2 = 1\ 571536^2$	$0414775^2 + 1530000^2 = 1\ 585225^2$
$1020\ 0428464^2 + 152712000^2 = 10201\ 571536^2$	$1020\ 0414775^2 + 154530000^2 = 10201\ 585225^2$
$10203020\ 0428464^2 + 15272712000^2 = 102030201\ 571536^2$	$10203020\ 0414775^2 + 15454530000^2 = 102030201\ 585225^2$
$102030403020\ 0428464^2 + 1527272712000^2 = 1020304030201\ 571536^2$ (5.1755)	$102030403020\ 0414775^2 + 1545454530000^2 = 1020304030201\ 585225^2$ (5.1764)
$0426951^2 + 1514000^2 = 1\ 573049^2$	$0413244^2 + 1532000^2 = 1\ 586756^2$
$1020\ 0426951^2 + 152914000^2 = 10201\ 573049^2$	$1020\ 0413244^2 + 154732000^2 = 10201\ 586756^2$
$10203020\ 0426951^2 + 15292914000^2 = 102030201\ 573049^2$	$10203020\ 0413244^2 + 15474732000^2 = 102030201\ 586756^2$
$102030403020\ 0426951^2 + 1529292914000^2 = 1020304030201\ 573049^2$ (5.1756)	$102030403020\ 0413244^2 + 1547474732000^2 = 1020304030201\ 586756^2$ (5.1765)
$0425436^2 + 1516000^2 = 1\ 574564^2$	$0411711^2 + 1534000^2 = 1\ 588289^2$
$1020\ 0425436^2 + 153116000^2 = 10201\ 574564^2$	$1020\ 0411711^2 + 154934000^2 = 10201\ 588289^2$
$10203020\ 0425436^2 + 15313116000^2 = 102030201\ 574564^2$	$10203020\ 0411711^2 + 15494934000^2 = 102030201\ 588289^2$
$102030403020\ 0425436^2 + 1531313116000^2 = 1020304030201\ 574564^2$ (5.1757)	$102030403020\ 0411711^2 + 1549494934000^2 = 1020304030201\ 588289^2$ (5.1766)
$0423919^2 + 1518000^2 = 1\ 576081^2$	$0410176^2 + 1536000^2 = 1\ 589824^2$
$1020\ 0423919^2 + 153318000^2 = 10201\ 576081^2$	$1020\ 0410176^2 + 155136000^2 = 10201\ 589824^2$
$10203020\ 0423919^2 + 15333318000^2 = 102030201\ 576081^2$	$10203020\ 0410176^2 + 15515136000^2 = 102030201\ 589824^2$
$102030403020\ 0423919^2 + 1533333318000^2 = 1020304030201\ 576081^2$ (5.1758)	$102030403020\ 0410176^2 + 1551515136000^2 = 1020304030201\ 589824^2$ (5.1767)
$0422400^2 + 1520000^2 = 1\ 577600^2$	$0408639^2 + 1538000^2 = 1\ 591361^2$
$1020\ 0422400^2 + 153520000^2 = 10201\ 577600^2$	$1020\ 0408639^2 + 155338000^2 = 10201\ 591361^2$
$10203020\ 0422400^2 + 15353520000^2 = 102030201\ 577600^2$	$10203020\ 0408639^2 + 15535338000^2 = 102030201\ 591361^2$
$102030403020\ 0422400^2 + 1535353520000^2 = 1020304030201\ 577600^2$ (5.1759)	$102030403020\ 0408639^2 + 1553535338000^2 = 1020304030201\ 591361^2$ (5.1768)
$0420879^2 + 1522000^2 = 1\ 579121^2$	
$1020\ 0420879^2 + 153722000^2 = 10201\ 579121^2$	
$10203020\ 0420879^2 + 15373722000^2 = 102030201\ 579121^2$	
$102030403020\ 0420879^2 + 1537373722000^2 = 1020304030201\ 579121^2$ (5.1760)	

$0407100^2 + 1540000^2 = 1\ 592900^2$	$0393159^2 + 1558000^2 = 1\ 606841^2$
$1020\ 0407100^2 + 155540000^2 = 10201\ 592900^2$	$1020\ 0393159^2 + 157358000^2 = 10201\ 606841^2$
$10203020\ 0407100^2 + 15555540000^2 = 102030201\ 592900^2$	$10203020\ 0393159^2 + 15737358000^2 = 102030201\ 606841^2$
$102030403020\ 0407100^2 + 155555540000^2 = 1020304030201\ 592900^2$ (5.1769)	$102030403020\ 0393159^2 + 1573737358000^2 = 1020304030201\ 606841^2$ (5.1778)
$0405559^2 + 1542000^2 = 1\ 594441^2$	$0391600^2 + 1560000^2 = 1\ 608400^2$
$1020\ 0405559^2 + 155742000^2 = 10201\ 594441^2$	$1020\ 0391600^2 + 157560000^2 = 10201\ 608400^2$
$10203020\ 0405559^2 + 15575742000^2 = 102030201\ 594441^2$	$10203020\ 0391600^2 + 15757560000^2 = 102030201\ 608400^2$
$102030403020\ 0405559^2 + 1557575742000^2 = 1020304030201\ 594441^2$ (5.1770)	$102030403020\ 0391600^2 + 1575757560000^2 = 1020304030201\ 608400^2$ (5.1779)
$0404016^2 + 1544000^2 = 1\ 595984^2$	$0390039^2 + 1562000^2 = 1\ 609961^2$
$1020\ 0404016^2 + 155944000^2 = 10201\ 595984^2$	$1020\ 0390039^2 + 157762000^2 = 10201\ 609961^2$
$10203020\ 0404016^2 + 15595944000^2 = 102030201\ 595984^2$	$10203020\ 0390039^2 + 15777762000^2 = 102030201\ 609961^2$
$102030403020\ 0404016^2 + 1559595944000^2 = 1020304030201\ 595984^2$ (5.1771)	$102030403020\ 0390039^2 + 1577777762000^2 = 1020304030201\ 609961^2$ (5.1780)
$0402471^2 + 1546000^2 = 1\ 597529^2$	$0388476^2 + 1564000^2 = 1\ 611524^2$
$1020\ 0402471^2 + 156146000^2 = 10201\ 597529^2$	$1020\ 0388476^2 + 157964000^2 = 10201\ 611524^2$
$10203020\ 0402471^2 + 15616146000^2 = 102030201\ 597529^2$	$10203020\ 0388476^2 + 15797964000^2 = 102030201\ 611524^2$
$102030403020\ 0402471^2 + 1561616146000^2 = 1020304030201\ 597529^2$ (5.1772)	$102030403020\ 0388476^2 + 1579797964000^2 = 1020304030201\ 611524^2$ (5.1781)
$0400924^2 + 1548000^2 = 1\ 599076^2$	$0386911^2 + 1566000^2 = 1\ 613089^2$
$1020\ 0400924^2 + 156348000^2 = 10201\ 599076^2$	$1020\ 0386911^2 + 158166000^2 = 10201\ 613089^2$
$10203020\ 0400924^2 + 15636348000^2 = 102030201\ 599076^2$	$10203020\ 0386911^2 + 15818166000^2 = 102030201\ 613089^2$
$102030403020\ 0400924^2 + 1563636348000^2 = 1020304030201\ 599076^2$ (5.1773)	$102030403020\ 0386911^2 + 1581818166000^2 = 1020304030201\ 613089^2$ (5.1782)
$0399375^2 + 1550000^2 = 1\ 600625^2$	$0385344^2 + 1568000^2 = 1\ 614656^2$
$1020\ 0399375^2 + 156550000^2 = 10201\ 600625^2$	$1020\ 0385344^2 + 158368000^2 = 10201\ 614656^2$
$10203020\ 0399375^2 + 15656550000^2 = 102030201\ 600625^2$	$10203020\ 0385344^2 + 15838368000^2 = 102030201\ 614656^2$
$102030403020\ 0399375^2 + 1565656550000^2 = 1020304030201\ 600625^2$ (5.1774)	$102030403020\ 0385344^2 + 1583838368000^2 = 1020304030201\ 614656^2$ (5.1783)
$0397824^2 + 1552000^2 = 1\ 602176^2$	$0383775^2 + 1570000^2 = 1\ 616225^2$
$1020\ 0397824^2 + 156752000^2 = 10201\ 602176^2$	$1020\ 0383775^2 + 158570000^2 = 10201\ 616225^2$
$10203020\ 0397824^2 + 15676752000^2 = 102030201\ 602176^2$	$10203020\ 0383775^2 + 15858570000^2 = 102030201\ 616225^2$
$102030403020\ 0397824^2 + 1567676752000^2 = 1020304030201\ 602176^2$ (5.1775)	$102030403020\ 0383775^2 + 1585858570000^2 = 1020304030201\ 616225^2$ (5.1784)
$0396271^2 + 1554000^2 = 1\ 603729^2$	$0382204^2 + 1572000^2 = 1\ 617796^2$
$1020\ 0396271^2 + 156954000^2 = 10201\ 603729^2$	$1020\ 0382204^2 + 158772000^2 = 10201\ 617796^2$
$10203020\ 0396271^2 + 15696954000^2 = 102030201\ 603729^2$	$10203020\ 0382204^2 + 15878772000^2 = 102030201\ 617796^2$
$102030403020\ 0396271^2 + 1569696954000^2 = 1020304030201\ 603729^2$ (5.1776)	$102030403020\ 0382204^2 + 1587878772000^2 = 1020304030201\ 617796^2$ (5.1785)
$0394716^2 + 1556000^2 = 1\ 605284^2$	
$1020\ 0394716^2 + 157156000^2 = 10201\ 605284^2$	
$10203020\ 0394716^2 + 15717156000^2 = 102030201\ 605284^2$	
$102030403020\ 0394716^2 + 1571717156000^2 = 1020304030201\ 605284^2$ (5.1777)	

$$\begin{array}{l}
0380631^2 + 1574000^2 = 1\ 619369^2 \\
1020\ 0380631^2 + 158974000^2 = 10201\ 619369^2 \\
10203020\ 0380631^2 + 15898974000^2 = 102030201\ 619369^2 \\
102030403020\ 0380631^2 + 1589898974000^2 = 1020304030201\ 619369^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1786)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0369564^2 + 1588000^2 = 1\ 630436^2 \\
1020\ 0369564^2 + 160388000^2 = 10201\ 630436^2 \\
10203020\ 0369564^2 + 16040388000^2 = 102030201\ 630436^2 \\
102030403020\ 0369564^2 + 1604040388000^2 = 1020304030201\ 630436^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1793)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0379056^2 + 1576000^2 = 1\ 620944^2 \\
1020\ 0379056^2 + 159176000^2 = 10201\ 620944^2 \\
10203020\ 0379056^2 + 15919176000^2 = 102030201\ 620944^2 \\
102030403020\ 0379056^2 + 1591919176000^2 = 1020304030201\ 620944^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1787)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0367975^2 + 1590000^2 = 1\ 632025^2 \\
1020\ 0367975^2 + 160590000^2 = 10201\ 632025^2 \\
10203020\ 0367975^2 + 16060590000^2 = 102030201\ 632025^2 \\
102030403020\ 0367975^2 + 1606060590000^2 = 1020304030201\ 632025^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1794)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0377479^2 + 1578000^2 = 1\ 622521^2 \\
1020\ 0377479^2 + 159378000^2 = 10201\ 622521^2 \\
10203020\ 0377479^2 + 15939378000^2 = 102030201\ 622521^2 \\
102030403020\ 0377479^2 + 1593939378000^2 = 1020304030201\ 622521^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1788)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0366384^2 + 1592000^2 = 1\ 633616^2 \\
1020\ 0366384^2 + 160792000^2 = 10201\ 633616^2 \\
10203020\ 0366384^2 + 16080792000^2 = 102030201\ 633616^2 \\
102030403020\ 0366384^2 + 1608080792000^2 = 1020304030201\ 633616^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1795)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0375900^2 + 1580000^2 = 1\ 624100^2 \\
1020\ 0375900^2 + 159580000^2 = 10201\ 624100^2 \\
10203020\ 0375900^2 + 15959580000^2 = 102030201\ 624100^2 \\
102030403020\ 0375900^2 + 1595959580000^2 = 1020304030201\ 624100^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1789)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0364791^2 + 1594000^2 = 1\ 635209^2 \\
1020\ 0364791^2 + 160994000^2 = 10201\ 635209^2 \\
10203020\ 0364791^2 + 16100994000^2 = 102030201\ 635209^2 \\
102030403020\ 0364791^2 + 1610100994000^2 = 1020304030201\ 635209^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1796)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0374319^2 + 1582000^2 = 1\ 625681^2 \\
1020\ 0374319^2 + 159782000^2 = 10201\ 625681^2 \\
10203020\ 0374319^2 + 15979782000^2 = 102030201\ 625681^2 \\
102030403020\ 0374319^2 + 1597979782000^2 = 1020304030201\ 625681^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1790)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0363196^2 + 1596000^2 = 1\ 636804^2 \\
1020\ 0363196^2 + 161196000^2 = 10201\ 636804^2 \\
10203020\ 0363196^2 + 16121196000^2 = 102030201\ 636804^2 \\
102030403020\ 0363196^2 + 1612121196000^2 = 1020304030201\ 636804^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1797)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0372736^2 + 1584000^2 = 1\ 627264^2 \\
1020\ 0372736^2 + 159984000^2 = 10201\ 627264^2 \\
10203020\ 0372736^2 + 1599984000^2 = 102030201\ 627264^2 \\
102030403020\ 0372736^2 + 159999984000^2 = 1020304030201\ 627264^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1791)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0361599^2 + 1598000^2 = 1\ 638401^2 \\
1020\ 0361599^2 + 161398000^2 = 10201\ 638401^2 \\
10203020\ 0361599^2 + 16141398000^2 = 102030201\ 638401^2 \\
102030403020\ 0361599^2 + 1614141398000^2 = 1020304030201\ 638401^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1798)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0371151^2 + 1586000^2 = 1\ 628849^2 \\
1020\ 0371151^2 + 160186000^2 = 10201\ 628849^2 \\
10203020\ 0371151^2 + 16020186000^2 = 102030201\ 628849^2 \\
102030403020\ 0371151^2 + 1602020186000^2 = 1020304030201\ 628849^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1792)
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
0360000^2 + 1600000^2 = 1\ 640000^2 \\
1020\ 0360000^2 + 161600000^2 = 10201\ 640000^2 \\
10203020\ 0360000^2 + 16161600000^2 = 102030201\ 640000^2 \\
102030403020\ 0360000^2 + 1616161600000^2 = 1020304030201\ 640000^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1799)
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
0358399^2 + 1602000^2 = 1\ 641601^2 \\
1020\ 0358399^2 + 161802000^2 = 10201\ 641601^2 \\
10203020\ 0358399^2 + 16181802000^2 = 102030201\ 641601^2 \\
102030403020\ 0358399^2 + 1618181802000^2 = 1020304030201\ 641601^2 \\
\hspace{15em} (5.1800)
\end{array}$$

$0356796^2 + 1604000^2 = 1\ 643204^2$	$0342279^2 + 1622000^2 = 1\ 657721^2$
$1020\ 0356796^2 + 162004000^2 = 10201\ 643204^2$	$1020\ 0342279^2 + 163822000^2 = 10201\ 657721^2$
$10203020\ 0356796^2 + 16202004000^2 = 102030201\ 643204^2$	$10203020\ 0342279^2 + 16383822000^2 = 102030201\ 657721^2$
$102030403020\ 0356796^2 + 1620202004000^2 = 1020304030201\ 643204^2$ (5.1801)	$102030403020\ 0342279^2 + 1638383822000^2 = 1020304030201\ 657721^2$ (5.1810)
$0355191^2 + 1606000^2 = 1\ 644809^2$	$0340656^2 + 1624000^2 = 1\ 659344^2$
$1020\ 0355191^2 + 162206000^2 = 10201\ 644809^2$	$1020\ 0340656^2 + 164024000^2 = 10201\ 659344^2$
$10203020\ 0355191^2 + 16222206000^2 = 102030201\ 644809^2$	$10203020\ 0340656^2 + 16404024000^2 = 102030201\ 659344^2$
$102030403020\ 0355191^2 + 1622222206000^2 = 1020304030201\ 644809^2$ (5.1802)	$102030403020\ 0340656^2 + 1640404024000^2 = 1020304030201\ 659344^2$ (5.1811)
$0353584^2 + 1608000^2 = 1\ 646416^2$	$0339031^2 + 1626000^2 = 1\ 660969^2$
$1020\ 0353584^2 + 162408000^2 = 10201\ 646416^2$	$1020\ 0339031^2 + 164226000^2 = 10201\ 660969^2$
$10203020\ 0353584^2 + 16242408000^2 = 102030201\ 646416^2$	$10203020\ 0339031^2 + 16424226000^2 = 102030201\ 660969^2$
$102030403020\ 0353584^2 + 1624242408000^2 = 1020304030201\ 646416^2$ (5.1803)	$102030403020\ 0339031^2 + 1642424226000^2 = 1020304030201\ 660969^2$ (5.1812)
$0351975^2 + 1610000^2 = 1\ 648025^2$	$0337404^2 + 1628000^2 = 1\ 662596^2$
$1020\ 0351975^2 + 162610000^2 = 10201\ 648025^2$	$1020\ 0337404^2 + 164428000^2 = 10201\ 662596^2$
$10203020\ 0351975^2 + 16262610000^2 = 102030201\ 648025^2$	$10203020\ 0337404^2 + 16444428000^2 = 102030201\ 662596^2$
$102030403020\ 0351975^2 + 1626262610000^2 = 1020304030201\ 648025^2$ (5.1804)	$102030403020\ 0337404^2 + 1644444428000^2 = 1020304030201\ 662596^2$ (5.1813)
$0350364^2 + 1612000^2 = 1\ 649636^2$	$0335775^2 + 1630000^2 = 1\ 664225^2$
$1020\ 0350364^2 + 162812000^2 = 10201\ 649636^2$	$1020\ 0335775^2 + 164630000^2 = 10201\ 664225^2$
$10203020\ 0350364^2 + 16282812000^2 = 102030201\ 649636^2$	$10203020\ 0335775^2 + 16464630000^2 = 102030201\ 664225^2$
$102030403020\ 0350364^2 + 1628282812000^2 = 1020304030201\ 649636^2$ (5.1805)	$102030403020\ 0335775^2 + 1646464630000^2 = 1020304030201\ 664225^2$ (5.1814)
$0348751^2 + 1614000^2 = 1\ 651249^2$	$0334144^2 + 1632000^2 = 1\ 665856^2$
$1020\ 0348751^2 + 163014000^2 = 10201\ 651249^2$	$1020\ 0334144^2 + 164832000^2 = 10201\ 665856^2$
$10203020\ 0348751^2 + 16303014000^2 = 102030201\ 651249^2$	$10203020\ 0334144^2 + 16484832000^2 = 102030201\ 665856^2$
$102030403020\ 0348751^2 + 1630303014000^2 = 1020304030201\ 651249^2$ (5.1806)	$102030403020\ 0334144^2 + 1648484832000^2 = 1020304030201\ 665856^2$ (5.1815)
$0347136^2 + 1616000^2 = 1\ 652864^2$	$0332511^2 + 1634000^2 = 1\ 667489^2$
$1020\ 0347136^2 + 163216000^2 = 10201\ 652864^2$	$1020\ 0332511^2 + 165034000^2 = 10201\ 667489^2$
$10203020\ 0347136^2 + 16323216000^2 = 102030201\ 652864^2$	$10203020\ 0332511^2 + 16505034000^2 = 102030201\ 667489^2$
$102030403020\ 0347136^2 + 1632323216000^2 = 1020304030201\ 652864^2$ (5.1807)	$102030403020\ 0332511^2 + 1650505034000^2 = 1020304030201\ 667489^2$ (5.1816)
$0345519^2 + 1618000^2 = 1\ 654481^2$	$0330876^2 + 1636000^2 = 1\ 669124^2$
$1020\ 0345519^2 + 163418000^2 = 10201\ 654481^2$	$1020\ 0330876^2 + 165236000^2 = 10201\ 669124^2$
$10203020\ 0345519^2 + 16343418000^2 = 102030201\ 654481^2$	$10203020\ 0330876^2 + 16525236000^2 = 102030201\ 669124^2$
$102030403020\ 0345519^2 + 1634343418000^2 = 1020304030201\ 654481^2$ (5.1808)	$102030403020\ 0330876^2 + 1652525236000^2 = 1020304030201\ 669124^2$ (5.1817)
$0343900^2 + 1620000^2 = 1\ 656100^2$	
$1020\ 0343900^2 + 163620000^2 = 10201\ 656100^2$	
$10203020\ 0343900^2 + 16363620000^2 = 102030201\ 656100^2$	
$102030403020\ 0343900^2 + 1636363620000^2 = 1020304030201\ 656100^2$ (5.1809)	

$0329239^2 + 1638000^2 = 1\ 670761^2$	$0314416^2 + 1656000^2 = 1\ 685584^2$
$1020\ 0329239^2 + 165438000^2 = 10201\ 670761^2$	$1020\ 0314416^2 + 167256000^2 = 10201\ 685584^2$
$10203020\ 0329239^2 + 16545438000^2 = 102030201\ 670761^2$	$10203020\ 0314416^2 + 16727256000^2 = 102030201\ 685584^2$
$102030403020\ 0329239^2 + 1654545438000^2 = 1020304030201\ 670761^2$ (5.1818)	$102030403020\ 0314416^2 + 1672727256000^2 = 1020304030201\ 685584^2$ (5.1827)
$0327600^2 + 1640000^2 = 1\ 672400^2$	$0312759^2 + 1658000^2 = 1\ 687241^2$
$1020\ 0327600^2 + 165640000^2 = 10201\ 672400^2$	$1020\ 0312759^2 + 167458000^2 = 10201\ 687241^2$
$10203020\ 0327600^2 + 16565640000^2 = 102030201\ 672400^2$	$10203020\ 0312759^2 + 16747458000^2 = 102030201\ 687241^2$
$102030403020\ 0327600^2 + 1656565640000^2 = 1020304030201\ 672400^2$ (5.1819)	$102030403020\ 0312759^2 + 1674747458000^2 = 1020304030201\ 687241^2$ (5.1828)
$0325959^2 + 1642000^2 = 1\ 674041^2$	$0311100^2 + 1660000^2 = 1\ 688900^2$
$1020\ 0325959^2 + 165842000^2 = 10201\ 674041^2$	$1020\ 0311100^2 + 167660000^2 = 10201\ 688900^2$
$10203020\ 0325959^2 + 16585842000^2 = 102030201\ 674041^2$	$10203020\ 0311100^2 + 16767660000^2 = 102030201\ 688900^2$
$102030403020\ 0325959^2 + 1658585842000^2 = 1020304030201\ 674041^2$ (5.1820)	$102030403020\ 0311100^2 + 1676767660000^2 = 1020304030201\ 688900^2$ (5.1829)
$0324316^2 + 1644000^2 = 1\ 675684^2$	$0309439^2 + 1662000^2 = 1\ 690561^2$
$1020\ 0324316^2 + 166044000^2 = 10201\ 675684^2$	$1020\ 0309439^2 + 167862000^2 = 10201\ 690561^2$
$10203020\ 0324316^2 + 16606044000^2 = 102030201\ 675684^2$	$10203020\ 0309439^2 + 16787862000^2 = 102030201\ 690561^2$
$102030403020\ 0324316^2 + 1660606044000^2 = 1020304030201\ 675684^2$ (5.1821)	$102030403020\ 0309439^2 + 1678787862000^2 = 1020304030201\ 690561^2$ (5.1830)
$0322671^2 + 1646000^2 = 1\ 677329^2$	$0307776^2 + 1664000^2 = 1\ 692224^2$
$1020\ 0322671^2 + 166246000^2 = 10201\ 677329^2$	$1020\ 0307776^2 + 168064000^2 = 10201\ 692224^2$
$10203020\ 0322671^2 + 16626246000^2 = 102030201\ 677329^2$	$10203020\ 0307776^2 + 16808064000^2 = 102030201\ 692224^2$
$102030403020\ 0322671^2 + 1662626246000^2 = 1020304030201\ 677329^2$ (5.1822)	$102030403020\ 0307776^2 + 1680808064000^2 = 1020304030201\ 692224^2$ (5.1831)
$0321024^2 + 1648000^2 = 1\ 678976^2$	$0306111^2 + 1666000^2 = 1\ 693889^2$
$1020\ 0321024^2 + 166448000^2 = 10201\ 678976^2$	$1020\ 0306111^2 + 168266000^2 = 10201\ 693889^2$
$10203020\ 0321024^2 + 16646448000^2 = 102030201\ 678976^2$	$10203020\ 0306111^2 + 16828266000^2 = 102030201\ 693889^2$
$102030403020\ 0321024^2 + 1664646448000^2 = 1020304030201\ 678976^2$ (5.1823)	$102030403020\ 0306111^2 + 1682828266000^2 = 1020304030201\ 693889^2$ (5.1832)
$0319375^2 + 1650000^2 = 1\ 680625^2$	$0304444^2 + 1668000^2 = 1\ 695556^2$
$1020\ 0319375^2 + 166650000^2 = 10201\ 680625^2$	$1020\ 0304444^2 + 168468000^2 = 10201\ 695556^2$
$10203020\ 0319375^2 + 16666650000^2 = 102030201\ 680625^2$	$10203020\ 0304444^2 + 16848468000^2 = 102030201\ 695556^2$
$102030403020\ 0319375^2 + 1666666650000^2 = 1020304030201\ 680625^2$ (5.1824)	$102030403020\ 0304444^2 + 1684848468000^2 = 1020304030201\ 695556^2$ (5.1833)
$0317724^2 + 1652000^2 = 1\ 682276^2$	$0302775^2 + 1670000^2 = 1\ 697225^2$
$1020\ 0317724^2 + 166852000^2 = 10201\ 682276^2$	$1020\ 0302775^2 + 168670000^2 = 10201\ 697225^2$
$10203020\ 0317724^2 + 16686852000^2 = 102030201\ 682276^2$	$10203020\ 0302775^2 + 16868670000^2 = 102030201\ 697225^2$
$102030403020\ 0317724^2 + 1668686852000^2 = 1020304030201\ 682276^2$ (5.1825)	$102030403020\ 0302775^2 + 1686868670000^2 = 1020304030201\ 697225^2$ (5.1834)
$0316071^2 + 1654000^2 = 1\ 683929^2$	
$1020\ 0316071^2 + 167054000^2 = 10201\ 683929^2$	
$10203020\ 0316071^2 + 16707054000^2 = 102030201\ 683929^2$	
$102030403020\ 0316071^2 + 1670707054000^2 = 1020304030201\ 683929^2$ (5.1826)	

$0301104^2 + 1672000^2 = 1\ 698896^2$	$0285975^2 + 1690000^2 = 1\ 714025^2$
$1020\ 0301104^2 + 168872000^2 = 10201\ 698896^2$	$1020\ 0285975^2 + 170690000^2 = 10201\ 714025^2$
$10203020\ 0301104^2 + 16888872000^2 = 102030201\ 698896^2$	$10203020\ 0285975^2 + 17070690000^2 = 102030201\ 714025^2$
$102030403020\ 0301104^2 + 1688888872000^2 = 1020304030201\ 698896^2$ (5.1835)	$102030403020\ 0285975^2 + 1707070690000^2 = 1020304030201\ 714025^2$ (5.1844)
$0299431^2 + 1674000^2 = 1\ 700569^2$	$0284284^2 + 1692000^2 = 1\ 715716^2$
$1020\ 0299431^2 + 169074000^2 = 10201\ 700569^2$	$1020\ 0284284^2 + 170892000^2 = 10201\ 715716^2$
$10203020\ 0299431^2 + 16909074000^2 = 102030201\ 700569^2$	$10203020\ 0284284^2 + 17090892000^2 = 102030201\ 715716^2$
$102030403020\ 0299431^2 + 1690909074000^2 = 1020304030201\ 700569^2$ (5.1836)	$102030403020\ 0284284^2 + 1709090892000^2 = 1020304030201\ 715716^2$ (5.1845)
$0297756^2 + 1676000^2 = 1\ 702244^2$	$0282591^2 + 1694000^2 = 1\ 717409^2$
$1020\ 0297756^2 + 169276000^2 = 10201\ 702244^2$	$1020\ 0282591^2 + 171094000^2 = 10201\ 717409^2$
$10203020\ 0297756^2 + 16929276000^2 = 102030201\ 702244^2$	$10203020\ 0282591^2 + 17111094000^2 = 102030201\ 717409^2$
$102030403020\ 0297756^2 + 1692929276000^2 = 1020304030201\ 702244^2$ (5.1837)	$102030403020\ 0282591^2 + 1711111094000^2 = 1020304030201\ 717409^2$ (5.1846)
$0296079^2 + 1678000^2 = 1\ 703921^2$	$0280896^2 + 1696000^2 = 1\ 719104^2$
$1020\ 0296079^2 + 169478000^2 = 10201\ 703921^2$	$1020\ 0280896^2 + 171296000^2 = 10201\ 719104^2$
$10203020\ 0296079^2 + 16949478000^2 = 102030201\ 703921^2$	$10203020\ 0280896^2 + 17131296000^2 = 102030201\ 719104^2$
$102030403020\ 0296079^2 + 1694949478000^2 = 1020304030201\ 703921^2$ (5.1838)	$102030403020\ 0280896^2 + 1713131296000^2 = 1020304030201\ 719104^2$ (5.1847)
$0294400^2 + 1680000^2 = 1\ 705600^2$	$0279199^2 + 1698000^2 = 1\ 720801^2$
$1020\ 0294400^2 + 169680000^2 = 10201\ 705600^2$	$1020\ 0279199^2 + 171498000^2 = 10201\ 720801^2$
$10203020\ 0294400^2 + 16969680000^2 = 102030201\ 705600^2$	$10203020\ 0279199^2 + 17151498000^2 = 102030201\ 720801^2$
$102030403020\ 0294400^2 + 1696969680000^2 = 1020304030201\ 705600^2$ (5.1839)	$102030403020\ 0279199^2 + 1715151498000^2 = 1020304030201\ 720801^2$ (5.1848)
$0292719^2 + 1682000^2 = 1\ 707281^2$	$0277500^2 + 1700000^2 = 1\ 722500^2$
$1020\ 0292719^2 + 169882000^2 = 10201\ 707281^2$	$1020\ 0277500^2 + 171700000^2 = 10201\ 722500^2$
$10203020\ 0292719^2 + 16989882000^2 = 102030201\ 707281^2$	$10203020\ 0277500^2 + 17171700000^2 = 102030201\ 722500^2$
$102030403020\ 0292719^2 + 1698989882000^2 = 1020304030201\ 707281^2$ (5.1840)	$102030403020\ 0277500^2 + 1717171700000^2 = 1020304030201\ 722500^2$ (5.1849)
$0291036^2 + 1684000^2 = 1\ 708964^2$	$0275799^2 + 1702000^2 = 1\ 724201^2$
$1020\ 0291036^2 + 170084000^2 = 10201\ 708964^2$	$1020\ 0275799^2 + 171902000^2 = 10201\ 724201^2$
$10203020\ 0291036^2 + 17010084000^2 = 102030201\ 708964^2$	$10203020\ 0275799^2 + 17191902000^2 = 102030201\ 724201^2$
$102030403020\ 0291036^2 + 1701010084000^2 = 1020304030201\ 708964^2$ (5.1841)	$102030403020\ 0275799^2 + 1719191902000^2 = 1020304030201\ 724201^2$ (5.1850)
$0289351^2 + 1686000^2 = 1\ 710649^2$	$0274096^2 + 1704000^2 = 1\ 725904^2$
$1020\ 0289351^2 + 170286000^2 = 10201\ 710649^2$	$1020\ 0274096^2 + 172104000^2 = 10201\ 725904^2$
$10203020\ 0289351^2 + 17030286000^2 = 102030201\ 710649^2$	$10203020\ 0274096^2 + 17212104000^2 = 102030201\ 725904^2$
$102030403020\ 0289351^2 + 1703030286000^2 = 1020304030201\ 710649^2$ (5.1842)	$102030403020\ 0274096^2 + 1721212104000^2 = 1020304030201\ 725904^2$ (5.1851)
$0287664^2 + 1688000^2 = 1\ 712336^2$	
$1020\ 0287664^2 + 170488000^2 = 10201\ 712336^2$	
$10203020\ 0287664^2 + 17050488000^2 = 102030201\ 712336^2$	
$102030403020\ 0287664^2 + 1705050488000^2 = 1020304030201\ 712336^2$ (5.1843)	

$$\begin{array}{l}
0272391^2 + 1706000^2 = 1727609^2 \\
10200272391^2 + 172306000^2 = 10201727609^2 \\
102030200272391^2 + 17232306000^2 = 102030201727609^2 \\
1020304030200272391^2 + 1723232306000^2 = 1020304030201727609^2 \quad (5.1852) \\
0270684^2 + 1708000^2 = 1729316^2 \\
10200270684^2 + 172508000^2 = 10201729316^2 \\
102030200270684^2 + 17252508000^2 = 102030201729316^2 \\
1020304030200270684^2 + 1725252508000^2 = 1020304030201729316^2 \quad (5.1853) \\
0268975^2 + 1710000^2 = 1731025^2 \\
10200268975^2 + 172710000^2 = 10201731025^2 \\
102030200268975^2 + 17272710000^2 = 102030201731025^2 \\
1020304030200268975^2 + 1727272710000^2 = 1020304030201731025^2 \quad (5.1854) \\
0267264^2 + 1712000^2 = 1732736^2 \\
10200267264^2 + 172912000^2 = 10201732736^2 \\
102030200267264^2 + 17292912000^2 = 102030201732736^2 \\
1020304030200267264^2 + 1729292912000^2 = 1020304030201732736^2 \quad (5.1855) \\
0265551^2 + 1714000^2 = 1734449^2 \\
10200265551^2 + 173114000^2 = 10201734449^2 \\
102030200265551^2 + 17313114000^2 = 102030201734449^2 \\
1020304030200265551^2 + 1731313114000^2 = 1020304030201734449^2 \quad (5.1856) \\
0263836^2 + 1716000^2 = 1736164^2 \\
10200263836^2 + 173316000^2 = 10201736164^2 \\
102030200263836^2 + 17333316000^2 = 102030201736164^2 \\
1020304030200263836^2 + 1733333316000^2 = 1020304030201736164^2 \quad (5.1857) \\
0262119^2 + 1718000^2 = 1737881^2 \\
10200262119^2 + 173518000^2 = 10201737881^2 \\
102030200262119^2 + 17353518000^2 = 102030201737881^2 \\
1020304030200262119^2 + 1735353518000^2 = 1020304030201737881^2 \quad (5.1858) \\
0260400^2 + 1720000^2 = 1739600^2 \\
10200260400^2 + 173720000^2 = 10201739600^2 \\
102030200260400^2 + 17373720000^2 = 102030201739600^2 \\
1020304030200260400^2 + 1737373720000^2 = 1020304030201739600^2 \quad (5.1859) \\
0258679^2 + 1722000^2 = 1741321^2 \\
10200258679^2 + 173922000^2 = 10201741321^2 \\
102030200258679^2 + 17393922000^2 = 102030201741321^2 \\
1020304030200258679^2 + 1739393922000^2 = 1020304030201741321^2 \quad (5.1860) \\
0256956^2 + 1724000^2 = 1743044^2 \\
10200256956^2 + 174124000^2 = 10201743044^2 \\
102030200256956^2 + 17414124000^2 = 102030201743044^2 \\
1020304030200256956^2 + 1741414124000^2 = 1020304030201743044^2 \quad (5.1861) \\
0255231^2 + 1726000^2 = 1744769^2 \\
10200255231^2 + 174326000^2 = 10201744769^2 \\
102030200255231^2 + 17434326000^2 = 102030201744769^2 \\
1020304030200255231^2 + 1743434326000^2 = 1020304030201744769^2 \quad (5.1862) \\
0253504^2 + 1728000^2 = 1746496^2 \\
10200253504^2 + 174528000^2 = 10201746496^2 \\
102030200253504^2 + 17454528000^2 = 102030201746496^2 \\
1020304030200253504^2 + 1745454528000^2 = 1020304030201746496^2 \quad (5.1863) \\
0251775^2 + 1730000^2 = 1748225^2 \\
10200251775^2 + 174730000^2 = 10201748225^2 \\
102030200251775^2 + 17474730000^2 = 102030201748225^2 \\
1020304030200251775^2 + 1747474730000^2 = 1020304030201748225^2 \quad (5.1864) \\
0250044^2 + 1732000^2 = 1749956^2 \\
10200250044^2 + 174932000^2 = 10201749956^2 \\
102030200250044^2 + 17494932000^2 = 102030201749956^2 \\
1020304030200250044^2 + 1749494932000^2 = 1020304030201749956^2 \quad (5.1865) \\
0248311^2 + 1734000^2 = 1751689^2 \\
10200248311^2 + 175134000^2 = 10201751689^2 \\
102030200248311^2 + 17515134000^2 = 102030201751689^2 \\
1020304030200248311^2 + 1751515134000^2 = 1020304030201751689^2 \quad (5.1866) \\
0246576^2 + 1736000^2 = 1753424^2 \\
10200246576^2 + 175336000^2 = 10201753424^2 \\
102030200246576^2 + 17535336000^2 = 102030201753424^2 \\
1020304030200246576^2 + 1753535336000^2 = 1020304030201753424^2 \quad (5.1867) \\
0244839^2 + 1738000^2 = 1755161^2 \\
10200244839^2 + 175538000^2 = 10201755161^2 \\
102030200244839^2 + 17555538000^2 = 102030201755161^2 \\
1020304030200244839^2 + 1755555538000^2 = 1020304030201755161^2 \quad (5.1868)
\end{array}$$

$0243100^2 + 1740000^2 = 1756900^2$	$0227359^2 + 1758000^2 = 1772641^2$
$10200243100^2 + 175740000^2 = 10201756900^2$	$10200227359^2 + 177558000^2 = 10201772641^2$
$102030200243100^2 + 17575740000^2 = 102030201756900^2$	$102030200227359^2 + 17757558000^2 = 102030201772641^2$
$1020304030200243100^2 + 1757575740000^2 = 1020304030201756900^2$ (5.1869)	$1020304030200227359^2 + 1775757558000^2 = 1020304030201772641^2$ (5.1878)
$0241359^2 + 1742000^2 = 1758641^2$	$0225600^2 + 1760000^2 = 1774400^2$
$10200241359^2 + 175942000^2 = 10201758641^2$	$10200225600^2 + 177760000^2 = 10201774400^2$
$102030200241359^2 + 17595942000^2 = 102030201758641^2$	$102030200225600^2 + 1777760000^2 = 102030201774400^2$
$1020304030200241359^2 + 1759595942000^2 = 1020304030201758641^2$ (5.1870)	$1020304030200225600^2 + 177777760000^2 = 1020304030201774400^2$ (5.1879)
$0239616^2 + 1744000^2 = 1760384^2$	$0223839^2 + 1762000^2 = 1776161^2$
$10200239616^2 + 176144000^2 = 10201760384^2$	$10200223839^2 + 177962000^2 = 10201776161^2$
$102030200239616^2 + 17616144000^2 = 102030201760384^2$	$102030200223839^2 + 17797962000^2 = 102030201776161^2$
$1020304030200239616^2 + 1761616144000^2 = 1020304030201760384^2$ (5.1871)	$1020304030200223839^2 + 1779797962000^2 = 1020304030201776161^2$ (5.1880)
$0237871^2 + 1746000^2 = 1762129^2$	$0222076^2 + 1764000^2 = 1777924^2$
$10200237871^2 + 176346000^2 = 10201762129^2$	$10200222076^2 + 178164000^2 = 10201777924^2$
$102030200237871^2 + 17636346000^2 = 102030201762129^2$	$102030200222076^2 + 17818164000^2 = 102030201777924^2$
$1020304030200237871^2 + 1763636346000^2 = 1020304030201762129^2$ (5.1872)	$1020304030200222076^2 + 1781818164000^2 = 1020304030201777924^2$ (5.1881)
$0236124^2 + 1748000^2 = 1763876^2$	$0220311^2 + 1766000^2 = 1779689^2$
$10200236124^2 + 176548000^2 = 10201763876^2$	$10200220311^2 + 178366000^2 = 10201779689^2$
$102030200236124^2 + 17656548000^2 = 102030201763876^2$	$102030200220311^2 + 17838366000^2 = 102030201779689^2$
$1020304030200236124^2 + 1765656548000^2 = 1020304030201763876^2$ (5.1873)	$1020304030200220311^2 + 1783838366000^2 = 1020304030201779689^2$ (5.1882)
$0234375^2 + 1750000^2 = 1765625^2$	$0218544^2 + 1768000^2 = 1781456^2$
$10200234375^2 + 176750000^2 = 10201765625^2$	$10200218544^2 + 178568000^2 = 10201781456^2$
$102030200234375^2 + 17676750000^2 = 102030201765625^2$	$102030200218544^2 + 17858568000^2 = 102030201781456^2$
$1020304030200234375^2 + 1767676750000^2 = 1020304030201765625^2$ (5.1874)	$1020304030200218544^2 + 1785858568000^2 = 1020304030201781456^2$ (5.1883)
$0232624^2 + 1752000^2 = 1767376^2$	$0216775^2 + 1770000^2 = 1783225^2$
$10200232624^2 + 176952000^2 = 10201767376^2$	$10200216775^2 + 178770000^2 = 10201783225^2$
$102030200232624^2 + 17696952000^2 = 102030201767376^2$	$102030200216775^2 + 17878770000^2 = 102030201783225^2$
$1020304030200232624^2 + 1769696952000^2 = 1020304030201767376^2$ (5.1875)	$1020304030200216775^2 + 1787878770000^2 = 1020304030201783225^2$ (5.1884)
$0230871^2 + 1754000^2 = 1769129^2$	$0215004^2 + 1772000^2 = 1784996^2$
$10200230871^2 + 177154000^2 = 10201769129^2$	$10200215004^2 + 178972000^2 = 10201784996^2$
$102030200230871^2 + 17717154000^2 = 102030201769129^2$	$102030200215004^2 + 17898972000^2 = 102030201784996^2$
$1020304030200230871^2 + 1771717154000^2 = 1020304030201769129^2$ (5.1876)	$1020304030200215004^2 + 1789898972000^2 = 1020304030201784996^2$ (5.1885)
$0229116^2 + 1756000^2 = 1770884^2$	
$10200229116^2 + 177356000^2 = 10201770884^2$	
$102030200229116^2 + 17737356000^2 = 102030201770884^2$	
$1020304030200229116^2 + 1773737356000^2 = 1020304030201770884^2$ (5.1877)	

$0213231^2 + 1774000^2 = 1786769^2$	$0200764^2 + 1788000^2 = 1799236^2$
$10200213231^2 + 179174000^2 = 10201786769^2$	$10200200764^2 + 180588000^2 = 10201799236^2$
$102030200213231^2 + 17919174000^2 = 102030201786769^2$	$102030200200764^2 + 18060588000^2 = 102030201799236^2$
$1020304030200213231^2 + 1791919174000^2 = 1020304030201786769^2$ (5.1886)	$1020304030200200764^2 + 1806060588000^2 = 1020304030201799236^2$ (5.1893)
$0211456^2 + 1776000^2 = 1788544^2$	$0198975^2 + 1790000^2 = 1801025^2$
$10200211456^2 + 179376000^2 = 10201788544^2$	$10200198975^2 + 180790000^2 = 10201801025^2$
$102030200211456^2 + 17939376000^2 = 102030201788544^2$	$102030200198975^2 + 18080790000^2 = 102030201801025^2$
$1020304030200211456^2 + 1793939376000^2 = 1020304030201788544^2$ (5.1887)	$1020304030200198975^2 + 1808080790000^2 = 1020304030201801025^2$ (5.1894)
$0209679^2 + 1778000^2 = 1790321^2$	$0197184^2 + 1792000^2 = 1802816^2$
$10200209679^2 + 179578000^2 = 10201790321^2$	$10200197184^2 + 180992000^2 = 10201802816^2$
$102030200209679^2 + 17959578000^2 = 102030201790321^2$	$102030200197184^2 + 18100992000^2 = 102030201802816^2$
$1020304030200209679^2 + 1795959578000^2 = 1020304030201790321^2$ (5.1888)	$1020304030200197184^2 + 1810100992000^2 = 1020304030201802816^2$ (5.1895)
$0207900^2 + 1780000^2 = 1792100^2$	$0195391^2 + 1794000^2 = 1804609^2$
$10200207900^2 + 179780000^2 = 10201792100^2$	$10200195391^2 + 181194000^2 = 10201804609^2$
$102030200207900^2 + 17979780000^2 = 102030201792100^2$	$102030200195391^2 + 18121194000^2 = 102030201804609^2$
$1020304030200207900^2 + 1797979780000^2 = 1020304030201792100^2$ (5.1889)	$1020304030200195391^2 + 1812121194000^2 = 1020304030201804609^2$ (5.1896)
$0206119^2 + 1782000^2 = 1793881^2$	$0193596^2 + 1796000^2 = 1806404^2$
$10200206119^2 + 179982000^2 = 10201793881^2$	$10200193596^2 + 181396000^2 = 10201806404^2$
$102030200206119^2 + 17999982000^2 = 102030201793881^2$	$102030200193596^2 + 18141396000^2 = 102030201806404^2$
$1020304030200206119^2 + 1799999982000^2 = 1020304030201793881^2$ (5.1890)	$1020304030200193596^2 + 1814141396000^2 = 1020304030201806404^2$ (5.1897)
$0204336^2 + 1784000^2 = 1795664^2$	$0191799^2 + 1798000^2 = 1808201^2$
$10200204336^2 + 180184000^2 = 10201795664^2$	$10200191799^2 + 181598000^2 = 10201808201^2$
$102030200204336^2 + 18020184000^2 = 102030201795664^2$	$102030200191799^2 + 18161598000^2 = 102030201808201^2$
$1020304030200204336^2 + 1802020184000^2 = 1020304030201795664^2$ (5.1891)	$1020304030200191799^2 + 1816161598000^2 = 1020304030201808201^2$ (5.1898)
$0202551^2 + 1786000^2 = 1797449^2$	$0188199^2 + 1802000^2 = 1811801^2$
$10200202551^2 + 180386000^2 = 10201797449^2$	$10200188199^2 + 182002000^2 = 10201811801^2$
$102030200202551^2 + 18040386000^2 = 102030201797449^2$	$102030200188199^2 + 18202002000^2 = 102030201811801^2$
$1020304030200202551^2 + 1804040386000^2 = 1020304030201797449^2$ (5.1892)	$1020304030200188199^2 + 18202002000^2 = 1020304030201811801^2$ (5.1900)
$0190000^2 + 1800000^2 = 1810000^2$	
$10200190000^2 + 181800000^2 = 10201810000^2$	
$102030200190000^2 + 18181800000^2 = 102030201810000^2$	
$1020304030200190000^2 + 1818181800000^2 = 1020304030201810000^2$ (5.1899)	

$0186396^2 + 1804000^2 = 1\ 813604^2$	$0170079^2 + 1822000^2 = 1\ 829921^2$
$1020\ 0186396^2 + 182204000^2 = 10201\ 813604^2$	$1020\ 0170079^2 + 184022000^2 = 10201\ 829921^2$
$10203020\ 0186396^2 + 18222204000^2 = 102030201\ 813604^2$	$10203020\ 0170079^2 + 18404022000^2 = 102030201\ 829921^2$
$102030403020\ 0186396^2 + 1822222204000^2 = 1020304030201\ 813604^2$ (5.1901)	$102030403020\ 0170079^2 + 1840404022000^2 = 1020304030201\ 829921^2$ (5.1910)
$0184591^2 + 1806000^2 = 1\ 815409^2$	$0168256^2 + 1824000^2 = 1\ 831744^2$
$1020\ 0184591^2 + 182406000^2 = 10201\ 815409^2$	$1020\ 0168256^2 + 184224000^2 = 10201\ 831744^2$
$10203020\ 0184591^2 + 18242406000^2 = 102030201\ 815409^2$	$10203020\ 0168256^2 + 18424224000^2 = 102030201\ 831744^2$
$102030403020\ 0184591^2 + 1824242406000^2 = 1020304030201\ 815409^2$ (5.1902)	$102030403020\ 0168256^2 + 1842424224000^2 = 1020304030201\ 831744^2$ (5.1911)
$0182784^2 + 1808000^2 = 1\ 817216^2$	$0166431^2 + 1826000^2 = 1\ 833569^2$
$1020\ 0182784^2 + 182608000^2 = 10201\ 817216^2$	$1020\ 0166431^2 + 184426000^2 = 10201\ 833569^2$
$10203020\ 0182784^2 + 18262608000^2 = 102030201\ 817216^2$	$10203020\ 0166431^2 + 18444426000^2 = 102030201\ 833569^2$
$102030403020\ 0182784^2 + 1826262608000^2 = 1020304030201\ 817216^2$ (5.1903)	$102030403020\ 0166431^2 + 1844444426000^2 = 1020304030201\ 833569^2$ (5.1912)
$0180975^2 + 1810000^2 = 1\ 819025^2$	$0164604^2 + 1828000^2 = 1\ 835396^2$
$1020\ 0180975^2 + 182810000^2 = 10201\ 819025^2$	$1020\ 0164604^2 + 184628000^2 = 10201\ 835396^2$
$10203020\ 0180975^2 + 18282810000^2 = 102030201\ 819025^2$	$10203020\ 0164604^2 + 18464628000^2 = 102030201\ 835396^2$
$102030403020\ 0180975^2 + 1828282810000^2 = 1020304030201\ 819025^2$ (5.1904)	$102030403020\ 0164604^2 + 1846464628000^2 = 1020304030201\ 835396^2$ (5.1913)
$0179164^2 + 1812000^2 = 1\ 820836^2$	$0162775^2 + 1830000^2 = 1\ 837225^2$
$1020\ 0179164^2 + 183012000^2 = 10201\ 820836^2$	$1020\ 0162775^2 + 184830000^2 = 10201\ 837225^2$
$10203020\ 0179164^2 + 18303012000^2 = 102030201\ 820836^2$	$10203020\ 0162775^2 + 18484830000^2 = 102030201\ 837225^2$
$102030403020\ 0179164^2 + 1830303012000^2 = 1020304030201\ 820836^2$ (5.1905)	$102030403020\ 0162775^2 + 1848484830000^2 = 1020304030201\ 837225^2$ (5.1914)
$0177351^2 + 1814000^2 = 1\ 822649^2$	$0160944^2 + 1832000^2 = 1\ 839056^2$
$1020\ 0177351^2 + 183214000^2 = 10201\ 822649^2$	$1020\ 0160944^2 + 185032000^2 = 10201\ 839056^2$
$10203020\ 0177351^2 + 18323214000^2 = 102030201\ 822649^2$	$10203020\ 0160944^2 + 18505032000^2 = 102030201\ 839056^2$
$102030403020\ 0177351^2 + 1832323214000^2 = 1020304030201\ 822649^2$ (5.1906)	$102030403020\ 0160944^2 + 1850505032000^2 = 1020304030201\ 839056^2$ (5.1915)
$0175536^2 + 1816000^2 = 1\ 824464^2$	$0159111^2 + 1834000^2 = 1\ 840889^2$
$1020\ 0175536^2 + 183416000^2 = 10201\ 824464^2$	$1020\ 0159111^2 + 185234000^2 = 10201\ 840889^2$
$10203020\ 0175536^2 + 18343416000^2 = 102030201\ 824464^2$	$10203020\ 0159111^2 + 18525234000^2 = 102030201\ 840889^2$
$102030403020\ 0175536^2 + 1834343416000^2 = 1020304030201\ 824464^2$ (5.1907)	$102030403020\ 0159111^2 + 1852525234000^2 = 1020304030201\ 840889^2$ (5.1916)
$0173719^2 + 1818000^2 = 1\ 826281^2$	$0157276^2 + 1836000^2 = 1\ 842724^2$
$1020\ 0173719^2 + 183618000^2 = 10201\ 826281^2$	$1020\ 0157276^2 + 185436000^2 = 10201\ 842724^2$
$10203020\ 0173719^2 + 18363618000^2 = 102030201\ 826281^2$	$10203020\ 0157276^2 + 18545436000^2 = 102030201\ 842724^2$
$102030403020\ 0173719^2 + 1836363618000^2 = 1020304030201\ 826281^2$ (5.1908)	$102030403020\ 0157276^2 + 1854545436000^2 = 1020304030201\ 842724^2$ (5.1917)
$0171900^2 + 1820000^2 = 1\ 828100^2$	
$1020\ 0171900^2 + 183820000^2 = 10201\ 828100^2$	
$10203020\ 0171900^2 + 18383820000^2 = 102030201\ 828100^2$	
$102030403020\ 0171900^2 + 1838383820000^2 = 1020304030201\ 828100^2$ (5.1909)	

$0123904^2 + 1872000^2 = 1876096^2$	$0106975^2 + 1890000^2 = 1893025^2$
$10200123904^2 + 189072000^2 = 10201876096^2$	$10200106975^2 + 190890000^2 = 10201893025^2$
$102030200123904^2 + 18909072000^2 = 102030201876096^2$	$102030200106975^2 + 19090890000^2 = 102030201893025^2$
$1020304030200123904^2 + 1890909072000^2 = 1020304030201876096^2$ (5.1935)	$1020304030200106975^2 + 1909090890000^2 = 1020304030201893025^2$ (5.1944)
$0122031^2 + 1874000^2 = 1877969^2$	$0105084^2 + 1892000^2 = 1894916^2$
$10200122031^2 + 189274000^2 = 10201877969^2$	$10200105084^2 + 191092000^2 = 10201894916^2$
$102030200122031^2 + 18929274000^2 = 102030201877969^2$	$102030200105084^2 + 19111092000^2 = 102030201894916^2$
$1020304030200122031^2 + 1892929274000^2 = 1020304030201877969^2$ (5.1936)	$1020304030200105084^2 + 1911111092000^2 = 1020304030201894916^2$ (5.1945)
$0120156^2 + 1876000^2 = 1879844^2$	$0103191^2 + 1894000^2 = 1896809^2$
$10200120156^2 + 189476000^2 = 10201879844^2$	$10200103191^2 + 191294000^2 = 10201896809^2$
$102030200120156^2 + 18949476000^2 = 102030201879844^2$	$102030200103191^2 + 19131294000^2 = 102030201896809^2$
$1020304030200120156^2 + 1894949476000^2 = 1020304030201879844^2$ (5.1937)	$1020304030200103191^2 + 1913131294000^2 = 1020304030201896809^2$ (5.1946)
$0118279^2 + 1878000^2 = 1881721^2$	$0101296^2 + 1896000^2 = 1898704^2$
$10200118279^2 + 189678000^2 = 10201881721^2$	$10200101296^2 + 191496000^2 = 10201898704^2$
$102030200118279^2 + 18969678000^2 = 102030201881721^2$	$102030200101296^2 + 19151496000^2 = 102030201898704^2$
$1020304030200118279^2 + 1896969678000^2 = 1020304030201881721^2$ (5.1938)	$1020304030200101296^2 + 1915151496000^2 = 1020304030201898704^2$ (5.1947)
$0116400^2 + 1880000^2 = 1883600^2$	$0099399^2 + 1898000^2 = 1900601^2$
$10200116400^2 + 189880000^2 = 10201883600^2$	$10200099399^2 + 191698000^2 = 10201900601^2$
$102030200116400^2 + 18989880000^2 = 102030201883600^2$	$102030200099399^2 + 19171698000^2 = 102030201900601^2$
$1020304030200116400^2 + 1898989880000^2 = 1020304030201883600^2$ (5.1939)	$1020304030200099399^2 + 1917171698000^2 = 1020304030201900601^2$ (5.1948)
$0114519^2 + 1882000^2 = 1885481^2$	$0097500^2 + 1900000^2 = 1902500^2$
$10200114519^2 + 190082000^2 = 10201885481^2$	$10200097500^2 + 191900000^2 = 10201902500^2$
$102030200114519^2 + 19010082000^2 = 102030201885481^2$	$102030200097500^2 + 19191900000^2 = 102030201902500^2$
$1020304030200114519^2 + 1901010082000^2 = 1020304030201885481^2$ (5.1940)	$1020304030200097500^2 + 1919191900000^2 = 1020304030201902500^2$ (5.1949)
$0112636^2 + 1884000^2 = 1887364^2$	$0095599^2 + 1902000^2 = 1904401^2$
$10200112636^2 + 190284000^2 = 10201887364^2$	$10200095599^2 + 192102000^2 = 10201904401^2$
$102030200112636^2 + 19030284000^2 = 102030201887364^2$	$102030200095599^2 + 19212102000^2 = 102030201904401^2$
$1020304030200112636^2 + 1903030284000^2 = 1020304030201887364^2$ (5.1941)	$1020304030200095599^2 + 1921212102000^2 = 1020304030201904401^2$ (5.1950)
$0110751^2 + 1886000^2 = 1889249^2$	$0093696^2 + 1904000^2 = 1906304^2$
$10200110751^2 + 190486000^2 = 10201889249^2$	$10200093696^2 + 192304000^2 = 10201906304^2$
$102030200110751^2 + 19050486000^2 = 102030201889249^2$	$102030200093696^2 + 19232304000^2 = 102030201906304^2$
$1020304030200110751^2 + 1905050486000^2 = 1020304030201889249^2$ (5.1942)	$1020304030200093696^2 + 1923232304000^2 = 1020304030201906304^2$ (5.1951)
$0108864^2 + 1888000^2 = 1891136^2$	
$10200108864^2 + 190688000^2 = 10201891136^2$	
$102030200108864^2 + 19070688000^2 = 102030201891136^2$	
$1020304030200108864^2 + 1907070688000^2 = 1020304030201891136^2$ (5.1943)	

$0091791^2 + 1906000^2 = 1\ 908209^2$	$0074556^2 + 1924000^2 = 1\ 925444^2$
$1020\ 0091791^2 + 192506000^2 = 10201\ 908209^2$	$1020\ 0074556^2 + 194324000^2 = 10201\ 925444^2$
$10203020\ 0091791^2 + 19252506000^2 = 102030201\ 908209^2$	$10203020\ 0074556^2 + 19434324000^2 = 102030201\ 925444^2$
$102030403020\ 0091791^2 + 1925252506000^2 = 1020304030201\ 908209^2$ (5.1952)	$102030403020\ 0074556^2 + 1943434324000^2 = 1020304030201\ 925444^2$ (5.1961)
$0089884^2 + 1908000^2 = 1\ 910116^2$	$0072631^2 + 1926000^2 = 1\ 927369^2$
$1020\ 0089884^2 + 192708000^2 = 10201\ 910116^2$	$1020\ 0072631^2 + 194526000^2 = 10201\ 927369^2$
$10203020\ 0089884^2 + 19272708000^2 = 102030201\ 910116^2$	$10203020\ 0072631^2 + 19454526000^2 = 102030201\ 927369^2$
$102030403020\ 0089884^2 + 1927272708000^2 = 1020304030201\ 910116^2$ (5.1953)	$102030403020\ 0072631^2 + 1945454526000^2 = 1020304030201\ 927369^2$ (5.1962)
$0087975^2 + 1910000^2 = 1\ 912025^2$	$0070704^2 + 1928000^2 = 1\ 929296^2$
$1020\ 0087975^2 + 192910000^2 = 10201\ 912025^2$	$1020\ 0070704^2 + 194728000^2 = 10201\ 929296^2$
$10203020\ 0087975^2 + 19292910000^2 = 102030201\ 912025^2$	$10203020\ 0070704^2 + 19474728000^2 = 102030201\ 929296^2$
$102030403020\ 0087975^2 + 1929292910000^2 = 1020304030201\ 912025^2$ (5.1954)	$102030403020\ 0070704^2 + 1947474728000^2 = 1020304030201\ 929296^2$ (5.1963)
$0086064^2 + 1912000^2 = 1\ 913936^2$	$0068775^2 + 1930000^2 = 1\ 931225^2$
$1020\ 0086064^2 + 193112000^2 = 10201\ 913936^2$	$1020\ 0068775^2 + 194930000^2 = 10201\ 931225^2$
$10203020\ 0086064^2 + 19313112000^2 = 102030201\ 913936^2$	$10203020\ 0068775^2 + 19494930000^2 = 102030201\ 931225^2$
$102030403020\ 0086064^2 + 1931313112000^2 = 1020304030201\ 913936^2$ (5.1955)	$102030403020\ 0068775^2 + 1949494930000^2 = 1020304030201\ 931225^2$ (5.1964)
$0084151^2 + 1914000^2 = 1\ 915849^2$	$0066844^2 + 1932000^2 = 1\ 933156^2$
$1020\ 0084151^2 + 193314000^2 = 10201\ 915849^2$	$1020\ 0066844^2 + 195132000^2 = 10201\ 933156^2$
$10203020\ 0084151^2 + 19333314000^2 = 102030201\ 915849^2$	$10203020\ 0066844^2 + 19515132000^2 = 102030201\ 933156^2$
$102030403020\ 0084151^2 + 1933333314000^2 = 1020304030201\ 915849^2$ (5.1956)	$102030403020\ 0066844^2 + 1951515132000^2 = 1020304030201\ 933156^2$ (5.1965)
$0082236^2 + 1916000^2 = 1\ 917764^2$	$0064911^2 + 1934000^2 = 1\ 935089^2$
$1020\ 0082236^2 + 193516000^2 = 10201\ 917764^2$	$1020\ 0064911^2 + 195334000^2 = 10201\ 935089^2$
$10203020\ 0082236^2 + 19353516000^2 = 102030201\ 917764^2$	$10203020\ 0064911^2 + 19535334000^2 = 102030201\ 935089^2$
$102030403020\ 0082236^2 + 1935353516000^2 = 1020304030201\ 917764^2$ (5.1957)	$102030403020\ 0064911^2 + 1953535334000^2 = 1020304030201\ 935089^2$ (5.1966)
$0080319^2 + 1918000^2 = 1\ 919681^2$	$0062976^2 + 1936000^2 = 1\ 937024^2$
$1020\ 0080319^2 + 193718000^2 = 10201\ 919681^2$	$1020\ 0062976^2 + 195536000^2 = 10201\ 937024^2$
$10203020\ 0080319^2 + 19373718000^2 = 102030201\ 919681^2$	$10203020\ 0062976^2 + 19555536000^2 = 102030201\ 937024^2$
$102030403020\ 0080319^2 + 1937373718000^2 = 1020304030201\ 919681^2$ (5.1958)	$102030403020\ 0062976^2 + 1955555536000^2 = 1020304030201\ 937024^2$ (5.1967)
$0078400^2 + 1920000^2 = 1\ 921600^2$	$0061039^2 + 1938000^2 = 1\ 938961^2$
$1020\ 0078400^2 + 193920000^2 = 10201\ 921600^2$	$1020\ 0061039^2 + 195738000^2 = 10201\ 938961^2$
$10203020\ 0078400^2 + 19393920000^2 = 102030201\ 921600^2$	$10203020\ 0061039^2 + 19575738000^2 = 102030201\ 938961^2$
$102030403020\ 0078400^2 + 1939393920000^2 = 1020304030201\ 921600^2$ (5.1959)	$102030403020\ 0061039^2 + 1957575738000^2 = 1020304030201\ 938961^2$ (5.1968)
$0076479^2 + 1922000^2 = 1\ 923521^2$	
$1020\ 0076479^2 + 194122000^2 = 10201\ 923521^2$	
$10203020\ 0076479^2 + 19414122000^2 = 102030201\ 923521^2$	
$102030403020\ 0076479^2 + 1941414122000^2 = 1020304030201\ 923521^2$ (5.1960)	

$0059100^2 + 1940000^2 = 1\ 940900^2$	$0041559^2 + 1958000^2 = 1\ 958441^2$
$1020\ 0059100^2 + 195940000^2 = 10201\ 940900^2$	$1020\ 0041559^2 + 197758000^2 = 10201\ 958441^2$
$10203020\ 0059100^2 + 19595940000^2 = 102030201\ 940900^2$	$10203020\ 0041559^2 + 19777758000^2 = 102030201\ 958441^2$
$102030403020\ 0059100^2 + 1959595940000^2 = 1020304030201\ 940900^2$ (5.1969)	$102030403020\ 0041559^2 + 1977777758000^2 = 1020304030201\ 958441^2$ (5.1978)
$0057159^2 + 1942000^2 = 1\ 942841^2$	$0039600^2 + 1960000^2 = 1\ 960400^2$
$1020\ 0057159^2 + 196142000^2 = 10201\ 942841^2$	$1020\ 0039600^2 + 197960000^2 = 10201\ 960400^2$
$10203020\ 0057159^2 + 19616142000^2 = 102030201\ 942841^2$	$10203020\ 0039600^2 + 19797960000^2 = 102030201\ 960400^2$
$102030403020\ 0057159^2 + 1961616142000^2 = 1020304030201\ 942841^2$ (5.1970)	$102030403020\ 0039600^2 + 1979797960000^2 = 1020304030201\ 960400^2$ (5.1979)
$0055216^2 + 1944000^2 = 1\ 944784^2$	$0037639^2 + 1962000^2 = 1\ 962361^2$
$1020\ 0055216^2 + 196344000^2 = 10201\ 944784^2$	$1020\ 0037639^2 + 198162000^2 = 10201\ 962361^2$
$10203020\ 0055216^2 + 19636344000^2 = 102030201\ 944784^2$	$10203020\ 0037639^2 + 19818162000^2 = 102030201\ 962361^2$
$102030403020\ 0055216^2 + 1963636344000^2 = 1020304030201\ 944784^2$ (5.1971)	$102030403020\ 0037639^2 + 1981818162000^2 = 1020304030201\ 962361^2$ (5.1980)
$0053271^2 + 1946000^2 = 1\ 946729^2$	$0035676^2 + 1964000^2 = 1\ 964324^2$
$1020\ 0053271^2 + 196546000^2 = 10201\ 946729^2$	$1020\ 0035676^2 + 198364000^2 = 10201\ 964324^2$
$10203020\ 0053271^2 + 19656546000^2 = 102030201\ 946729^2$	$10203020\ 0035676^2 + 19838364000^2 = 102030201\ 964324^2$
$102030403020\ 0053271^2 + 1965656546000^2 = 1020304030201\ 946729^2$ (5.1972)	$102030403020\ 0035676^2 + 1983838364000^2 = 1020304030201\ 964324^2$ (5.1981)
$0051324^2 + 1948000^2 = 1\ 948676^2$	$0033711^2 + 1966000^2 = 1\ 966289^2$
$1020\ 0051324^2 + 196748000^2 = 10201\ 948676^2$	$1020\ 0033711^2 + 198566000^2 = 10201\ 966289^2$
$10203020\ 0051324^2 + 19676748000^2 = 102030201\ 948676^2$	$10203020\ 0033711^2 + 19858566000^2 = 102030201\ 966289^2$
$102030403020\ 0051324^2 + 1967676748000^2 = 1020304030201\ 948676^2$ (5.1973)	$102030403020\ 0033711^2 + 1985858566000^2 = 1020304030201\ 966289^2$ (5.1982)
$0049375^2 + 1950000^2 = 1\ 950625^2$	$0031744^2 + 1968000^2 = 1\ 968256^2$
$1020\ 0049375^2 + 196950000^2 = 10201\ 950625^2$	$1020\ 0031744^2 + 198768000^2 = 10201\ 968256^2$
$10203020\ 0049375^2 + 19696950000^2 = 102030201\ 950625^2$	$10203020\ 0031744^2 + 19878768000^2 = 102030201\ 968256^2$
$102030403020\ 0049375^2 + 1969696950000^2 = 1020304030201\ 950625^2$ (5.1974)	$102030403020\ 0031744^2 + 1987878768000^2 = 1020304030201\ 968256^2$ (5.1983)
$0047424^2 + 1952000^2 = 1\ 952576^2$	$0029775^2 + 1970000^2 = 1\ 970225^2$
$1020\ 0047424^2 + 197152000^2 = 10201\ 952576^2$	$1020\ 0029775^2 + 198970000^2 = 10201\ 970225^2$
$10203020\ 0047424^2 + 19717152000^2 = 102030201\ 952576^2$	$10203020\ 0029775^2 + 19898970000^2 = 102030201\ 970225^2$
$102030403020\ 0047424^2 + 1971717152000^2 = 1020304030201\ 952576^2$ (5.1975)	$102030403020\ 0029775^2 + 1989898970000^2 = 1020304030201\ 970225^2$ (5.1984)
$0045471^2 + 1954000^2 = 1\ 954529^2$	$0027804^2 + 1972000^2 = 1\ 972196^2$
$1020\ 0045471^2 + 197354000^2 = 10201\ 954529^2$	$1020\ 0027804^2 + 199172000^2 = 10201\ 972196^2$
$10203020\ 0045471^2 + 19737354000^2 = 102030201\ 954529^2$	$10203020\ 0027804^2 + 19919172000^2 = 102030201\ 972196^2$
$102030403020\ 0045471^2 + 1973737354000^2 = 1020304030201\ 954529^2$ (5.1976)	$102030403020\ 0027804^2 + 1991919172000^2 = 1020304030201\ 972196^2$ (5.1985)
$0043516^2 + 1956000^2 = 1\ 956484^2$	
$1020\ 0043516^2 + 197556000^2 = 10201\ 956484^2$	
$10203020\ 0043516^2 + 19757556000^2 = 102030201\ 956484^2$	
$102030403020\ 0043516^2 + 1975757556000^2 = 1020304030201\ 956484^2$ (5.1977)	

$$\begin{array}{ll}
0025831^2 + 1974000^2 & = 1974169^2 \\
10200025831^2 + 199374000^2 & = 10201974169^2 \\
102030200025831^2 + 19939374000^2 & = 102030201974169^2 \\
1020304030200025831^2 + 1993939374000^2 & = 1020304030201974169^2 \\
& \quad (5.1986) \\
0023856^2 + 1976000^2 & = 1976144^2 \\
10200023856^2 + 199576000^2 & = 10201976144^2 \\
102030200023856^2 + 19959576000^2 & = 102030201976144^2 \\
1020304030200023856^2 + 1995959576000^2 & = 1020304030201976144^2 \\
& \quad (5.1987) \\
0021879^2 + 1978000^2 & = 1978121^2 \\
10200021879^2 + 199778000^2 & = 10201978121^2 \\
102030200021879^2 + 19979778000^2 & = 102030201978121^2 \\
1020304030200021879^2 + 1997979778000^2 & = 1020304030201978121^2 \\
& \quad (5.1988) \\
0019900^2 + 1980000^2 & = 1980100^2 \\
10200019900^2 + 199980000^2 & = 10201980100^2 \\
102030200019900^2 + 19999980000^2 & = 102030201980100^2 \\
1020304030200019900^2 + 1999999980000^2 & = 1020304030201980100^2 \\
& \quad (5.1989) \\
0017919^2 + 1982000^2 & = 1982081^2 \\
10200017919^2 + 200182000^2 & = 10201982081^2 \\
102030200017919^2 + 20020182000^2 & = 102030201982081^2 \\
1020304030200017919^2 + 2002020182000^2 & = 1020304030201982081^2 \\
& \quad (5.1990) \\
0015936^2 + 1984000^2 & = 1984064^2 \\
10200015936^2 + 200384000^2 & = 10201984064^2 \\
102030200015936^2 + 20040384000^2 & = 102030201984064^2 \\
1020304030200015936^2 + 2004040384000^2 & = 1020304030201984064^2 \\
& \quad (5.1991) \\
0013951^2 + 1986000^2 & = 1986049^2 \\
10200013951^2 + 200586000^2 & = 10201986049^2 \\
102030200013951^2 + 20060586000^2 & = 102030201986049^2 \\
1020304030200013951^2 + 2006060586000^2 & = 1020304030201986049^2 \\
& \quad (5.1992) \\
0011964^2 + 1988000^2 & = 1988036^2 \\
10200011964^2 + 200788000^2 & = 10201988036^2 \\
102030200011964^2 + 20080788000^2 & = 102030201988036^2 \\
1020304030200011964^2 + 2008080788000^2 & = 1020304030201988036^2 \\
& \quad (5.1993) \\
009975^2 + 1990000^2 & = 1990025^2 \\
10200009975^2 + 200990000^2 & = 10201990025^2 \\
102030200009975^2 + 20100990000^2 & = 102030201990025^2 \\
1020304030200009975^2 + 2010100990000^2 & = 1020304030201990025^2 \\
& \quad (5.1994) \\
007984^2 + 1992000^2 & = 1992016^2 \\
10200007984^2 + 201192000^2 & = 10201992016^2 \\
102030200007984^2 + 20121192000^2 & = 102030201992016^2 \\
1020304030200007984^2 + 2012121192000^2 & = 1020304030201992016^2 \\
& \quad (5.1995) \\
005991^2 + 1994000^2 & = 1994009^2 \\
10200005991^2 + 201394000^2 & = 10201994009^2 \\
102030200005991^2 + 20141394000^2 & = 102030201994009^2 \\
1020304030200005991^2 + 2014141394000^2 & = 1020304030201994009^2 \\
& \quad (5.1996) \\
003996^2 + 1996000^2 & = 1996004^2 \\
10200003996^2 + 201596000^2 & = 10201996004^2 \\
102030200003996^2 + 20161596000^2 & = 102030201996004^2 \\
1020304030200003996^2 + 2016161596000^2 & = 1020304030201996004^2 \\
& \quad (5.1997) \\
001999^2 + 1998000^2 & = 1998001^2 \\
10200001999^2 + 201798000^2 & = 10201998001^2 \\
102030200001999^2 + 20181798000^2 & = 102030201998001^2 \\
1020304030200001999^2 + 2018181798000^2 & = 1020304030201998001^2 \\
& \quad (5.1998)
\end{array}$$

Based on above 999 patterns, below are some remarks:

5.3 Remarks

(i) The first line of first pattern (??) and (5.1000) is the third line as given in pattern (2.1) or (2.3), i.e.,

$$999999^2 + 2000^2 = 1000001^2.$$

(ii) From the results appearing in subsections 4.1, 4.2.2, ?? ..., ?? ??, it is interesting to observe that the **last six digits** in each case forms perfect square. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Examples (5.1) and (5.1000)} &\Rightarrow 000001 = 1^2 \\
 \text{Examples (5.2) and (5.1001)} &\Rightarrow 000004 = 2^2 \\
 \text{Examples (5.3) and (5.1002)} &\Rightarrow 000009 = 3^2 \\
 \text{Examples (5.4) and (5.1003)} &\Rightarrow 000016 = 4^2 \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 \text{Examples (5.997) and (5.1996)} &\Rightarrow 994009 = 997^2 \\
 \text{Examples (5.998) and (5.1997)} &\Rightarrow 996004 = 998^2 \\
 \text{Examples (5.999) and (5.1998)} &\Rightarrow 998001 = 999^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

(iii) The sum of the **last six digits** of first and third members of each line is same, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Examples (5.1) and (5.1000)} &\Rightarrow 999999 + 000001 = 1000000 \\
 \text{Examples (5.2) and (5.1001)} &\Rightarrow 999996 + 000004 = 1000000 \\
 \text{Examples (5.3) and (5.1002)} &\Rightarrow 999991 + 000009 = 1000000 \\
 \text{Examples (5.4) and (5.1003)} &\Rightarrow 999984 + 000016 = 1000000 \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 &\dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\
 \text{Examples (5.997) and (5.1996)} &\Rightarrow 005991 + 994009 = 1000000 \\
 \text{Examples (5.998) and (5.1997)} &\Rightarrow 003996 + 996004 = 1000000 \\
 \text{Examples (5.999) and (5.1998)} &\Rightarrow 001999 + 998001 = 1000000.
 \end{aligned}$$

(iv) In many cases, the second term in first line is out of pattern, but the continuations is well patterned. From n=20 to 999, we have written only first four lines. The rest 5 lines follows on similar way.

More studies on **palindromic-type pandigital patterns** and **general Pythagorean patterns** can be seen in author’s work [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. Connections of Pythagorean triples with magic squares refer [3, 4, 9].

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